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for a healthy future

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Reporting for first and second set of substances

By CGLs

Deliverable Report

AD5.7

WP5 - Translation of results into policies

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2 Abstract

This deliverable is the final reporting on the achievements of HBM4EU from 2017 until 2022 per substance group. The results are reported in relation to the policy questions. The information has been compiled by the chemical group leaders and has been drafted in close exchange with the work package leaders and the substance-specific contact points for each work package. The information is based on the published deliverables, on the annual reports that have been produced by the Consortium and on the latest scientific results obtained within the workpackages that will be made available in peer reviewed publications. The information presents the main outcome and results of HBM4EU and serves as an input for targeted dissemination and communication of HBM4EU results to decision makers and stakeholders such as policy briefs and substance reports that will be released before 30/06/2022.

The information in the report adds to the scoping documents. The scoping documents can be found on the substance-group-specific web page of the HBM4EU web site. They contain for each substance group a review of the available evidence on hazardous properties, exposure characteristics, technical aspects, policy relevance, substance categorisation, a list of policy-related questions, and identify knowledge gaps and propose research activities. The reporting in D5.7 is in table format and lists next to the policy questions (column 1) also the status and approaches taken within HBM4EU to answer the policy questions (column 2). A third column provides the answer to the policy questions and column 4 contains the references to Deliverables and publications produced in HBM4EU.

3 Acrylamide

1. Policy Question	2. Short Summary of status and of HBM4EU activities to answer the policy question	3. Concise answer to the policy questions – based on HBM4EU results	4. Links to relevant documents, such as the scoping document, HBM4EU deliverables and peer-reviewed articles.
<p>1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to Acrylamide?</p> <p>2. Does the exposure to acrylamide differ significantly between countries and population groups? Are the main reasons for these differences related to different dietary habits or to other factors?</p> <p>3. Which population groups are more at risk? Are there other sources of exposure of acrylamide that need to be discovered (e.g. smoking habits or other food</p>	<p>To answer these specific policy questions on current exposure, geographical differences and exposure determinants in the EU population, two research protocols have been developed (Task 10.4). An extensive search has been conducted to identify HBM studies performed in EU (n=25). Few studies were identified with HBM data available for acrylamide and the invitation response was very low (0.2%). The European HBM dashboard has 1 dataset with acrylamide exposure data integrated.</p> <p>Already published studies reported determinants of exposure in certain foods such as coffee (and solid coffee substitute), fried potato products (including potatoes and vegetables crisps), biscuits, cereals and other products such as roasted nuts, olives in brine, prunes and dates and baby food. Very few European studies have investigated other exposure determinants of acrylamide exposure in the general population. To our knowledge no European biomonitoring studies have investigated exposure determinants of acrylamide in newborns, only one study in children. Hence, one of the proposed research protocols aimed to investigate the most relevant determinants of acrylamide</p>	<p>New data for 2 acrylamide biomarkers (AAMA and GAMA) is available from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in children (6-11 years) and adults (20-39 years). The Aligned Studies in children collected data between 2014-2021 across 4 sampling sites in Europe (Norway, Italy, Germany and France) representing 1198 individuals. The Aligned Studies in adults collected data between 2014-2021 across 5 sampling sites in Europe (Iceland, Portugal, France, Germany and Luxembourg) representing 1180 individuals. P50 of urinary AAMA concentrations are in the range of 51.44 -83.88 µg/g crt across studies in children and 28.78 - 91.70 µg/g crt across studies in adults. P95 of urinary AAMA concentrations are in the range of 126.39-220.50 µg/g crt across studies in children and 90.82-503.92 µg/g crt across studies in adults. P50 of urinary GAMA concentrations are in the range of 8.32 - 30.74 µg/g crt across studies in children and 7.13 - 25.01 µg/g crt across studies in adults. P95 of urinary GAMA concentrations are in the range of 17.72-65.16 µg/g crt across studies in children and 13.51-48.82 µg/g crt across studies in adults. For AAMA the share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the BE-value of 16 µg/g crt ranges from 98.33%-100% for children and 90.20%-100% for adults. However,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ <p>Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 "Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires" https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/</p> <p>A manuscript has been produced and will be submitted by June 2022.</p>

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sources)?	<p>exposure among European adults, children and whether the exposure determinants may differ among children and adults. The project will not cover newborns as this study population is not included in the aligned studies and there is no response from the only available study (NewGeneris) considering this age group. We also investigated whether the exposure determinants are different for dietary or non- dietary regional differences. The statistical analysis was performed with individual data from existing European studies performed in the general population of adults and children and included cohorts from the following geographical areas (North, West, South), available information on biomarkers of acrylamide in urine (AAMA and GAMA) and a concomitant assessment of other variables considered as possible determinants of the exposure of acrylamide. HBM4EU data were obtained from the following countries: 4 cohorts of children from Italy, France, Germany and Norway and 6 cohorts of adults from Portugal, Spain, France, Germany, Luxembourg and Iceland. Each variable selected as exposure determinants (dietary and non- dietary determinants) was assessed in relation to urine levels of urinary acrylamide exposure biomarkers using adequate regression quantile models. Analysis were performed for children and adults separately. Each variable was tested in univariate and</p>	<p>compared to the HBM orientation values (OV)-calculated according to EFSA BMDL10 value of 0.43 mg/kg b.w. per day for peripheral neuropathy in rats- 7% of adults (France and Portugal) had acrylamide values higher than the HBM-OV (291.4µg/L for adults with a body weight of 70 kg) and 2% of children had acrylamide values higher than the HBM-OV (321.7 µg/L for children).</p> <p>The exposure to acrylamide in the HBM4EU studies showed that the levels of acrylamide exposure measured in urines are higher in the participating studies from Southern Europe when compared to Northern and Western studies in both children and adults. The reasons for these differences are still unclear and were not fully revealed through our investigation. Certain non- dietary determinants might explain these geographical differences in adults.</p> <p>Children have slightly higher levels of exposure than adults suggesting that they might be a susceptible group. In both children and adults, gender seems not a determinant of exposure levels. Smoking was confirmed to be a strong determinant of acrylamide exposure. In adults we found that acrylamide levels were higher in relation to high consumption of potato fried and coffee but lower in relation to increase in body mass index, intake of fruit/vegetables and cereals. These results may indicate a strategy to reduce acrylamide in certain foods as well as</p>	

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	<p>multiadjusted models.</p> <p>A second protocol for analysis of current exposures to acrylamide in the European population (together with time trends) has been developed and applied on the data of the HBM4EU aligned studies.</p> <p>The aligned studies made use of a variety of materials produced in WP7 that provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct of HBM studies in Europe. For Acrylamide, questionnaires for adults and children are available.</p> <p>New data for 2 acrylamide biomarkers (AAMA and GAMA) is available from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in children (6-11 years) and adults (20-39 years). The Aligned Studies in children collected data between 2014-2021 across 4 sampling sites in Europe (Norway, Italy, Germany and France) representing 1198 individuals. The Aligned Studies in adults collected data between 2014-2021 across 5 sampling sites in Europe (Iceland, Portugal, France, Germany and Luxembourg) representing 1180 individuals.</p>	<p>make the citizen more aware of healthy choices.</p> <p>In children, higher levels of acrylamide were found in relation to low socioeconomic factors, living in cities but lower in relation to increasing age. These results found in children might indicate that the awareness of acrylamide, and in general, healthy lifestyle/choices, among certain groups exposed to low socioeconomic education or living in cities (where the access to fast food might be easy and of easy choice) is still low. Also, these results may suggest that urinary biomarkers of acrylamide may not capture fully dietary exposure of acrylamide in children.</p> <p>We also found an association between higher levels of acrylamide with increasing sampling year (2014-2017) in children, suggesting that the typical food eaten by children is still high in acrylamide. These results are also confirmed by the time trends analysis (below explained).</p> <p>Overall, our results may suggest a strategy to reduce acrylamide in certain foods and to make certain susceptible groups more aware of the acrylamide problem or in general healthy choices.</p>	
<p>4. Is there an impact from the mitigation for the production in food processing and manufacturing and</p>	<p>Strategies for mitigation and reduction of acrylamide in food and foodstuff have been carried out since the discovery in 2000.</p> <p>Currently, no country has set legally binding</p>	<p>Findings from this protocol are important to understand whether the measures adopted to decrease acrylamide formation in food have been effective in lowering the levels of exposure to acrylamide in the European population. Of</p>	<p>A manuscript has been produced and will be submitted within the next weeks</p>

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<p>REACH restrictions on the distribution of acrylamide exposure? Do we need to implement other restrictions to decrease the level of exposure of acrylamide?</p>	<p>maximum AA levels for foods. Only in 2017, the first EU regulation 2017/2158 was released with the aim to establish mitigation measures and benchmark levels for the reduction of AA in food. So far, no studies have been performed at European level to evaluate time trends of acrylamide exposure in the general population. Moreover, the awareness of acrylamide exposure has been shown to differ by European countries.</p> <p>Within the Task 10.4, one the research protocols aim to investigate whether the adopted measures at European level have been effective to decrease the exposure of acrylamide from 2002 up to now in the European population. Moreover, we investigate whether these trends are equally observed in all European countries. This study is performed using the aggregated data from published European studies with available biomarkers of acrylamide measured in urine or blood during the period 2002-2017 and aligned studies with available biomarkers of acrylamide measured in urine covering the period from 2014 up to now. We utilise data on AA and GA concentrations in blood and urine. Published studies have data available on biomarkers measured in urine and blood whereas the aligned studies will only have urinary biomarker data. Due to the heterogeneity in the measurements of acrylamide within participating studies, data</p>	<p>note, results from this project will be helpful to evaluate the current exposure of acrylamide in the European population.</p> <p>Results from analysis of aggregated data indicate an overall increase of acrylamide exposure between the year 2000 and 2017 in non-smokers. Such a trend results also from statistical analysis of individual data from HBM4EU aligned studies by comparing yearly means of single studies from children. Studies focusing on adults with samples collected after 2018 do not show increasing exposure or even declining values. Regional differences appear to affect absolute values, but not the overall time-trend of exposure.</p> <p>As in 2018, benchmark levels for acrylamide content in food have been adopted in Europe, our results may show first slight effects of these measures, but only indicated for adults as according data are still missing for children. We encourage further biomonitoring studies with samples taken after 2019 in both children and adults to check furtherly the effect of these measures in the European population.</p>	

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	<p>are harmonised to obtain comparable values using a transmatrix calculation. Time points are treated as continuous. Time-line analysis for aggregated data were performed to evaluate the relationship between time points and the mean of distribution of urine acrylamide biomarkers. The results are finalised and a manuscript has been drafted.</p>		
<p>5. Are the exposure levels a concern for health? Is the exposure to acrylamide associated to cancer, neurological alterations and fetal growth in humans? Is the health risk dependent on long term or intermittent exposure to low quantity of acrylamide?</p> <p>6. Are the health risks dependent on age and gender?</p>	<p>To answer the policy questions whether the exposure levels for acrylamide are a concern for health, specifically for cancer, neurological alteration and fetal growth, and whether the health risk is dependent on long-term or intermittent exposure to low quantities of acrylamide, activities are ongoing within WP13/WP14.</p> <p>To address these policy questions, Task 13.1 on mechanistic information for AOPs and 13.2 on the epidemiological evidences in relation to acrylamide and cancer, neurological and early developmental disorders and fetal growth have been implemented.</p> <p>1) Acrylamide and cancer: We performed a systematic literature review and meta-analysis of epidemiological studies evaluating the shape of the association between increasing levels of acrylamide and the risk of subtypes of cancer (Task 13.2). The meta-analysis has been finalised.</p> <p>A manuscript has been submitted (Please see</p>	<p>Questionnaires described above can support answering this question</p> <p>1) Acrylamide and cancer: Geometric mean urinary AAMA concentrations in the HBM4EU aligned studies were in the range of 50-70 µg/L in children and 20-100 µg/L in adults. In previously published studies with the general population, the corresponding range has been 30-73 µg/L. Taking the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA 2015) risk assessment for dietary intake of acrylamide as a basis, an acrylamide tumour risk of 1 : 1 000 at 0.425 µg/kg bw/d corresponding 28.8 µg/L of AAMA (in 70 kg adult) was estimated. This means that acrylamide cancer risk for children varied from 1:570 to 1:464 and in adults from 1:1384 to 1:288, when biomonitoring data from HBM4EU aligned studies were used as a starting point. These risks correspond to mean acrylamide intakes of 0.75 – 0.92 µg/kg bw/d in children and 0.31 – 1.47 µg/kg bw/d in adults, respectively. These levels are in line with the EFSA estimates on acrylamide intake via food</p>	<p>Acrylamide and cancer metanalysis: abstract presented to 33rd Annual Conference of the International Society for Environmental Epidemiology that was held between August 23 - 26, 2021.</p> <p>Manuscript submitted to Frontiers in Nutrition (accepted)</p> <p>Acrylamide and fetal growth meta-analysis: a manuscript has been submitted to Environment International (under review)</p> <p>Deliverable 13.6 will be published including information related to AOP for acrylamide and cancer and neurological alteration.</p> <p>Deliverable 13.7 will be published with information related to the acrylamide and fetal growth and cancer.</p> <p>Deliverable Report D14.8 has been</p>

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	<p>column 4).</p> <p>Information on the AOPs leading to the development of oesophageal, gastric, breast, lung, ovarian, endometrial pancreatic, prostate, renal and colorectal Cancer (Task 13.1) were also gathered. The molecular initiating event of the AOP involves the formation of adducts between acrylamide and its epoxide metabolite glycidamide and DNA. Acrylamide affects hormonal balances in animals, leading to increased occurrence of mammary gland tumors in rats. The main route of exposure is dietary acrylamide meaning that the gastrointestinal tract is exposed to considerable amounts of the agent; however, since the acrylamide molecule is small and hydrophilic, it reaches every organ and virtually every tissue in the body. In addition, we have conducted an animal experiment to test the effects of dietary acrylamide on colon tissue. For this purpose, 10 male Balb/c mice (6 weeks old) were randomised to one mock-treated and one acrylamide treated group. The mice in the treatment group received oral gavage of 0.1 mg/kg acrylamide (AA) daily for 4 weeks. At the end of the 4-week period, tissue samples (brain, epididymis + Vas and colon) were obtained from mice following euthanasiation. Brain and epididymis + Vas samples were snap frozen and sent to the Norwegian Institute of Public Health for further</p>	<p>(mean intake 0.4 - 1.9 µg/kg bw/d). The risk assessment is based on the Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit (BMDL10) of 0.17 mg/kg bw/d based on neoplastic effects in mice derived by EFSA (2015), it was concluded that acrylamide potentially increases the risk of developing cancer in all age groups of the general population, since the main exposure to acrylamide happens via dietary intake. EFSA (2015) derived for acrylamide a health-based limit value for dietary intake.</p> <p>This risk assessment has quite high uncertainty and is conservative since the risk was based on the linear extrapolation to zero from the mice carcinogenicity data using the BMDL10 value of 0.17 mg/kg bw/d derived from the most sensitive tumour type as a POD.</p> <p>Results from the meta-analysis, based on 31 epidemiological studies, showed that high dietary intake of acrylamide was not associated with an increased risk of any of the investigated specific cancers, including oral cavity, oesophageal, gastric, colon-rectal, pancreatic, prostate, bladder, lung, renal, lymphoma, myeloma, thyroid, brain, larynx, and melanoma. As a novel finding, we found that the potential shape of the association between different levels of dietary acrylamide and the risk of any of the specific cancers considered, if present, would be linear. Considering studies performed in Western geographical areas, a borderline</p>	<p>published containing information and results from the selected biomarkers of the effect for acrylamide.</p> <p>Deliverable D5.11 with information on the risk assessment.</p>

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	<p>processing. Colon samples were sent to “ATLAS Biolabs GmbH” (Berlin, Germany) for RNA sequencing, as a subcontract service. A list of differentiated genes and related pathways were identified in the acrylamide-treated group compared to the control group. Further data analysis is underway and will be completed by the end of the project.</p> <p>2) Acrylamide and neurological alteration: For Task 13.1 (mechanistic information for AOPs relevant for neurological and early developmental disorders including sex related disorders) and 13.2, critical assessment of possible associations with neurological alterations in cohorts, a literature search has been performed by NIPH Library on developmental neurotoxicity of acrylamide (AA) (human cohorts, occupational, animals and in vitro studies) resulting in approximately 500 abstracts after filtration (out of an initial search of 1389 abstracts; search was updated Nov 2020). A literature summary of cohort and mechanistic studies was performed. Different neurodevelopmental adverse effects in animals and humans as well as key event information from in vitro studies are summarised in forest plots and various adverse outcome pathways / networks are explored, selecting the impairment of learning, memory and cognitive function as adverse outcome.</p>	<p>increased risk of lymphoma was observed in relation to high intake of dietary acrylamide. In general, findings did not differ by smoking status except for lung cancer in smokers and melanoma for never smokers. Most of the epidemiological studies identified on acrylamide and cancer were performed using dietary assessment of acrylamide. There is a lack of epidemiological studies investigating the risk of acrylamide in relation to cancer using HBM studies. This observation is of importance since it may explain the reason why epidemiological studies have failed to show an increased risk of cancer with acrylamide exposure. We encourage further highquality epidemiological studies using biomarkers of acrylamide to understand better whether acrylamide is associated with cancer in humans.</p> <p>Results from the mechanistic information on AOP:</p> <p>Based on the literature review, increased risk of gastrointestinal cancer observed in experimental animals may be related to intermediate levels of acrylamide rather than low levels of exposure to acrylamide and may also be related to sex differences. No conclusions could be derived on whether the current exposure levels pose a concern for health or whether age plays a role on the risk of developing oesophageal, gastric, or colorectal cancer. Also, an increased risk of oesophageal</p>	

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	<p>3) Acrylamide and fetal growth: a dose response meta-analysis summarising the results of individual data available in this field has been performed. The study is the most up-to-date meta-analysis covering this topic, including 5 epidemiological studies. Among them, three were performed with estimated dietary acrylamide exposure assessed through dietary questionnaires and the remaining two with validated biomarkers of acrylamide i.e. hemoglobin adducts of acrylamide and glycidamide. Compared to the previous meta-analysis published by Zhag et al. in 2020, we added one study performed using biomarkers, one additional birth outcome (birth length) and we evaluated the shape of the relationship using the novel approach of dose-response meta-analysis whenever possible.</p> <p>The meta-analysis is finalised and a manuscript has been recently submitted.</p> <p>Implementation of specific effect biomarkers related with human exposure to AA through proteomic profiling (WP13 and WP14) has been performed. This proteomic panel aimed to identify new circulating markers of effect related to acrylamide exposure in the existing European EuroMix human biomonitoring study (n=141). Olink was used for a proteomics analysis of inflammation (92 proteins) and neurological markers.</p> <p>Risk assessment of acrylamide has been</p>	<p>cancer (on the basis of 341 cases) emerged in subjects with intermediate levels as compared to low acrylamide intake. In relation to gender, acrylamide might be associated with colorectal cancer with specific somatic mutations, differentially in men (increased risk if activating KRAS mutation) and women (decreased risk if truncating APC mutation). No mechanistic information was found on the pathways induced by acrylamide for the development of other types of cancers examined including breast, endometrial, pancreatic, lung and prostate. No conclusions could be derived on whether the current exposure levels pose a concern for health or whether age plays a role in the risk of developing oesophageal, gastric, or colorectal cancer.</p> <p>2) Acrylamide and neurological alteration: Health based guidance values are available to which the newly generated HBM data in the HBM4EU aligned studies can be compared. The critical endpoints are nerve damage or peripheral neuropathy in rats. For AAMA the share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the Biomonitoring equivalent (BE-value) of 16 µg/g crt ranges from 98.33%-100% for children and 90.20%-100% for adults. However, compared to a more recently derived HBM orientation values (OV)- calculated according to the EFSA BMDL10 value of 0.43 mg/kg b.w. per day for peripheral neuropathy in rats- 7% of adults (France and Portugal) had</p>	

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	<p>performed in WP 5.3, based on the aligned study data on urinary levels of acrylamide mercapturic acid (AAMA) and glycidamide mercapturic acid (GAMA). The risk assessment covers general dietary intake of acrylamide in the general population and cancer risk.</p>	<p>acrylamide values higher than the HBM-OV (291.4µg/L for adults with a body weight of 70 kg) and 2% of children had acrylamide values higher than HBM OV (321.7 µg/L for children).</p> <p>There are no studies on neurodevelopmental functional effects in the general population exposed to acrylamide. Moreover, evidence from animal studies indicate that acrylamide exposure during neural development has the potential to affect key events known to lead to cognitive impairment in children.</p> <p>The lowest “low observed adverse effect level” (LOAEL) reported for neurodevelopmental toxicity in rats was 0.5 mg/kg bw/day after maternal exposure of acrylamide in drinking water up to 3.0 mg/kg bw/day [starting at GD6 until 2 years of age]. However, in most cases the neurodevelopmental NOAEL was below the dose levels of acrylamide tested in the studies and therefore unknown. It is thus currently not established a NOAEL for developmental neurotoxicity of acrylamide.</p> <p>Furthermore, most in vitro studies were performed using concentrations far above the levels estimated from the daily dietary intake in the general population.</p> <p>Thus, there is an urgent need for further research to examine whether pre- and perinatal acrylamide exposure might impair neurodevelopment in humans. Also, to be able</p>	

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		<p>to elucidate which of the mechanisms attributed to acrylamide exposure are relevant for humans performing long-term studies at real-life concentrations in human relevant neural stem cell models are needed. The higher exposure in children than in adults makes it particularly important to assess the potential pre- and postnatal neurodevelopmental effects.</p> <p>Since it is currently not possible to estimate a threshold dose for induction of neurodevelopmental toxicity in experimental animal studies for use in risk assessment, there is consequently also insufficient evidence to conclude whether the developing brain is more susceptible to acrylamide toxicity than the adult brain. We did not identify any studies of neurodevelopmental effects in humans. Possible gender differences in acrylamide neurodevelopmental toxicity therefore need to be based on animal experiments, and there is not enough evidence to conclude on gender differences in relation to effects on the developing brain.</p> <p>3) acrylamide and fetal growth:</p> <p>Based on a dose-response meta analysis of epidemiological studies, we observed that higher gestational acrylamide exposure was associated with lower birth length, head circumference, and weight, and with a higher risk of SGA. Results were stronger and more consistent for the studies pooling the</p>	

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		<p>biomarkers. Moreover, whenever it was possible to investigate the shape of the relationship (only with birth weight), we found no clear evidence of departure from linearity. Based on the results of our current meta-analysis, we encourage the development of further epidemiological studies to confirm these results. In light of the Developmental Origins of Health and Disease hypothesis, our meta-analysis suggests that prenatal acrylamide exposure may have detrimental effects at a later age. However, in the meantime, based on the current body of evidence, we think a strategy to reduce the acrylamide intake of pregnant women through targeted public health education is warranted.</p> <p>In our studies we have identified a few potential biomarkers of effect associated with AA exposure. However, in order to get enough power, a higher number of individuals should be analysed, or individuals should be selected from a high vs a low exposure group. None of the associations were significant after correction for multiple testing but four proteins, JAM-B, CNTN5, CLEC10A and EPHB6, were significantly associated with AA-Hb-adducts following a Lasso procedure. These proteins are candidates for inclusion in larger cohort studies.</p>	

4 Aniline family

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<p>1. What is the current occupational exposure to aniline and different aniline derivatives (including diamine forming diisocyanates) in the EU?</p>	<p>The available data on the occupational exposure to relevant aniline compounds have been collected under WP7.1 and summarised under AD8.1 (Report on access to occupational data). According to this analysis, the data are scattered and its coverage is limited. Many aniline compounds are nowadays restricted, which limits occupational exposure to them. Use of MOCA and technical MDA is authorised under REACH and exposure to them is rather limited in terms of number of workers. Since biomonitoring is the only method to measure occupational exposure to them reliably, in WP9 those laboratories which are able to provide MOCA/MDA biomonitoring were identified. These laboratories performing analysis of different aniline compounds (including MOCA and MDA) have been listed in D9.3 (Database of candidate laboratories for the 1st prioritisation round of substances) and ICI/EQUAS for aromatic amines was performed between 2019-2020.</p> <p>Occupational exposure to aniline itself is mostly related to its use in chemical manufacturing. Regarding diisocyanates, a systematic review on occupational exposure to diisocyanates was made under HBM4EU. This showed that the recent biomonitoring data on occupational exposure to diisocyanates is limited, especially in some specific uses e.g. in construction sector (Scholten et al., Ann Work Expo Health. 2020 Jul 1;64(6):569-585). Therefore, an occupational</p>	<p>Occupational exposure to MOCA and MDA is limited mainly due to REACH authorisation. In those uses, in which it occurs (in case of MOCA specific polyurethane product manufacturing) biomonitoring is an important method to assess exposure and risk. When exposure is controlled properly, risk levels remain low. Available (although limited) HBM data on o-toluidine suggests low cancer risk for workers and well below to 1:1000000 for general population. New data from HBM4EU study suggests low, but still measurable exposure to MDI and HDI in construction sector, in use of MDI glues and in the motor vehicle sector. However, levels remained below or close to LOQ, especially when MDI glues, adhesives or sealants were used. In polyurethane foam spraying or in HDI paint spraying high air levels could be measured but the use of RPE kept the internal exposure low. Dermal wipe samples were often unable to detect exposure.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/AD8.1 (Report on access to occupational data) • Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds • Deliverable 9.5 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances

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	<p>study on the exposure to diisocyanates in specific sectors was designed. Focus was mainly on the use of MDI in different construction uses or in glues and the use of HDI in the motor vehicle sector. Preliminary results on this study suggest that the exposure especially to MDI remains rather low, below the proposed limit values for diisocyanates. These low levels require highly sensitive methods for their biomonitoring since the levels are close to the currently used LOQs. However, asthma risk cannot be excluded even at the relatively low exposure levels, as noted in risk assessment made under WP5.3. Therefore, monitoring of exposure and use and further development of highly sensitive HBM methods is needed. More sensitive methods to detect dermal exposure is also needed since dermal exposure can contribute to the health risk. PBPK models developed under WP 12 help us to convert urinary MDA/TDA levels as external intake allowing the assessment of asthma risk. There are also some data on the occupational exposure to specific anilines (carcinogen o-toluidine and sensitiser PDA) through e.g. hair dyes but the biomonitoring data on these exposures, which may concern large number of workers, is still limited. However, available biomonitoring data on o-toluidine allowed the risk assessment for workers and the general population.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D8.13 Report on occupational studies. (in preparation) • Scholten et al Ann Work Expo Health. 2020 Jul 1;64(6):569-585). • Louro et al 2019 Human biomonitoring in Health Risk Assessment in Europe: current practices and recommendations for the future. Int J Hyg Environ Health. 2019 Jun;222(5):727-737. <p>Publications in preparation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Huuskonen P et al. (2022) Health risk assessment of ortho-toluidine by utilising human biomonitoring data of workers and general population. Accepted for publication in Toxics. • Jones K et al., HBM4EU diisocyanates study – study protocol for a collaborative European human biological monitoring study on occupational exposure
<p>2. What is the exposure to paracetamol (aniline)</p>	<p>There are single studies in Germany and Denmark on the exposure of the general population to paracetamol. These have been described in the aniline scoping document (D4.2</p>	<p>Based on the data from two countries, paracetamol exposure in general population is ubiquitous. No new, additional data on paracetamol</p>	<p>Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances</p>

AD5.7 - Reporting for first and second set of substances	Security: Public
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metabolite) among the general population?	<p>Scoping documents for 2018). To get a better overview of the paracetamol exposure, inclusion of paracetamol in the studies conducted under WP8 in the general population would be needed. This is not, however, currently planned.</p> <p>The European HBM dashboard has 1 dataset (from Denmark) with paracetamol exposure data integrated.</p>	<p>exposure were produced within HBM4EU.</p>	
3. What are the risks related to these exposures?	<p>WP5.3 deliverable report D5.1 (Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: analysis of the current practice and 1st examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals) describes the recent risk assessment of MOCA under REACH, which serves as a good example on the use of biomonitoring in risk assessment.</p> <p>In 2018 a risk assessment utilising HBM data was performed for o-toluidine under WP5, included in the Deliverable Report D5.5 (Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals). In summary, a one-compartment model-based approach was used to estimate the urinary levels corresponding to the external intake levels of o-toluidine or vice versa. This allowed the comparison between available HBM data and existing binding occupational exposure level (OEL) and established cancer risk estimates. A scientific paper on this is in preparation (Huuskonen et al., 2022).</p>	<p>The risk assessment of f o-toluidine under WP5.3 suggested a cancer risk below 1:10 000. However, it should be noted that the exposure data used for the assessment was very limited, and therefore the risk assessment should be seen as an example, demonstrating how HBM data can be used to support the RA of o-toluidine. General population cancer risks were well below 1:1000000. If o-toluidine will become authorised under REACH, HBM is recommended to be used to support exposure assessment, as regardless of the uncertainties, it is the only method able to provide information on the total internal exposure via all routes of exposure.</p> <p>Regarding diiscyanates, the main health concern is related to asthma. Even at the relatively low exposure levels below the current exposure limit values, asthma risk cannot be excluded but still an increase in the number of</p>	<p>Deliverable report D5.1: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: analysis of the current practice and 1st examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p> <p>Deliverable Report D5.5: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p> <p>Deliverable report D5.11: Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p> <p>Deliverable report D8.13: Report on occupational studies.</p> <p>Deliverable 12.5: Risk characterisation of the 1st set of prioritised substances using external exposure estimated from HBM data: a methodological approach</p> <p>Louro et al., 2019. Human biomonitoring in Health Risk Assessment in Europe: current practices and recommendations for the</p>

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	<p>The results suggested that the workers exposed to o-toluidine have a cancer risk below 1:10 000. The exposure levels calculated based on HBM data were below the binding occupational exposure level set under the EU Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive (BOELV, 0.44 mg/m³ corresponding to 2.2 mg/L as urinary total o-toluidine).</p> <p>However, the result includes several uncertainties, related especially to the limited amount of HBM data available, and therefore the RA should be seen as an example. In addition, further data on the toxicokinetics of o-toluidine in occupational settings, focusing especially on the correlations between external intake and urinary levels, would strengthen the assessment.</p> <p>To strengthen risk assessment of o-toluidine, PBPK modelling to calculate external intake on the basis of the urinary o-toluidine levels was performed under WP12. The results of this modelling are comparable to those obtained earlier by using urinary mass balance-based calculation approach. These results were used to calculate RCRs and were reported in D12.5.</p> <p>AOPs for anilines have been developed under WP13 to support human health risk assessment.</p>	<p>asthma cases can be expected. Therefore, continuous monitoring of exposure is needed.</p>	<p>future. Int J Hyg Environ Health. 2019 Jun;222(5):727-737.</p> <p>Huuskonen P et al. (2022) Health risk assessment of ortho-toluidine by utilising human biomonitoring data of workers and general population. Accepted for publication in Toxics.</p>
<p>4. What is the possible impact of REACH on the exposure and risks?</p>	<p>WP5.3 deliverable report D5.1 (Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: analysis of the current practice and 1st examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals) describes the current situation with</p>	<p>It seems that REACH authorisation has already decreased the use of MOCA in Europe and strict risk management measures, which include the use of biomonitoring for the assessment of</p>	<p>Louro et al., 2019. Human biomonitoring in Health Risk Assessment in Europe: current practices and recommendations for the future. Int J Hyg Environ Health. 2019 Jun;222(5):727-737.</p>

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	<p>MOCA and MDA which are authorised under REACH. Because of the authorisation there is only a limited number of exposed workers in EU. Occupational biomonitoring data collected under WP7.1 and summarised under AD8.1 (Report on access to occupational data) describes a decline in the exposure to MOCA observed in UK and in Finland. Therefore, MOCA was not considered as a good candidate for further research under HBM4EU although laboratories performing biomonitoring of MOCA are still needed in EU as long as it is used.</p> <p>Regarding MDA, AD8.1 describes the potential exposure to MDA (and similar diamine TDA) via the production and use of diisocyanates.</p> <p>A study to collect new data on occupational exposure to diisocyanates was conducted in 5 countries between 2020-2021. Although the results cannot yet inform on the impact of REACH restriction, it will provide baseline data for the future assessment of the impact of REACH restriction/becoming EU OEL for diisocyanates.</p>	<p>exposure are required in authorisation conditions. The requirement on biomonitoring helps to ensure the low exposure levels at workplaces.</p> <p>Since REACH restriction on diisocyanates is coming in force only in 2023, it is too early to evaluate the possible impact of this restriction. HBM4EU diisocyanate study, however, provides baseline data for future assessment of the impact of the restriction. Since there is a binding limit value for diisocyanates also under preparation in EU, this is also likely to have an impact on the exposures. However, in HBM4EU diisocyanate study, in many cases MDI and HDI levels were already below these levels.</p>	<p>Deliverable report D8.13: Report on occupational studies.</p>

5 Aprotic solvents

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<p>2. What is the current internal exposure of the workers in EU to reprotoxic aprotic solvents, especially with respect to female workers at reproductive age, and do they exceed Guidance values (reference and HBM values), where they are available? What data gaps exist?</p> <p>3. Are there geographical differences and differences caused by industrial sector in the exposure of workers in EU to reprotoxic aprotic solvents?</p> <p>4. What is the current exposure of the general EU population to reprotoxic aprotic solvents, especially with respect to females at</p>	<p>In order to answer questions on exposure levels and sources and further support current and future HBM studies, WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe. For Aprotic solvents, questionnaires for adults are made available.</p> <p>No new data were obtained for aprotic solvents in the HBM4EU aligned studies. A literature search was carried out.</p> <p>Statistical analysis plan (SAP) for aprotic solvents is developed within WP10. The aim of the SAP is to set a procedure for answering the exposure related research questions defined in the scoping document. The general part of the SAP includes statistical plans for the evaluation of time trends, geographic comparisons, evaluation of exposure determinants, a strategy for the calculation of EU reference values and a plan for conducting uncertainty analysis. It is assumed that urine (urine-spot, urine-24h, urine-morning) will be the obligatory matrix to be used for determination of chosen NMP, NEP, DMF and DMAC metabolites. Optionally a number of parameters characterising urine will be determined - total volume of urine collected,</p>	<p>A literature search was carried out and revealed that exposure data for aprotic solvents are scarce for the general population in Europe. Data for the general population for NMP and NEP are available from Germany for children and adolescents (GerEs V) as well as for young adults of 20–30 years age (ESB-samples taken from 1991 to 2014).</p> <p>The analysis of time trends of NMP and NEP exposure (years 1991-2014) revealed a continuous exposure to both NMP and NEP over the time span investigated. For DMF (years 2000-2021) a > 50% decrease of AMCC concentrations could be observed for the time span investigated.</p> <p>Within HBM4EU, human biomonitoring guidance values for the general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) have been derived for NMP and NEP. For children, this value is 10 mg/L for both NMP and NEP. For adolescents and adults, an HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 15 mg/L has been derived both for NMP and NEP. For DMF, a provisional HBM-GV_{Workers} of 10 mg/g creatinine has been derived for the metabolite AMCC. For the purpose of this risk assessment, this value was adjusted</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Deliverable 5.9 “3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/deliverables/ • Deliverable 9.6 “Databases of candidate laboratories for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/deliverables/

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<p>reproductive age as well as mothers and their young children, and do they exceed Guidance values (reference and HBM values), where they are available? What data gaps exist?</p>	<p>urine density of the sample, concentration of creatinine in urine of the sample, osmotic concentration of urine of the sample, specific gravity of urine (ratio of urine density compared with water density). Certain obligatory or optional variables characterising participants of the study will be applied – age, sex, education, current labour status, industrial sector of occupation, life style (frequent use of chemical household products (for cleaning, etc.) or focus on natural „ecological“ products) and consumption patterns (frequency of usage of cosmetics).</p> <p>Comprehensive information on toxicokinetics of NMP, NEP, DMF and DMAC including the biological half-life and internal dosimetry of substances in question is gathered, available in D 12.7. Based on this information, available human physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models for NMP, NEP, DMF and DMAC linking an external exposure to an internal dosimetry (e.g., concentration in blood, urine or in tissues) are reviewed, available in AD 12.8 and AD 12.10.</p> <p>14 candidate laboratories in 7 countries have been identified for analysis of NMP, NEP, DMF and DMAC metabolite, available in D 9.6.</p> <p>HBM-GVs have been derived for the general population regarding NMP and</p>	<p>to a provisional HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 1 mg/g creatinine for a comparison with the data from ESB.</p> <p>A risk assessment of NMP, NEP and DMF (data from the German Environmental Specimen Bank) regarding reproductive toxicity has been based on these data for the general population and on the newly derived HBM-GV_{GenPop}. The assessment showed that exposure for adults, children and adolescents is well below the guidance values both for NMP and NEP as well as for DMF. Maximum values of the studies were a factor of 4.7 to 10 lower than the corresponding HBM-GV_{GenPop} values. The maximum value found in the data from ESB for the DMF metabolite AMCC was a factor of 2.5 lower than the provisional HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 1 mg/g creatinine.</p> <p>Even when considering the combined exposure to NMP and NEP, the values are not exceeded. The calculated hazard index (HI) was well below 1 in all cases considered (i.e., children, adolescents and adults) with maximum HI values of 0.3, indicating that there was no exceedance of the HBM-GVs. For young adults, the HI was calculated for the combined exposure to NMP, NEP and DMF resulting in a maximum HI value of 0.6. However, a possible combined exposure with other reprotoxic substances present in the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 12.7 “Biological half-life and internal dosimetry of the 2nd set of priority compounds” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/deliverables/ • Additional Deliverable 12.8 “Review of available models for the 2nd set of prioritised substances” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/deliverables/ • Additional Deliverable 12.10 “Report on the parameterisation of the 2nd set of priority compounds” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/deliverables/ <p>Publication: David M, Gerofke A, Lange R, Kolossa-Gehring M, Apel P. The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU): Human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) for the aprotic solvents N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP). Int J Hyg Environ Health. 2021 Sep;238:113856. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113856. Epub 2021 Oct 5. PMID: 34619432; PMCID: PMC8573589.</p>

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	<p>NEP and for workers regarding DMF and DMAC, available in D 5.9. Publication on NMP and NEP is available.</p> <p>The European HBM dashboard has 2 datasets with aprotic solvents exposure data integrated.</p> <p>Risk assessment of NMP, NEP and DMF with respect to the general population regarding reproductive toxicity has been performed in WP 5.3. (D5.11). It is based on German exposure data including the newly obtained German DMF exposure data as well as the newly derived HBM-GV_{GenPop}.</p>	<p>environment should be considered in “real-life-situations”, since these might increase the risk for common effects (Kortenkamp and Faust, 2018).</p> <p>However, the high percentage of values above the limit of quantification, clearly shows that the investigated German population was exposed to NMP, NEP and DMF. For NMP, the highest exposure was found in young children, but exposure pathways could not be revealed. Exposure to NEP was highest in adolescents and participants with low socio-economic status or migration backgrounds. Associations to usage of personal care products suggested that the choice of products had a distinct impact on NEP exposure.</p>	

6 Arsenic

1. Policy Question	2. Short Summary of Status	3. Concise answer to the policy questions – based on HBM4EU results	4. Links to relevant documents, such as the scoping document, HBM4EU deliverables and peer-reviewed articles.
<p>1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to arsenic?</p>	<p>In order to further support current and future HBM studies, HBM4EU developed a variety of publicly available groundwork materials for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe (WP7, HBM4EU online library). For arsenic species, questionnaires for adults and adolescents are available.</p> <p>A prioritised list with most suitable biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods has been produced (WP9, D9.7). Interlaboratory assays (ICI/EQUAS) have been organised for measurement of arsenic species in urine, as this was considered most appropriate. Chemical analyses of arsenic have been improved. A total of 3 laboratories participated in the ICI/EQUAS. There are 2 qualified laboratories (WP9, D9.8).</p> <p>A sampling frame has been established to align the planning of ongoing/planned studies to collect HBM data of the prioritised chemicals (including bisphenols) with EU wide coverage (WP8, D8.3).</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2018) have measured arsenic (6 markers: Total arsenic (As), arsenic(3+) (As III), arsenic(5+) (As V), monomethylarsonic</p>	<p>New HBM data collected in HBM4EU Aligned Studies show that P50 and P95 sum of DMA + MMA + As(III) + As(V) concentrations in teenagers are in the range of 2.27-5.52 µg/g crt and 6.65-15.93 µg/g crt respectively. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the BE-value of 6.4µg/L range from 15.63-52.00%. The extent of exceedance ranges from 1.55-3.36 in teenagers.</p> <p>P50 and P95 DMA concentrations are in the range of 1.44-3.59 µg/g crt and 5.01-12.57 µg/g crt, respectively.</p> <p>P50 and P95 MMA concentrations are in the range of 0.36-1.02 µg/g crt and 0.84-2.57 µg/g crt, respectively. P50 and P95 As(III) concentrations are in the range of 0.11-0.31 µg/g crt and 0.46-0.98 µg/g crt, respectively. P50 and P95 As(V) concentrations are in the range of 0.14-0.24 µg/g crt (3 studies P50 < detection level: 0.1 µg/L) and 0.22-1.01 µg/g crt (1 study P95 < detection level: 0.1µg/L), respectively.</p> <p>P50 and P95 arsenobetaine concentrations are in the range of 0.39-8.28 µg/g crt and 17.88-128.02 µg/g crt, respectively.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • European HBM dashboard that allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections by country obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Deliverable 7.8 Report on ongoing activities and existing data and data gaps: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-7-8-report-on-ongoing-activities-and-existing-data-and-data-gaps/

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	<p>acid (MMA), dimethylarsinic acid (DMA), and arsenobetaine (Asb)) in urine samples from teenagers between 12 and 18 years of age from 6 different sampling sites in Europe (Sweden, Spain, Slovenia, France, Belgium and Germany) representing 1445 individuals.</p> <p>A specific statistic data analysis plan for arsenic has been elaborated (WP10).</p> <p>A research protocol has been developed under the activities of WP 10 (Task 10.4) on the possibility of using available studies related to the As exposure. From the available data, prior to HBM4EU sampling frame, 30 studies in adults, adolescents, children and pregnant women were identified. Based on the diversity in study design, sampled matrices, sampling periods, sampled age groups, it was decided to not further use these studies to answer policy questions.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 7.9 Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-7-9-overall-report-on-wp7-documents-for-survey-design-study-protocols-sops-and-guidelines-and-questionnaires/ • Additional D8.3: Implementation of effect biomarkers and implementation of 2nd set priority chemicals in the aligned studies: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-8-3-implementation-of-effect-biomarkers-and-implementation-of-2nd-set-priority-chemicals-in-the-aligned-studies/ • Additional Deliverable 9.6 Partners performing chemical analyses of substances on the 1st priority list in the aligned studies: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-9-6-partners-performing-chemical-analyses-of-substances-on-the-1st-priority-list-in-the-aligned-studies/ • Additional D9.7: Partners performing chemical analyses of substances on the 2nd priority list in the aligned studies: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-9-7-partners-performing-chemical-analyses-of-substances-on-the-2nd-priority-list-in-the-

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			<p>aligned-studies/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-9-8-list-of-qualified-laboratories-scientific-evaluation-and-the-compilation-of-the-lists-of-the-laboratories-that-completed-successfully-the-hbm4eu-qaqc-programme-for-the-substances-inc/
<p>2. What biomonitoring and exposure (environmental and occupational) data on arsenic, relevant to the European population, are currently available.</p>	<p>WP7 collected information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium in an easily accessible tool providing up-to-date information.</p> <p>The European HBM dashboard provides summary statistics for HBM data from different European countries, with 14 aggregated datasets. In IPCHEM (Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring), metadata for 30 datasets are available. It consists of studies in newborns and their mothers, in children, in teenagers, and in adults. The studies measured arsenic in (cord) blood, breast milk, and/or urine. One data collection is included that measured arsenic in brain, bone, liver, kidney and lung tissue.</p> <p>Studies that assessed the different arsenic</p>	<p>In the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, arsenic has been assessed in 6 teenager studies consisting of 1445 teenagers between 12 and 18 years. Total As in urine is available in 596 teenagers; As III, As V, DMA, and MMA in 586 teenagers; and Asb in 505 teenagers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • European HBM dashboard that allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections by country obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Deliverable 4.6 Scoping documents for the second round priority substances: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-4-6-scoping-documents-for-the-second-round-priority-substances/ • IPCHEM: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

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	<p>species are limited.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2018) have measured arsenic (6 markers: Total As, As III, As V, MMA, DMA, Asb) in urine samples from teenagers between 12 and 18 years of age from 6 different studies in Europe (Sweden (Riskmaten Ungdom), Spain (BEA), Slovenia (CRP), France (Esteban), Belgium (FLEHSIV) and Germany (GerES)) representing 1445 individuals. Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore the number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p>		
<p>3. What is the geographic spread of the current exposure and how does it relate to different exposure sources (environmental; dietary sources)?</p>	<p>A critical review of the existing scientific literature was performed. In Europe there are several hotspots of arsenic contamination, including Hungary, Croatia, Finland and Spain. In these regions, arsenic exposure is mainly related to the type (thermal, drinking) and content of water. Maximal As concentrations were found to be between 8 and 8000 µg/l. Poland is an area where exposure to As in some regions depends on industrial emissions (above 10 µg/m³).</p> <p>In the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, the geographic spread of the current exposure has not been assessed, due to the limited number of studies available for Northern, Eastern, Southern, and Western Europe. The statistical analyses in the HBM4EU</p>	<p>Current exposure of the average EU population to arsenic from drinking water is low due to the limited presence of iAs in drinking water. The main source of iAs is diet, especially rice and other cereals, juices and seafood. Average exposure levels (daily doses) calculated from food intake and iAs concentrations in food were in the range of 0.07 to 0.20 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day for seven age-stratified population groups (from toddlers to very elderly) and P95 levels lay between 0.19 and 0.64 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day.</p> <p>iAs exposure estimates from dietary intake were compared with existing HBM data and matched well, indicating that main iAs intake of the general population is through dietary exposure.</p>	

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	<p>Aligned Studies focus on differences in exposures based on diet.</p> <p>Concerning the studies compiled before HBM4EU, geographical spread could not be assessed due to the diversity in study design, sampled matrices, analytical techniques, sampling periods, and sampled age groups.</p> <p>T5.3 summarised recent work related to background levels of inorganic arsenic (iAs) in food and environment in the European Union (EU). Most data included were from studies from 2000 until 2020. Exposure of different population groups was calculated by combining intake and iAs concentrations of food items to obtain daily doses. A conservative approach was used for iAs bioavailability, i.e. assumed to be 100%. -</p>	<p>The analyses in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies focus on differences in exposures based on diet. The sum of As(III), As(V), MMA, and DMA was associated with (recent) seafood and/or rice consumption in all cohorts of teenagers included in the analyses.</p>	
<p>4. Which population groups are most at risk?</p>	<p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2018) have measured arsenic (6 markers: Total As, As III, As V, MMA, DMA, Asb) in urine samples from teenagers between 12 and 18 years of age from 6 different sampling sites in Europe (Sweden, Spain, Slovenia, France, Belgium and Germany) representing 1445 individuals.</p> <p>The European HBM dashboard provides summary statistics for studies measuring arsenic exposure in newborns and their</p>	<p>Concerning the studies compiled before HBM4EU, it could not be assessed which population groups are most at risk due to the diversity in study design, sampled matrices, analytical techniques, and sampling periods.</p> <p>In the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, arsenic exposure was measured in teenagers. HBM data were compared with already available health-based guidance values for cancer and for non-cancer effects. Between 15.6 and 52.0 % of study participants exceeded the</p>	

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	<p>mothers, in children, in teenagers, and in adults.</p> <p>Risk assessment based on HBM data for arsenic has been performed by T5.3. iAs daily doses were calculated from urine iAs metabolites by reverse dose calculation. Daily iAs dose estimates were used for the assessment of cancer risks – based on dose-response relationship proposed by JEFCA (2011) and ECHA (2013) (WP5, D5.8).</p> <p>WP13 performed a brief literature survey to provide an up-to-date summary of mechanisms of action and susceptibility factors.</p>	<p>Biomonitoring Equivalent set as a guidance value to prevent adverse effects (hyperpigmentation and vascular complications).</p> <p>Sex and SES were no major exposure determinants in the aligned studies.</p> <p>The daily intake dose of iAs (0.16 µg kg⁻¹ bw/day including iAs, monomethylarsonic acid (MMA) and dimethylarsinic acid (DMA)) that was estimated based on average HBM levels from 28 HBM studies in different population groups in the EU (including from 11 to 1737 participants exposed to “normal” levels of iAs), and kinetic modelling corresponded with a lifetime excess lung cancer risk of 2.7 x 10⁻⁴. Credible justification of assumptions, necessary to assure the credibility of such calculation, was beyond the scope of this work, therefore, the calculated value must be interpreted with caution. The approach can be considered as conservative, overestimating the risk especially at low exposure levels.</p> <p>The magnitude of toxic manifestations of arsenic is influenced by individual characteristics such as age, gender, nutritional status, genetic factors, lifestyle, and the presence of other diseases. Many of these characteristics can affect the toxicity of arsenic via their impact on the metabolic pathway. In general, population-based investigations show that the male populations have a lower methylation capacity, which could make them</p>	

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		<p>more susceptible to arsenic toxicity than females. Highly effective methylation during infancy has also been observed, which may also be related to the effect of estrogen and folate donors on arsenic methylation.</p> <p>Susceptible subgroups may also be identified based on the mode of action of arsenic (which has not been fully elucidated). For instance, endocrine disruption by arsenic may be mediated via hormone receptors or steroid levels, which may differ across life stages or physiologic conditions resulting in differences in susceptibility between individuals.</p>	
<p>5. What factors (genetic polymorphisms) make people more susceptible or not to the risk of health effects due to arsenic exposure?</p> <p>Which are the best and most sensitive biomarkers for reliable identification of arsenic exposure and how can they be linked to potential adverse</p>	<p>WP13 performed a brief literature survey to provide an up-to-date summary of mechanisms of action and susceptibility factors.</p> <p>WP 13 (Task 13.2) and WP14 groups have coordinated the selection of biomarkers of effect according to their utility in human studies, the identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and novel biomarkers of effect and the decision criteria for their validation.</p> <p>Effect biomarkers for cancer, metabolic syndrome and diabetes, cardiovascular effects, and neurobehavioral endpoints were identified by a comprehensive literature search and consultation of the AOP-Wiki (WP14, D14.5/6 'Selection</p>	<p>As reported in AD13.6, preferred biomarkers are determination of arsenic and its chemical forms in urine. The sum of As(III), As(V), MMA, and DMA correlates well with drinking water concentration or estimated daily dose calculated using drinking water concentrations. The concentrations of total arsenic and iAs, MMA, and DMA are all fairly constant over time with small intra-individual variabilities. First morning voids of total arsenic are indicative of and correlated with subsequent voids throughout the day. For these reasons, speciated arsenic in urine (iAs III, iAs V, MMA, and DMA) are the preferred biomarker(s) for exposures to inorganic arsenic. Urinary DMA is widely included as one of the markers of iAs exposure. However, it can also be excreted in urine after direct ingestion or after ingestion of less toxic arsenosugars and arsenolipids</p>	<p>AD13.6 Draft answers to exposure-health policy questions for the 2nd priority compounds</p> <p>D14.5/6 'Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances</p>

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health-effects?	<p>criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances’).</p> <p>As part of the assessment of potential effects of various chemical compounds, including arsenic, human health, a publication was prepared entitled "Arsenic and human health. "Scoping review - the association between asthma and environmental chemicals".</p>	<p>hence overestimating the exposure to iAs. Biotransformation rate (i.e. methylation of arsenic species) has a major influence on arsenic tumorigenicity. The methylation patterns of arsenic have been reported to be potentially affected by genetic polymorphisms (ASMT3 polymorphisms) and epigenetics. Besides, increased KEAP1 and Nrf2 mutations and polymorphisms of NADPH oxidase may increase ROS-mediated carcinogenic and cardiovascular effects of arsenic, respectively.</p> <p>In HBM4EU Aligned Studies, arsenic species in urine have been measured in teenagers. The above mentioned mutations and polymorphisms have however not been assessed and hence not linked to arsenic exposure.</p> <p>Concerning the studies compiled before HBM4EU, no data on genetic polymorphisms are available that have not been published yet. Stajanko et al. 2019 (https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2018.11.045) reported on polymorphisms in the Slovenian Phime-Crome cohort.</p>	
6. What are possible health effects resulting from chronic low exposure to arsenic from food consumption?	<p>WP13 and WP14 performed brief literature searches to provide an up-to-date summary of health outcomes associated to arsenic exposure.</p> <p>In search of the interdependencies between the exposure and health effects and new specific effect biomarkers, in task</p>	<p>A causal association between human arsenic exposure and lung, skin, and bladder cancer has been recognised. The strength of evidence of causal associations with ischemic heart disease and cardiovascular disease, hypertension, stroke, diabetes, skin lesions, and effects on pregnancy outcomes (fetal and</p>	<p>Additional D12.10 Report on the parameterisation of the 2nd set of priority compounds: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-12-10-report-on-the-parameterisation-of-the-2nd-set-of-priority-compounds/</p> <p>AD13.6 Draft answers to exposure-health</p>

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	<p>12.3, parameterisation of the PBTk model was performed.</p> <p>The work performed within this task was presented in "AD12.10 - Report on parameterisation of the second set of priority substance"</p>	<p>infant morbidity, fetal loss, stillbirth, and neonatal mortality) is also considered to be robust. Causal associations with liver and kidney cancer, non-malignant respiratory disease, neurodevelopment, and effects on the immune system are less certain. A scoping review evaluating the link between arsenic exposure and asthma only found a potential association in epidemiological studies. US EPA is currently performing an in-depth investigation of the shape of the dose-response curves in the low dose region. The scientific community has not yet agreed whether it is possible or not to define a threshold for the carcinogenicity of arsenic.</p>	<p>policy questions for the 2nd priority compounds</p> <p>Deliverable 14.5 Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-14-5-selection-criteria-and-inventory-of-effect-biomarkers-for-the-2nd-set-of-substances/</p> <p>Tiina Mattila et al. Scoping Review—The Association between Asthma and Environmental Chemicals. Int J Environ Res Pub Hlth, 2021; doi:10.3390/ijerph18031323</p>
<p>7. What is the safe intake level for arsenic that is without any appreciable health risk in the general European population?</p>	<p>Data from 4 studies compiled before HBM4EU are used to study the effects of arsenic exposure on birth weight, gestational diabetes, and maternal blood pressure. This will enable to estimate changes in effect for increasing exposures within the observed exposure range. This will indicate whether the observed exposure levels are a reason for health concerns for newborns and their mothers.</p>	<p>Data analyses of exposure response associations are currently ongoing and will be reported by the end of HBM4EU. The analysis of existing cohort data will provide insight in exposure-effect associations and will enable to estimate changes in effect for increasing exposures within the observed exposure range. This will indicate whether the observed exposure levels are a reason for health concerns.</p> <p>The scientific community has not yet agreed whether it is possible or not to define a threshold for the carcinogenicity of arsenic.</p> <p>For non-neoplastic diseases a biomonitoring equivalent for inorganic arsenic has been proposed (Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology 58 (2010) to prevent adverse</p>	

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		effects (hyperpigmentation and vascular complications).	
8. What are the best analytical methods to allow for differentiating species in urine?	The determination of arsenic in biological specimens requires sensitive analytical methods, performed under good quality control conditions. Due to the possibility of separating the different chemical forms that are relevant in the toxicity assessment, it was considered that the assessment of the different forms alongside total arsenic would be the most advantageous biomarker in the exposure assessment.	The use of the ICP-MS technique in combination with separation techniques, e.g. HPLC, now appears to be the most advantageous analytical technique to use in the As exposure assessment. Under WP9 activities, laboratories invited to participate in proficiency testing were qualified on the basis of QA/QC checks carried out. Currently, the proficiency tests are completed, 2 laboratories that have successfully passed the controls are included in the list of laboratories performing the tests in the assessment of the second list of priority substances.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-9-8-list-of-qualified-laboratories-scientific-evaluation-and-the-compilation-of-the-lists-of-the-laboratories-that-completed-successfully-the-hbm4eu-qaqc-programme-for-the-substances-inc/
9. How can harmonised, validated and comparable information be collected to support and evaluate current policies?	<p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2018) have measured arsenic (6 markers: Total As, As III, As V, MMA, DMA, Asb) in urine samples from teenagers between 12 and 18 years of age from 6 different sampling sites in Europe (Sweden, Spain, Slovenia, France, Belgium and Germany) representing 1445 individuals.</p> <p>This is supported by the materials developed in WP7 (see question 1).</p>	<p>As HBM4EU Aligned Studies showed an association of arsenic exposure with seafood and rice intake and exceedance of BE-values, policy action could aim at reducing rice intake in children.</p> <p>Also we recommend to strive for more upfront harmonisation, more representative studies, and inclusion of additional age groups in future EU-wide initiatives.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Additional D8.3: Implementation of effect

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			biomarkers and implementation of 2nd set priority chemicals in the aligned studies: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-8-3-implementation-of-effect-biomarkers-and-implementation-of-2nd-set-priority-chemicals-in-the-aligned-studies/
10. How can HBM4EU results support European policy decisions?	The results of the project will identify stakeholder groups, prioritise the assessment of exposure to chemicals and meet the needs for biological monitoring research for stakeholders, starting with policy makers and researchers	The policy relevance of the results has been addressed in answers to specific policy questions mentioned above.	HBM4EU policy briefs and substance reports

7 Benzophenones

1. Policy Question	2. Short Summary of Status and of HBM4EU activities to answer the policy question	3. Concise answer to the policy questions – based on HBM4EU results	4. Links to relevant documents, such as the scoping document, HBM4EU deliverables and peer-reviewed articles.
<p>1. Are sensitive reliable and cost-effective methods and biomarkers available to measure UV filters?</p>	<p>List of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods is available (WP 9).</p> <p>UV-filters (benzophenones; BPs) are analysed as total, free or conjugated BPs in urine. Determination of total or conjugated BPs include enzymatic hydrolysis, for which various conditions have been described. Internal standards should be used for the analyses, preferably labelled standards of the target compounds. The extraction procedures consisted of dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction, SPE, and automated online SPE. The automated online SPE systems have the highest throughput. BP3 has been measured in most laboratories. Most laboratories used LC-MS/MS with ESI (positive and or negative) for the analysis of UV-filters.</p> <p>Analysis of HBM4EU UV filter samples originally covered four benzophenone biomarkers and was performed in urine. Proficiency tests were organised by IPASUM and included three rounds (three ICIs). Ultimately, two laboratories from two European countries (Germany and Denmark) qualified for the analysis of BP1 and BP3 in HBM4EU samples. BP2 and BP7 were included in the QA/QC program of HBM4EU, but no laboratories provided satisfactory results.</p> <p>As part of WP8 (fieldwork preparation) AD7.2 included information on stability of BP-3 in urine. It was reported that urinary conjugates of benzophenone-3 (BP-3) are stable for one week</p>	<p>Analytical methods are available to measure benzophenone UV filters in urine. Benzophenone-3 (BP3) is the urinary biomarker most commonly measured in this group.</p>	<p>Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances</p> <p>Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds</p> <p>Deliverable 9.5 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances</p> <p>Additional deliverable 7.2 Literature research and concept for a sample quality study on impact of thawing and freezing on integrity of human samples for selected 1st and 2nd priority substances</p> <p>Results of the UV-filters ICI/EQUAS are available in the online library of HBM4EU website, under the laboratories folder, ICI/EQUAS reports section.</p>

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	<p>when urine is stored at 4°C and for at least six months when stored at -70°C. In contrast, BP-3 conjugates commenced to degrade after three days when the urine was stored at room temperature.</p>		
<p>2. What are current exposure levels to benzophenones in the EU population (cumulative exposure from different exposures sources)?</p>	<p>Harmonised aggregated data and exposure distributions for BP-1, BP-3 and the metabolite 2,2'-dihydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone (DHMB) in urine, stratified by age and gender is available (WP 10-D10.6). These harmonised aggregated data are obtained from two data collections from Denmark: DEMOCOPHES with exposure data for children and adults, and DYMS (Danish Young Men Study) with exposure data for teenagers; and one from Germany: Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) with exposure data for young adults. Data is available from these collections on morning urine (DEMOCOPHES), random spot urine (RegionH) or 24 hr urine (ESB).</p> <p>The heterogeneity of the data collections (different age range, different sampling types, different sampling years) makes it difficult to compare the levels between data collections.</p> <p>Review on the available literature on Benzophenone-3 and -1 (WP13-WP14) includes maps showing number of studies from EU countries.</p> <p>The European HBM dashboard has 7 datasets with UV-filters exposure data integrated and in IPCHEM metadata for 10 datasets with UV-filters data are available.</p>	<p>Aligned studies results from 2014-2018 from studies in Germany, Luxembourg, Sweden, Norway, Spain, and Poland indicate that there is widespread exposure to BP-3 in adults and adolescents in Europe. Exposure to BP-2 and BP-7 was very limited (detected in less than 10% of urine samples). BP-3 and BP-1 were more commonly measured, with concentrations of BP-3 much higher than BP-1.</p> <p>Urinary concentrations of benzophenones were measured in six aligned studies within HBM4EU in 2014- 2018 in Germany, Luxembourg, Sweden, Norway, Spain, and Poland. Based on these studies, exposure to BP-2 and BP-7 was very limited (detected in less than 10% of urine samples). BP-3 and BP-1 were more commonly measured, with concentrations of BP-3 much higher than BP-1.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of urinary BP-1 concentrations in teenagers are in the range of 0.47 - 1.66 µg/g crt (1 study with P50 value < detection limit: 0.5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • HBM dashboard shows 7 datasets with UV filter exposure data, the dashboard will be updated to include data from aligned studies • https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Deliverable 10.6 Second annual list of exposure distributions and/or European Reference Values

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		<p>µg/L) and 6.66– 26.35 µg/g crt . In adults P50 and P95 are in the range of 0.37 – 0.69 µg/g crt (1 study with P50 value < detection limit: 0.5µg/L) and 6.85 - 20.43 µg/g crt in adults.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of urinary BP-3 concentrations are in the range of 0.88 - 3.68 µg/g crt (1 study with P50 < detection limit: 2 µg/L and 14.34-68.83 µg/g crt in teenagers and 0.94-2.33 µg/g crt (1 study with P50 value < detection limit: 2 µg/L) and 18.97 - 64.98 µg/g crt in adults.</p>	
<p>3. What are the major sources of exposure to benzophenones in the EU population and in vulnerable groups such as children and pregnant women?</p>	<p>Development of questionnaires for adults and adolescents was completed. The main variables in the questionnaire for UV filters cover use of cleaning products and scents in the home, consumption of food in food contact materials, use of cosmetics and hygiene products, type of sunscreen used, and DIY hobbies and activities.</p>	<p>Based on the literature review, personal care products are the most common exposure source, mainly sunscreen.</p> <p>This association was difficult to explore in the aligned studies because of missing data.</p> <p>In terms of personal care products determinants, only deodorant use showed any statistically significant association with UV filters. For both BP-1 and BP-3, higher levels were associated with every day or almost every day use of deodorant when compared to the reference of never or rarely use deodorant.</p> <p>No other statistically significant associations or patterns were</p>	<p>Specific questions (as part of the HBM4EU questionnaire) on exposure to benzophenones is available in deliverable 7.6</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-7-6-2nd-prioritisation-report-on-survey-design-study-protocols-sops-and-guidelines-tailored-and-transferred-questionnaires-for-recruitment-and-sampling/</p>

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		observed.	
4. Do exposure levels differ significantly between different EU countries (possibly related to climate)?	<p>Available data from literature (studies between 2004 – 2017) on average urinary BP-3 levels from studies from Western Europe (4 studies), Southern Europe (1 study) and Northern Europe (19 studies) were compared in a random-effects meta-regression model. No studies with data on urinary BP-3 were identified from Eastern Europe.</p>	<p>Based on available literature, there are no significant regional differences in BP-3 exposure in Europe. No significant difference in average urinary BP-3 levels between the three EU regions (North, West and South) were observed when adjusting for sex, age and period of sample collection. (WP13).</p>	<p>(WP13 review in process)</p>
5. Do exposure levels differ between different sub-groups: elderly, adults, and children? Between males and females? Between adults of different age groups? Between individuals in different ethnic subgroups (perhaps due to differences in use of sunscreen products)?	<p>Exposure distributions BP-1, BP-3 and DHMB in urine, stratified by age and gender is available (WP 10, D10.6), however only 3 data collections were obtained. Reported average BP-3 levels in urine stratified by age and gender based on the literature is available for Northern Europe (WP13).</p> <p>Aligned studies results indicate that sex was a significant determining factor with females having significantly higher BP-3 levels.</p>	<p>Based on results from the aligned studies, females have significantly higher BP-3 urinary concentrations than males.</p> <p>Based on the Danish DEMOCOPHES data collection that female children have slightly higher median urinary levels than male children for BP3.</p> <p>Studies in Northern Europe (literature information) showed no significant difference in reported average BP-3 levels in urine between males and females in these European studies. Average urinary BP-3 levels were significantly lower in children and adolescents compared to adults.</p> <p>In addition, a systematic integrative review of BP-3, together with a meta-analysis of human biomonitoring data on BP-3 and BP-1 was performed in</p>	<p>UV Filters: WP10 Report from Aligned Study Data for teenagers and adults (in process)</p> <p>Deliverable 10.6</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-10-6-second-annual-list-of-exposure-distributions-and-or-european-reference-values/</p>

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		<p>WP14. The meta-analysis of HBM studies showed that urinary BP-3 concentrations were around 10- and 20- fold higher in North America compared to Europe and Asia, respectively. Although median urinary BP-3 concentrations usually found in Europe correspond to a low-dose range, top percentiles of population exposure (P90 and P95) were significantly higher, being possibly linked to peak-exposure scenarios after sunscreen and cosmetic use.</p>	
<p>6. Are current exposure levels safe in relation to the endocrine and carcinogenic properties of benzophenones? (for the general population and for vulnerable groups such as children and pregnant women)?</p>	<p>Appropriate effect biomarkers were identified (WP 14.1) These include:</p> <p>Reproductive hormones: BP-3 could alter the androgen/estrogen balance based on experimental findings, and urinary exposure to BP-3 was associated with decreased serum TT levels in adolescent males in the NHANES. Thyroid hormones: Exposure to BP-3 is associated with altered thyroid hormone levels in several studies, including both pregnant women and adults. Experimental studies support that benzophenones may alter thyroid hormone balance by influencing their central regulation and metabolism and inhibition of thyroid peroxidase (TPO) appears as a potential mechanism.</p> <p>WP12 prepared a review of available PBTK models for benzophenones. Three human model PBTK models for benzophenones have been published.</p> <p>A review of human toxicokinetic studies (WP13-14)</p>	<p>The most sensitive endpoint for the hazardous properties of benzophenone-3 was maternal and developmental toxicity.</p> <p>Risk assessment of BP-3 based on urinary levels and effect levels, in studies from 2010 and 2013 showed that exposure estimates of BP-3 ranged from 0.60 to 4.40 µg/g creatinine for the average exposure, and 16.30 to 392.00 µg/g creatinine for the reasonable worst-case exposure. With the derived provisional HBM guidance value of 333 µg/g creatinine, the exposure estimates of the average exposure did not exceed the guidance value. The exposure estimates of the extensive exposure did exceed the guidance value.</p>	<p>The risk assessment of BP3 is included in Deliverable 5.8 Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals.</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-5-8-human-biomonitoring-in-risk-assessment-3rd-set-of-examples-on-the-use-of-hbm-in-risk-assessments-of-hbm4eu-priority-chemicals/</p> <p>D5.11 HBM risk assessment 4th set of examples</p> <p>Published manuscript comparing results of risk assessment using HBM data and traditional risk assessment approaches is available:</p>

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	<p>highlighted that high internal free BP-3 concentrations are achieved in few hours after a unique whole-body exposure to a sunscreen formulation containing BP-3 at lower concentrations than those allowed by the current European regulation (max. 6% weight/weight of sunscreen formulation). Revision of both animal and in vitro studies has identified some of the effects elicited at the lowest doses. Benzophenone-1 (BP-1) appears considerably more estrogenic and anti-androgenic than BP-3, showing a longer half-life.</p> <p>While human toxicokinetic intervention studies only measured BP-3, human internal BP-1 data after sunscreen and cosmetic use is currently unknown, being this information important to improve the comparability between rodent and human toxicokinetic data. There is a need to assess BP-1 and BP-3 concentrations in cosmetic products commercialised in Europe, as well as to better characterise human peak-exposure scenarios after sunscreen and cosmetic use.</p> <p>Provisional HBM guidance values was determined based on effects on spermatocytes in developing pups.</p> <p>Risk assessment of BP-3 based on urinary levels and effect levels, in studies from 2010 and 2013 has been performed, and updated based on aligned studies results from 2014-2018.</p>	<p>Based on data from the aligned studies in 2014-2018 the average and reasonable worst-case scenario exposure levels did not exceed the provisional HBM guidance value. Urinary levels (average <LOQ to 3.68 µg/g and reasonable worst-case exposure 18.97 to 68.83 µg/g) were below the guidance value and were no longer of concern.</p> <p>This finding implies that in general there is no risk indicated to the population included in the aligned studies. There are notable differences in exposure between the groups investigated, with the most highly exposed groups approaching (but not surpassing) the acceptable risk levels for BP-3.</p> <p>There is a need to assess BP-1 and BP-3 concentrations in cosmetic products commercialised in Europe, as well as to better characterise human peak-exposure scenarios after sunscreen and cosmetic use.</p>	<p>Rousselle C, Meslin M, Berman T, Woutersen M, Bil W, Wildeman J, Chaudhry Q. Using Human Biomonitoring Data to Support Risk Assessment of Cosmetic Ingredients-A Case Study of Benzophenone-3. <i>Toxics</i>. 2022 Feb 19;10(2):96. doi: 10.3390/toxics10020096. PMID: 35202282; PMCID: PMC8877280.</p> <p>PBTK model for benzophenones available, https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-12-8-review-of-available-models-for-the-2nd-set-of-prioritised-substances/</p> <p>Review of effect biomarkers for benzophenones available: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-14-5-selection-criteria-and-inventory-of-effect-biomarkers-for-the-2nd-set-of-substances/</p>
<p>7. Was the restriction of BP-3 in cosmetics in the EU (September 2017) effective in</p>	<p>When comparing the results of the literature from 2010-2013 with results of the aligned studies in 2014-2018, both median and 95th percentile urinary concentrations are lower in later studies.</p>	<p>Yes, urinary levels of BP-3 were lower in 2014-2018 compared to those in 2010-2013. Data is not available to evaluate whether exposure to other</p>	<p>Data is available, document in process (D5.11)</p>

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<p>reducing public exposure? Did exposure to other benzophenone or other UV filter compounds increase as a result?</p>	<p>Of the six studies the highest Risk Characterisation Ratio at the P95 was 0.2, where it was 1.15 in the previous assessment.</p>	<p>UV filters increased during this period.</p>	

8 Bisphenols

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<p>1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to BPA, BPS and BPF?</p>	<p>In order to further support current and future HBM studies, HBM4EU developed a variety of publicly available groundwork materials for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe. (WP7, HBM4EU online library)</p> <p>A prioritised list with most suitable biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods has been produced (WP9, D9.2, D9.7).</p> <p>Interlaboratory assays (ICI/EQUAS) have been organised. Chemical analyses of BPS and BPF have been improved. A total of 32 laboratories participated in the ICI/EQUAS. The number of qualified laboratories per biomarker are: 24 for BPA, 18 for BPS and 13 for BPF (WP9, D9.8).</p> <p>A sampling frame has been established to align the planning of ongoing/planned studies to collect HBM data of the prioritised chemicals (including bisphenols) with EU wide coverage (WP8, D8.8).</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2021) have measured bisphenols (3 markers: BPA, BPS and BPF) in urine samples from adult men and women</p>	<p>The European HBM dashboard reports urinary BPA levels comparable between the three age categories (children, teenagers and adults), indicating that BPA exposure is similar for children, teenagers and adults. The individual data collections prepared and made available within HBM4EU also contained aggregated data stratified by sex and educational level. From these stratifications it can be seen that the BPA concentrations are in general higher in men compared to women for all three age categories. Second, there seems a trend that teenagers and adults with higher educational level have lower exposure levels to BPA compared to teenagers and adults with medium educational level.</p> <p>New HBM data collected in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies show that median levels of urinary BPA are still pronounced in all European regions. The P50 of BPA varied between 0.55 and 2.35 µg/g creatinine and P95 between 2.41 and 12.19 µg/ g creatinine. The substitutes BPF and BPS are also detected in most participants and concern is raised as their toxicity is not well known. P50 and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • HBM4EU online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ <p>Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/Deliverable D8.8: Progress report on strategies adopted to align HBM studies across Europe and preliminary results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable D9.2: Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances • AD 9.3: Report on activities in the analytical phase • Deliverable D9.7: First report on analytical results and new methods development • Deliverable 9.8: List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds • European HBM dashboard that allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project:

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	<p>between 20 and 39 years of age from 11 different sampling sites in Europe (DK, IS, FI, PL, CZ, HR, PT, FR, CH, DE, LU) representing 2756 individuals. Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore the number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p> <p>A specific statistic data analysis plan for bisphenols has been elaborated (WP10, D10.5).</p> <p>In addition, the European HBM dashboard provides summary statistics for HBM data from different European countries, with 33 aggregated datasets including bisphenols exposure data. In IPCHEM, metadata are available for 44 datasets on Bisphenols.</p> <p>Aggregated data for BPA concentration in urine samples were reported in 13 studies involving children, in 8 studies involving teenagers and in 12 studies involving adults. All studies included at least 54 participants and samples were collected between 2005 and 2015.</p> <p>Aggregated data for bisphenol F, S and BPA free/unconjugated could not be obtained as for each of the three chemicals, only 1 study involving children and only 1 study involving adults were reported.</p> <p>HBM based indicators for bisphenols</p>	<p>P95 of urinary BPS concentrations are in the range of 0.06 – 0.34 µg/g creatinine (4 studies have a P50 value < detection limit: 0.01, 0.09 and 0.05 µg/L) and 0.39- 8.77 µg/g creatinine, respectively. The share of individuals with exposure levels of BPS exceeding HBM-GV of 1 µg/L range from 0.56%-19.26%.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of urinary BPF concentrations are in the range of 0.10 -0.72 µg/g creatinine (3 studies have a P50 value < detection limit: 0.03, and 0.15 µg/L) and 0.56-17.03 µg/g creatinine respectively. The P95 values of the substitute BPF are higher compared to those of BPA in 5 of 11 sampling sites.</p>	<p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM) that includes metadata and aggregated data from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#discovery Deliverable D10.6: Second annual list of exposure distributions and/or European Reference Values Deliverable 10.12: Statistical analysis plan co-funded studies of WP8 including the plans for bisphenols for the aligned studies (link not available in the HBM4EU website yet). Research protocol describing the ongoing statistical analyses for the research questions on BPs using existing data collections (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-package-webpage/data-management-and-analysis/research-protocols-codebooks/).

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	with indicator graphs on time patterns, geographical differences and health impact have been developed under WP5 (statistical analysis in progress)		
<p>2. Do different regulatory controls across the EU concerning in particular BPA lead to different exposures?</p>	<p>The Policy Brief and Substance Report for Bisphenols (in progress) presents an overview of current EU policies related to bisphenols (WP2). Since 2011 different measures have been taken to limit population exposure to BPA at the European level. It has been banned from infant feeding bottles across Europe (Commission Directive 2011/8/EU) and its use in certain food-contact materials has been further restricted since 2018. Additional measures have been taken in several countries. For example, France banned BPA in all food contact materials (French Law No 2012-1442), other countries (Denmark, Belgium and Sweden) banned it in those materials intended for children under age of 3.</p> <p>HBM4EU has generated EU-wide HBM data on bisphenols both by collecting data from different existing studies and by generating new data in 11 countries representing the 4 European Regions (North, East, South and West) in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies.</p> <p>HBM based indicators for bisphenols</p>	<p>Comparing the results of different HBM4EU Aligned Studies between the 4 European geographical areas (North, East, South and West) revealed that median BPA levels of exposure are higher than exposure levels for substituents (BPF and BPS) in all of Europe. The P95 values of the substitute BPF are however higher compared to those of BPA in 5 of 11 sampling sites. The Northern area is globally less exposed to bisphenols than other areas.</p> <p>When HBM4EU Aligned Studies data were compared to data from the DEMOCOPHES project that preceded HBM4EU, some changes can be observed (e.g. a decrease of BPA in Denmark and an increase in Poland and Luxembourg; an increase in BPS Czech Republic), but whether this is related to differences in regulation is unclear at this stage. The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data will form baseline European human exposure levels for BPA and its substituents BPS and BPF, allowing follow up studies to monitor increased or decreased usage.</p> <p>A mapping of BPA substitution which</p>	<p>Deliverable 10.12: Statistical analysis plan co-funded studies of WP8 including the plans for bisphenols for the aligned studies (link not available in the HBM4EU website yet).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research protocol describing the ongoing statistical analyses for the research questions on BPs using existing data collections (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-package-webpage/data-management-and-analysis/research-protocols-codebooks/) • HBM4EU Policy brief – Bisphenols (in preparation)

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	<p>with indicator graphs on time patterns, geographical differences and health impact are being developed under WP5 (statistical analysis in progress).</p>	<p>includes human biomonitoring data on less regulated bisphenols is needed as well as the investigation of human exposure and effects and the assessment of need for further regulation.</p>	
<p>3. Are bisphenols exposure levels of concern for health?</p>	<p>Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population have been derived for BPA and BPS, and a substance dossier on BPF has been prepared. Data for derivation of HBMB-GVs for BF were not sufficiently robust. HBM-GVs for BPA have also been derived based on the recent draft opinion of EFSA on TDI (WP5, D5.14 - see answer to Policy Question 8)</p> <p>Risk assessment based on HBM data for bisphenols has been performed for BPA and BPS (WP5, D5.8).</p> <p>A strategy for the selection of effect biomarkers for potential implementation in HBM4EU aligned studies has been outlined in relation to bisphenols (WP14, AD14.3).</p> <p>First inventory of effect biomarkers for bisphenols has been produced through extensive literature review: BDNF, kisspeptin and gene expression of nuclear receptors were prioritised (WP14, D14.3; Mustieles et al. 2020, Steffensen et al. 2020). New effect</p>	<p>BPA exposure levels measured in the adult population from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies are below the established HBM-GVs based on the temporary tolerable daily intake (t-TDI) of 4 µg/kg bw/day. If the HBM-GVs would be based on the new draft EFSA proposal for a TDI, all measured values would largely exceed the HBM-GV. For populations in which exposure exceeds the HBM-GV, health risks cannot be excluded. In eight sampling locations out of ten, at least 5% of the European adults (20-39 years) from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies exceed the HBM-GV for BPS. The most concerned studies were conducted in Southern Europe.</p> <p>Human biomonitoring, toxicity and toxicokinetics data are needed to assess the health risk of exposure to other BPA analogues.</p> <p>Since HBM4EU Aligned Studies indicate co-exposure to BPA and its substituents BPS and BPF, mixture studies should be considered, particularly since BPA substituents appear to display similar effects to BPA</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable D5.8: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals • Deliverable 5.14: Derivation of Bisphenol A HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population and occupationally exposed adults • Deliverable 5.9: 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values • HBM4EU input to the EFSA draft re-evaluation of the health risks of BPA derived from its presence in food • HBM4EU Indicator 2.2 Human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) • Information of effect biomarkers available on: • Deliverable D14.3: Report on available biomarkers of effect of utility in human epidemiological studies for the 1st set of prioritised substances • AD14.3: Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies Bisphenol A as a case-study • Deliverable 13.4: Report on AOPs of priority substances • Peer-reviewed articles from HBM4EU: • Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU): Human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) derived for bisphenol A. (Ougier et al., 2021) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106563 • Mustieles et al. Bisphenol A and its analogues: a

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	<p>biomarkers were developed linking BPA to health effects (e.g. behaviour, Mustieles et al. 2022) and were shown to have added value in human studies, increasing the weight of evidence for causal relationship between exposure and adverse health outcome.</p> <p>A report on adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) for the first set of HBM4EU prioritised substances (including bisphenols) within HBM4EU has been produced (D13.4)</p>	<p>and to be linked to similar AOPs.</p> <p>A cohort HBM4EU case study (INMA-Granada cohort) linked BPA childhood exposure to a potential biomarker of effect, the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), and an adverse outcome pathway leading to behavioural and cognitive alterations. Childhood BPA exposure was linked to higher BDNF DNA methylation at adolescence. An adverse outcome pathway (AOP) network was also constructed, supporting that BPA may interfere with BDNF signalling through different but converging biological mechanisms (thyroid, estrogenic and glutamatergic-related pathways), potentially leading to behavioral and cognitive impairments (Mustieles et al., 2022).</p>	<p>comprehensive review to identify and prioritise effect biomarkers for human biomonitoring. Environment International. 2020; 144:105811. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105811</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steffensen I-L, Dirven H, Couderq S, David A, D’Cruz SC, Fernández MF, Mustieles V, Rodríguez-Carrillo A, Hofer T. Bisphenols and Oxidative Stress Biomarkers—Associations Found in Human Studies, Evaluation of Methods Used, and Strengths and Weaknesses of the Biomarkers. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 2020; 17(10):3609. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17103609 Mustieles V, Rodríguez-Carrillo A, Vela-Soria F, D’Cruz SC, David A, Smagulova F, Mundo-López A, Olivas-Martínez A, Reina-Pérez I, Olea N, Freire C, Arrebola JP, F. Fernández MF. BDNF as a potential mediator between childhood BPA exposure and behavioral function in adolescent boys from the INMA-Granada cohort, Science of The Total Environment, Volume 803, 2022, 150014, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150014
<p>4. Is occupational exposure of cashiers a health concern?</p>	<p>The presence of BPA in thermal paper represents a threat most especially to cashiers, who are in constant contact with the material. BPA was restricted from use in thermal paper in 2016, with entering into force in 2020.</p> <p>Risk assessment based HBM data for bisphenols has been performed for BPA and BPS (WP5, D5.8).</p> <p>A HBM4EU systematic review on retrieved 30 studies on occupational</p>	<p>Because of the background environmental exposure to bisphenols, it has not been possible to derive an HBM-GV for workers.</p> <p>Available data in the literature and gathered under the project framework indicate that the risk from occupational exposure should not be disregarded, especially in industrial scenarios with BPA exposure levels 10-20-fold higher than background exposures, and that protective measures need to be taken</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverable D5.8: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals AD12.13: Updates on the contribution to answering policy questions for the 1st and 2nd second set of priority substances (link not available in the HBM4EU website yet) <p>Peer-reviewed articles from HBM4EU:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bousoumah R, Leso V, Iavicoli I, Huuskonen P, Viegas S, Porras SP., Santonen T, Frery N, Robert A,

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	<p>human biomonitoring of BPA and only 4 and 2 publications on BPS and BPF, respectively (Bousoumah et al. 2022).</p> <p>Bisphenol intake estimates have been derived based on the aggregate data available within the European HBM dashboard, that include both the HBM4EU repository data, as well as the data from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies (WP12, AD12.13).</p>	<p>regarding BPS exposure.</p> <p>Regarding the data coming from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies of bisphenols, the estimated median daily intake of BPA for adults across different European countries was 0.19 µg/kg_bw/day. The estimated median daily intake level of BPF for adults of France and Luxembourg was 0.004 µg/kg_bw/day. For BPS, it was 0.0001 µg/kg_bw/day for adults of Czech Republic, France and Luxembourg. As regards the data coming from other studies, the countries with the lower exposure to BPA were Belgium, Czech Republic and Denmark with the median daily intake for adults of 0.13 µg/kg_bw/day compared to Israel where the median concentration was 0.27 µg/kg_bw/day. These data indicate that exposure of adults does not exceed the reference levels for any of the adults, independent of their occupational activity. However, should the newly proposed TDI of 0.04 ng/kg_bw/day be established, occupational exposure of cashiers (similarly to other non-occupational groups) to BPA will be of health concern.</p> <p>Taking into account the current policies leading to the substitution of BPA by analogue substances, there is a need for research on the occupational</p>	<p>Ndaw S. Biomonitoring of occupational exposure to bisphenol A, bisphenol S and bisphenol F: A systematic review. Sci Total Environ. Volume 783, 2021, 146905. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146905</p>

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		<p>exposure to these compounds, including BPS and BPF. This would include studying cashier work in which BPS may have replaced BPA (Bousoumah et al. 2021).</p>	
<p>5. What is the toxicity of BPA substitutes and are current exposure level of concern?</p>	<p>New computational tools, based on text mining (using artificial intelligence) and on systems biology tools, have been developed to assess the most likely toxic outcomes of exposure to BPS and BPF.</p> <p>Adverse Outcome Pathways studies on BPS and BPF suggested that these compounds are linked to health effects such as metabolic diseases and cancer.</p> <p>European HBM dashboard: the BPA exposure of the Elfe study in pregnant women was estimated individually from the HBM data (here, the urinary concentration of total BPA) using a reverse dosimetry approach based on PBPK modelling. The aim was to estimate the internal exposure in the mothers and their foetuses (WP12, AD12.5).</p> <p>Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population have been derived for BPA and BPS, and a substance dossier on BPF has been prepared. Data for derivation of HBMB-GVs for BF were</p>	<p>Using computational tools developed under the project framework, obesity appeared as one of the major potential health endpoints of BPS exposure (Carvaillo et al.2019). BPF has been linked to an adverse outcome pathway (AOP) network for thyroid cancer (Rugard et al. 2020).</p> <p>Both a lifecourse PBTK model and a pregnancy PBTK model were used to allow for more accurate reconstruction of external exposure taking note of the physiological and metabolic differences characteristic of different age windows during the lifecourse and in utero. Estimated internal exposure levels of the developing foetus were only 10 to 20% higher than in the mother.</p> <p>The recommended HBM-GV for BPS is based on endocrine disrupting health effects occurring in animals at very low doses and was set in HBM4EU at 1 µg/L based on animal toxicity studies for mammary gland and neurodevelopmental toxicity (since these were the outcomes with highest sensitivity to BPS). Between 2014-2021, in all sampling locations except</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 5.14: Derivation of Bisphenol A HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population and occupational exposed adults • Deliverable 5.9: 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values • AD12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data <p>Peer-reviewed articles from HBM4EU:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carvaillo, J-C., Barouki, R., Coumoul, X., Audouze, K., 2019. Linking bisphenol S as an environmental chemical stressor to key events and adverse outcomes using a text mining-based computational approach. EHP- Environmental Health Perspectives. https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP4200 • Rugard M., Coumoul X., Carvaillo J-C., Barouki R., Audouze K. (2020) Deciphering Adverse Outcome Pathway Network Linked to Bisphenol F Using Text Mining and Systems Toxicology Approaches, Toxicological Sciences, 173 (1), 32–40, https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfz214

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	<p>not sufficiently robust. HBM-GVs for BPA have also been derived based on the recent draft opinion of EFSA on TDI (WP5, D5.14 - see answer to Policy Question 8)</p> <p>HBM based indicators for bisphenols with indicator graphs on time patterns, geographical differences and health impact are being developed under WP5 (statistical analysis in progress).</p>	<p>Poland and Germany, the P95 value, representing the 5% most exposed participants, exceeds the guidance value of 1 µg/L.</p> <p>Because of the current EFSA re-evaluation and draft proposal for a (much lower) TDI value for BPA, it is critical to revise those for BPA substituents as well.</p> <p>There is a need to explore the health impacts of bisphenols further (particularly substituents), to support hazard and risk assessment as well as evaluate the impact of regulatory actions - those already in place and future wider restrictions on bisphenol exposure in European population.</p>	
<p>6. Are health risks age and gender dependent?</p>	<p>An online consultation on existing HBM surveys (124 surveys analysed) was performed. Results showed that bisphenols were mostly studied in the Northern and Western Region. In studies in children, bisphenols were among the most analysed substances (WP 7, D7.1)</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2021) have measured bisphenols (3 markers: BPA, BPS and BPF) in urine samples from adult men and women between 20 and 39 years of age from 11 different sampling sites in Europe (DK, IS, FI, PL, CZ, HR, PT, FR, CH,</p>	<p>From the collected HBM data (sampling between 2005 and 2015) that are available via the European HBM dashboard, it seems that urinary BPA levels are similar for children, teenagers and adults. However, the HBM-GV of BPA for children is lower than for adults, illustrating their higher sensitivity to adverse health effects of BPA exposure.</p> <p>The individual data collections prepared and made available within HBM4EU also contained aggregated data stratified by sex and educational level. From these stratifications it can</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable D7.1: Report on ongoing activities and existing data and data gaps for the 1st prioritised substances including a list of metadata that can be uploaded in IPCheM • Deliverable D7.8: Report on ongoing activities and existing data and data gaps • European HBM dashboard allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Deliverable 12.3: Biological half-life and internal dosimetry of the 1st set of priority compounds • Deliverable 12.8: Report on the results of exposure reconstruction algorithms on available HBM data in the EU for all priority compounds (link not available in the HBM4EU website yet)

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	<p>DE, LU) representing 2756 individuals. Specific questionnaires for different age and sex groups were developed to identify exposure levels and sources of exposure to bisphenols.</p> <p>A specific statistic data analysis plan for bisphenols has been elaborated (WP10, D10.5).</p> <p>In addition, the European HBM dashboard provides summary statistics for HBM data from different European countries, with 33 datasets including Bisphenols exposure data. In IPCHEM, metadata are available for 44 datasets on Bisphenols.</p> <p>Biological half-lives (t1/2) in human have been compiled to inform exposure modelling (WP12, D12.3).</p> <p>A dedicated physiology-based toxicokinetic (PBTK) model to link HBM data, environmental monitoring and external exposure modelling was developed and implemented to obtain BPA, BPS and BPF intake estimates derived from the HBM4EU HBM data (WP12, D12.8). The BPA exposure of the Elfe study in pregnant women was estimated individually from the HBM data (urinary concentration of total BPA) using a reverse dosimetry approach based on PBPK modelling. Also, the placental levels were</p>	<p>be seen that the BPA concentrations are in general higher in men compared to women for all three age categories.</p> <p>For BPA we were able to estimate intake levels based on the available HBM data and to differentiate internal dose in relation to age, accounting for the significant differences in bioavailability related to the age-dependent maturity of the detoxification process (slower in early developmental stages and maximal capacity at one year of age). Internal exposure levels of the developing foetus are 10 to 20% higher than in the mother. Also, internal dose modification under co-exposure to BPA, BPS and BPF has been investigated; co-exposure to BPS and BPF only marginally changes the foetal exposure to BPA.</p> <p>Estimated median adult daily intake levels of BPA, BPF and BPS derived from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies showed no significant difference between male and female gender.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AD12.13: Updates on the contribution to answering policy questions for the 1st and 2nd second set of priority substances (link not available in the HBM4EU website yet)

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	<p>estimated based on urinary levels.</p> <p>Bisphenol intake estimates have been derived based on the aggregate data available within the European HBM dashboard, that include both the HBM4EU repository data, as well as the one from the HBM4EU aligned studies (WP12, AD12.13).</p>		
<p>7. Can we find evidence for low-dose effects within mixtures?</p>	<p>A biomonitoring case study was performed assessing co-exposure to BPA and five bisphenol analogues in blood and urine samples of an adult cohort with a diet rich in canned foodstuffs (Gonzalez et al.2020).</p> <p>A mixture risk assessment case study was performed assessing combined exposures to bisphenols and other chemicals with focus on male reproductive health outcomes (WP15).</p>	<p>Two different HBM4EU case studies refer to low-dose effects within mixtures. A biomonitoring survey of co-exposure to bisphenols (BPA and analogues) by consumers of canned foodstuffs indicates that participants with a diet rich in canned food were more exposed to BPA when compared to the control group. Trace levels of other BP analogues were found only promptly, but at much lower quantities than those of BPA.</p> <p>A mixture risk assessment with focus on male reproductive health shows that combined exposures to bisphenols and other chemicals is associated with declines in semen quality in Western countries. The exposure levels to these chemicals were relatively low since they were determined based on human biomonitoring studies.</p>	<p>González N, Marquès M, Cunha SC, Fernandes JO, Domingo JL, Nadal M. Biomonitoring of co-exposure to bisphenols by consumers of canned foodstuffs, Environment International, Volume 140, 2020, 105760,</p>
<p>8. How can HBM feed into assessment of</p>	<p>Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population have been derived for BPA</p>	<p>An HBM-GV of 230 µg /L was derived for BPA exposure in adults and 135 µg/L for BPA exposure in children (>3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 5.14: Derivation of Bisphenol A HBM Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for the general population and occupational exposed adults

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<p>the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) for BPA, as set by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)?</p>	<p>and BPS, and a substance dossier on BPF has been prepared. Data for derivation of HBMB-GVs for BF were not sufficiently robust. An HBM-GV for BPA has also been derived based on the recent draft opinion of EFSA on TDI (WP5, D5.14).</p>	<p>years). Below these values no adverse effects are expected according to current knowledge. The HBM-GV was set at a urinary concentration of total BPA consistent with a steady-state exposure to the temporary TDI of 4 µg/kg bw/day derived by EFSA in 2015 based on kidney weight increase in mice. The EFSA Panel on Food Contact and Materials, Enzymes and Processing Aids (CEP) recently released a consultation for a re-evaluation of the t-TDI set in 2015 that would result in a TDI of 0.04 ng/kg bw/d of total BPA. The provisional HBM-GVs recalculated based on the proposed TDI using PBPK modelling are 2.3 ng total BPA/l urine for adults and 1.4 ng total BPA/l urine for children assuming 100% oral intake in each case. If these new values would be confirmed this would mean that essentially all the European population is above the TDI and health risks cannot be excluded. HBM4EU recommends that the guidance values for the BPA substituents should in this case also be revisited.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 5.9: 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values • HBM4EU input to the EFSA draft re-evaluation of the health risks of BPA derived from its presence in food • Peer-reviewed articles from HBM4EU: • Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU): Human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) derived for bisphenol A. (Ougier et al., 2021) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106563
<p>9. Is it important to eliminate legacy BPA from material cycles (i.e. waste till receipt rolls)</p>	<p>A report on “HBM4EU Priority Substances in the Circular Economy” focuses on how human biomonitoring can support understanding of exposure to chemicals via secondary material</p>	<p>HBM4EU prepares a report on certain chemicals in the circular economy. The report will focus on how human biomonitoring can support understanding of exposure to chemicals via secondary material flows</p>	

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<p>when implementing a circular economy in order to protect human health?</p>	<p>flows and recycling. (WP2, in progress)</p>	<p>and recycling. This will be addressed through five case studies, three of which will focus on bisphenols - in consumer goods made from recycled plastics, in recycled paper, and in dietary exposure from reusing sewage sludge and wastewater on agricultural lands.</p>	

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9 Cadmium

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<p>1. What is the current exposure of the European population to Cd?</p>	<p>Inventory of studies holding Cd exposure data was obtained through WP7 (Task 7.1) with an online questionnaire which was distributed with an aim to identify existing HBM studies. Within WP10 (task 10.4) a substance-specific research protocol has been elaborated to exploit the available datasets with an aim to assess current Cd exposure of the European population and its geographical distribution. Individual data has been received for 32 studies from 15 countries in all 4 geographic regions, covering population groups of children, adolescents, adults, pregnant or lactating women and new-borns. The data refers to the time period 2007-2018. The existing data collection includes 22428 single measurement data, with the largest proportion of data for morning urine (n=7688), followed by whole blood (n=6740), spot random urine (n=3615) and cord blood (n=2717). The most represented groups are children and adults.</p> <p>Cd was measured in urine samples of the adult age group from the HBM4EU aligned studies.</p> <p>For Cd, questionnaires for adults,</p>	<p>The European HBM dashboard has 41 datasets with Cd exposure data integrated and in IPCHEM metadata for 74 datasets with Cd data are available.</p> <p>Based on the concentration ranges reported for adults, the levels in urine span from below LOD to 3.15 µg/L and in blood from below LOD to 7.07 µg/L. In cord blood the levels are <LOD-5.31 µg/L, while in children <LOD-1.33 µg/L (blood) and <LOD-5.18 µg/L (urine) and in adolescents <LOD-22.9 µg/L (blood) and <LOD-0.154 µg/L (urine) The LODs ranged between 0.0001 and 0.06 µg/L in urine, between 0.02 and 0.2 µg/L in blood, and between 0.01 and 0.12 in cord blood.</p> <p>New data for cadmium from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies included 2510 individuals. P50 and P95 of urinary cadmium concentrations are in the range of 0.10-0.37 µg/g crt and 0.26- 1.71 µg/g crt across studies in adults. For the subpopulation of non-smokers P50 and P95 of urinary cadmium concentrations are in the range of 0.09- 0.36 µg/g crt and 0.23- 1.56 µg/g crt across studies in adults.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scoping document for cadmium and hexavalent chromium: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/HBM4EU_D4.9_Scoping_Documents_HBM4EU_priority_substances_v1.0-Cadmium.pdf; or deliverable D4.9: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/HBM4EU_D4.9_Scoping_Documents_HBM4EU_priority_substances_v1.0.pdf • Preparation of publications in progress (Snoj Tratnik et al., Cadmium exposure among European residents and its geographical variability; Current Cd exposure in adults across Europe: Results from the HBM4EU aligned studies survey 2014-2021) • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-

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	<p>adolescents and children are available.</p> <p>Questionnaires for the 2nd occupational study on e-waste (incl. total Cd as a biomarker) have also been developed.</p> <p>The newly derived data from HBM4EU Aligned Studies includes data from 9 countries (10 studies) in urine of adults (20-39 years old) and represents the time-period 2014-2021. Biomarker data from 8 countries (9 studies) was assured by the HBM4EU QA/QC program. The participating studies are distributed among 4 geographical areas of Europe and include the following countries: Denmark, Iceland, Czech Republic, Poland, Croatia, Portugal, France, Luxembourg, and Germany.</p>		<p>library/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/
<p>2. Does the exposure to Cd differ significantly between countries and population groups? What are the main reasons for differences in exposure?</p>	<p>The data from existing and HBM4EU aligned studies were compared between the countries, regions (North, East, South, West) and based on the NUTS areas across Europe.</p>	<p>There were no distinct geographic patterns observed, although the HBM4EU Aligned Studies data revealed differences in internal exposure up to a factor 3 between the specific EU study sites.</p> <p>When comparing the four regions, higher levels were observed in West and East than in North and South, but after accounting for the main influencing factors (age, sex, smoking status and sampling year), the differences between the regions were not statistically significant.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cadmium indicators report (VITO) Preparation of publications in progress (Snoj Tratnik et al., Cadmium exposure among European residents and its geographical variability; Current Cd exposure in adults across Europe: Results from the HBM4EU aligned studies survey 2014-2021)
<p>3. Is there a significant time trend of Cd levels in</p>	<p>Only 3 datasets have been identified that have repeated Cd measurements available: German ESB and GerES (from</p>	<p>No significant time trend was revealed from the existing and the HBM4EU aligned studies data. As described by Becker et al. (2013), no obvious</p>	<p>Cadmium indicators report (VITO)</p>

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<p>existing population studies?</p>	<p>1986), Czech Republic (from 1996) and Belgium with limited time points (3). Therefore, data is insufficient to evaluate time-trend on the EU-wide scale.</p>	<p>trends of decreasing Cd concentrations have been observed in neither of the followed population groups in Germany. Similarly, also in Czech Republic, no significant trend was reported (Cerna et al., 2012).</p> <p>The data from HBM4EU Aligned studies (2014-2021) and its comparison with the DEMOCOPHES data (2012-2014) confirmed that there is no obvious time trend in the last decade. The exposure levels in adults from the two time periods are similar.</p>	
<p>4. Is there a link between high soil contamination with Cd and human exposure via dietary sources?</p>	<p>Within the work package WP5 (task 5.3) available data has been identified and applied into the mathematical models to describe the transfer from soil via fertilisers to plants (dietary source) and from plant to human via diet. Due to the scarcity of the external data available (soil, food, fertilisers, etc), the application was limited to the region-specific case study in Slovenia. The local case study is described in the Deliverable 5.8. The model enables to predict an oral intake via data on Cd concentrations in soil, phosphate fertilisers and food. Furthermore, European databases were exploited to obtain Cd concentrations in soil, percentages of agricultural areas and phosphorous fertiliser application for different countries and NUTS areas.</p>	<p>Linking HBM and „environmental data” revealed that there is a significant contribution of Cd exposure in humans from phosphorous fertilisers.</p> <p>Meta-analysis of existing data, representing the period 2007-2018, showed inconsistent associations between HBM and soil cadmium concentrations across different countries, population groups or different types of matrices. At specific study sites, positive and statistically significant associations between Cd in soil and Cd in urine and/or blood were observed, suggesting a link between Cd in soil and exposure level through consumption of local food in those areas and/or population groups. This was further confirmed by positive associations between HBM data and percentage of agricultural and/or cropland, and phosphorous fertiliser consumption in the older HBM datasets as well as in the new datasets from the HBM4EU Aligned studies. Furthermore, association analysis with individual food consumption data</p>	<p>Deliverable Report D5.8: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p> <p>Preparation of publications in progress (Snoj Tratnik et al., Cadmium exposure among European residents and its geographical variability)</p>

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		<p>available from participants' questionnaires in the Aligned studies showed an important contribution of vegetarian diet to the overall exposure, with approx. 35% higher levels in vegetarians as opposed to non-vegetarians.</p>	
<p>5. Which population groups are most at risk?</p>	<p>Dietary intake limit values are derived based on the relationship between renal tubular impairments (proteinuria) and urinary Cd for women aged above 50 years (EFSA, JEFCA, ATSDR). The kidney dysfunction is considered as the critical effect, but there is also evidence for low dose bone effects.</p> <p>The EFSA evaluation (2009) of the dietary Cd exposure showed that exposure of some subgroups, such as vegetarians, children and smokers and people living in highly contaminated areas could exceed the TWI of 2.5 ug/kg bw/week by about 2-fold. However, the revised assessment (EFSA 2012) indicated that the actual risk of adverse effects for an individual at current dietary exposure in the EU was low for adults, because the TWI was established based on an early indicator of changes in kidney function suggesting possible kidney damage later in life.</p> <p>Within task 5.3 (Deliverable 5.5), evaluation of fractions of urinary samples exceeding the threshold value of 1 µg/g creatinine has been assessed for the</p>	<p>The task 5.3 analysis indicated exceedance of the HBM guidance value for the higher percentile of exposure. These data, however, are not representative of the population at large and should be dealt with caution.</p> <p>Osteoporosis cases attributable to Cd exposure was estimated in three European countries (Belgium, France and Spain), based on measured urinary Cd levels from HBM studies conducted in these countries. The targeted population was women over 55 years old. Around 23% of the cases were attributed to Cd exposure. In women aged under 55, it was estimated that between 6 and 34% of the considered populations under 55 years were at risk for osteoporosis.</p>	<p>Deliverable Report D5.5: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals.</p> <p>Deliverable 13.4: Report on AOPs of priority substances</p> <p>Deliverable 13.5: Identified gaps for the establishment of AOPs and required studies</p> <p>Ougier E, Fiore K, Rousselle C, Assunção R, Martins C, Buekers J. Burden of osteoporosis and costs associated with human biomonitored cadmium exposure in three European countries: France, Spain and Belgium. <i>Int J Hyg Environ Health</i>. 2021 May;234:113747. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113747. Epub 2021 Apr 13. PMID: 33862487.</p>

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	<p>available HBM data for women >50 years.</p> <p>Furthermore, attributable burden of disease related to Cd exposure was calculated in women aged > 50 years for chronic kidney disease, as a critical health effect, and osteoporosis at hip or spine. However, the estimations are preliminary and still premature for the use in policy recommendation.</p> <p>The main uncertainty arises from the questionable causality between Cd exposure and bone/kidney effects at low doses of exposure (below 5 µg Cd/g creatinine) that are commonly observed in the general European population.</p> <p>This has been outlined also in the Deliverables 13.4 and 13.5 elaborated within the task 13.2 with a purpose to establish exposure-health relationships.</p>		
<p>6. Are the overall exposure levels (in different population groups) above any health-relevant assessment levels (HBM guidance values, TDI)?</p>	<p>The methodology agreed within the framework of the HBM4EU project was used to derive HBM-GVs of urinary cadmium for the general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) and for workers (HBM-GV_{Worker}) exposed to cadmium (Cd) and its compounds. Taken into account the accumulation of Cd in the human body throughout life, HBM4EU derived age-dependent alert values to prevent exceeding the guidance value of 1 µg/g creatinine for adults over 50 years and</p>	<p>The task 5.3 analysis indicated exceedance of the HBM guidance value for the higher percentile of exposure. These data, however, are not representative of the population at large and should be dealt with caution.</p> <p>Also based on the EFSA evaluation of the dietary Cd exposure, mean exposure of adults across Europe is close to, or slightly exceeding the TWI of 2.5 µg/kg bw/week.</p> <p>In the aligned studies, the share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the HBM-GV</p>	<p>Cadmium indicators report (VITO)</p> <p>Deliverable Report D5.5: Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals.</p> <p>Lamkarkach F, Ougier E, Garnier R, Viau C, Kolossa-Gehring M, Lange R, Apel P. Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU): Human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) derived</p>

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	<p>therefore prevent adverse kidney effects. These were set to 0.1 µg/g creatinine (crt) for children of 10 years of age or younger, 0.2 µg/g crt for 11-20 years, 0.3 µg/g crt for 21-30 years, 0.5 µg/g crt for 31-40 years, 0.8 µg/g crt for 41-50 years (Lamkarkach et al., 2021).</p> <p>For occupational exposure, an HBM-GV_{Worker} of 2 µg/g creat is derived from the study of Chaumont et al., (2011) for U-Cd, and in addition to this recommendation a HBM-GV_{Worker} for B-Cd of 5 µg/L is also proposed. The HBM-GV_{Worker} for U-Cd is similar to the biological limit value (BLV) set by the new amendment of the European Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive in June 2019 (2 µg/g creat for U-Cd).</p> <p>The work conducted within task 5.3 (Deliverable 5.5) included evaluation of fractions of urinary samples exceeding the threshold value of 1 µg/g creatinine (critical Cd urinary level established by EFSA; HBM-I value and HBM4EU HBM guidance value) from the available HBM data (urinary Cd in women >50 years from Spain and France – BIOAMBIENT_ES and ENNS studies; and urinary Cd in women 35-45 years from 17 EU countries - DEMOCOPHES).</p> <p>Furthermore, HBM4EU Aligned Studies data was used to estimate the percentage</p>	<p>value of 0.3 µg/g crt for adults (21-30 years) ranges from 2.13-56.39%. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the HBM-GV value of 0.5 µg/g crt for adults (31-40 years) ranges from 0-35.43%. For the subpopulation of non-smokers the share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the HBM-GV value of 0.3 µg/g crt for adults (21-30 years) ranges from 0.96-51.22%. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the HBM-GV value of 0.5 µg/g crt for adults (31-40 years) ranges from 0-33.88%.</p> <p>So, at most study sites, there is a certain proportion of people that showed elevated exposure, with levels that cannot be considered safe.</p> <p>A comprehensive PubMed search identified recent HBM studies together with mechanistic data that allowed the selection of sensitive and specific biomarkers of effect for Cd exposure (WP14). The most frequently used biomarkers of effect were β-2-microglobulin (B2-MG) and N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase (NAG) in relation to renal tubular dysfunction. Omics-based biomarkers (e.g. changes in the (epi-)genome, transcriptome, proteome and metabolome) were considered promising biomarkers of effect, which will need to be validated in future HBM studies (Ventura et al., 2021).</p>	<p>for cadmium and its compounds. Environ Int. 2021 Feb;147:106337.</p> <p>Ventura et al. Biomarkers of effect as determined in human biomonitoring studies on hexavalent chromium and cadmium in the period 2008-2020. Environ Res. 2021; 197:110998. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.110998.</p>

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	of study population exceeding the age-dependant HBM-GVs.		
7. Has the regulation under REACH had the favourable impact like a reduction of GM/median concentrations?	<p>Based on the very limited availability of the systematically repeated exposure data available (as explained under the time trends policy question activities), this question will be difficult to answer at this stage and will have to wait until repeated HBM exercises are performed in the future.</p> <p>However, HBM4EU Aligned Studies data enabled comparison with the DEMOCOPHES study data collected in DK, SE, CZ, HU, PL, SK, ES, SI, BE, LU and DE in years 2011-2012.</p>	<p>The cadmium levels in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies are broadly similar to those of the previous DEMOCOPHES study that sampled children and their mothers between 2011 and 2012.</p> <p>Based on the available datasets there seems not yet a clear trend for decreasing internal concentrations of Cd with time.</p>	Cadmium indicators report (VITO)
8. Are environmental quality standards for Cd in water sufficiently restrictive to protect human health from exposure to cadmium via the environment and via dietary sources?	This question has been addressed within WP10 and WP12, but the work will continue in PARC. A PBPK model has been developed for cadmium, exposure reconstruction to estimate dietary intake was based on numerous studies on different geographic scales and population sizes covering a large part of the EU Member States (including HBM4EU Aligned Studies data).	<p>Based on the available HBM data, mean daily intake of Cd is in the range of 0.1 to 0.7 µg/kg bw/day, with the highest levels observed in Poland, indicating that the highly exposed individuals might be close to the EFSA tolerable weekly intake of 2.5 µg/kg bw/week.</p> <p>This shows that the current cadmium regulations and measures are not protective enough and that further reduction of Cd exposure in the general population is needed.</p>	<p>Deliverable AD12.5: Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data.</p> <p>Deliverable D12.8: Report on the results of exposure reconstruction algorithms on available HBM data in the EU for all priority compounds.</p>
9. What is the maximum acceptable level for Cd in food stuffs?	Regulation (EC) No. 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 sets maximum levels for Cd in foodstuffs (https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02006R1881-20150521). The maximum levels are set		

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	<p>at 0.050 mg/kg for vegetables (excluding root and tuber and leaf vegetables), fruits and meat (without offal and horsemeat); 0.10 mg/kg for root and tuber vegetables, and cereal grains (excluding wheat and rice); 0.20 mg/kg for leaf vegetables, wheat grains, rice and soy beans; 1.0 mg/kg for funghi (excluding some exceptions), etc. However, the levels in food continue to be reviewed by the Commission.</p>		
<p>10. Can input be given to the decision as to whether the exemption for Cd in quantum dots under the RoHS Directive can be scrapped?</p>	<p>It is difficult to establish such a relationship for the general population, as currently the level of exposure is rather low and the time trends not established. Moreover, at this stage studies on occupational exposure in production line are also not available. It is currently difficult to assess the risks of Cd in quantum dots for the general population as this requires specific modelling for Cd exposure for use of Cd-containing quantum dots in electronic equipment. No attempts have been made in WP12 to model quantum dot related exposure of workers to Cd.</p>		

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10 Chemical mixtures

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<p>1. What is the information need of regulatory bodies and stakeholders?</p>	<p>Unintentional chemical mixtures, that result from exposures from the ambient and indoor environment, occupation, consumer products and cosmetics, food, etcetera are of societal concern as chemicals in the human body may in combination possess hazardous (toxic) properties and may adversely affect human health. One particular concern is the potential impact of exposure to mixtures of pesticides arising from occupational exposure, dietary, domestic use or via the wider environment. In addition, new chemicals and new applications of existing chemicals are continuously introduced to the market. Thus, intentional and unintentional exposure to mixtures of chemicals possessing hazardous properties add to the total chemical burden to which the population is exposed.</p> <p>While mixtures are high on the research, regulatory and policy agendas, opinions on how to deal with mixture risk problems vary considerably. This became apparent from a first exploratory assessment, carried out in the framework of HBM4EU WP15, of potential information needs from a governance perspective for mixture risk management. In this exercise, a set of questions was used in structured interviews</p>	<p>In the absence of real-life mixture exposure data, documentation of actual health risks in the population to date is rather limited. The current regulatory practice is still largely based on considering single chemical substances. One of the main conclusions of the structured interviews was that information needs from policy makers and experts are still rather diffuse and unarticulated, in line with the ‘systemic risk’ nature of mixtures. Thus, consequences for functionality of HBM mixture data cannot directly be derived. Also, views on responsibilities and criteria to guide risk reduction strategies varied considerably. Potential problems in cooperation between different policy domains (like DG’s) were seen as mainly stemming from differences in regulations and the absence of a common regulatory framework. The statement published in 2018 and 2020 (Bopp et al., 2018, Drakvik et al., 2020) includes a call for action to ensure better management to protect public health and the environment from hazardous chemical mixtures. Such action should include initiatives that investigate the opportunities for including prospective mixture risk assessment in all relevant regulatory frameworks. Precautionary approaches and intermediate measures could already be applied for regulatory purposes, even though significant knowledge and data gaps</p>	<p>Deliverable 15.1 Information needs from policy makers translated in terms of functionality of HBM mixture information https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-1-information-needs-from-policy-makers-translated-in-terms-of-functionality-of-hbm-mixture-information/</p> <p>Bopp SK, Barouki R, Brack W, Dalla Costa S, Dorne JCM, Drakvik PE, Faust M, Karjalainen TK, Kephelopoulos S, van Klaveren J, Kolossa-Gehring M, Kortenkamp A, Lebrecht E, Lettieri T, Nørager S, Rüegg J, Tarazona JV, Trier X, van de Water B, van Gils J, Bergman Å. Current EU research activities on combined exposure to multiple chemicals. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2018 Nov;120:544-562. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2018.07.037. Epub 2018 Aug 28. PMID: 30170309; PMCID: PMC6192826.</p> <p>Drakvik E, Altenburger R, Aoki Y,</p>

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	<p>with researchers and policy makers to delineate the current discourse on mixture risk governance. Information needs on mixtures was operationalised here as “How can we effectively and efficiently manage the health risks associated with chemical mixtures in the European population in such a way that residual mixture risks are considered acceptable from a public health and personal health point of view, while maintaining to the degree possible the societal and personal benefits of the products that lead to the mixture exposures”.</p> <p>The conclusions from the literature and interviews were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixture can be viewed as ‘systemic risks’ given the properties of uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity and the general ‘embeddedness’ of chemicals in daily life; risk governance approaches for mixtures should therefore be targeted as such and the contextual aspects may require tailored approaches instead of generic regulation. • The information needs from policy makers and experts are, at least at the time of the assessment, still rather diffuse and unarticulated. • As can be expected from the literature on systemic risks, views on responsibilities and criteria to guide risk reduction strategies vary considerably; this warrants 	<p>remain. Furthermore, a European strategy needs to be defined for the governance of combined exposure to multiple chemicals and mixtures. The strategy would include research aimed at scientific advancement in mechanistic understanding and modelling techniques, as well as research to address regulatory and policy needs.</p> <p>With the aim to improve current procedures for risk assessment of chemical mixtures, various approaches were being investigated within HBM4EU. These include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) estimating exposure to mixtures through differential network analyses of existing HBM data (Task 15.1); ii) estimating exposure to pesticide mixtures using suspect screening analyses of citizens living in ‘hot spot’ versus ‘control’ areas (Task 15.2); and iii) establishing an advanced workflow for assessing mixture health effects (Task 15.3). These activities were carried out by HBM4EU partners working closely together and in dialogue with EU regulatory agencies and similar initiatives in the EU. <p>Results were presented through four webinars and lessons learnt discussed at a two day online workshop in the fall of 2021. There, a series of recommendations for both research and mixture risk management policies were formulated in</p>	<p>Backhaus T, Bahadori T, Barouki R, Brack W, Cronin MTD, Demeneix B, Hougaard Bennekou S, van Klaveren J, Kneuer C, Kolossa-Gehring M, Lebret E, Posthuma L, Reiber L, Rider C, Rüegg J, Testa G, van der Burg B, van der Voet H, Warhurst AM, van de Water B, Yamazaki K, Öberg M, Bergman Å. Statement on advancing the assessment of chemical mixtures and their risks for human health and the environment. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2020 Jan;134:105267. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2019.105267. Epub 2019 Nov 6. PMID: 31704565; PMCID: PMC6979318.</p> <p>Deliverable 15.8. Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-8-lessons-learnt-from-hbm4eu-wp15-on-mixtures-intermediate-recommendations/</p> <p>Workshop on mixtures : October 2021</p>

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	<p>further exploration of views and mental models held by the stakeholders involved.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A broader dialogue on information needs for mixture risk governance with stakeholders is needed. <p>On the basis of the literature and interviews, D15.1 also developed a long list of ‘statements’ (or positions in terms of argumentation analysis) for future use in exploration of information needs in policy makers and stakeholders. These can be used in further delineation of information needs.</p> <p>In addition, HBM4EU contributed to initiatives from several EU research projects dedicated to study mixture health risks. They published a Statement on advancing the assessment of chemical mixtures and their risks for human health and the environment (Bopp et al., 2018, Drakvik et al., 2020).</p>	D15.8 (see below).	https://www.hbm4eu.eu/training/past-trainings/#mixturesworkshop
2. What are common HBM mixture patterns in the European population?	<p>Initially, there was insufficient existing HBM mixture data available through the repository to directly address this question. Therefore, statistical scripts and approaches have been developed and tested on a simulated data set. These have been described in AD15.3 and D15.3. The scripts involve a combination of methods, both graphical and analytical, and combine alternative methods.</p> <p>In 2019 the scripts have been successfully</p>	<p>The network analysis and SNMU analysis identified a number of mixture patterns in each data. Some were, as expected, chemical families such as PAH’s, PCBs, and PFAS. Strongest co-occurrence patterns were found for metabolites of the same parent compound, e.g., among DINCH metabolites, or acrylamide. We also observed, however, examples of less expected combinations of substances in co-occurrence patterns. Notably selenium, chromium, antimony, and aprotic solvent HMSI. Also, the co-</p>	<p>Deliverable 15.3 Report real-life exposure profiles from re-analysis of existing HBM mixture data</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-3-report-real-life-exposure-profiles-from-re-analysis-of-existing-hbm-mixture-data/</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 15.3 HBM</p>

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	<p>applied to real HBM mixture data from the Flemish 'FLEHS' cohort under bilateral agreement. The results have been described in a scientific manuscript (Ottenbros et al. 2021).</p> <p>The developed and tested network analysis approaches were then applied more widely on four other data sets. Based on data availability, willingness to co-operate and availability of relevant expertise, similar analyses have been done for the Belgian '3xG' data, Czech data, the German 'GerES' V data, and Spanish 'Bioambient.es' data. For one of these datasets, i.e. GerES V, it was explored whether toxicity weighting could be used to prioritise specific mixtures. Also, an alternative approach, the SNMU (Sparse Non-negative Matrix Underestimation) was applied to the Flemish FLEHS data and compared to the network analysis results obtained for this dataset.</p>	<p>occurrence of parabens (MeP and EP) with Lysmeral (TBBA) was observed, which may point at the role of cosmetics. The analysis revealed co-occurrence patterns of chemicals that are regulated under different regulations, stemming from different regulatory domains.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of co-occurrence of substances using HBM data is feasible through network and SNMU analyses, each with its own strengths and limitations. Combined application of these approaches to explore and quantify co-occurrence is recommended. • Correlations amongst HBM levels were generally positive, with low to moderate values between parent compounds • The SNMU analysis of the FLEHS data indicate that a substantial part of the variation in the HBM data (> 70 %) can be captured with a limited number of clusters. While this needs to be replicated in other datasets, there is no reason to believe that this will be very different in other HBM datasets. • The role of HBM determinants can be assessed via the use of co-variables in the analysis, e.g. smoking, BMI, age, sex, education, diet, or other exposure information, in so-called Comparative Network Analysis (CNA) • Existing databases of early HBM studies are useful for the first exploration of co-occurrence of substances in the human body. The number of individuals in which the full range of 	<p>mixture database description and proposal statistical analysis plan https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-15-3-hbm-mixture-database-description-and-proposal-statistical-analysis-plan/</p> <p>Ottenbros I, Govarts E, Lebre E, Vermeulen R, Schoeters G, Vlaanderen J. Network Analysis to Identify Communities Among Multiple Exposure Biomarkers Measured at Birth in Three Flemish General Population Samples. <i>Front Public Health</i>. 2021 Feb 10;9:590038. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.590038. PMID: 33643986; PMCID: PMC7902692.</p> <p>Vernet C, Philippat C, Agier L, Calafat AM, Ye X, Lyon-Caen S, Hainaut P, Siroux V, Schisterman EF, Slama R. An Empirical Validation of the Within-subject Biospecimens Pooling Approach to Minimise Exposure Misclassification in Biomarker-based Studies. <i>Epidemiology</i>. 2019 Sep;30(5):756-767. doi: 10.1097/EDE.0000000000001056.</p>

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		<p>chemicals of interest is measured, however, is limited and needs to be expanded.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The stability and consistency of identified networks and mixture communities deserves further study, particularly for high dimensional data when strata of covariates are being studied. • Toxicity weighting of mixture communities/clusters is feasible, but severely limited by the shortage of available HBGVs or other indicators of toxic potency of the substances involved. More generic inroads need to be explored, the more so when suspect screening and untargeted screening is wider applied in HBM studies. • So far, four existing datasets were subjected to network analysis techniques, in one dataset network analysis and SNMU were compared, and toxicity weighting was explored in one dataset. The datasets varied widely in study population, study design, matrixes under study and chemicals analysed. It is recommended to expand current analysis to a wider set of existing data. 	<p>Deliverable 15.7 Report on re-analysis of existing HBM data for priority substances to identify mixtures (under EC review)</p>
<p>3. Can we identify hotspots or risk groups with high mixture exposures?</p>	<p>HBM4EU has run a survey of human internal exposure to mixtures of pesticides across five of the partner countries: Hungary, Czech Republic, Spain, Latvia and the Netherlands. Switzerland also collected urine samples, with a slightly different design. This survey, entitled 'SPECIMEn', explores exposure to pesticides and focusses on “hotspot”</p>	<p>The corona pandemic necessitated some adaptations to the execution and planning of the work. Due to the delays, further and more in-depth analysis of the data is needed.</p> <p>Through the novel suspect screening techniques, in total 95 pesticide-related markers were identified in the collected urine samples. Of</p>	<p>A questionnaire for the SPECIMEn study was developed jointly with WP7 and is available in the Online Library https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 15.7 Joint</p>

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	<p>residential areas or close to agricultural fields where pesticides are applied, in comparison to control areas. The survey was designed to assess concomitant/combined exposure to multiple pesticides in hotspot and control areas using human biomonitoring. Details of the joint pesticide survey are described in AD15.7.</p> <p>The field work for this survey covered two seasons started in the fall of 2019 (non-spraying season) and was completed in the summer of 2020 (spraying season). Urine samples have been collected in 50 parent-child pairs in hotspots (residences within 250 m of agricultural application of pesticides) and 50 parent-child pairs in control areas. Samples and questionnaires were collected in a non-spraying and a spraying season. Samples were analysed through pesticide suspect screening in five different laboratories, using harmonised approaches for sample preparation, data acquisition, data processing, incl. annotation of pesticides and metabolites. This work was done in conjunction to CGL Emerging Chemicals (WP16). All samples from each single country were analysed in one laboratory. These suspect screening approaches are built on non-selective analytical workflow and allow the qualitative monitoring of several hundred (up to several thousands) of exposure markers, including</p>	<p>these, 41 markers were identified with a high level of confidence. These related to 30 parent compounds that were identified with high confidence. Examples include acetamiprid, chlorpropham, boscalid and clothianidin.</p> <p>The detection frequencies for parent pesticides varied substantially between, but also within countries. Across all countries, the pesticides acetamiprid, and chlorpropham were most frequently detected. Boscalid, fludioxonil, pirimiphos-methyl, and pyrimethanil were detected at frequencies above >10% in all countries except Hungary. Similarly, clothianidin, fluazifop, and propamocarb were detected at frequencies above >10% in all countries except Latvia. Finally, the markers for cyprodinil, flonicamid, and tebuconazole were detected at frequencies above 10 % in at least three countries. In Switzerland a comparable pattern of detection frequencies was detected compared to the SPECIMEn countries.</p> <p>Many of the pesticides identified showed differences in detection rates when comparing hotspot areas versus control areas, samples collected in summer versus winter, and children versus adults; however, differences were in many cases not statistically significant. The statistically significant differences were not consistent across countries.</p> <p>The co-occurrence patterns among the multiple compounds detected by the suspect screening,</p>	<p>survey of pesticides: details of approach and contributions</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-15-7-joint-survey-of-pesticides-details-of-approach-and-contributions/</p> <p>Vernet C, Philippat C, Agier L, Calafat AM, Ye X, Lyon-Caen S, Hainaut P, Siroux V, Schisterman EF, Slama R. An Empirical Validation of the Within-subject Biospecimens Pooling Approach to Minimise Exposure Misclassification in Biomarker-based Studies. <i>Epidemiology</i>. 2019 Sep;30(5):756-767. doi: 10.1097/EDE.0000000000001056.</p> <p><</p> <p>D15.6 - Report on the results of the joint survey on HBM mixtures (IRAS)</p>

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	<p>various pesticide classes under their parent or metabolite form. This approach should gain insight into the occurrence of extended exposure patterns of pesticide-biomarkers, differences across the countries participating in SPECIMEn, differences between two seasons (spraying season with active application, and non-spraying season with no active application) and/or location (living close to agricultural areas or not).</p> <p>The results obtained contribute to the prioritisation of certain substances in terms of further exposure and risk assessment, and to possibly generate early warning information.</p>	<p>were described by the use of a correlation network analysis. Eight different co-occurrence patterns were observed: The largest patterns were formed through co-occurrence of acetamiprid (insecticide), chlorpropham (herbicide and plant growth regulator), chlorpyrifos (insecticide), flonicamid (insecticide), pirimiphos-methyl (insecticide and acaricide), tebuconazole (fungicide), thiacloprid (insecticide) and triclosan (antifungal and algicide). Overall, however, the underlying correlations were weak.</p> <p>In conclusion, using suspect screening analyses, HBM4EU generated valuable exposure data across Europe on a broad combination of pesticides. Consistent strong contributions from agricultural application to detection rates in hotspots or in spraying season were not observed.</p> <p>Suspect screening is a valuable approach to get a broader overview and a semi quantitative evaluation of substance exposures across the EU. This allows prioritisation of substances for targeted analysis and comparison of the suspect screening data with reported substance usage.</p> <p>Mixture risk assessment would strongly benefit from a strategy for the measurement of multiple exposure and effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes, as demonstrated by e.g. Vernet et al. 2019. This requires the development of an inclusive HBM/exposome</p>	

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		<p>infrastructure in Europe.</p> <p>More in-depth analysis of the collected information is still ongoing.</p>	
<p>4. Which sources & pathways contribute most to HBM mixture values?</p>	<p>This policy question could only partly and indirectly be addressed. Limitations in data availability, and delays due to the corona pandemic restricted possibilities to perform ‘Comparative Network Analysis’ (CNA) to study the role of co-variates at this time (task 15.1). Moreover, due to the pandemic it was not possible to collect house dust samples during the spraying season. Again, time constraints limited the ability to analyse observed pesticides against questionnaire information to date (task 15.2).</p>	<p>Late data availability and limited number of individuals in which the full range of HBM markers were measured in existing studies precluded adequate assessment of sources and pathways contributing most to HBM mixtures. Nonetheless, CNA was performed as a proof-of-concept, performing network analysis broken down by co-variates such as age, sex, BMI, level of education, smoking and dietary aspects. However, it is too early to draw firm conclusions on these exploratory analysis. Some co-occurrence patterns, like of parabens with Lysmeral hint to the role of cosmetics.</p> <p>Also, in the SPECIMEn study, time restraints impeded the analysis of pesticide markers against co-variate information, e.g., from questionnaires</p>	<p>Deliverable 15.3 Report real-life exposure profiles from re-analysis of existing HBM mixture data https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-3-report-real-life-exposure-profiles-from-re-analysis-of-existing-hbm-mixture-data/</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 15.3 HBM mixture database description and proposal statistical analysis plan https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-15-3-hbm-mixture-database-description-and-proposal-statistical-analysis-plan/</p> <p>Ottenbros I, Govarts E, Lebret E, Vermeulen R, Schoeters G, Vlaanderen J. Network Analysis to Identify Communities Among Multiple Exposure Biomarkers Measured at Birth in Three Flemish General Population Samples. <i>Front Public Health</i>. 2021 Feb 10;9:590038. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.590038.</p>

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			PMID: 33643986; PMCID: PMC7902692. Deliverable 15.7 Report on re-analysis of existing HBM data for priority substances to identify mixtures (under EC review)
5.What are the impacts of chemical mixtures on human health?	<p>Within Task 15.3, seven case studies have been conducted to identify methods for the prediction of mixture effects that can be used consistently for human health risk assessments and can inform biomonitoring strategies.</p> <p>Case study 1: A mixture risk assessment for male reproductive health with a focus on semen quality</p> <p>Case study 2: Mixture risk assessment of antiandrogenic chemicals based on human-derived hazard and exposure data</p> <p>Case study 3: A mixture risk assessment for developmental neurotoxicity with a focus on declines in IQ</p> <p>Case study 4: Occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium, nickel and PAHs and lung cancer</p> <p>Case study 5: Hazard index assessment of the combined chronic dietary exposure to heavy metals in the general population</p> <p>Case study 6: Risk assessment of the</p>	<p>The HBM4EU case studies collectively highlight the need to take combined exposures into account in chemical risk assessment. It became evident that a disregard for combined exposures will lead to significant underestimations of the risks associated with chemical exposures. This is true both for the general population and for more specific exposure scenarios, e.g., those relevant to occupational settings.</p> <p>Based on the lessons learned in the case studies, an advanced decision tree and workflow scheme for assessing hazards from exposure to chemical mixtures were developed. In many cases, it was possible to identify drivers of mixture risks, i.e., chemicals that contribute more strongly to the estimated health risks than other chemicals in the mixtures. Therefore, it is recommended that methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies and authorities should also include approaches for the identification of risk drivers that contribute most to the mixture risk, with the aim to focus and facilitate risk management. Furthermore, the case studies demonstrated that assessment of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional Deliverable 15.1 Plan for development of case studies https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-15-1-plan-for-development-of-case-studies/ • Deliverable 15.4 Report on approaches to identify mixture health effects https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-4-report-on-approaches-to-identify-mixture-health-effects/ • Deliverable 15.5 Case study reports on mixture health effects https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-5-case-study-reports-on-mixture-health-effects/

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	<p>occupational exposure to a mixture of four toxic metals</p> <p>Case study 7: Relying on repeated biospecimens to reduce the effects of classical-type exposure measurement error in studies linking the exposome to health.</p> <p>The case studies produced a framework and an advanced workflow for the conduct of such mixture risk assessments.</p>	<p>risks associated with combined exposures is generally possible by using the Hazard Index and/or the Point of Departure Index method. In the interpretation of results from the Hazard Index in a tiered approach, sufficient attention should be given to the underlying uncertainties in the applied assessment factors for the substance-specific Hazard Quotients used in the Hazard Index.</p> <p>A bottleneck in the MRA is in the provision of exposure data. HBM markers measured in the same individuals may help solve this in the future. The co-occurrence patterns observed in the re-analysis of existing HBM mixture data may give guidance in this respect, but expansion to other suitable data sources is needed.</p> <p>Case study 7 underscored the need for more repeated HBM measurements for substances with a relatively short half-life in the human body, to assess the within-person variation against the between-persons variation. Single one-time measurements of such HBM markers may not adequately reflect longer-term exposure profiles and are therefore less suitable to benchmark against health-based guidance values based on effects from longer-term exposures.</p>	
<p>6. What action perspectives are available to reduce mixture levels?</p>	<p>The EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (European Commission, 2020a) expresses the ambition to account for the cocktail effect of chemicals when</p>	<p>In policy terms, the risk management of 'mixture health risk problems' can be seen as a 'wicked problem', due to the nature of the problem (i.e., high uncertainty about risks, high complexity and</p>	<p>D15.1 Information needs from policy makers translated in terms of functionality of HBM mixture information.</p>

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	<p>assessing risks from chemicals, with the overall aim to work towards a toxic-free environment. Among others, the Commission aims to introduce or reinforce provisions to take account of the combination effects in relevant legislations, such as legislation on water, food additives, toys, food contact material, detergents and cosmetics.</p> <p>For REACH, it will be assessed how to best introduce (a) mixture assessment factor(s) for the chemical safety assessment of substances. More details can be found in the accompanying Staff Working Document (European Commission, 2020b), which describes the progress made since 2012 on the assessment of (un)intentional mixtures and to provide background information and evidence base to actions announced in EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.</p> <p>While a range of positions have been brought forward in assessment of information needs and in discussions on action perspectives with respect to mixture risk governance, the overall picture as yet is anecdotal. It is unclear to what degree the various options have support in a wider constituency of experts, policy makers or the general public and stakeholders. A more systematic and broader consultation will be needed, e.g., in the framework of PARC to</p>	<p>diversity of interests with high ambiguity of values). Thus, a risk governance approach involving stakeholders is required to effectively and efficiently address the mixture health risk problem.</p> <p>In line with the nature of 'wicked' problem of mixture risk governance, views on responsibilities and on criteria to guide risk reduction strategies varied considerably in the exploratory assessment of information needs (D15.1). Concrete action perspectives therefore, remain unarticulated.</p> <p>Based on the insights and lessons learned thus far in the context of HBM4EU, conclusions as well as 14 recommendations for risk assessment of chemical mixtures and for further research have been drafted and were widely endorsed by policy makers, scientists and stakeholders.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implementation of available methodologies for mixture risk assessment by (national and international) regulatory agencies should be accelerated to the degree possible, based on the evidence HBM4EU has generated on mixture exposures and health risks. 2. HBM data of appropriate quality and granularity, particularly data on the common occurrence of chemicals, need to be more widely utilised, both in design of toxicological mixture studies, epidemiological studies and in risk assessment and management. 	<p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-1-information-needs-from-policy-makers-translated-in-terms-of-functionality-of-hbm-mixture-information/</p> <p>Deliverable 15.8 Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures:</p> <p>intermediate recommendations https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-15-8-lessons-learnt-from-hbm4eu-wp15-on-mixtures-intermediate-recommendations/</p>

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	<p>gauge support for the (sometimes incompatible) alternative action perspectives to reduce mixture risks in the population.</p> <p>In the final year of the project, results and lessons learnt were discussed in a two day online workshop together with policy makers and stakeholders. This yielded a set of recommendations.</p>	<p>3. A strategy for the measurement of multiple exposure and effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes needs to be developed, building on the HBM4EU experience. This requires the development of an inclusive HBM/exposome infrastructure in Europe.</p> <p>4. HBM4EU (mixture) data and experience should be applied to support the science-based derivation of an appropriate Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF). Simulation studies and sensitivity analyses, using HBM4EU (mixture) data, cases studies and overall experience would allow to assess consequences of a MAF on ensuing mixture exposures and HBM mixture levels, as well as gauge the impact of a MAF on the resulting mixture risk reduction.</p> <p>5. Further research should focus on broadening and refinement of a combination of approaches to identify real-life chemical mixtures of concern to which the population is exposed. This will allow prioritisation of mixtures of concern and support policy decisions. This involves data-driven approaches and methodologies to incorporate toxicological potency information and to group substances with common modes of action.</p> <p>6. When data on substance use and exposures is limited, it is recommended to apply suspect screening analysis in human samples to get a broader overview and a semi-quantitative evaluation of substance exposures across the</p>	

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		<p>EU. This will allow prioritisation of substances for targeted analysis and comparison of the suspect screening data with reported substance usage.</p> <p>7. Future HBM studies should aim to collect data on the full range of chemicals of interest by targeted analysis in sufficiently large study populations measured in the same individuals, to assess the actual mixture exposures in the population and co-occurrence in the body.</p> <p>8. Existing samples collected within the HBM4EU WP8 framework and earlier relevant HBM studies should be screened on feasibility aspects for re-analysis through suspect screening and untargeted analysis. This will allow to expand the assessment of actual mixture exposures in the population and to assess time trends.</p> <p>9. Methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies and authorities should also include approaches for the identification of risk drivers that contribute most to the mixture risk, with the aim to focus and facilitate risk management.</p> <p>10. In the risk assessment for the authorisation of a new chemical, existing mixture exposures and body burdens of substances with similar adverse outcomes, need to be taken in account to the degree possible.</p> <p>11. Compliance or non-compliance of some chemicals with their single regulatory values should not distract from their possible</p>	

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		<p>contribution to mixture problems/risks.</p> <p>12. In the interpretation of results from the Hazard Index in a tiered approach, sufficient attention should be given to the underlying uncertainties in the applied assessment factors for the substance-specific Hazard Quotients used in the Hazard Index.</p> <p>13. In the risk assessment and management of mixtures, chemicals from other sources, e.g. medication or recreational drugs, that produce similar adverse outcomes, should also be taken into account to the degree possible. A legal basis to do so needs to be further developed.</p> <p>14. The identification of groups of co-occurring substances, regulated in different domains and sectors, and of toxicological concern, as through network analysis and mixture risk assessment, underscores the need to strengthen mixture risk assessment across regulatory domains and sectors.</p>	

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<p>1. What is the current (last 5 years) exposure of the European population to Cr(VI)?</p>	<p>Inventory of studies holding Cr(VI) exposure data was obtained in WP7 with an online questionnaire which was distributed with the aim to identify existing HBM studies. Data available and data gaps are summarised in a report (see D7.1). Among all the priority substances Cr(VI) was one of the least studied substances; in particular, a total of 5 studies included Cr(VI) measurements: 2 of them from Western European regions; 2 from Southern European regions and 1 in Israel. Although the preferred matrix for internal Cr assessment was blood, measurements were also available for blood erythrocytes, plasma, serum and urine spot random samples.</p> <p>WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe. For Chromium VI, questionnaires for adults are available as well as specific questionnaires for the 1st and 2nd (e-waste) occupational studies. A sampling frame to obtain EU recent HBM exposure data was developed by WP8 (see D8.1). In AD8.1 an inventory of databases or datasets targeting occupational exposure to Cr in Europe (from WP 7.1 questionnaire) was reported.</p>	<p>In all the EU countries the lack of studies on environmental exposure to Cr(VI) was evident, due to the very low exposure levels of Cr(VI) in the general population.</p> <p>Six countries reported occupational biomonitoring data on Cr but the majority of data comes from the use of total Cr measurements. Since this is not specific for Cr(VI), it was decided to use new Cr(VI) specific biomarkers and to expand the scattered EU data on Cr(VI) (see below).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/
<p>2. What is the level of exposure,</p>	<p>Cr(VI) has been identified as the first priority for a targeted occupational study under WP8 (see D8.5). Altogether 9 countries (Belgium,</p>	<p>Within the targeted occupational study (WP8), workers from different occupational settings, as chrome platers,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional Deliverable AD 8.2 Research plan for chromates study under HBM4EU

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<p>environmentally and occupationally relevant to Cr(VI) in the EU population?</p>	<p>Finland, France, Italy, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, UK, Luxembourg) volunteered to participate to the study on chromate exposure. This study focused on occupational exposure to Cr(VI) during surface treatment activities and welding in eight different countries in Europe, including approximately 40 companies and almost 580 workers and control subjects (not occupationally exposed to Cr(VI)). Research plan for chromates study was published as AD8.2.</p> <p>After the publication of the research plan, Cr(VI) information sheet, information leaflets to the participating companies and to workers as well as informed consent forms for companies and workers have been prepared in collaboration with task 7.5. These were translated for local languages (French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish, German, Dutch and Finnish). In order to collect relevant background information on possible confounding exposures and operating conditions and risk management measures in place at the workplace, a questionnaire for data collection was prepared (Annex1, D8.5). In addition, to collect comparable data in a harmonised way, great efforts were made to develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for the collection, handling, sample storage and transfer for each of the biological and industrial hygiene samples covered within the Cr(VI) occupational study. SOPs for each specific matrix have been published in the</p>	<p>surface treatment workers and welders, have been analysed to test differences in Cr(VI) levels respect to controls and depending on the task, using HBM matrices (urine, RBC, EBC) and industrial hygiene samples (inhalable and respirable air, dermal wipes).</p> <p>All of the biomarkers of exposure analysed demonstrate that workers from all the occupational settings have higher exposure to Cr and Cr(VI) when compared with control groups. Strong correlations were observed between urinary Cr levels and atmospheric concentration of Cr(VI) in platers and welders, supporting the use of urinary Cr as a primary method for the biomonitoring of Cr(VI) exposure at workplaces (Santonen et al. 2022).</p> <p>In addition, workers show higher Cr(VI) levels in post-shift than in pre-shift urinary samples.</p> <p>Moreover, all the occupational settings show higher values of Cr in dermal wipes samples during and in the end of the shift suggesting that hands contamination increases during the day.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 8.5 Initial Report on Occupational Studies • Deliverable 8.9 Report on progress targeted occupational studies <p>Santonen, T, Alimonti, A, Bocca, B, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Gomes, B, Hanser, O, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Kiilunen, M, Koch, HM, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Ndaw, S, Porras, SP, Robert, A, Ruggieri, F, Scheepers, PTJ, Silva, MJ, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Castano, A, Sepai, O, 2019. Setting up a collaborative European human biological monitoring study on occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 177, 108583. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108583</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuyse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p>

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	<p>HBM4EU on-line library. In the same time, an ICI/EQUAS for Cr analysis in different biological matrices has started within WP9 in order to select candidate labs for the analysis of samples of workers exposed to Cr(VI) and the list of candidates is available in D9.3. Results obtained in the chromate occupational study (WP8) allowed to answer to the level of exposure to Cr(VI) in occupational settings. Analyses of biomarkers of exposure have been completed.</p>		
<p>3. Does the exposure to Cr(VI) differ significantly between countries and population groups? What are the main reasons for differences in exposure?</p>	<p>In WP7 questions specific for Cr(VI) were identified to collect all the necessary information concerning countries and population characteristics (sociodemographic, dietary, occupational, lifestyle, environmental and health factors) with the aim to characterise possible differences among EU populations (see D7.3). In particular, exposure to metallic dust, type of work (surface treatment, handling metals, etc.), body modifications (piercings, tattoos), metallic jewellery on the skin, type of food and drink consumed before the sampling, have been identified as the main possible reasons for differences in Cr(VI) exposure.</p> <p>In addition, WP10 has developed a substance-specific statistical analysis plan for Cr(VI) (see D10.2, D10.5 and D10.6), including the definition and harmonisation of the variables, the statistical test to be applied, the specific procedure for calculating EU reference values, uncertainty analyses, data</p>	<p>In all countries participating in the occupational study, the results of the targeted occupational study show higher exposure to Cr(VI) among the workers in Cr(VI)-using industries respect to controls.</p> <p>The chromium plating sector shows the highest biomarkers exposure levels.</p> <p>The lower biomarker values in surface treatment workers, when compared to chrome platers, may reflect the use of RPE.</p>	<p>Deliverable 8.9 Report on progress targeted occupational studies</p> <p>Santonen, T, Alimonti, A, Bocca, B, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Gomes, B, Hanser, O, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Kiilunen, M, Koch, HM, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Ndaw, S, Porras, SP, Robert, A, Ruggieri, F, Scheepers, PTJ, Silva, MJ, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Castano, A, Sepai, O, 2019. Setting up a collaborative European human biological monitoring study on occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 177, 108583. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108583</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall</p>

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	<p>descriptions, and visualisations. Variables on general exposure levels, geographic comparisons and exposure determinants were defined in relation to Cr(VI) exposure (like SES, education, type of area of residence, density of traffic in the residential area, smoking, passive smoking, cotinine, local food, seafood, tattoo, jewellery, nutrients). These variables were mandatory included in the statistical analyses to address Cr(VI)-specific differences among countries and population groups.</p> <p>Despite these protocols and procedures, the poor availability of HBM data on Cr(VI) in different countries and population groups does not allow to answer to this policy question based on literature.</p> <p>Within WP8, observations from newly gathered data from occupational exposed cohorts brought further evidence.</p>		<p>results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p>
<p>4. Is there a significant time trend of Cr(VI) levels in existing population studies?</p>	<p>A protocol for examination of the temporal trends of Cr has been elaborated (WP10; D10.2). However, no study was identified that have repeated Cr measurements available. Therefore, data are insufficient to evaluate time-trends on the EU-wide scale and to answer to this policy question.</p>	<p>Verdonck et al. (2021) reported a decreasing time trend of urine Cr concentrations in workers, based on an unpublished biomonitoring dataset (comprising urinary levels of 3799 workers from different industries in Belgium collected during 1998 and 2018).</p> <p>Data are insufficient to evaluate time-trends on the EU-wide scale.</p>	<p>Verdonck J, Duca RC, Galea KS, Iavicoli I, Poels K, Töreyn ZN, Vanoirbeek J, Godderis L. Systematic review of biomonitoring data on occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Int J Hyg Environ Health. 2021 Jul;236:113799. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113799. Epub 2021 Jul 22. PMID: 34303131.</p>
<p>5. What are the groups at risk?</p>	<p>The literature review within the framework of the scoping document (D4.2) and of</p>	<p>The results obtained, under the WP8 Cr(VI) occupational study, reveal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority

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	<p>deliverable AD8.1 has identified occupations with potentially elevated exposure to Cr(VI). In EU the estimated number of Cr(VI)-exposed workers in 2012 was ~786,000, with the largest numbers exposed to welding. Other major uses of Cr(VI) include metal plating, manufacture of pigments and dyes, corrosion inhibitors, chemical synthesis, refractory production, leather tanning, and wood preservation.</p> <p>The results of the occupational chromate study aid to evaluate the Cr(VI) exposure in some of the most exposed classes of workers (chromium plating and welding). The main uncertainty for the evaluation of risk arises from the lack of knowledge on the relationship between Cr(VI) exposure and health effects. This issue has been reported in WP13 with a purpose to establish exposure-health relationships. WP13 give a detailed overview of the available knowledge on AOPs for Cr(VI) (D13.4 and D13.5) and subsequently summarised key knowledge gaps emerging from previous research. Specific activities, studies or other relevant steps to fill the missing information on Cr(VI) have been proposed in D13.5.</p> <p>In D5.5, the inclusion of HBM data in risk assessment (RA) and health impact assessment (HIA) strategies has been exemplified. RA was performed also for Cr(VI). Since the data were limited to Finland and pre-authorisation period, this policy question was better answered when new, EU</p>	<p>significant differences between subgroups of workers by industrial sector (Tables 10-12, D8.9).</p> <p>In general, based on the biomonitoring data, chrome plating workers are exposed to higher levels than surface treatment workers and welders.</p>	<p>substances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 8.9 Report on progress targeted occupational studies <p>Santonen, T, Alimonti, A, Bocca, B, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Gomes, B, Hanser, O, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Kiilunen, M, Koch, HM, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Ndaw, S, Porras, SP, Robert, A, Ruggieri, F, Scheepers, PTJ, Silva, MJ, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Castano, A, Sepai, O, 2019. Setting up a collaborative European human biological monitoring study on occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 177, 108583. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108583</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p> <p>Viegas S et al., HBM4EU Chromates Study: Determinants of Exposure to Hexavalent Chromium in Plating, Welding and</p>

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	wide data on occupational exposure to Cr from the chromate study under WP8.		Other Occupational Settings. Accepted for publication in IJERPH.
6. Are the overall exposure levels (in different population groups) above any health-relevant assessment levels (HBM guidance values, TDI)?	<p>Relevant HBM guidance values for the exposure to Cr have been reported on a national basis, but not at EU level. In the scoping document (D4.2) all the available limits have been reviewed. In Spain, a biological limit value (BLV) for total Cr concentration of 10 µg/L in urine measured during a shift and 25 µg/L at the end of the workweek has been reported (INSHT, 2016). In the UK, a biological monitoring guidance value (BMGV) of 10 µmol/mol creatinine in post shift urine was established (HSE, 2011). In Germany, DFG established the DFG-EKA values (biological exposure equivalents for carcinogenic substances) for Cr(VI) that set the range of total Cr in urine (from 10 µg/L to 40 µg/L) and in erythrocyt fraction of whole-blood (from 9 µg/L to 35 µg/L) if soluble alkaline chromate of a certain concentration and/or hexavalent welding fumes (only for urine) were inhaled over a work shift (DFG, 2015). Management of Cr(VI) formed during the welding process is achieved by compliance with occupational exposure limit values (OELs). The recent binding OEL set under EU Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work is 0.010 mg/m³ for a period of 5 years after the date of transposition of the directive; after that period a limit of 0.005 mg/m³ will apply. For welding or plasma-cutting processes or</p>	<p>Data from Cr(VI) occupational study highlight that in the industrial hygiene measurements, the 90th percentile (P90) of inhalable Cr(VI) levels is below the binding occupational limit value of 5 µg/m³ in welding and chrome plating, whereas in surface treatment the P90 is above the transient BOELV of 10 µg/m³.</p>	<p>D 5.12, part 4: Derivation of Chromium (VI) HBM Guidance Value (HBM-GV) for occupationally exposed adults</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p>

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	<p>similar work processes that generate fumes, there is a derogation, with an OEL value of 0.025 mg/m³ until 5 years after the transposition date and after that period the limit will be 0.005 mg/m³. On the other hand, in France and the Netherlands, an OEL of 1 µg/m³ has been set for Cr(VI) in all uses. These are the most stringent OELs currently set in workplace in EU.</p> <p>In HBM4EU an HBM-ELCR for Chromium VI has been derived of 8 µg/g cr based on an OEL of 5 µg/m³ corresponding to an excess lifetime risk of 20 cases of lung cancer per 1000 workers exposed 8 hours a day for 40 years</p>		
<p>7. Has the regulation under REACH had the favourable impact like a reduction of GM/median concentrations?</p>	<p>Cr(VI) is one of the most important occupational carcinogens, which has been shown to cause lung cancer in humans. It is currently an issue in the EU since some Cr(VI) compounds are authorised under Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). The current occupational biomonitoring data on Cr(VI) is scattered and its coverage is limited. Moreover, based on the very limited availability of the systematically repeated Cr(VI) exposure data available (as evidenced under the time trends policy question activities) this question cannot be answered at this stage.</p>	<p>Results obtained under the Cr(VI) occupational study, even with several regulatory frameworks in place (REACH and OSH), show that exposure to Cr(VI) in plating still occurs and at higher levels than in the other investigated sectors.</p> <p>Although the chemical form of the chromates used and the effect of wearing RPE are likely to have an impact on this, available results also suggest that other exposure routes (ingestion due to hand-to-mouth contact) may also have a role in the total exposure.</p> <p>In order to conclude whether new regulations have already had a favourable impact on Cr(VI) exposure, further evaluation and comparison to</p>	<p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p> <p>Viegas S et al., HBM4EU Chromates Study: Determinants of Exposure to Hexavalent Chromium in Plating, Welding and Other Occupational Settings. Accepted for</p>

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		<p>earlier data need to be performed. However, in the HBM4EU study a rich dataset has been collected, which can be used as a baseline for future research applying the same methodology.</p>	<p>publication in IJERPH.</p>
<p>8. What are the current HBM methods for Cr(VI)?</p>	<p>Within the WP9, an inventory of available methods and matrices suitable for Cr measurements have been reported (see D9.2). This inventory, covering articles published in the years 2010-2017, revealed the presence of 16 references in total, but only 8 fulfilled the analytical requirements. Chromium is analysed in urine, whole blood, exhaled breath condensate (EBC) and red blood cells (RBC). All described methods use ICP-MS, GF-AAS, EAAS and AAS, and the most frequent sample preparations are: liquid extraction, centrifugation and clean up using strong acid. In conclusion, the preferred technique for Cr determination is ICP-MS. An alternative is the speciation of Cr (VI) and Cr (III) by coupling ICP-MS to liquid chromatography.</p> <p>Within WP11, information about biological matrix previously used for the Cr(VI) measurement use in previous studies and obstacle to link HBM data and health was given (D 11.1).</p> <p>Within WP8 and WP9 harmonised methodology for total Cr and Cr(VI) analyses including collection, conservation, transport, preparation and analysis of biological (urine, blood and exhaled breath condensate EBC)</p>	<p>Within WP8, new and more specific methods for biomonitoring of Cr(VI) are tested, and harmonised methodology for the collection of biological samples (urine, RBC and EBC) and environmental industrial hygiene samples (as dermal wipes and air) have been developed.</p> <p>Cr(VI) in exhaled breath condensate (Cr EBC) has been proposed as a new biomarker. There are currently few data on the relationship between the levels in the EBC and in atmospheric air. EBC at early stages, has analytical and consistency issues making it difficult to compare.</p> <p>The HBM4EU chromate study demonstrated a high correlation between chromium urinary levels and air Cr(VI) or dermal total Cr exposure. Urinary chromium showed its value as a first approach for the assessment of total, internal exposure. Correlations between urinary chromium and Cr(VI) in EBC and Cr in RBC were low, probably due to differences in kinetics and indicating that these biomonitoring approaches may not be interchangeable but rather</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 8.9 Report on progress targeted occupational studies <p>Santonen, T, Alimonti, A, Bocca, B, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Gomes, B, Hanser, O, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Kiilunen, M, Koch, HM, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Ndaw, S, Porras, SP, Robert, A, Ruggieri, F, Scheepers, PTJ, Silva, MJ, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Castano, A, Sepai, O, 2019. Setting up a collaborative European human biological monitoring study on occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 177, 108583. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108583</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p>

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	<p>and industrial hygiene samples (air and dermal wipes) were developed (as above reported).</p> <p>Moreover, SOPs were developed for any of these matrices (as above reported).</p> <p>In the same time, within the WP9, laboratories performing laboratory Cr analysis have been tested through QA/QC schemes for the determination of Cr in urine, whole blood and serum. The 3rd° round of proficiency tests has been completed. Additionally, a few laboratories have set up the methodology for the analysis of Cr(VI) in EBC (D9.7).</p> <p>In addition, for EBC-Cr(VI) a small-scale interlaboratory comparison to ensure the quality of the analysis has also been conducted (D8.5). The first list of approved laboratories for Cr analyses is available (see D9.3) and all qualified laboratories were asked for information on price, capacity, time frames and technical details of Cr analyses (AD9.3).</p>	<p>complementary.</p> <p>Several other studies carried out in occupational settings reported measurements of urinary Cr and their correlations with Cr(VI) air concentrations and/or in some cases with biomarkers of toxicity (renal toxicity or oxidative mechanisms) (ANSES, 2017).</p>	
<p>9. Which are the appropriate biomarkers for Cr(VI)?</p>	<p>Regarding biomarkers of exposure, scoping document (D4.9) and deliverables (AD8.1) identified the urinary Cr levels (U-Cr) as a measure of total Cr exposure as Cr(VI) is reduced within the body to Cr(III). The analysis of plasma is indicative of total Cr exposure because Cr(VI) may be reduced to Cr(III) in the plasma. Cr measurements in red blood cells (RBCs) were selected as a suitable biomarker for the analysis of Cr(VI)</p>	<p>By the determination of U-Cr, it is possible to distinguish Cr(VI)-exposed workers from controls and demonstrate an increase over the shift for all sectors.</p> <p>In addition, correlation between U-Cr and Cr(VI) air levels is found in chrome platers and welders and between U-Cr and wipe samples in chrome platers.</p> <p>Even though urinary total Cr is an easy</p>	<p>Deliverable 8.9 Report on progress targeted occupational studies</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porrás, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates</p>

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	<p>exposure because Cr(VI) passes through cell membranes, while Cr(III) does not. The analysis of the exhaled breath condensate (EBC) was selected as a potentially good biomarker of occupational exposure to Cr(VI). Currently the most appropriate matrix for the determination of Cr(VI) is the analysis of RBC because only Cr (VI) can enter into them. An alternative to invasive matrices is the determination of Cr (VI) and Cr (III) in EBC to measure exposure to Cr(VI) compounds long after exposure. Furthermore, Cr-RBC correlated with Cr(VI) in exhaled breath condensate (EBC).</p> <p>Concerning biomarkers of effects, in WP8 (task 8.5) the chromate study includes also the collection and analysis of samples for several effect biomarkers analyses. Effect markers analysed in the chromate study (see D8.5) were reticulocyte micronuclei (MN), MN in peripheral blood lymphocyte (in collaboration with WP14), comet assay in leukocytes, global methylation analysis (and specific epigenetic markers), telomer length in blood, metabolomics studies (urine), oxidative stress biomarkers in urine.</p> <p>Moreover, a literature survey was performed for Cr(VI) in order to create an inventory of available biomarkers of effects for this specific exposure. The results of that survey are presented in AD14.5. The traditional effect biomarkers included oxidative stress (e.g., malondialdehyde) and genotoxicity (e.g., micronucleus analysis) markers. Among the</p>	<p>method for biomonitoring and useful in sectors where Cr-exposure is mainly or only Cr(VI), in tasks with co-exposure to Cr(III), it might be difficult to distinguish Cr(VI) contribution to the total urinary levels.</p> <p>The biomarkers more specific to Cr(VI) exposures are the RBC-Cr(VI) and EBC-Cr. Both are indeed significantly elevated in workers compared to controls.</p> <p>The chromate study also includes a collection of the samples for several effect biomarkers analyses which can be used as an indirect exposure biomarker. Analysis of the results of the effect markers reveal that workers in electrolytic bath plating display the highest levels of DNA and chromosomal damage in leukocytes and the second highest level of chromosomal damage in reticulocytes. Welders exhibited the highest frequency of micronuclei in reticulocytes despite the lower U-Cr levels, suggesting recent exposure to Cr(VI) that might not have been captured by post-shift U-Cr levels. The frequency of micronucleated lymphocytes was significantly related to the U-Cr level with the highest exposed group (3rd tercile of U-Cr level) displaying the highest frequency of micronucleated cells. Likewise, the micronucleus frequency in reticulocytes was also related to the U-Cr level. The data of genotoxicity biomarkers also evidenced that controls recruited within the industries (e.g., office workers) displayed levels of genotoxic damage much higher than those of controls</p>	<p>study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p> <p>Santonen, T, Porras, SP, Bocca, B, Bousoumah, R, Duca, RC, Galea, KS, Godderis, L, Göen, T, Hardy, E, Iavicoli, I, Janasik, B, Jones, K, Leese, E, Leso, V, Louro, H, Majery, N, Ndaw, S, Pinhal, H, Ruggieri, F, Silva, MJ, van Nieuwenhuysse, A, Verdonck, J, Viegas, S, Wasowicz, W, Sepai, O, Scheepers, PTJ, HBM4EU chromates study team, 2022. HBM4EU chromates study - Overall results and recommendations for the biomonitoring of occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium. Environ. Res. 204, 111984. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111984</p> <p>Ventura et al. Biomarkers of effect as determined in human biomonitoring studies on hexavalent chromium and cadmium in the period 2008-2020. Environ Res. 2021;197:110998. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.110998.</p> <p>Viegas S et al., HBM4EU Chromates Study: Determinants of Exposure to Hexavalent Chromium in Plating, Welding and Other Occupational Settings. Accepted for publication in IJERPH.</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 14.5 Report on the 2nd</p>

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	<p>novel effect biomarkers, those relying on gene expression and epigenetic effects (e.g., DNA methylation analysis) were identified as the most informative ones.</p>	<p>recruited outside the companies. The comparison of global DNA methylation levels between the exposed and the control groups revealed a statistically significant decrease in levels observed in workers, suggesting deregulation of gene expression. The changes in abundance of urinary excreted metabolites observed in workers reflected fatty acid and monoamine neurotransmitter metabolism, oxidative modifications of the amino acid residues, excessive formation of abnormal amino acids metabolites and changes in steroid and thyrotropin-releasing hormone.</p>	<p>Granada Workshop: Implementing Effect Biomarkers</p> <p>D8.13 Report on occupational studies. (in preparation)</p>

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<p>1.What is current occupational exposure to diisocyanates?</p>	<p>Under WP8.5 a systematic review on the existing diisocyanate data was performed. This has been published as a paper by Scholten et al., Annals of Work Exposures and Health, 1-17, 2020. Although several studies were found describing exposures at different sectors, most of the studies were >10 years old and variable exposures were described. In addition, for example data on the use of diisocyanates in the construction sector was limited. The systematic review also highlighted the need for a harmonised approach to study and report biomonitoring levels. It also revealed a need to develop and test new, more specific biomarkers for the biomonitoring of diisocyanates. In order to address these needs the HBM4EU diisocyanate study was conducted under WP8. This study was conducted during 2020-2022 and the data is currently analysed for reporting in April 2022.</p> <p>For Diisocyanates, questionnaires for adults are available. For the 2nd occupational study (on diisocyanates) performed under HBM4EU, a questionnaire was developed and used to collect contextual data on the exposure and information on the respiratory tract symptoms among the exposed workers.</p>	<p>The new data from HBM4EU diisocyanate study (performed under WP8) suggests low, but still measurable exposure to MDI and HDI in construction sector, in use of MDI glues and in motor vehicle sector. Highest exposures were observed in activities involving either polyurethane foam or HDI paint spraying. In many cases, however, levels remained below or close to LOQ, especially when MDI glues, adhesives or sealants were used. In polyurethane foam spraying or in HDI paint spraying high air levels may be measured but the use of RPE limited the internal exposure of workers. Therefore, air levels alone cannot inform on the real exposure of workers but biomonitoring data is needed to assess the exposure and confirm the proper functioning of personal protection. Dermal wipe samples were often unable to detect exposure.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • D8.13 Report on occupational studies. • Scholten et al Ann Work Expo Health. 2020 Jul 1;64(6):569-585). • Jones K et al., HBM4EU diisocyanates study • study protocol for a collaborative European human biological

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			monitoring study on occupational exposure
2.What are the best markers to identify hazardous exposures to diisocyanates?	In addition to the systematic review by Scholten et al. (2020), D9.5 (Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances) summarises the current state-of-art on the biomonitoring of diisocyanates. Although measurement of urinary diamines is currently “a golden standard”, this method is not specific for diisocyanates. However, it is possible to measure diisocyanate specific albumin or Hb adducts, which is recommended as a second option for biomonitoring. Within the HBM4EU diisocyanate study, different biomarkers of exposure were applied and compared. These included urinary diamines, diisocyanate specific IgG, urinary lysine adducts for MDI and MDI Hb adducts.	Urinary diamines are the most commonly used biomarker for the monitoring of exposure to diisocyanates. Hb adduct analyses can be also used but require blood sampling. Preliminary results show that current exposures are often close or even below the LOQs of the urinary diamine methods. Further analyses of the HBM4EU diisocyanate study data will inform us on the usability of IgG and urinary lysine adduct analyses in the biomonitoring of diisocyanate exposure. The currently available commercial wipe sampling methods to detect dermal exposure to diisocyanates do not seem sensitive enough at the current exposure levels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds • Deliverable 9.5 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances • Deliverable report D8.13: Report on occupational studies. • Scholten et al Ann Work Expo Health. 2020 Jul 1;64(6):569-585).
3.What is the likely impact of forthcoming REACH restriction/possible EU wide OEL of disocyanates?	<p>This will be studied in the planned occupational diisocyanate study which will be performed in 2020-2021. The research plan for this second occupational study has been published as AD8.4 “Detailed research plan for the occupational diisocyanate and E-waste study” in the beginning of 2020.</p> <p>Laboratories performing analysis of different aniline compounds have been listed in D9.3 (Database of candidate laboratories for the 1st prioritisation round of substances) and ICI/EQUAS for aromatic amines started in June 2019 and the results are finalised in mid-2020. Laboratories passing the QA for urinary diamines will be</p>	Since the REACH restriction on diisocyanates is coming in force only in 2023, it is too early to evaluate the possible impact of this restriction. The HBM4EU diisocyanate study (together with the systematic review by Scholten et al., 2020), however, provides baseline data for future assessment of the impact of the restriction. Since there is a binding limit value for diisocyanates also under preparation in EU, this is also likely to impact on the exposures. However, in the HBM4EU diisocyanate study, in many cases MDI and HDI levels were already below these levels.	Deliverable report D8.13: Report on occupational studies. Scholten et al Ann Work Expo Health. 2020 Jul 1;64(6):569-585).

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	<p>candidates to perform U-diamine analyses in this occupational diisocyanate study.</p>		
<p>4. What are the health risks and human health impacts of the current occupational diisocyanate exposures?</p>	<p>Health risk assessment of diisocyanates is under preparation in WP5.3. This will use available information on the dose-responses of diisocyanate induced asthma and existing information on diisocyanate exposure gathered from the literature and by WP10. PBPK model will be prepared under WP12 to link biomarker levels to external exposure levels. A first version of the model was finished in fall 2020 and the model was tested and refined as part of WP8.5 occupational diisocyanate study. A substance dossier on TDI and diisocyanates has been prepared (task 5.2) and sent out for consultation. HBM-GVs couldn't be derived so far. AOPs for diisocyanates are developed in WP13 to support human health risk assessment.</p>	<p>The main health concern in the case of diisocyanates is related to asthma. Based on the risk assessment performed under WP5.3, even at the low exposure levels, which are well below the current exposure limit values, asthma risk cannot be excluded but still a small increase in the number of asthma cases can be expected. Therefore, continuous monitoring of exposure is needed.</p> <p>PBPK models developed for TDI and MDI within WP12 are essential for the interpretation of the biomonitoring data and for the use of biomonitoring data in the assessment of asthma risks caused by diisocyanates. However, some further validation of these PBPK models is still needed. Deliverable report D5.11 demonstrates how these models can be used to support risk assessment of diisocyanates.</p>	<p>Deliverable report D5.11: Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p>

13 Emerging Chemicals

1. Policy Question	2. Short Summary of Status and approaches used in HBM4EU to answer the policy questions	3. Concise answer to the policy questions – based on HBM4EU results	4. Links to relevant documents, such as the scoping document, HBM4EU deliverables and peer-reviewed articles.
<p>1. Early warning of presence of hazardous chemicals in EU population?</p>	<p>Early warning methods for chemicals of emerging concern in HBM4EU implies new measurements in human samples of chemicals that have been recently introduced in the environment, but for which few Human Biomonitoring data exist (WP9, WP16), or detection of early warning signals of toxicity of chemicals present in the human population (WP14, WP16). HBM4EU develops and applies new methods for targeted analysis of these emerging compounds (WP9, AD9.1 D9.7 and D9.9) to obtain robust quantitative information on the corresponding human internal exposure levels. HBM4EU complements this information with strategies and implementation of suspect screening (qualitative determination of an extended number of a priori known markers as a support to further prioritisation) and non- targeted screening (detection of unknown compounds as a support to new marker discovery) (WP16). In addition, early warning of the presence of hazardous chemicals in the population is addressed through the use of effect biomarkers (WP14) that may signal biological imprints of chemical</p>	<p>Suspect and non-targeted screening:</p> <p>From the initial state-of-the-art at the early stage of the HBM4EU initiative, the work achieved within WP16 first permitted to build the basis of an EU network with harmonised competences in the field of suspect and non-targeted screening (SS/NTS) applied to human matrices, and secondly to develop and conduct several proof-of-concept studies illustrating the usefulness of these approaches. Overall, these efforts resulted in more than 3000 analysed samples and several hundreds of detected exposure markers associated to emerging chemicals. This work also permitted to identify a number of limitations associated to these approaches, in particular the bottleneck associated to the identification of the exposure markers detected by the large-scale approaches, still impairing their real high throughput implementation.</p> <p>To identify new emerging substances, 5 European laboratories have joined forces and are applying their suspect screening capabilities to analyse 160 human urine/blood samples from various cohorts. They used a predefined list of suspect markers for which the expected detected signal characteristics have been inventoried within a MS reference laboratory. Based on this list, they identified dozens of markers from various substance groups including those for pesticides, plasticisers, UV-filters, and PFAS. Several were</p>	<p>Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances</p> <p>Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 9.9 Compilation of the analytical methods used by the HBM4EU laboratories for the substances on the 1st and 2nd prioritisation list</p> <p>Deliverable 9.7 First report on analytical results and new methods development</p> <p>Deliverable 9.9 Second report on analytical results and new methods developed</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 9.1 General guidance for new method development within HBM4EU and role of task 9.3 therein</p> <p>Deliverable 9.2 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round</p>

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	<p>exposures.</p> <p>In addition, specific “emerging” substances are being measured for the first time in biobanked urine or blood samples of the general European population that have been collected after 2014. The strategy is described in D8.4 (WP8).</p> <p>HBM4EU focused on substitutes and alternatives for already well regulated hazardous substances. As such capacity has been inventorised and expanded in Europe for targeted analysis of new phthalates (MCHP, DnPeP, DiDP, DiNP) with between 5 and 19 qualified laboratories depending on the metabolite. For the DINCH metabolites 7 and 8 laboratories were qualified depending on the metabolite. For BPF and BPS, respectively 13 and 18 qualified laboratories were identified and for organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs) 4 to 5 laboratories were qualified depending of the metabolite (D 9.8 and AD9.9). WP9 has selected the most suitable biomarkers for the first set of prioritised substances (D9.2) and for the second set of priority chemicals (D9.5).</p> <p>The phthalates and substitutes were analysed in samples from 2950 children (NO, DK, HU, SK, SL, PL, EL, IT,</p>	<p>detected with high frequencies which demonstrates their widespread presence in the populations of various EU countries (D16.4). Another proof-of-concept illustrating the WP16 outputs is concerning the particular suspect screening of pesticides and their metabolites in 2000 human urine samples under harmonised conditions between 5 laboratories. The aim was to annotate a maximal number of exposure markers present in urine samples that are being collected in mother-child pairs of 5 different countries and in 2 different seasons (D15.6).</p> <p>A user-friendly software module- haloseeker – has been developed as an open access resource to identify markers of exposure to halogenated substances in human samples. It allows to handle large and complex datasets which are generated by LC-HRMS (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30758179). Special emphasis is on human samples collected in the early life period, considered as the most vulnerable period of life and an important time window that should be protected from exposure to hazardous compounds. A first success story was then obtained on breast milk samples where 4-hydroxy-chlorothalonil was identified without any a priori knowledge (D16.3). The same approach is applied to meconium samples. 25 Spanish placenta samples have been also analysed using untargeted LC-HRMS profiling, metal, steroid hormones and PFAS profiling and an array of bioassays has been applied on the samples (AD14.4). The results of the suspect and non-</p>	<p>of substances</p> <p>Deliverable 9.5 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances</p> <p>AD16.4 Emerging Substances</p> <p>AD16.3 Direct effect based approaches applied to the screening of emerging substances</p> <p>D16.3/D16.5 Report on generated HBM data and global framework for emerging chemicals</p> <p>Pourchet M, Narduzzi L, Jean A, Guiffard I, Bichon E, Cariou R, Guitton Y, Hutinet S, Vlaanderen J, Meijer J, Le Bizec B, Antignac JP. Non-targeted screening methodology to characterise human internal chemical exposure: Application to halogenated compounds in human milk. <i>Talanta</i>. 2021 Apr 1;225:121979. doi: 10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121979. Epub 2020 Dec 9. PMID: 33592727.</p> <p>Vorkamp K, Castaño A, Antignac JP, Boada LD, Cequier E, Covaci A, Esteban López M, Haug LS, Kasper-Sonnenberg M, Koch HM, Pérez-Luzardo O, Osite A, Rambaud L, Pinorini MT, Sabbioni G, Thomsen C. Biomarkers, matrices and analytical</p>

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	<p>NL,FR,DE) and 2900 teenagers (O,SE,PO,CZ,SK,SL,EL,ES,FR,BE,DE). Organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs) were analysed in 2950 samples of children, the bisphenols in 3165 adult samples. Some of the newer perfluorinated compounds were analysed in samples from teenagers (NO, SE, PO, CZ, SK, SL,EL,ES,FR,BE,DE).</p> <p>Furthermore, new methods have been developed for detection of urinary metabolites of some reprotoxic classified and EU-regulated phthalates such as di(methoxyethyl) phthalate (DMEP), di-iso/npentyl phthalate (Di/nPeP), di-iso/n-hexyl phthalate (Di/nHexP) and di-C7-11 branched and linear alkyl ester phthalate (DHNUP). Smallscale ICIs have been performed in order to expand the phthalate methodology for inclusion of these biomarkers for HBM investigations in the general population. Also, for analysis of CrVI in exhaled breath condensate (EBC) SOPs have been developed and a small scale ICI has been organised to allow implementation and generation of HBM data in the occupational studies.</p>	<p>targeted chemical analysis will be combined with the outcome of the bioassays to link the exposure profiles with biological activity.</p> <p>Targeted measurement of substitutes of regulated compounds:</p> <p>Phthalate substitutes: Increasing regulations of certain phthalates lead to a decrease in measured concentrations of these compounds. Concurrently, a shift to non-regulated phthalates or substitutes (such as DINCH) takes place leading to an increase of measured concentrations for these substitutes in human urine samples of children and adolescents as shown in HBM4EU aligned studies.</p> <p>Bisphenols: P95 values (representing 5% of the participants with the highest levels) of the substitute BPF measured in urine samples of adults, are higher compared to BPA in 5 of 11 HBM4EU aligned studies. This indicates a growing concern for exposure to substitutes, like BPF, in Europe.</p> <p>Exposure to multiple perfluoroalkyl substances has been documented in blood samples of EU teenagers of HBM4EU aligned studies.</p> <p>Organophosphate ester-based flame retardants (OPFRs) were detected in urine of 99% of children participating in HBM4EU studies. These OPFRs substitute persistent flame retardants that are regulated. There are limited capabilities within Europe for current use FRs, particularly OPFRs. Analytical methods vary for different sub-groups</p>	<p>methods targeting human exposure to chemicals selected for a European human biomonitoring initiative. Environ Int. 2021 Jan;146:106082. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106082. Epub 2020 Nov 20. PMID: 33227583.</p> <p>Mol HGJ, Elbers I, Pålme C, Bury D, Göen T, López ME, Nübler S, Vaccher V, Antignac JP, Dvořáková D, Hajšlová J, Sakhi AK, Thomsen C, Vorkamp K, Castaño A, Koch HM. Proficiency and Interlaboratory Variability in the Determination of Phthalate and DINCH Biomarkers in Human Urine: Results from the HBM4EU Project. Toxics. 2022 Jan 26;10(2):57. doi: 10.3390/toxics10020057. PMID: 35202244.</p> <p>Vaccher V, Lopez ME, Castaño A, Mol H, Haji-Abbas-Zarrabi K, Bury D, Koch HM, Dvorakova D, Hajslova J, Nübler S, Kaur Sakhi A, Thomsen C, Vorkamp K, Göen T, Antignac JP. European interlaboratory comparison investigations (ICI) and external quality assurance schemes (EQUAS) for the analysis of bisphenol A, S and F in human urine: Results from the HBM4EU project. Environ Res. 2022 Feb 17;210:112933. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2022.112933. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 35182598.</p>

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		<p>of FRs due to differences in chemical structure and there is a general need for methods to be optimised.</p>	<p>Nübler S, Schäfer M, Haji-Abbas-Zarrabi K, Marković S, Marković K, Esteban López M, Castaño A, Mol H, Koch HM, Antignac JP, Hajslova J, Thomsen C, Vorkamp K, Göen T. Interlaboratory Comparison Investigations (ICIs) for human biomonitoring of chromium as part of the quality assurance programme under HBM4EU. J Trace Elem Med Biol. 2022 Mar;70:126912. doi: 10.1016/j.jtemb.2021.126912. Epub 2021 Dec 15. PMID: 34954563.</p> <p>Dvorakova D, Pulkrabova J, Gramblicka T, Polachova A, Buresova M, López ME, Castaño A, Nübler S, Haji-Abbas-Zarrabi K, Klausner N, Göen T, Mol H, Koch HM, Vaccher V, Antignac JP, Haug LS, Vorkamp K, Hajslova J. Interlaboratory comparison investigations (ICIs) and external quality assurance schemes (EQUASSs) for flame retardant analysis in biological matrices: Results from the HBM4EU project. Environ Res. 2021 Nov;202:111705. doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.111705. Epub 20</p> <p>Vinggaard AM, Bonfeld-Jørgensen EC, Jensen TK, Fernandez MF, Rosenmai AK, Taxvig C, Rodriguez-Carrillo A, Wielsøe M, Long M, Olea N,</p>

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			<p>Antignac JP, Hamers T, Lamoree M. Receptor-based in vitro activities to assess human exposure to chemical mixtures and related health impacts. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2021 Jan;146:106191. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106191. Epub 2020 Oct 14. PMID: 33068852.</p> <p>Léon A, Cariou R, Hutinet S, Hurel J, Guitton Y, Tixier C, Munsch C, Antignac JP, Dervilly-Pinel G, Le Bizec B. HaloSeeker 1.0: A User-Friendly Software to Highlight Halogenated Chemicals in Nontargeted High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry Data Sets. <i>Anal Chem.</i> 2019 Mar 5;91(5):3500-3507. doi: 10.1021/acs.analchem.8b05103. Epub 2019 Feb 19. PMID: 30758179.</p>
<p>2. Inform REACH process to identify substances of potential concern?</p>	<p>The substances that fall under the 1st and 2nd priority substance groups of HBM4EU have been categorised according to existing knowledge of internal exposure (WP4). Category C substances are substances for which HBM data are scarce or doesn't exist. Category D substances are substances for which a toxicological concern exists but HBM data are not available. Suspect screening is recommended to explore the presence of these chemicals in</p>	<p>Overall an ambitious open access EU database of known substances to be addressed as chemicals of emerging concern was elaborated, that includes more than 70 000 parent and more than 300 000 metabolites, as a support to the implementation of suspect screening analyses. To facilitate prioritisation for confirmation efforts and reduce the amount of chemicals to be considered further, QSAR predictions related to physicochemical properties, environmental fate, toxicity and Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion (ADME) processes could be performed</p>	<p>AD 16.1 Screening methods inventory</p> <p>AD 16.6 Last updated version of the elaborated inventory of already identified chemicals of emerging concern coupled to the developed MS reference library for annotation, capable to be released as a public and sustainable resource</p>

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	<p>human samples and further prioritise the necessary investment in term of developing quantitative methods and the inclusion of certain markers in HBM programs. Category E substances are substances not yet identified as of toxicological concern and for which no HBM data are available. Non-targeted screening approaches are needed to identify yet unknown substances.</p> <p>The results of this categorisation for individual compounds of the prioritised substance groups in HBM4EU can be consulted in the scoping documents on the substance specific web pages at the HBM4EU web site. It is the ambition of HBM4EU to move substances gradually towards category A as more information is being collected.</p> <p>Within HBM4EU WP 16, we have successfully built the framework and capacities for generating comprehensive suspect lists and linked tandem mass spectral databases. Chemicals included in 51 publicly available databases related to CECs were collected and aggregated into a single and QA/QC consolidated database (CECScreen). In order to make the database applicable for suspect screening in HRMS data from human samples (so-called MS ready), chemical structures were standardised and required chemical</p>	<p>for 64,684 structures (AD16.5).</p> <p>A basis of structured competent EU network and harmonisation for suspect and non-targeted screening approaches dedicated to emerging chemicals in human matrices was established, paving the way to further extension within the environment-food-Human continuum communities.</p>	

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	<p>properties were calculated. The database includes mainly parent compounds, however, most of these compounds are metabolised by the human body and, as such, the parent compound might not be detected in human samples. Therefore, and as a first step, a number of phase I metabolites were simulated and included into a separate list which can also be used in suspect screening approaches. The number of compounds in the aggregated database is extensive (70,397) even more so in the simulated metabolites list (306,279). In order to facilitate prioritisation for confirmation efforts and reduce the amount of chemicals to be considered further, metadata related to physicochemical properties, environmental fate and toxicity was included for the compounds in the CECs inventory.</p>		
<p>3. Development of strategy for a non-toxic environment -> first step?</p>	<p>Strategies for suspect and non- targeted screening were developed to identify yet unknown compounds of toxic concern in human biological matrices such as urine, blood, milk, meconium or placenta. To identify new emerging substances in human samples, WP16 has developed a data driven approach, a chemistry driven approach and a biology driven approach.</p> <p>For the data driven approach, reference</p>	<p>Three approaches were considered.</p> <p>A data driven approach: capacity on acquisition of high-resolution mass spectrometric data within the consortium was inventorised and brought together. The workflow for harmonisation and QAQC consolidation of the necessary reference MS data is laid down in AD16.4 “Annotation framework”.</p> <p>A chemically driven approach, which highlights crucial methodological questions of non-targeted</p>	<p>AD16.4 “Annotation framework</p> <p>D16.4 Reference Mass Spectral Libraries for Suspect Screening of Chemicals of Emerging Concern</p> <p>AD 16.1 An inventory of screening techniques</p> <p>D16.2 First workflow for screening</p>

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	<p>mass spectrometric data were collected, reviewed, acquired, and published so that they can be used and annotated to profiles that are generated when screening the HBM samples.</p> <p>An inventory of screening techniques (AD16.1) and a first workflow for screening emerging chemicals (D16.2) has been published on the HBM4EU web site.</p> <p>A chemically driven approach: D16.2 highlights crucial methodological questions of non-targeted analysis workflows including sample preparation, data acquisition, data mining and expert reviewing and proposes guidelines to implement NTA in Human Biomonitoring research. A set of QA/QC actions dedicated to sample collection, sample preparation and acquisition method specifically applied to the identification of chemicals of emerging concern in human matrices by non-target approaches is being developed and published. As a proof of concept non-targeted screening of halogenated emerging chemicals (incl. their metabolites) using gas/liquid chromatography coupled to high resolution mass spectrometry (GC/LC-HRMS) is developed and applied to various human matrices.</p>	<p>analysis workflows including sample preparation, data acquisition, data mining and expert reviewing and proposes guidelines to implement NTA in Human Biomonitoring research (D16.2).</p> <p>A biology driven approach, that combines suspect and non-targeted methodologies with effect directed analyses (EDA). An overview of bioassays for analysing human samples and EDA approaches has been published (AD16.3)</p> <p>As proof of concept 25 placenta samples have been analysed with an array of bioassays including epigenetic markers (D14.4 and AD14.4). The results are combined with the outcome of untargeted LC-HRMS profiling of the samples to link the exposure profiles with biological activity.</p> <p>In addition, effect markers were selected and implemented in some of the HBM studies of WP8 as early warning signals for toxicity from exposure to multiple chemicals as occurs in real life. WP14 has defined effect markers as quantifiable changes in biochemical, physiologic or other parameters in the organism that occur as a result of exposure to chemicals. Criteria for selection of effect biomarkers (D14.1) and effect markers for the 1st set of priority chemicals (D14.2) have been identified. A distinction is made between novel effect markers, traditional effect markers with the novel markers relating more to early biological imprints of exposures, while the traditional markers are often clinical well validated markers that are reliable predictors of health risks but less specific for chemical exposures (D14.3).</p>	<p>emerging chemicals</p> <p>AD16.3 Direct effect based approaches applied to the screening of emerging substances</p> <p>Pourchet M, Debrauwer L, Klanova J, Price EJ, Covaci A, Caballero-Casero N, Oberacher H, Lamoree M, Damont A, Fenaille F, Vlaanderen J, Meijer J, Krauss M, Sarigiannis D, Barouki R, Le Bizec B, Antignac JP. Suspect and non-targeted screening of chemicals of emerging concern for human biomonitoring, environmental health studies and support to risk assessment: From promises to challenges and harmonisation issues. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2020 Jun;139:105545. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.105545. Epub 2020 Apr 29. PMID: 32361063.</p>

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	<p>A biology driven approach: combines suspect and non-targeted methodologies with effect directed analyses (EDA) (WP14). An overview of bioassays for analysing human samples and EDA approaches has been published (AD16.3) and a scientific publication is finalised.</p>		

14 Flame retardants

1. Policy Question	2. Short Summary of Status and approaches used in HBM4EU to answer the policy questions	3. Concise answer to the policy questions – based on HBM4EU results	4. Links to relevant documents, such as the scoping document, HBM4EU deliverables and peer-reviewed articles.
<p>1. What are current HBM levels of legacy/regulated FRs (e.g., PBDEs and HBCDD)? How do these compare to any historical records? Is the current legislative framework and proposed actions leading to a significant decline in restricted compounds and is this uniform across the EU?</p>	<p>In WP10, five legacy/regulated FRs were identified as the focus for statistical analysis of existing HBM data. These are four polybrominated diphenyl ethers (BDE 47, 99, 153 and 209) and hexabromocyclododecane (HBCDD). The European HBM dashboard provides summary statistics for HBM data from different European countries, with 8 aggregated datasets including legacy FRs exposure data in blood serum or plasma. These data, covering different age groups from largely Western and Northern European populations, were insufficient to evaluate spatial and temporal trends as planned. Thus, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to gather literature data for a joint analysis of spatial and temporal trends in Europe and on a global scale, to place European population levels in a broader context. Literature data mining and statistical analysis focused on maternal milk as a target biomonitoring matrix.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2021) have measured brominated FR in serum samples from children</p>	<p>Meta-analysis of existing biomonitoring data of FRs in the European population indicates an impact of restrictions on PBDEs and HBCDDs on population levels. PBDE levels in breast milk show a decline in selected lower brominated PBDE congeners (BDE 47, 99), however, higher brominated PBDE congeners (BDE-153, BDE-209) do not yet show a decline. This reflects the later restrictions on BDE-209.</p> <p>Existing biomonitoring data of HBCDD in breast milk in the European population suggest a decline after 2010, however this trend is not yet conclusive due to the scarcity of data.</p> <p>New biomonitoring data collected in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies show that PBDEs and HBCDD continue to be detected in serum of European children, however it is not possible with the available data to distinguish if this concerns legacy exposure from maternal transfer or new exposure from flame retarded products. The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data will form baseline European exposure levels for FR in children, allowing follow up studies to monitor increased or decreased usage.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • European HBM dashboard that allows to visualize summary statistics from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Deliverable 8.7 Second report on targeted new fieldwork and results • Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of exposure distributions and/or European exposure values • Deliverable 10.10 Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8

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	<p>between 6 and 11 years of age from 4 different sampling sites in Europe representing 711 individuals. This has improved the data coverage of current knowledge on FR exposure to children within Europe, with new data generated for PBDEs in children from France, Greece, Slovenia and Norway and new data on HBCDDs in France, Greece, and Slovenia.</p>		
<p>2. What is the exposure of the European population to current use FRs? In particular, what is the exposure of sensitive sub-groups (e.g., infants and children)?</p>	<p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2021) have measured halogenated FR (10 biomarkers) in serum samples from children between 6 and 11 years of age from 4 different sampling sites in Europe (Norway, Slovenia, Greece, and France) representing 711 individuals and organophosphate FR (4 biomarkers) in urine samples from children between 6 and 11 years of age from 7 different sampling sites in Europe (Norway, Denmark, Slovakia, Slovenia, France, Belgium and Germany) representing 1770 individuals. Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p> <p>In order to support current and future HBM studies, HBM4EU developed a variety of publicly available groundwork materials for a</p>	<p>For many current-use FRs we lack biomonitoring data. New data collected in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies demonstrate widespread children's exposure to metabolites of TPHP, TDCIPP and TCIPP across all regions of Europe, with detection of DPHP (metabolite of TPHP and other OPFRs) in 99% of children.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of DPHP concentrations are in the range of 1.43-2.43 µg/g crt and 5.16-9.70 µg/g crt respectively.</p> <p>P50 of urinary BDCIPP concentrations are in the range of 0.38-0.64 µg/g crt across studies in children with 2 studies with a P50 value < detection limit (range: 0.09-0.5 µg/L). P95 of urinary BDCIPP concentrations are in the range of 0.70-4.55 µg/g crt across studies in children.</p> <p>P50 of urinary BCEP concentrations is 0.12 µg/g crt for 1 study, the other 2 studies have a P50 < detection limit (0.3 µg/L). P95 of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM4EU online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all materials developed under WP7: D7.9 "Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires" https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Deliverable 8.7 Second report on targeted new fieldwork and results • Deliverable D9.2: Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances • Deliverable 9.8: List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances

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	<p>harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe (WP7, HBM4EU online library).</p> <p>A prioritised list with most suitable biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods has been produced (WP9, D9.2, D9.7).</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies have substantially improved the coverage of current knowledge on FR exposure within Europe, with new data generated for Dechlorane Plus in children from France, Slovenia, and Norway.</p>	<p>urinary BCEP concentrations range from 0.86-4.01 µg/g crt across studies in children.</p> <p>P50 of urinary BCIPP concentrations is 0.09 µg/g crt in 1 study, all other 5 studies have a P50 value < detection limit (range: 0.19-0.9 µg/L). P95 of urinary BCIPP concentrations are in the range of 0.39-5.04 µg/g crt.</p> <p>There are no health-based guidance values available for organophosphate flame retardants.</p> <p>P50 of serum BDE-209 concentrations is 0.041 µg/L in 1 study in children, the 2 other studies have a P50 < detection limit (range: 0.0016-0.05 µg/L). P95 of serum BDE-209 concentrations are in the range of 0.06-0.58 µg/L across studies in children with 1 study with a P95 < detection limit of 0.0016 µg/L.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of serum TBBPA concentrations are both < detection limit of 0.7 µg/L in one study in children.</p> <p>All P50 of serum DBDPE concentrations are < detection limit (range: 0.01-1.9 µg/L) and P95 concentrations are in the range of 0.56-2.61 µg/L across studies in children.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of serum 2,4,6-TBP concentrations are both < detection limit of 0.7 µg/L in one study in children.</p> <p>P50 of serum BDE-47 concentrations is 0.003 µg/L in 1 study, the 3 other studies have a P50 < detection limit (range: 0.0001-</p>	<p>included in the two prioritisation rounds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of exposure distributions and/or European exposure values • Deliverable 10.10 Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8

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		<p>0.002 µg/L). P95 of serum BDE-47 concentrations are in the range of 0.002-0.01 µg/L across studies in children.</p> <p>P50 of serum BDE-153 concentrations are in the range of 0.0005-0.001 µg/L across studies in children with two studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 7x10⁻⁴-0.001 µg/L). P95 of serum BDE-153 concentrations are in the range of 0.004-0.007 µg/L.</p> <p>P50 of serum DP-syn concentrations is 0.009 µg/L in 1 study in children, the 3 other studies have a P50 < detection limit (range: 0.001 - 0.05 µg/L). P95 of serum DP-syn concentrations are in the range of 0.003-0.08 µg/L across studies in children with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.03 µg/L.</p> <p>P50 of serum DP-anti concentrations is 0.01 µg/L in 1 study in children with 3 studies that have a P50 < detection limit (range: of 0.001 - 0.04 µg/L). P95 of serum DP-anti concentrations are in the range of 0.006-0.16 µg/L across studies in children with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.0188 µg/L.</p> <p>P50 of serum α-HBCD concentrations are all < detection limit (range: 0.0075 - 0.01 µg/L) across studies in children. P95 of serum α-HBCD concentrations are in the range of 0.03-0.13 µg/L across studies in children with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.01 µg/L.</p>	

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		<p>P50 and P95 of serum γ-HBCD concentrations are all < detection limit (range: 0.0075 - 0.01 $\mu\text{g/L}$) across studies in children.</p> <p>The HBM-I values for α-HBCD and γ-HBCD (both 1.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$) are not exceeded. For the other FR, no HBM-GVs are available.</p>	
<p>3 & 13. How do the levels of legacy FRs compare to levels of new/emerging FRs? Is any temporal or spatial trend observed? Can we relate this to use patterns and/or production volume? As FR market shifts towards replacement/alternative FRs, does human exposure reflect that trend? E.g., DBDPE as replacement for BDE209</p>	<p>There are currently insufficient data to evaluate this question.</p> <p>To ensure comparability across newly generated biomonitoring data in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, four rounds of interlaboratory validation exercises were carried out. The intercomparison exercises identified a significant core network of comparable European laboratories for HBM of halogenated flame retardants (PBDEs, HBCDD, Dechlorane Plus). On the other hand, the data revealed a critically low analytical capacity in Europe for HBM of currently-used flame retardants (e.g., TBBPA, DBDPE, 2,4,6-TBP, and the OPFR biomarkers).</p> <p>In addition, as biomarkers of legacy FRs are typically quantified in serum/plasma, while many of the new/emerging FRs (i.e., organophosphate esters) biomarkers are quantified in urine, the measured</p>	<p>OPFRs are widely marketed and used as alternatives to now restricted PBDEs and HBCDDs. There are comprehensive data for a small subset of these OPFRs (notably TCIPP, TCEP, TDCIPP), however for the majority of current-used flame retardants the knowledge and data gaps extend across the spectrum from analytical methods for HBM to toxicity and determinants of exposures and effects.</p> <p>The understanding of exposure to legacy FRs is much more comprehensive than the understanding of trends in the replacement emerging FRs. Meta-analysis of legacy FRs in breast milk completed under WP10 has identified declines in BDE-47 and 99, and either decline or plateau in BDE 153, BDE-209 and HBCDD in European populations. The breakpoints in the temporal trends coincide with the introduction of restrictions on these compounds, indicating the impact of restrictions and market shifts on HBM levels.</p> <p>However, there is a lack of data on the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds • Dvorakova, D., Pulkrabova, J., Gramblicka, T., Polachova, A., Buresova, M., López, M.E., Castaño, A., Nübler, S., Haji-Abbas-Zarrabi, K., Klausner, N., Göen, T., Mol, H., Koch, H.M., Vaccher, V., Antignac, J.P., Haug, L.S., Vorkamp, K., Hajslova, J., 2021. Interlaboratory comparison investigations (ICIs) and external quality assurance schemes (EQUASs) for flame retardant analysis in biological matrices: Results from the HBM4EU project. Environ. Res. 202. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111705

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	<p>levels cannot be directly compared. Therefore, PK modelling is necessary to enable comparison of the legacy and emerging FRs. PK modelling has been performed under WP12 for both legacy (BDE 47) and current use FRs (TCEP), however not on identical populations, so the outcomes cannot be used to directly compare legacy and current use FRs.</p>	<p>levels of replacement FRs. Metabolites of chlorinated FRs used as replacements from some PBDEs have been detected in 64% of children from Belgium, Denmark, Germany, France, Slovenia, and Slovakia in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. DBDPE is a key alternative FR used to replace BDE 209. It was detected between 8-16% of children from France, Greece and Slovenia, however, the limitation in provision of new HBM data may be due to the analytical capacity of many European laboratories in targeting these emerging FRs.</p>	
<p>4 & 12. How does exposure to FRs differ between adults and children, males and females? What are the population groups most at risk?</p>	<p>There are very limited data to address this question, as the data produced under the HBM4EU Aligned Studies were limited to children ages 6-11.</p> <p>Young children typically have higher exposure due to transplacental transfer, flame retardants in breast milk, and behaviour. Children accidentally ingest indoor dusts which have high levels of FRs, and are exposed due to mouthing of objects and hand-to-mouth transfer.</p> <p>Exposure modelling for TCEP under WP12 has provided an indication of age-related differences in exposure. Toxicokinetics of TCEP exposure were assessed through INTERGRA PBTK model (AD12.5), however discrepancies between modelled</p>	<p>Under WP12, PBTK modeling has indicated higher TCEP intake and urinary metabolite levels in infants and young children, attributed to exposure to consumer products through mouthing of objects and direct dermal contact.</p> <p>New biomonitoring data generated for children in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies do not indicate any gender difference for either legacy FRs or current use OPFR metabolites.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of exposure distributions and/or European exposure values • Additional Deliverable 12.3 Exposure model testing results • Additional Deliverable 12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data

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	<p>exposure and measured urinary metabolites, particularly in infants and toddlers, indicate uncertainties and data gaps in FR exposure in infants and children.</p>		
<p>5. How does exposure differ by geographic area within Europe? Do countries/regions have different FR exposure levels?</p>	<p>This question has been addressed under WP10, both through the literature review and meta-analysis conducted for existing data on legacy FRs, and for children's populations through new data generated by the HBM4EU Aligned Studies.</p>	<p>Based on literature review and meta-analysis for PBDEs conducted under WP10, there are no differences within Europe in PBDE levels in breast milk. However, in a global context, European breast milk levels of PBDEs are substantially lower than North American levels, which is attributed to the higher flammability standards and PBDE use in North America compared to Europe.</p> <p>In contrast, the literature review and meta-analysis for HBCDDs has indicated comparable global levels of alpha-HBCDD in breast milk, but differences within Europe, with lower levels in Northern Europe; this is attributed to earlier restrictions on the use of HBCDD introduced in Nordic countries.</p> <p>New data generated under the HBM4EU Aligned Studies also indicate regional differences in serum levels of Dieldrin Plus when compared across France, Norway and Slovenia (SI>NO>FR), but no clear cause for the regional differences has been identified. Similarly, regional differences exist for OPFRs (DHP: SI>DE,FR,NO), also without a clear cause. There appears to be an incomplete understanding of the major determinants of</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 8.7 Second report on targeted new fieldwork and results • Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of exposure distributions and/or European exposure values • Deliverable 10.10 Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8

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		<p>exposure for OPFRs.</p> <p>Focused multimedia studies including potential exposure pathways (dust, diet) in conjunction with HBM are recommended to provide insight into the regional differences in exposure, particularly for Dechlorane Plus, which is under consideration for inclusion in the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants, and the chlorinated OPFRs, which have substantial evidence of toxicological concern.</p>	
<p>6. Are there one or more occupationally exposed sub-groups? What occupations are associated with high exposure to FRs?</p>	<p>The answer to this question is supported by the questionnaires developed in WP7, among others for the 2nd occupational studies. A framework for a study on exposure of e-waste workers to a wide range of chemicals, including FRs, has been prepared, covering the target matrices, questionnaires and framework for comprehensive biomonitoring and exposure assessment. Occupational exposure has not been addressed in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies as FR have only been measured in children ages 6-11.</p>	<p>The literature review completed within the framework of the scoping document (D4.9) has identified occupations with potentially elevated exposure to FRs (e.g., e-waste processors, computer repair, construction workers, some chemical industry workers, carpet installers). Workers in these settings are typically exposed to both legacy and current-use flame retardants at higher levels than the general population due to emissions of gaseous and particulate flame retardants during the dismantling of electrical and electronic waste.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Additional Deliverable 8.4 Detailed research plan for the occupational diisocyanate and E-waste study • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Scheepers, P.T.J.; Duca, R.C.; Galea, K.S.; Godderis, L.; Hardy, E.; Knudsen, L.E.; Leese, E.; Louro, H.; Mahiout, S.; Ndaw, S.; Poels, K.; Porras, S.P.; Silva, M.J.; Tavares, A.M.; Verdonck, J.; Viegas, S.; Santonen, T.; HBM4EU e-Waste Study Team. HBM4EU Occupational Biomonitoring Study on e-Waste—Study Protocol. <i>Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health</i> 2021, 18, 12987. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182412987

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<p>7 & 8. What are the relevant exposure pathways for FRs, e.g., diet, air, water, indoor environmental exposure? Is elevated exposure to FRs associated with particular consumption patterns or lifestyles?</p>	<p>In order to answer questions on exposure levels and sources and further support current and future HBM studies, WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe.</p> <p>When identifying exposure levels and sources as well as groups at risk, WP7 questionnaires are of great value. They can be used to set up new studies and allow the harmonised collection of data on a participant's individual characteristics and their potential exposure pathways from different sources (sociodemographic characteristics, residential environment/home exposures, dietary habits, lifestyle, occupational exposure and health status) with flame retardants. For flame retardants, questionnaires for adults, adolescents and children are available. Questionnaires for the 2nd occupational study on e-waste (incl. FRs as a biomarker) have also been developed.</p> <p>Under the framework of WP12, a web-based exposure database has been developed to support the modelling of exposure towards better HBM data interpretation. Chemical-</p>	<p>Human biomonitoring studies address the exposure of OPFR mainly through indoor environment via air and dust, since it is detected in high amounts in those matrices. Only recently, a few studies focused on the dietary exposure to OPFRs. The concentration in house dust is approximately three magnitudes higher than its occurrence in food. In contrast to this, a child consumes approximately 1.2 kg food per day compared to 30 mg of dust. It can be assumed that the dietary intake might be equal or even a greater contributor to the total human exposure to OPFR.</p> <p>This is supported by modelling under WP5 (D5.11), which identified that dietary contributions to children's exposure to selected OPFRs (TDCIPP, TCEP, TCIPP) is substantial, and in some cases may be the dominant exposure pathway. The estimated daily and dietary intake of TCEP did not exceed health-based guidance values. However, there is limited information on dietary exposure for most of the prioritised FRs, and the data that exist are from a small subset of countries. Therefore, OPFR exposure sources remain uncertain. Further research on e.g. the oral bioavailability and occurrence data are necessary to determine which exposure pathways (dietary or dust uptake) contribute the most to the general exposure.</p> <p>In the scoping document, FRs were</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.11 Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 "Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires" https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Additional Deliverable 12.1 Database of exposure-related and ancillary data for priority substances • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second second round HBM4EU priority substances

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	<p>specific data include information related to the contamination levels in several environmental matrices such as ambient air, indoor air, water, soil, dust, as well food residues in various food items, and concentration in consumer products. In the current iteration of the exposure database this is available for brominated flame retardants, with geographically disaggregated data from Austria, Germany, Greece, Norway, Spain, Sweden and UK for environmental exposure, and Norway + general EU for dietary exposure, and general data for consumer products.</p> <p>This tool has been used in estimating population exposures, e.g. exposure through ingestion, inhalation and dermal contact was evaluated for TCEP (AD12.3, 12.5), highlighting non-dietary ingestion of dust as a major exposure pathway.</p> <p>For various OPFRs, WP5 estimated the daily intake based on HBM data of TDCIPP, TCIPP and TCEP measured in urine samples from children in Germany, Belgium, Denmark, France, Slovenia and Slovakia and toxicokinetic modelling.</p>	<p>categorised in Cat. A-E according to the availability of data regarding exposure, HBM and toxicity. Categories C, D, and E contain 40 FR compounds, and for these, almost no data are available to estimate the exposure from indoor environment (air and dust) and dietary uptake.</p>	
<p>9. Do certain flame retardants co-occur in</p>	<p>A framework and statistical analysis plan has been developed within</p>	<p>There is strong evidence based on existing HBM data and new data generated via the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round

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HBM matrices?	<p>WP15 (AD 15.3) to provide a general concept and structure for how mixtures can be addressed.</p> <p>Mixture profiles for 26 flame retardants have been evaluated (D15.3) based on simulated data to gain insight into the determinants of mixture profiles in HBM data, but thus far is only simulated data and does not indicate direct biological relevance of these FR mixtures.</p> <p>Under WP10, correlations between biomarkers of BFR and OPFR exposure have been investigated within the new HBM4EU Aligned Study data.</p>	<p>HBM4EU Aligned studies that FRs occur in mixtures. Exposures to individual PBDEs are correlated, and exposure sources (diet, dust ingestion) are common to most FRs, suggesting that highly exposed populations (particularly infants and children) will be highly exposed to a mixture of FRs.</p> <p>Moreover, there is concern that mixture exposure posed a hazard that is not well-captured with compound-specific hazard evaluations and risk assessments. Under WP13, it was identified that many FRs have similar endocrine disrupting effects, suggesting potential for additive effects of exposure to multiple FRs.</p>	<p>HBM4EU priority substances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bajard, L., Negi, C.K., Mustieles, V., Melymuk, L., Jomini, S., Barthelemy-Berneron, J., Fernandez, M.F., Blaha, L., 2021. Endocrine disrupting potential of replacement flame retardants – Review of current knowledge for nuclear receptors associated with reproductive outcomes. <i>Environ. Int.</i> 153. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106550 • AD15.3 HBM mixture database description and proposal statistical analysis plan
10. What current information is available regarding toxicity of FRs, both as individual compounds and as the mixtures of FRs typically occurring in indoor environments and diet?	<p>Under WP13, 52 FRs used as replacement (such as OPFRs) were classified and prioritised according to the availability of toxicological information and potential toxicity, as follows: 10 FRs with substantial toxicological information, 9 of which have toxicological concern (TCEP, TCIPP, TDCIPP, TPhP, TMPP, TBBPA, EHDPP, TNBP, TBOEP), 20 FRs without toxicological data in mammals, and 22 FRs with only scarce toxicological data.</p> <p>In addition, systematic search (WP13) for in vitro information on</p>	<p>A comprehensive literature search showed that toxicological data was either incomplete or critically lacking for many flame retardants in use.</p> <p>A systematic search for data availability focused on the FRs used as substitutes, such as OPFRs and showed that for the majority of these 52 replacement FRs, in vivo toxicological data, mechanistic data and in vitro data on ED activities were either missing or insufficient for proper hazard characterisation. For 9 FRs (TCEP, TCIPP, TDCIPP, TPhP, TMPP, TBBPA, EHDPP, TNBP, TBOEP), substantial data allow some level of hazard identification and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D13.5 – “Identified gaps for the establishment of AOPs and required studies” • D13.2 – “Template for AOP update report for selected priority substances” • D13.4 – “Report on AOPs of priority substances” • Bajard et al. “Prioritisation of hazards of novel flame retardants using the mechanistic toxicology information from ToxCast and Adverse Outcome Pathways”, ESEU, 2019 • Bajard et al. “Endocrine disrupting potential of replacement flame retardants - Review of current knowledge for nuclear receptors associated with reproductive

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	<p>endocrine disruptive (ED) activities of the 52 replacement FRs highlights the absence of data for 24 of them. Complemented with structure-based predictive models, the search shows that antiandrogenic activity is reported and/or predicted for most of the 52 replacement FRs. In a follow up screening performed within WP13, the predicted antiandrogenic activity was confirmed for one FR, TDBP-TAZTO. This raises concerns regarding possible mixture effects that were confirmed in vitro. Besides, no information on the toxicity of FRs as mixtures was identified.</p>	<p>raises a toxicological concern. Literature search on ED activities combined with in silico predictions reveals that most of the 52 FRs may share antiandrogenic properties, raising concerns for mixture effects of combined exposure. This was confirmed in vitro for 7 FRs.</p> <p>Apart from these results obtained within WP 13, no information on the toxicity of typical FRs mixtures was identified.</p>	<p>outcomes”, Env. Int., 2021</p>
<p>11. Can exposure to FRs be linked with any adverse health effects?</p>	<p>Under WP13, decrease in male fertility, neurotoxicity and hepatotoxicity were identified as the main health effects for 9 prioritised FRs, based on toxicological data combined with AOPs. In addition, evidence was found linking TBBPA exposure with thyroid hormone homeostasis, carcinogenicity, and teratogenicity. The data collected also indicate that TPhP and TDCIPP may be considered as endocrine disruptive chemicals (EDCs). An AOP-based in vitro screening also highlighted the potential of 4 FRs to induce hepatic steatosis.</p> <p>Under WP14, a literature search was</p>	<p>For 9 replacement FRs, in vivo data, combined with mechanistic information from in vitro testing and AOP knowledge highlighted the main effects on male fertility, neurotoxicity, and hepatotoxicity. However, solid human epidemiology studies are critically missing to establish the health risks associated with exposure to replacement FRs.</p> <p>Additional in vitro studies performed within WP13 identify potential mechanisms underlying male reproductive toxicity and hepatic steatosis.</p> <p>Within WP14, a literature search identified biomarkers of effect related to neurotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, and cardiovascular</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moore, S., Paalanen, L., Melymuk, L., Katsonouri, A., Kolossa-Gehring, M., Tolonen, H., 2022. The Association between ADHD and Environmental Chemicals—A Scoping Review. Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 19, 2849. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052849 • D13.5 – “Identified gaps for the establishment of AOPs and required studies” • D13.2 – “Template for AOP update report for selected priority substances” • D13.4 – “Report on AOPs of priority substances” • Bajard et al. “Prioritization of hazards of novel flame retardants using the mechanistic toxicology information from

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	<p>completed for biomarkers of effect for BFRs and OPEs. For BFRs 23 biomarkers were identified in at least 2 studies. For OPEs, the literature search identified ten biomarkers proposed for implementation in human biomonitoring studies. Effect biomarkers were related to neurotoxicity, reproductive toxicity, and cardiovascular function.</p> <p>A review of the literature further supported the association of selected FRs with ADHD.</p>	<p>function that have been associated with OPFRs exposure. The association between FR exposure, molecular and clinical biomarkers of effect (including the novel biomarker BDNF), and neurodevelopment is currently evaluated in child cohorts included in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies.</p>	<p>ToxCast and Adverse Outcome Pathways”, ESEU, 2019</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bajard et al. “Endocrine disrupting potential of replacement flame retardants - Review of current knowledge for nuclear receptors associated with reproductive outcomes”, Env. Int., 2021 • D14.2 – “List of effect biomarkers for the first set of prioritised substances, September 2018” • Negi et al., “An adverse outcome pathway based in vitro characterisation of novel flame retardants-induced hepatic steatosis”, Env. Pol., 2021
<p>14. What additional FRs should be prioritised for further information regarding exposure and/or toxicity? How can use and risk information be combined to identify and prioritise knowledge gaps for further assessment?</p>	<p>The scoping document (D4.9) highlighted 20 of 62 flame retardants with evidence of toxicity but insufficient HBM data. These are also candidate compounds to be prioritised for exposure assessment. These compounds are TPHP, TMPP, TCEP, TCIPP, TDCIPP, TNBP, TBBPA, and TBOEP (Cat. B), TEHP, EHDPP, DDC-DBF, ip-TTP, V6, 2,4,6-TBP and TDBPP (Cat. C and D) and DBNPG, TDBP-TAZTO, RBDPP, melamine polyphosphate and EBTEBPI are Cat. E. See D4.2 Section 5.</p> <p>WP5 built on the prioritisation of the scoping document by further classifying and investigating regulatory, risk evaluation and data</p>	<p>Broad data gaps remain for many currently used FRs. For the majority of the 52 replacement FRs listed in HBM4EU, in vivo toxicological data, mechanistic data and in vitro data on ED activities were either missing or insufficient for proper hazard characterisation. Uncertainties also extend to analytical capacities, with a very limited set of European laboratories with capacity for HBM of current use FRs, and inconsistencies in analytical methods.</p> <p>The risk assessment on TCEP demonstrated that when sufficient exposure and HBM data are available, we can improve our understanding of risk. However, this is also influenced by uncertainty in hazard evaluation, as the risk assessment identified low risk according to one EU hazard threshold but possible risk based on</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Deliverable 5.5 Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals • Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation • Dvorakova, D., Pulkrabova, J., Gramblicka, T., Polachova, A., Buresova, M., López, M.E., Castaño, A., Nübler, S., Haji-Abbas-Zarrabi, K., Klausner, N., Göen, T., Mol, H., Koch, H.M., Vaccher, V., Antignac, J.P., Haug, L.S., Vorkamp,

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	<p>availability for the 20 highlighted FRs. TCEP emerged as the most urgent FR to address. An HBM-based risk assessment was performed for TCEP aimed at the general population, using model-reconstructed external exposure starting with HBM data.</p>	<p>US EPA threshold; uncertainty in both the hazard and exposures to TCEP leads to uncertainty in the risk assessment.</p>	<p>K., Hajslova, J., 2021. Interlaboratory comparison investigations (ICIs) and external quality assurance schemes (EQUASs) for flame retardant analysis in biological matrices: Results from the HBM4EU project. Environ. Res. 202. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111705</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hajeb, P., Castaño, A., Cequier, E., Covaci, A., López, M.E., Antuña, A.G., Haug, L.S., Henríquez-Hernández, L.A., Melymuk, L., Luzardo, O.P., Thomsen, C., Vorkamp, K., 2021. Critical review of analytical methods for the determination of flame retardants in human matrices. Anal. Chim. Acta 338828. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2021.338828
<p>15. Can reference values be established for any FRs?</p>	<p>Based on the exclusion and partitioning criteria set by WP10, there are currently insufficient data to establish reference values (limiting to general population, exclusion of hot spots, infants, children, adolescents and pregnant women/partitioning by matrix – serum or milk).</p>	<p>There is currently insufficient data to establish general population reference values for FRs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverable 10.6 Second annual list of exposure distributions and/or European Reference Values

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<p>1. What is the concentration of lead in the human blood nowadays (after phasing out leaded petrol) in the countries of Europe?</p>	<p>A systematic literature review in peer-reviewed journals was performed in the bibliographic database PubMed to identify human biomonitoring studies focusing on children's, pregnant women's and young people's exposure to lead. In total, 58 publications from European countries were included in the review.</p> <p>The European HBM dashboard has 23 datasets with lead exposure data integrated and in IPCHEM metadata for 43 datasets with lead data are available.</p>	<p>Information on blood lead levels in children and young people after 2015 is limited; however, the decreasing trend that started following the phasing out of leaded petrol came to a halt more or less in 2010 in the countries with regular nationwide surveys and levelled out at approximately 10 µg/L. Although, the blood lead concentrations were below the reference values set by different organisations, the most recent studies reported health outcomes at lower concentrations, and it was suggested that there is likely no safe threshold for lead neurotoxicity.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Gundacker et al. (2021) Lead (Pb) and neurodevelopment: A review on exposure and biomarkers of effect (BDNF, HDL) and susceptibility https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113855 • EU HBM Dashboard https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/
<p>2. Do blood lead levels of both adults and children still indicate permanent existence of lead exposure?</p>	<p>A systematic literature review in peer-reviewed journals was performed in the bibliographic database PubMed to identify human biomonitoring studies focusing on children's, pregnant women's and young people's exposure to lead. In total, 58 publications from European countries were included in the review.</p>	<p>The data collected in HBM4EU showed the decreasing exposure of the European population over the past decades that levelled off in 2010 which indicates permanent existence of Pb exposure. However, data on the most recent exposure is lacking for Europe.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gundacker et al. (2021) Lead (Pb) and neurodevelopment: A review on exposure and biomarkers of effect (BDNF, HDL) and susceptibility https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113855 • EU HBM Dashboard https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/
<p>3. What are the sources of still existing lead exposure in different countries of Europe?</p>	<p>A literature review in peer-reviewed journals was performed to answer this policy question.</p> <p>The work is still in progress in WP10.</p>	<p>Based on the literature review, it is assumed that some foods, particularly cereals and grain-based products, still may contain lead at non-negligible levels when the raw materials had been grown</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.6 Scoping documents for the second round priority substances • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round

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	<p>The protocol has been elaborated for the statistical analysis and the principal representatives of 6 studies agreed to provide individual data for analysis.</p> <p>Furthermore, WP7 produced several materials I to provide support for future studies to be able to comprehensively investigate the associations between lead levels and potential sources.</p> <p>For Lead, questionnaires for adults are available. Questionnaires for the 2nd occupational study on e-waste (incl. lead as a biomarker) have also been developed.</p>	<p>at contaminated sites. Tap water from lead pipes in non-renovated, old houses can also be sources of lead exposure. Old paint can contain lead. Household dust can also be important sources. Exposure to lead occurs through smoking and inhaling particles from burning waste. Certain workplaces may present risk of occupational exposure. Furthermore, herbal and traditional medicines or cosmetics could be sources for people using these products. Lead can accumulate in certain parts of the body, thus the transplacental and breast milk mediated exposure of successors of employed European women with relatively high age at child birth is of concern. The high variation in breast milk Pb levels and the relatively high concentrations found in some studies suggest that breast milk can pose a source of exposure for infants in some areas.</p>	<p>HBM4EU priority substances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gundacker et al. (2021) Lead (Pb) and neurodevelopment: A review on exposure and biomarkers of effect (BDNF, HDL) and susceptibility https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113855 • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonized questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/
<p>4. What kind of exposure sources are the most important for the children of various age groups and the younger or older adult population?</p>	<p>A literature review in peer-reviewed journals was performed to answer this policy question.</p> <p>Due to the low number of studies available for the statistical analysis, the work is still in progress in WP10. The protocol has been elaborated for the statistical analysis.</p>	<p>Based on the literature review, milk and cereals are the most important sources of lead for children, and grain-based foods for adults.</p> <p>In some more deprived and polluted areas children’s Pb exposure can be of concern.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.6 Scoping documents for the second round priority substances • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances

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<p>5. Taking the hazard from transplacental lead exposure of the unborn child into consideration, what are the blood lead levels of pregnant women?</p>	<p>A literature review in peer-reviewed journals was performed to answer this policy question.</p> <p>The available human physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models were reviewed in WP12.</p> <p>Due to the low number of studies available for the statistical analysis, the work is still in progress in WP10. The protocol has been elaborated for the statistical analysis.</p>	<p>Based on the literature review, the mean maternal and cord blood Pb concentrations did not exceed the EFSA BMDL01 value of 12 µg/L in the European surveys implemented after 2005. Lead concentrations were only slightly lower in cord than in maternal blood, indicating that the placenta does not constitute a barrier for Pb transfer from the maternal to the foetal compartment.</p> <p>The toxicokinetics of lead have been studied extensively using experimental studies and modelling and different toxicokinetic models are available to predict blood lead concentrations. The extension of the physiologically based pharmacokinetic model to pregnancy would be needed to fully assess the foetal exposure.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gundacker et al. (2021) Lead (Pb) and neurodevelopment: A review on exposure and biomarkers of effect (BDNF, HDL) and susceptibility https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113855 • Additional Deliverable 12.8 Review of available models for the 2nd set of prioritised substances
<p>6. Taking the presumably low concentration of lead in blood, is it feasible to measure blood lead levels in children from as small amount of blood as it can be gained from capillary samples? What criteria should be applied in order to avoid contamination from</p>	<p>As lead is not investigated in the HBM4EU aligned studies this question could not yet be addressed.</p>		

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outside sources?			
<p>7. As it is difficult to connect later outcomes with exposures, which biomarkers of effects can be used in relation to effects caused by lead exposure?</p>	<p>A review on the biomarkers of effect associated with lead exposure was published.</p>	<p>There is not sufficient information for mandatory inclusion of specific effect markers in future HBM studies concerning lead exposure associated with neurodevelopmental disorders. Reduced brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) is a potential biomarker of Pb-induced neurotoxicity that should be further investigated.</p> <p>BDNF is a key regulator of brain development and neural plasticity and is involved in the pathophysiology of diverse neurological and psychiatric disorders. BDNF can be assessed in different biological matrices and at different exposure levels. Among other environmental chemicals, including bisphenols, phthalates and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons can influence the expression and regulation of this protein.</p> <p>Epigenetic changes due to environmental exposures, including DNA methylation, can influence BDNF expression and regulation, thus the DNA methylation status of the BDNF gene seems to be another (more stable) biomarker of neurotoxic effects caused by lead exposure.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 14.5 Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances • Gundacker et al. (2021) Lead (Pb) and neurodevelopment: A review on exposure and biomarkers of effect (BDNF, HDL) and susceptibility https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113855

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<p>1. How effective are policy actions to reduce human exposure to mercury in Europe? (Including the EU's Strategy on Mercury and the Minamata Convention, which was ratified by the EU and Member States)?</p>	<p>WP4: The “Mercury & Methylmercury” Chemical substance Group was prioritised for action within HBM4EU in the 2nd round of prioritisation, was approved in May 2018 and a Chemical Group Leader was appointed (D4.5). A scoping document was developed, which summarises the state of the art, identifies knowledge gaps, presents policy questions and suggests actions to be carried out in the frame of HBM4EU to address them (D4.6). The scoping document is updated yearly (D4.9).</p> <p>WP 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 2: Implementation of the HBM4EU-MOM study (“Methylmercury-control in European pregnant women through suitable dietary advice for pregnancy”) in Cyprus, Greece, Iceland, Spain and Portugal (10/2020-6/2022). This is a randomised control trial of 654 pregnant women. Half of the participants of each national cohort received dietary advice for fish consumption during pregnancy. The central theme of the intervention was “fish is good, eat good fish” and species to be consumed / species to be avoided were provided using the ‘traffic light system’. Mercury biomonitoring (using maternal hair and questionnaires) was done at early pregnancy and at ≤3 months after provision of advice to the intervention participants. The resulting harmonized European databases were used for statistical</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM4EU results confirm the existing association between HBM mercury levels and the consumption fish and seafood • The level of exposure to mercury through the fish/seafood consumption depends on the types of species (and portions / frequency) included in the diet • Responsible fish consumption during pregnancy, can help to control exposure to mercury, while maintaining the nutritional benefits of fish • Health-care providers of pregnant women are important stakeholders for awareness-raising and educational actions • Harmonised, quality-assured HBM results can support the evaluation of the effectiveness of policy actions at European and international level 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. D4.5 - Second list of HBM4EU priority substances and Chemical Substance Group Leaders for 2019-2021 2. D4.6 - Scoping documents for the second-round priority substances 3. D4.9 - Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances <p>Knowledge Lab “Mercury in the European Environment and Population”, 2nd Conference of the Parties (COP2) to the “UN Minamata Convention on Mercury”, Geneva, November 2018</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Letter with input on Gender and Mercury submitted by the CGL to the Secretariat of the UN Minamata Convention on Mercury, on behalf of HBM4EU, in December 2020 (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/the-project/science-to-policy/) 5. Presentations on mercury CG: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1 14th International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Krakow, 2019 (oral presentation) 5.2 CLIMATICO conference, Limassol, 2019 (oral presentation) 5.3 Chemistry conference, Nicosia, 2020 (oral presentation)

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	<p>analyses and modelling.</p> <p>WP2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in UN Minamata COP2 (2018) <p>To explore how HBM4EU might contribute at global level, the WPL2 and the CGL-Hg attended the 2nd Conference of the Parties (COP2) to the “UN Minamata Convention on Mercury”, (Geneva, 11/2018). The CGL presented HBM4EU and its work on mercury in the frame of a Knowledge Lab on “Mercury in the European Environment and Population”, organised by the EEA. Ways in which HBM may contribute to the effectiveness evaluation of the convention and possible collaborations with the World Health Organisation to support global harmonisation of mercury biomonitoring were explored.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the HBM4EU work on mercury at international conferences. • Feature on mercury as a prioritised Substance Group in HBM4EU in the 4th HBM4EU (of April 2019) • Policy brief and substance report on mercury is being developed and will summarise toxicity, exposure, and policy status, any updates in legislation and relevant HBM4EU research results. <p>Work Packages (WP) 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 overarching activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • update current knowledge regarding the 		<p>5.4 ISEE2021 (2 poster presentations: (a) HBM4EU-mom: Intervene to raise awareness to specific dietary recommendations and reduce prenatal exposure to mercury and (b) Obstetricians’ engagement for successful recruitment of participants in a randomised controlled trial promoting healthful fish consumption during pregnancy) and 1 e-poster discussion)</p> <p>5.5 HBM4EU 5th Consortium Meeting (poster presentation)</p> <p>5.6 HBM4EU 4th & 5th Consortium Meeting (oral presentations)</p> <p>5.7 HBM4EU 5th Stakeholder Forum (oral presentation)</p> <p>5.8 Workshop of the World Health Organisation – Region for Europe on the Implementation of the Minamata Convention on Mercury in the Health Sector</p> <p>5.9 Invited presentation at PPTOX2022 (International Conference on Prenatal Programming and Toxicity, Jan 10-13, 2022)</p> <p>5.10 Minamata Convention Pre-COP4 Side Event, “Can human biomonitoring, combined with fish consumption advice to pregnant women, help to control prenatal exposure to mercury? Insights from</p>

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	<p>baseline exposure of European populations,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collect and develop tools and expertise to harmonise exposure assessment in Europe so that time-trends can be followed, evaluated and interpreted regarding health risks (details elsewhere in this table) • Overarching meeting on mercury (Berlin, 2019), a survey of NHCPs and several internal meetings fostered discussions and provided the forum to discuss the ongoing and planned activities under the HBM4EU, culminating in the approval of HBM4EU-mom: an aligned intervention study in 5 high-fish consuming countries (CY, GR, ES, IS, PT) with the aim to control foetal exposure to mercury by combining HBM with the provision of suitable dietary to pregnant women, which provides new knowledge relevant to policy questions 2,4,5. • The CGL applied to the Minamata Convention Secretariat for the organization of a Minamata Convention pre-COP4 side event. The application was approved. The event was promoted by the UN, the EEA and the CGL on social media and it took place on March 9, 2022 as a webinar hosted by the UN. Mercury in the context of HBM4EU was presented and the MOM study was featured. All five implementing countries (Cy:MOH-CY, EL: AUTH, ES: ISCI, IS: UI, PT: INSA) presented aspects and lessons learnt from the 		<p>the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU)”. The recording of the event is available on the Minamata Secretariat website.</p>

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	<p>implementation of the study and preliminary conclusions from the statistical analysis. Mercury modelling of the MOM data was presented by the AUTH. The EEA moderated the discussion. More than 100 persons participated in this event, which was mentioned as one of the most popular site events by the Minamata secretariat and was praised for the work presented and the successful engagement of the participants.</p>		
<p>2. How can harmonised, validated and comparable information be collected and transferred to support and evaluate current policies?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM4EU-MOM study (Pillar 2: WPs 8,9,10,12,2) prepared and used harmonised targeted tools for the assessment of exposure, practices and attitudes of pregnant women related to mercury and diet. Tools were also developed for dietary intervention about fish/seafood consumption in pregnancy. The preliminary assessment from the use of these materials suggests that they were well suited for their indented purpose. • WP 7, 9 and 10 developed a frame to assure the quality of new collections of biomonitoring data and of existing samples and data, which are made available to the project. <p>WP9 elaborated criteria for the identification and selection of the best exposure biomarkers and matrices and for the evaluation of analytical methods, which can be used in European HBM surveys (see D9.1). Based on these criteria, a prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and methods for the assessment of human exposure to mercury and methylmercury was elaborated (see D9.5).</p>	<p>WP7 developed strategies, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and materials, which can support the harmonised recruitment, sampling (including sample exchange), questionnaire implementation and communication with participants in HBM studies, taking into account ethical and personal data protection requirements (AD7.1, D7.2, D7.3, D7.4, D7.7, AD7.2, D7.6).</p> <p>For Mercury, questionnaires for adults, adolescents and children are available. Questionnaires for the 2nd occupational study on e-waste (incl. Mercury as a biomarker) have also been developed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • “AD7.1: Upgrade of the strategy for

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	<p>The matrices of choice for both mercury and methylmercury were identified to be urine, whole blood and hair (with the latter being an easily available, non-invasive and inexpensive matrix for the estimation of methylmercury exposure). Dried blood spot samples and meconium are new matrices, which may prove valuable for the evaluation of internal exposure of newborns based on recent literature reports. The recommended analytical techniques for the determination of methylmercury are AAS (atomic absorption after generation of cold vapor of Hg) and ICP-MS. A list of 43 candidate laboratories for the determination of mercury was elaborated in D9.6.</p> <p>WP10 elaborated a preliminary version of the final Data Management Plan (DMP) in AD10.1, which describes the data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, processed and/or generated by HBM4EU (including criteria/methods and standards for data collection, data handling and sharing, data storage, data accessibility, while respecting ethics/legal requirements).</p> <p>This Plan includes the HBM4EU Data Policy. WP10 also developed a Statistical Analysis Plan (D10.5), which includes issues common to all HBM analyses, description of the statistical approach to look into time-trends, geographical comparisons, exposure determinants, exposure distributions and reference values, uncertainty analysis as well as a specific statistical analysis plan for the mercury priority substance group.</p>		<p>human sample exchange, including SOPs”;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “D7.2: Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands”; • “D7.3: 1st prioritisation Report on survey design: Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, tailored and transferred questionnaires for recruitment and sampling”; • “D7.4: 1st material for communication to participants, including informed consent”; • “D7.7: 2nd set of materials for communication to participants, including informed consent”; • “AD7.2: Literature research and concept for a sample quality study on impact of thawing and freezing on integrity of human samples for selected 1st and 2nd priority substances”; • “D7.6 - 2nd prioritisation Report on survey design: Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, tailored and transferred questionnaires for recruitment and sampling”. • AD8.6: HBM4EU-MOM Research Plan • AD8.7: HBM4EU-MOM Interim Report • AD8.8: HBM4EU-MOM Final Report • “D9.1: Criteria for prioritisation of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods”

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	<p>Moreover, the statistical analysis plan for the MOM-study was elaborated in D10.12. It includes data handling, descriptive statistics, approach to investigate association between hair Hg and seafood consumption patterns with an aim to discover effects of the intervention applied in the mom study. It also covers the plan to evaluate geographic patterns All materials, which have been developed to support harmonised practices, are publicly available to the whole consortium and any other interested party, via the online library. Work Package 7 (WP7) developed strategies, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and materials, which can support the harmonised recruitment, sampling (including sample exchange), questionnaire implementation and communication with participants in HBM studies, taking into account ethical and personal data protection requirements.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D9.5: Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances • D9.6: Database of candidate laboratories for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances. • AD10.1 Preliminary version of final Data Management Plan (DMP) • D10.5 Statistical Analysis Plan • D10.12 Statistical analyses plan co-funded studies WP8, including mom-study
<p>3. What biomonitoring and exposure data on mercury (and its species), relevant to the European population, are currently available and what new data are needed to address policy-related questions?</p>	<p>Pillar 2 (WP8,9,10,2). As a result of discussions of the knowledge gaps and policy needs with the NHCPs and relevant consortium partners, a proposal was elaborated for an aligned intervention study in 5 high fish-consuming countries, targeting pregnant women (AD8.6), which was approved and kicked off in October 2020 (HBM4EU-MOM study, see under PQ1 and AD8.6, AD8.7, forthcoming AD8.8 and MOM study publications). In the frame of the MOM study, new harmonised HBM data about the exposure of pregnant women to mercury were collected in CY,GR,ES,IS,PT. Nationally tuned harmonised dietary advice was provided in a randomised control trial and HBM is now used to</p>	<p>See answer to the question 2 (data platform developed by WP7)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonised, quality-controlled data on vulnerable populations collected at different time-points for time-trends are important for the assessment of the effectiveness evaluation of policies • The new, harmonised biomonitoring data of fish-consuming pregnant women in PT,ES,GR,CY,IS collected in the frame of the HBM4EU-MOM study, provide a basis to compare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • D7.5 Report on ongoing activities and existing data and data gaps for the 2nd prioritised substances • AD8.6 Research Plan for Hg Study • AD8.7 An interim report for the Management Board for decision during meeting in May 2021 • AD8.8 - Final report for the assessment of the impact on an intervention on mercury exposure during pregnancy (• D10.6 - 2nd annual list of exposure

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	<p>assess the impact of the intervention on the levels of mercury exposure.</p> <p>WP4. The Scoping Document on Mercury and Methylmercury, which was developed in the frame of Work Package 4 (WP4), presents currently available data, and identifies open policy questions and data gaps to fill in order to address them. The policy questions and proposed actions took into consideration feedback received from the internal experts, the EU Policy Board and the Work Package Leaders.</p> <p>WP7. reported (in D7.5) European ongoing activities, existing data and data gaps for the 2nd prioritised substances, including mercury. This information was collected through a questionnaire distributed via the National Hub Contact Points of participating countries in HBM4EU and completed by Principal Investigators. A total of 25 European studies concluded within the last 10 years, ongoing, or planned for starting up in the next five years included assessment of mercury.</p> <p>WP10 achieved progress regarding the inclusion of existing European HBM data in the European commission's Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM) and the European HBM dashboard was developed to interactively visualise the aggregated HBM data.</p> <p>For total mercury, aggregated data from the following studies were made publicly available via the EU HBM dashboard from the 4 European</p>	<p>exposures in 2021 with exposures in 2011 (from DEMOCOPHES, which used a similar protocol to assess exposures of women of reproductive age. 3 countries participated in both studies)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing data coming from studies, which were implemented without a harmonised frame, hinder the risk assessment process Aggregated data, that is summary statistics (percentiles) for mercury exposure data available from existing HBM data collections are integrated in IPCHEM and the European HBM dashboard. WP5, task 5.3 about the Risk Assessment (RA) of mercury and its organic compounds have identified high variability in the data from European HBM studies regarding Hg (blood and hair, total Hg and/or MeHg) in the general population. This highlights the need for harmonised sampling protocols and chemical analysis to obtain comparable results between countries, in order to identify differences in European exposure. 	<p>distributions and/or European reference values</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IPCHEM HBM Module European HBM dashboard D5.11 - 4th substance-group specific risk assessment Freire et al. Concentrations and determinants of lead, mercury, cadmium, and arsenic in pooled donor breast milk in Spain. <i>Int J Hyg Environ Health.</i> 2021;240:113914. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113914. In this study from South Spain, mercury and other heavy metals were measured in longitudinally collected donor breast milk samples and associated factors were investigated. Freire C on behalf of INMA Project. Placental metal concentrations and birth outcomes: The Environment and Childhood (INMA) project. <i>Int J Hyg Environ Health.</i> 2019;222(3):468-478. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2018.12.014. Freire C, on behalf of INMA Project. Prenatal co-exposure to neurotoxic metals and neurodevelopment in preschool children: The Environment and Childhood (INMA) Project. <i>Sci Total Environ.</i> 2018;621:340-351. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.273.

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	<p>regions (i.e. East, North, South and West) :</p> <p>Using urine: Eighteen studies on adults (>20y; East : 3, South: 2, West: 13) and 4 studies on children/teenagers (East : 3, West: 1).</p> <p>Using Blood: Eleven available studies on adults (East: 4, South: 2, West: 4, North: 1), four studies on children/teenagers (East: 3 and West: 1) and one study in newborns (cord blood) (East: 1).</p> <p>Using Breast Milk: One available study from Southern Europe (Freire et al, 2021) and one from Eastern Europe. ++</p> <p>Fifteen available studies on adults (>20y; East: 5, South: 4, West:4, North:2), sixteen studies on children/teenagers (East: 6, South: 2, West: 6, North: 2).</p> <p>Fewer studies were available with data on methylmercury (MeHg):</p> <p>Using Blood: One study from Eastern Europe on newborns (cord blood);</p> <p>Using Hair: Three studies on adults (>20y: East: 1, West: 2) and three on teenagers (12-19y, West: 3).</p> <p>Using human placenta: One study from Southern Europe (Spain) (see Freire et al 2019)</p>		
<p>4. What is the geographic spread of the current exposure and how does it relate to</p>	<p>This question is addressed by the HBM4EU-MOM study, where ~650 pregnant women in five high fish consuming countries in the Mediterranean (CY,GR,ES,PT)_and the Artic (IS) were assessed for mercury exposure (total mercury in hair) and</p>	<p>See answer to the question 2 (questionnaires developed by WP7, that assist answering this question)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Stratification of available data by 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IPCHEM HBM Module • European HBM dashboard • D5.11 - 4th substance-group specific risk assessment

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<p>different exposure sources (environmental; contaminated sites; dental amalgams; dietary, including different species of sea-food)? Ideally, this should capture the exposure of highly exposed populations (e.g. high seafood consumers with distinction of populations consuming predator fish from those with low/no consumption of such fish, such as Southern & Northern Europeans, European arctic populations), but also of low-exposure populations for comparison.</p> <p>Which populations</p>	<p>provided detailed information about their diet related to types of fish/seafood species, portions and frequencies of consumption. In a randomised trial, half of the women received nationally-tuned dietary advice for nutrition and mercury control and a second set of hair samples and personal information were collected from all participants after a minimum of 12 weeks. The results are expected to be available in March 2022.</p> <p>The scoping document on mercury, developed under Work Package 4 (WP4), summarises a lot of available data related to the geographic spread of human exposure, reviews determining factors, provides some information on available relevant cohorts and identifies data gaps. The exposure is higher in coastal populations and correlates with high fish / seafood consumption. The formulation and provision of suitable dietary advice to vulnerable populations should consider both: the contamination levels in different species of fish, as well as the documented nutritional benefits of fish consumption.</p> <p>Work Package 10 (WP10) collects, integrates and makes available existing HBM data on mercury into IPCHEM and the European HBM dashboard. The existing and available HBM data are analysed to assess the baseline exposure of Europeans to total and methyl mercury and the determinants of the exposure. In the European HBM dashboard, the available mercury data from European studies, provided to the project by the participating</p>	<p>sex, educational level, degree of urbanisation, etc. showed that exposure to mercury is higher among participants of high educational status as compared to low educational status. The difference isn't pronounced for participants with middle educational status. As more data become available to the HBM4EU consortium, this work will be updated</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The preliminary analysis of the MOM study results shows geographic variability of mercury exposures of pregnant European women, associated with fish consumption patterns. Though the GMs were lower than the current GVs (EFSA-2012, WHO/FAO-2006), some women exceeded these levels in early pregnancy. The highest exposures among the five countries were observed in PT, where also the provision of fish-consumption advice had the highest impact in protecting the foetus (as suggested by the mercury modelling). The HBM4EU-MOM approach, which employed the central theme 'fish is good, eat good food' and the 'traffic-light system' to recommend fish to be preferred and fish to be avoided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fish consumption patterns and hair mercury levels in children and their mothers in 17 EU countries https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013935114003934 AD8.6 - Research plan for the implementation of an intervention study designed to evaluate and reduce prenatal exposure to mercury in five European countries (2020) AD8.7 - HBM4EU-MOM Interim Report Forthcoming AD8.8 - HBM4EU-MOM final report Forthcoming scientific articles with HBM4EU-MOM study results

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<p>remain vulnerable to health impacts from mercury exposure and how can they be protected?</p>	<p>countries, were treated statistically in a harmonised way. Distribution plots were prepared, presenting the exposure data according to sex, European region, age group and educational level (as a measure of socioeconomic status) and other stratifying factors. See also under PQ3.</p> <p>Work Package 12 (WP12) prepared an integrated exposure modelling platform, which provides a web-based computational environment that brings together the different tools available from the HBM4EU consortium to address all the aspects of the full chain for aggregated exposure assessment in environmental and occupational settings (see “AD12.4 Conceptual design of the integrated computational platform”). The vertical modules include (a) the model run settings module, which serves to define some general settings for each platform run and the overall configuration of a specific platform simulation, (b) the multimedia model module, for the estimation of environmental media concentrations in different environmental matrixes, (c) the microenvironment module, for estimating chemical environmental concentration for indoor locations, (d) the exposure scenario definition module, which enables the development of an exposure scenario for the population group(s) selected, including all possible exposure routes and (e) the internal dosimetry module, which aims at estimating the internal doses of a chemical and its metabolites. The whole concept will be based on a suite of three different PBTK models according with their level of detail and complexity</p>	<p>during pregnancy is a valuable way to communicate with pregnant women.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The health-care providers of pregnant women are important stakeholders, who should be aware, educated and provided with suitable, scientifically-supported information to communicate with pregnant women regarding fish consumption during pregnancy • we have identified a lack of data from countries with high fish consumption, which is the main exposure source. To protect these populations, it would be necessary to establish more awareness campaigns during pregnancy on the most suitable fish species for them and their children, which could be accompanied by regular sampling plans of methylmercury (MeHg) in these populations. 	

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	<p>(the simpler PK model for data poor chemicals, the generic PBTK model and the life-stage changing mother-foetus generic PBTK model).</p> <p>The integrated exposure modelling platform will be optimised by updating the exposure model parameterisation for mercury using available data and will be used to identify the internal exposure to total mercury and methylmercury for various population groups.</p> <p>WP5, task 5.3 have developed the RA of MeHg related to neurodevelopmental diseases in vulnerable population groups (children and woman of childbearing age)</p>		
<p>5. How can the public be informed and how can public awareness and education be raised regarding the effects of mercury on health and the environment and about management options?</p> <p>What advice should be given regarding dietary recommendations to vulnerable</p>	<p>Pillar 2 - WP8 - A study plan was elaborated, for a new harmonised study (HBM4EU-MOM, 10/2020-6/2022) involving 654 pregnant women in five fish-consuming European countries (CY,GR,ES,PT,IS), with the aim to develop and provide suitable dietary advice to pregnant women and to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention using Human Biomonitoring (see under PQ1). This study developed targeted communication materials, which were used to intervene with the diet of pregnant women to promote healthful fish consumption of mercury control. The HBM4EU-MOM model planned the recruitment pregnant women participants via their health care providers, thereby creating opportunities for awareness raising in health professionals (also engaged: WP2,7,9,10,12).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The HBM4EU-MOM approach, which employed the central theme ‘fish is good, eat good food’ and the ‘traffic-light system’ to recommend fish to be preferred and fish to be avoided during pregnancy is a valuable way to communicate with pregnant women. • The health-care providers of pregnant women are important stakeholders, who should be aware, educated and provided with suitable, scientifically-supported information to communicate with pregnant women regarding fish consumption during pregnancy • Actions to engage citizens (as participants in HBM studies, focus groups, surveys, etc) are very 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before informing the public, it is important to know how the risk is perceived by the general population. For that, WP7 developed a questionnaire on risk perception of man-made chemicals which can be found in the online-library https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Targeted communication materials were prepared for the purpose of the HBM4EU-MOM study, which were tested and positively received by participants in five countries. Also, two targeted questionnaires were developed, which were used to interview participants. They included questions for collecting information about the attitudes and preferences of

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<p>Europeans (e.g. pregnant women, infants, high sea-food consumers) and other stakeholders (e.g. health practitioners, policy makers) to reduce exposure to mercury while in keeping with nutritional requirements and cultural dietary preferences? Ideally, this should consider the different types of foodstuff (e.g. types of seafood) consumed in different parts of the EU, the toxicity and occurrence of the different mercury species in different foodstuff and the positive effects of n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated</p>	<p>Work Package 2 (WP2) created a dedicated webpage on the Mercury Priority Substance Group on the HBM4EU website. It includes the scoping document and provides the venue for disseminating a summary of HBM4EU results on the mercury group. Different communication products are being prepared and dissemination actions are elaborated as the work on mercury progresses in the project. A factsheet on mercury for lay audiences was drafted and mercury was featured in the 4th HBM4EU Newsletter (April 2019). In September 2019, a Facebook Live Session on HBM4EU was broadcasted, during which the project coordinator (UBA) and an EEA expert discussed the project. The event engaged citizens from all over Europe, many of whom expressed concerns about mercury and asked related questions. The HBM4EU work on mercury was presented at international scientific conferences and at the 2nd Conference of the Parties to the UN Minamata Convention on Mercury. All open-access deliverables referenced in this summary of results on mercury are accessible on the HBM4EU online library (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/). Videos for lay audiences were prepared and are available on the HBM4EU website, to inform citizens about the problem of chemical exposures and how HBM4EU works to inform European policies for safer chemicals management.</p> <p>Work Package 4 (WP4) organised Citizen Focus Groups in Austria, Portugal, Ireland and the United</p>	<p>important for awareness-raising, assessing -addressing their needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	<p>the participants. These data are now under analysis and are expected to provide useful insights for this topic.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AD4.2 Report of the citizen’s focus groups” and AD4.4 for additional Focus groups in more HBM4EU countries • Matisāne et al. (manuscript in preparation): “Citizens’ Perception and Concerns on Chemical Exposures and Human Biomonitoring – Results from a Harmonized Qualitative Study in Seven European Countries” • Namorado et al 33rd ISEE Conference Abstracts, EHP (2021) DOI: 10.1289/isee.2021.P-481 and manuscript in preparation “The value of Human Biomonitoring to assess chemical exposure and support policies: perceptions of the European population” • Elonheimo et al. “Environmental Substances Associated with Alzheimer’s Disease—A Scoping Review”, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2021, 18(22), 11839; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182211839 • Haverinen et al. “Metabolic Syndrome and Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals: An Overview of Exposure and Health Effects”, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2021, 18(24), 13047;

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<p>fatty acids in fish and of micro nutrients (e.g. selenium) in the diet. Related to this, how can HBM4EU results support policy decisions at EFSA and ECHA?</p>	<p>Kingdom with the aim to gain information on the interests, needs, and questions of European citizens regarding exposure to chemicals in their daily lives and their opinions about possible future actions on Human Biomonitoring. Mercury was among the top five environmental pollutants causing concern to the participating citizens, who regard it as a priority which should be addressed in Human Biomonitoring studies (see “AD4.2 Report of the citizen’s focus groups” and AD4.4 for additional Focus groups in more HBM4EU countries). An Online (questionnaire) Survey was also organised in the countries, which carried out the focus groups, with the aim to understand what EU citizens know about Human Biomonitoring in general, as well as their needs and concerns. Four more countries will carry out similar citizen consultations in 2020 (The Netherlands, Hungary, Denmark and Cyprus).</p> <p>Work Package 11 (WP11) reviewed known relations between substance (including mercury) exposures and health outcomes, based on the information from the scoping documents of WP4. Scientific review-manuscripts are in preparation for Metabolic syndrome, diabetes, osteoporosis and asthma, with the aim to raise awareness in health professionals regarding the health effects of environmental contaminants. Also, WP11 evaluated opportunities and obstacles related to linking HBM, health surveys and administrative data sources (Deliverable D11.3), generated an inventory of European health studies, which could</p>		<p>https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182413047</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mattila et al. “Scoping Review—The Association between Asthma and Environmental Chemicals” Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2021, 18(3), 1323; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031323 • Moore et al. “The Association between ADHD and Environmental Chemicals—A Scoping Review”, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2022, 19(5), 2849; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052849 • Deliverable 11.1 Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies • Deliverable 11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances

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	<p>be linked to HBM studies (D11.1) and provided SOPs/guidelines for combining HBM/health studies and for obtaining information regarding identified health effected related to mercury exposure.</p> <p>Also see below under PQ6, for relevant work by Work Package 5 (WP5).</p>		
<p>6. At what level of exposure to different mercury species and to total mercury are health effects likely to occur? Current guidance values were based on studies of the Faroese people, who have a diet that is unique and does not relate to food consumption patterns in the EU. This important issue has not been given proper attention to date.</p>	<p>Work Package 5 (WP5): To facilitate the interpretation of HBM data in terms of health risks, WP5 developed and refined a procedure for the derivation of HBM-Guidance values (HBM-GV) for the general population and for workers (Apel et al 2020). Work is under way for the derivation of HBM-GV_{GenPop} in blood and urine for covering inhalation exposure (elemental mercury) and oral exposure, (inorganic mercury compounds and organic methylmercury) species (oral and inhalation exposure), provided that sufficient epidemiological / toxicological / toxicokinetic data are available. If not, recommendations will be elaborated for data needed to fill the gaps.</p> <p>In the frame of task 5.3, a RA of MeHg was conducted based on earlier approaches by EFSA in 2012 and integrating data from European HBM surveys. Children/adolescents from 3 to 17 years old and, women of childbearing age, from 18 to 50 years old were identified as vulnerable population groups for this RA. Two types of MeHg HBM datasets were selected: HBM studies (n= 21) with Hg levels (blood and hair, total Hg and/or MeHg) in the general population in different EU countries and the DEMOCOPHES harmonised study as</p>	<p>In general, the European population does not exceed the daily average/intake dose for MeHg/Hg or the HBM-I value. Only countries with high fish consumption such as Spain and Portugal in some cases exceed these values. However, we have identified lack of data from other European countries with also high fish consumption such as France, Italy, Greece & Iceland. For this reason, further RA refinement is needed with harmonised and widespread HBM data to account for differences in European exposure.</p> <p>The mercury species to be considered for deriving an HBM-GV_{GenPop} in urine are elemental mercury (dental amalgams, background exposure/air) and inorganic mercury compounds (non-fish food and drinking water consumption) covered by inhalation or oral studies measuring the mercury exposure level in urine.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.11 - 4th substance-group specific risk assessment • Apel et al. (2020): Human biomonitoring initiative (HBM4EU) – Strategy to derive human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) for health risk assessment. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113622 • Springer A. et al., in preparation: Derivation of human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GV) for mercury - HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the general population • Þórhallur Ingi Halldórsson et al. (partners from UI, MOH-CY, UBA and ISCI). Manuscript in preparation, with running title: Methylmercury and neurodevelopment: Do recent findings support the health-based guidance value set by the European Food Safety Authority in 2012?

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	<p>reference (urine and hair) (total Hg) in children/mothers in 17 EU countries. A total of 6 case-studies were suggested as strategies of RA for each group identified. These case-studies were based on estimations of the fraction of children/adolescents and women from the EU general population exceeding the TWI (or their equivalent to TDI) defined by EFSA in 2012 (case-studies 1 and 2, respectively); and based on estimations of the fraction of children/adolescent and women of childbearing age from the EU general population exceeding the HBM I value established by the German Human Biomonitoring Commission (Hazard Quotient-HQ) (case-studies 3 and 4). In addition, similar calculations but using the preliminary Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value defined for general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) provided by WP5 task 5.2 were conducted (case-studies 3b and 4b).</p> <p>Work Package 11 (WP11) develops guidelines to support the standardisation of measurements and comparability of collected health data relevant to mercury in future studies.</p> <p>A literature search by Work Package 12 (WP12), presented in “AD12.8 Review of available models for the 2nd set of prioritised substances”, found that methylmercury and excretion of organic and inorganic mercury have been studied in vivo in humans and animals and that toxicokinetic (PBPK and conceptual) models for methylmercury have been developed in humans to relate external</p>	<p>In contrast, methylmercury (fish consumption) essentially contributes only to the blood mercury level so that an HBM-GV_{GenPop} in blood is needed to cover the methylmercury exposure in fish-consuming populations. Epidemiological studies in the respective populations are the most important data sources in this regard measuring methylmercury or total mercury exposure levels typically in blood or hair.</p> <p>Nevertheless, the blood total mercury level is also triggered by the other mercury species, albeit negligible in fish-consuming populations, so that it is checked whether respective study data are available for a comparative analysis.</p> <p>If not a more sensitive endpoint or point of departure (PoD) can be determined from current study data, the derivations of existing toxicological reference values are used as a source, e.g. tolerable weekly intakes (TWIs) for methylmercury and inorganic mercury by EFSA (2012) or occupational exposure levels converted to general population levels if the respective data are available.</p> <p>Based on the EFSA TWI derivation for</p>	

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	<p>exposure to parent or derivative compound concentrations. Exposure to mercury is studied indirectly by exposure assessment of methylmercury through inhalation and/or oral routes and emphasis is given on the early stage of development during pregnancy, foetal development and lactation. All the studies presented modified PBPK models based on specific literature and can be used, if modified, to study other sensitive population groups. The cited research focuses mainly exposure to methylmercury.</p> <p>In AD12.10, available experimental and in silico data were reviewed to parameterise properly TK and PBTK models for 2nd priority substances, values of key toxicokinetic parameter were identified and differences in toxicokinetics that depend on gender/developmental stage were reported.</p> <p>WP 13: A systematic review has been conducted evaluating all epidemiological studies on mercury and neurodevelopment since publication on the EFSA opinion on mercury in 2012. This work falls under policy question 6 "At what level of exposure to different mercury species and to total mercury are health effects likely to occur? ". The purpose of this systematic review is to answer the question: Do recent studies support the current health-based guidance value as established by EFSA (JECFA and US-EPA) or does new evidence suggest that revision may be needed. Completion of the</p>	<p>methylmercury using Seychelles and Faroe Islands cohort data, the HBM-GV blood value would result in 7.2 µg/L expressed as mercury under the use of uncertainty/assessment factor of in total 6.4. Whether a lower value would result from the comparative analyses covering different endpoints and exposure routes is yet to be determined.</p> <p>Based on the EFSA TWI derivation for inorganic mercury using animal study data with effects on kidney weights, the PoD for the derivation of the HBM-GV in urine is proposed to be the benchmark dose lower confidence limit 10% BMDL10 of 0.06 mg/kg BW/d, expressed as mercury, if not a more sensitive PoD in urine will be determined for the inhalation route (ongoing work).</p>	

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	manuscript is in its finals stage (partners UI, UBA, ISCII, MU, Cyprus).		

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<p>7. How does exposure relate to the manifestation of adverse health effects? - What are possible health effects resulting from chronic low exposure to mercury and its organic compounds (such as from food consumption and dental amalgams)? This type of exposure is the most relevant for Europeans and can be addressed by speciation analysis of biobanked samples from existing cohorts and associations with adverse health effects.</p>	<p>Work Package 13 (WP13) carries out work to establish causal links between exposures and health. Tasks 13.1 and 13.2 jointly developed a WP13 Strategy on addressing the policy questions related to the 2nd list of priority compounds (see “AD13.1 Strategy on how to address policy questions related to the 2nd list of priority compounds”). A mercury-focus group was established and a leader for the substance group within WP13 was identified and actions on how to address the mercury policy questions were planned. In AD13.6 “Answers to exposure-health policy questions for the 2nd priority compounds”, the ongoing work is summarised: Existing cohorts are used to assess Hg impact on neurobehavior taking into account co-exposures to other elements with neurotoxic potency (Pb,As,Mn) and OP pesticides and also beneficial elements (including Se, Zn) and to investigate the allele frequencies of related SNPs across Europe and how this may contribute to contradicting associations between exposure and health outcomes found so far. This is done in association with WP10. Currently, an extensive literature search is ongoing to obtain Europe-wide SNP frequencies for genes that are known to have potential impact on vulnerability and on the association between Hg exposure or/and neurodevelopmental effects. This will be assessed in terms of the reported adverse associations with prenatal Hg exposure across Europe.</p> <p>Also under the frame of WP13, a systematic literature review was carried out of all</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New findings since 2012 do not provide robust evidence for adversity at or slightly above the current TWI • Based on scoping reviews of published studies, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▫ association of mercury with Alzheimer’s Disease is possible, but the results are inconsistent. ▫ mercury is only potentially associated with asthma, based on epidemiological studies ▫ Limited evidence exists for an association between ADHD and mercury ▫ Current evidence on environmental exposures and associations with metabolic disturbances and EDCs is still limited and heterogeneous, and mainly represent studies from North America and Asia, highlighting the need for well-conducted and harmonised HBM programmes among the European population ○ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AD13.1 Strategy on how to address policy questions related to the 2nd list of priority compounds • AD13.6 “Answers to exposure-health policy questions for the 2nd priority compounds • Þórhallur Ingi Halldórsson et al. (partners from UI, MOH-CY, UBA and ISCH). Manuscript in preparation, with running title: Methylmercury and neurodevelopment: Do recent findings support the health-based guidance value set by the European Food Safety Authority in 2012? • Janja Snoj Tratnik et al. Manuscript in preparation, with running title: Europe-wide genetic predisposition for adverse health impacts from prenatal mercury exposure. • Jean-Baptiste Fini et al. Manuscript in preparation “Novel effect biomarkers associated to mercury: a review of the epidemiological evidence for epigenetic modulation by mercury” • Elonheimo et al. “Environmental Substances Associated with Alzheimer’s Disease—A Scoping Review”, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2021, 18(22), 11839; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182211839 • Haverinen et al. “Metabolic Syndrome

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<p>- What factors make people more susceptible to the development of health effects due to mercury exposure?</p>	<p>epidemiological studies on prenatal exposure to Hg in relation to neurodevelopmental outcomes in the offspring. This work was conducted with the aim to evaluate new evidence from the epidemiological literature since EFSA's 2012 opinion, to evaluate if new developments have occurred to address the identified data gaps and if current knowledge supports or contradicts the EFSA's conclusions from eight years ago. The output of this work is now being written up for a peer-review publication and was communicated to task 5.2 for consideration for the derivation of HBM-GVs and to Task 5.3.</p> <p>Work Package 14 (WP14) carries out work to identify the most suitable biomarkers of effect for mercury through a focused literature search of mercury-related human and animal studies and reported health endpoints (see D14.5 - Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances). Comprehensive literature searches with defined search terms for mercury/methylmercury and selected health endpoints (reproduction, neurodevelopment, metabolic & cardiovascular, immune/allergy, endocrine, and cancer) were conducted in the PubMed/MEDLINE database (D14.5). To focus the literature search on novel biomarkers and to reduce the number of articles, search terms related to OMICS, epigenetics or biomarker-related were included, while exclusion terms were used to eliminate articles with irrelevant focus. The most relevant effect biomarkers used in epidemiological</p>		<p>and Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals: An Overview of Exposure and Health Effects”, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2021, 18(24), 13047; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182413047</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mattila et al. “Scoping Review—The Association between Asthma and Environmental Chemicals” Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2021, 18(3), 1323; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031323 • Moore et al. “The Association between ADHD and Environmental Chemicals—A Scoping Review”, Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2022, 19(5), 2849; https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052849

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	<p>settings are summarised, prioritised and linked to the available experimental or AOP support (D14.6). BDNF, oxidative stress and many epigenetic and gene expression markers were found to be correlated with higher exposure to mercury in human studies. Given the wide amount of specifically deregulated genes and epigenetic effects identified, future efforts should prioritise the most interesting molecular targets based on mechanistic and AOP information. The output of this work on new epigenetic biomarkers of effects on multiple endpoints (neurodevelopment, metabolism, cancer and reproduction) will be reported in a review article, which is under preparation (Tentative title: Novel effect biomarkers associated to mercury: a review of the epidemiological evidence for epigenetic modulation by mercury).</p> <p>Good examples of biomarkers of effect of mercury exposure are the determination of TSH at birth in children in order to detect (and to mitigate early) congenital hypothyroidism, as well as the epigenetic biomarker PON1 (hypomethylation in newborns) or pSEPP1 (hypomethylation in adults) (reviewed by Couderq et al., 2022 submitted). Experimental validation had been conducted to test the impact of exposure to mercury on the expression of genes, including the BDNF gene, using a 3R-compliant model to identify specific mechanism pathways and to construct reliable AOPs.</p>		

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17 Mycotoxins

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<p>1. Are there validated and harmonised analytical methods to assess the target mycotoxins exposure?</p>	<p>Under HBM4EU, an interlaboratory comparison study comprising three rounds, dedicated to urinary total DON (sum of free DON + DON-glucuronides after deconjugation), was conducted for the 1st time, and several European laboratories were identified that are capable of providing comparable HBM data for determination of this biomarker of exposure. Samples from the aligned studies of six European countries were analysed for urinary total DON by LC-MS/MS, in the four qualified HBM4EU laboratories.</p>	<p>There is a validated method for total DON (after deconjugation) in urine, that has been chosen as biomarker for exposure to DON and its derivatives (3/15-acetyl-DON, DON-3G).</p> <p>The fact that FB1 is mainly excreted in faeces and not in urine has impaired the development of reliable analytical methods to measure FB1 exposure, e.g., in urine.</p>	<p>D 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances</p> <p>D9.5 “Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances”, v4.0, 2021 update.</p> <p>D9.6 “Database of candidate laboratories for the 2nd prioritisation round of substances and update for the 1st round”, 2020.</p> <p>AD5.4 “Reporting for first and second set of substances”, 2020.</p>
<p>2. What are the current exposure levels of the European population to DON and FB1? Are there exposure data for other mycotoxins?</p>	<p>A literature search on mycotoxins human biomonitoring including the years from 2000 to 2022 was performed. HBM data were systemised in a single database. This database was used by WP5, task 5.3 for risk assessment of the targeted mycotoxins. Information on aggregated data for total DON (tDON), free DON (fDON) and FB1 and other mycotoxins was gathered and is reported in a paper on exposure determinants and geographical variability (in preparation).</p> <p>Regarding individual data, HBM studies were identified in a literature search (2010-2020) and Data Owners were invited to share the data collection with HBM4EU and to</p>	<p>New data for tDON is currently available from a HBM4EU Aligned Study focused on adults. The data was collected between 2014-2021 across 6 sampling sites in Europe (Iceland, Poland, France, Germany, Portugal and Luxembourg) representing 1270 individuals. P50 and P95 of urinary tDON concentrations are in the range of 0.39 - 9.05 µg/g crt and 2.38 - 39.18 µg/g crt respectively. Share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the BE-value of 23 µg/L range is from 0.0% - 20.73%.</p> <p>Concerning FB1, new data was not obtained due the limitations related to the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D10.5 “Data management and analysis”, 2019 • “Human Biomonitoring of mycotoxins in Europe: exposure determinants and geographical variability” (Research Protocol) • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for

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	<p>participate. Metadata was made publicly available via IPCHEM. A bilateral transfer agreement is ongoing between Data Owner/Data Provider and the data user to allow transfer of the individual data to the HBM4EU repository and its subsequent use. The codebook for the exposure variables was finalised.</p> <p>The HBM4EU dashboard has only 1 dataset with mycotoxins exposure data integrated and in IPCHEM metadata from 6 datasets with mycotoxins data are available.</p> <p>Under the aligned studies, a biomarker of DON exposure (urine total DON, tDON) was included in the aligned studies for the adult population across Europe that contributed to also answer this question. In 6 countries (Poland, Iceland, Portugal, Germany, France and Luxembourg) total DON was measured in 1270 samples from adults.</p> <p>For FB1, 10 studies were identified from literature search reporting urine concentration levels. However, only two detected FB1 due to its low urinary recovery and high inter-individual variability in absorption and excretion.</p> <p>Other mycotoxins exposure profiles are under study based on the available HBM data from literature search.</p>	<p>selection of a reliable exposure biomarker.</p> <p>In conclusion, urinary HBM data on total DON obtained from a literature search and from the aligned studies developed under HBM4EU confirm that the European population is exposed to DON and that a fraction of this population is, to some extent, exposed to levels that represent a potential health concern.</p>	<p>communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of exposure distributions and/or European exposure values 2 papers in preparation on exposure determinants and geographic variability and aligned studies for tDON: • -Human Biomonitoring of mycotoxins in Europe: exposure determinants and geographical variability • - Current exposure of the European adult population to mycotoxins: results from the HBM4EU aligned studies
<p>3. and 4. Does the exposure to mycotoxins</p>	<p>Differences on mycotoxins exposure profiles as well as the geographic variations of FB1</p>	<p>According to literature search, children and pregnant women, who are</p>	<p>2nd list of priority substances – Description of the assessment plan for</p>

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<p>differ among different population groups? Which are the main factors related with these differences (age, gender, settings, geographic localisation)?</p> <p>Is there a time trend in human exposure to mycotoxins across Europe? Which are the identifiable factors associated with these trends (regulation related with food safety, climate change, others)?</p>	<p>and DON exposure were analysed either through the literature survey or using the new data obtained in the aligned studies.</p> <p>An attempt was made under WP10 to address the time trends of mycotoxins exposure; however, the data available were limited and not sufficient to perform this analysis.</p>	<p>traditionally considered vulnerable population groups, were the groups with the highest risk. The Eastern region was not presented in the current assessment. Additionally, and based only on the data from the literature search, it is important to emphasise that some studies reported a statistically significant difference between workers and control groups, confirming that the occupational environment can have an important role in increasing the exposure to DON.</p> <p>The risk assessment performed using the exposure data obtained from the HBM4EU aligned studies indicates that a part of the adult population from Poland and, to some extent, from Luxembourg, France and Portugal is at high risk, which raises a potential health concern.</p> <p>The current HBM data from aligned studies set a baseline to allow future data comparison and time trend analysis.</p>	<p>Mycotoxins, 2020</p> <p>D 5.11 Human Biomonitoring in Risk Assessment</p>
<p>5. Is the risk associated to human exposure to these mycotoxins characterised?</p>	<p>A risk assessment of DON was developed in the scope of task 5.3. The main objectives were to assess the risk associated to human exposure to DON in populations from different European countries or regions, based both on published human biomonitoring data and on the new data generated for the adult population in the context of the aligned studies developed across Europe. FB1 was not included because there is very limited human</p>	<p>The HBM-GV derived for DON allowed, for the first time, to assess the risk of DON based on exposure biomarkers data.</p> <p>The risk assessment performed using published data and a mass balance approach showed that exposure to DON in the European population is generalised, affecting different age groups of the population. Children and pregnant</p>	<p>AD5.4 “Reporting for first and second set of substances”, 2020</p> <p>2nd list of priority substances – Description of the assessment plan for Mycotoxins, 2020</p> <p>D 5.11 Human Biomonitoring in Risk Assessment</p> <p>Data on RA of tDON based on aligned</p>

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	<p>biomonitoring data to support its exposure assessment therefore, only DON risk assessment was assessed.</p> <p>The establishment of an HBM-GV for DON was also performed under task 5.2 and it is considered of major importance for risk assessment, contributing to a significant decrease in uncertainty. The human biomonitoring guidance value for DON derived under HBM4EU allowed for the first time, to assess the risk of DON based on exposure biomarkers and an HBM-GV. This accomplishment was possible for DON due to the available kinetic models in humans. The same was not possible for FB1 due to the lack of models.</p>	<p>women, who are traditionally considered vulnerable population groups, presented the highest risk groups according to data from literature survey. The children group deserves particular attention considering the associated vulnerability and the potential long-term consequences that are difficult to predict.</p> <p>The risk assessment performed using results from the aligned studies conducted in the adult population, as referred above, showed that the highest percentiles of exposure (P90 and P95) represented a potential health concern for the population from Poland and, to a certain extent from Luxembourg, France and Portugal, since the hazard quotient determined is above one. However, the mean and median levels of exposure were considered as not representing a concern for health. The risk is low for populations from Iceland and Germany.</p> <p>Results obtained from the aligned studies conducted in Iceland and Germany revealed an exposure to DON that does not represent a health concern.</p>	<p>studies data will be included in a manuscript (in preparation, reported at PQ 2</p>
<p>6. Are there exposure models and toxicokinetics data for mycotoxins and which are their limitations?</p>	<p>In Task 12.3, the parameterisation of the generic PBTK model developed in Task 12.1 for mycotoxins was performed. Specifically, a published human PBTK model for DON, with a focus on pharmacokinetic parameter values and methods used to estimate these values</p>	<p>Kinetic models for DON in humans are available but not for FB1. A dedicated model for DON was developed within HBM4EU, but not for FB1.</p> <p>Regarding FB1, future efforts should be</p>	<p>AD 12.8 “Review of available models for the 2nd set of prioritised substances”, Deliverable Report AD 12.8, 2019 (+ ongoing paper)</p> <p>D12.7“Biological half-life and internal</p>

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	<p>was taken into account. In addition, literature data, generally obtained experimentally (in vivo or in vitro) was also used for the estimation of parameter values.</p> <p>As biological half-life values of mycotoxins DON and FB₁ in humans were not found, data from half-life values in different biological media (plasma, liver, kidney, muscles and brain) of animals were reported.</p>	<p>undertaken to increase the knowledge on their toxicokinetics and, consequently, contribute to a better human risk assessment. Other mycotoxins PBPK model available include zearalenone and its metabolites.</p>	<p>dosimetry of the 2nd set of priority compounds”, Deliverable Report D12.7, 2020.</p> <p>Mengelters M, Zeilmaker M, Vidal A, De Boevre M, De Saeger S and Hoogenveen R. Biomonitoring of Deoxynivalenol and Deoxynivalenol-3-glucoside in Human Volunteers: Renal Excretion Profiles. Toxins 2019, 11, 466; doi:10.3390/toxins11080466</p>
<p>7. Is it possible to set HBM guidance values for mycotoxins?</p>	<p>After consulting experts from WP 5, task 5.2 and the CGLs, identified the possibility of deriving an HBM guidance value for DON and a value was set for the first time, based on published data. The critical endpoint was “reduced body weight gain” from a chronic feeding study in mice (Iberson et al ,1995). This study had been previously identified by EFSA (2017) as the critical study for this purpose. The provisional HBM-GV was based on a BMDL05 as point of departure, using a reverse dosimetry factor and assessment factor of 100.</p>	<p>A provisional HBM-GV_{GenPop} (general population) was derived for DON that should be considered as an orientation value. The value was set as 23 µg DON/L urine for 24 h sample (CI: 5-33 µg/L) corresponding to an intake of 1 ug total DON/kg bw/total 24h.</p>	<p>Deliverable 5.9 Section “Derivation of a HBM Guidance Value (HBM-GV) for Deoxynivalenol (DON): HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the general population”, 2021</p>
<p>8. and 9. Which are the key events that determine the long-term health effects from low-dose continuous exposure to the target</p>	<p>A working group addressed the effect biomarkers reported in HBM studies for the selected mycotoxins, FB₁ and DON. The most relevant health outcomes were selected for each mycotoxin, based on the effects reported in several epidemiological and animal studies. In addition, the mechanisms of action that are</p>	<p>Neural tube defects in the fetuses of pregnant women after chronic exposure to FB1 may result from the inhibition of ceramide synthase, which affects sphingolipid metabolism in the cell.</p> <p>Combining toxicological information on</p>	<p>AD13.6 - Answers from WP13 to exposure-health policy questions for the 2nd priority compounds, 2020</p> <p>AD14.7 Report of the 3rd Granada Workshop:</p> <p>State of development of WP14</p>

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<p>mycotoxins?</p> <p>Which are the most reliable and informative AOP- based effect biomarkers for prioritised mycotoxins?</p>	<p>deemed to underlie their toxicity (in vitro/ex vivo and in vivo studies) were considered, in an attempt to link the identified health outcomes to central molecular, cellular or tissue/organ key events. This knowledge is relevant to try to establish the molecular initiation event and the key events in order contribute to production of AOP for FB1 in relation to hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity or carcinogenicity and central nervous system alterations. For DON, the health outcomes considered were immunotoxicity, reprotoxicity or endocrine disruption. These liaised with the work performed in WP13 on an AOP development for FB1 and neural tube defect. Regarding DON, a single study referring the use off effect biomarkers related to its immunotoxicity and autism was retrieved.</p>	<p>FB1 with AOPs (in vitro) and data from human studies allowed to identify the measurement of sphinganine (Sa) and sphingosine (So) and Sa/So ratio in urine as potential effect biomarkers associated with fumonisin FB1) exposure, which can be linked also to a health outcome, the neural tube defects.</p> <p>Other works have pointed to some endpoints and methodological approaches, e.g., gene expression or gene methylation analyses that deserve to be further explored to discover novel effect biomarkers.</p> <p>No human relevant long-term health effects were yet identified after chronic exposure to DON. Likewise, no informative effect biomarker was identified for DON.</p>	<p>interactions with other HBM4EU-WPs</p> <p>D 14.5 “Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances”, 2020.</p> <p>AD14.6” Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation”, 2020.</p> <p>van den Brand AD, Bajard L, Steffensen IL, Brantsæter AL, Dirven HAAM, Louisse J, Peijnenburg A, Ndaw S, Mantovani A, De Santis B, Mengelers MJB. Providing Biological Plausibility for Exposure-Health Relationships for the Mycotoxins Deoxynivalenol (DON) and Fumonisin B1 (FB1) in Humans Using the AOP Framework. <i>Toxins</i> (Basel). 2022 Apr 13;14(4):279. doi: 10.3390/toxins14040279. PMID: 35448888; PMCID: PMC9030459.</p>
<p>10. Which research needs and gaps on Human Biomonitoring activities related to prioritised mycotoxins?</p>	<p>The work developed in the context of several WPs and tasks has evidenced several research needs and gaps on HBM studies that should be addressed in future studies</p>	<p>Research needs and gaps identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • validation and harmonisation of analytical methods for mycotoxins, • standards and reference materials availability, • update of HBM exposure data, to perform a more accurate RA and risk characterisation as well as to try to 	<p>A manuscript is under preparation to address these gaps) on “Current advances, research needs and gaps in Mycotoxins Biomonitoring”.</p> <p>2 oral communications by invitation, performed by CGL, on HBM4EU results on mycotoxins performed in international conferences on food contaminants and</p>

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		<p>identify time trends and possible relation with climate changes (since exposure to some mycotoxins is expected to increase in Europe due to changes in climatic parameters),</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • determination of HBM GV and reference values for FB1, • further development of toxicokinetic models, • further epidemiological research on novel effect biomarkers for FB1 and validation of the existing ones; identification of effect biomarkers and AOP development for DON, • identification, characterisation and risk assessment of mycotoxin mixtures. • risk assessment of other mycotoxins, including unregulated mycotoxins (e.g., enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins) 	<p>World Mycotoxin Forum, May 2022.</p>

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18 Per-Polyfluorinated compounds (PFASs)

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<p>1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to PFASs and do they exceed Guidance values (reference and HBM values), where available?</p>	<p>The European HBM dashboard provides summary statistics for HBM data from different European countries, with 19 aggregated datasets including PFASs exposure data. In IPCHEM metadata for 33 datasets with PFASs data are available. Some harmonised datasets (however, a limited number) are currently available. The available datasets include aggregated data on exposure biomarker levels for FOSA, N-EtFOSA, N-MeFOSA, PFBA, PFBS, PFDA, PFDoDA, PFDS, PFHpA, PFHxA, PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA, PFOS, PFPeA, PFTeDA, PFTTrDA and/or PFUnDA, for the matrices serum, cord serum and/or breast milk. The datasets belong to studies from Belgium, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Demark and were collected within 2000-2017. Available stratifications include information on sex, age groups (including infants <1 yr), ISCED, current non-smokers, and current non-smokers vs smokers. From the existing European data collections studies including analyses of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS dated between 2008 and 2015, were selected. For PFHxS concentrations in urine samples were reported in 3 studies involving toddlers, 1 study involving children and 5 studies involving adults and aggregated data for PFOA and PFOS were reported in 4 studies involving toddlers, 1 study involving children, 1 study involving teenagers and 6 studies involving adults. All studies included at least 116 participants. Despite variations in design, populations, analytical methods, and geographic location, the median concentrations in the different European studies are</p>	<p>We collected information on the human PFAS exposure levels in Europe sampled between 2005 and 2015. These aggregated data are now available at the European HBM dashboard. P50 values for PFOA range from 0.76 to 4.8 µg/L, PFNA levels from 0.28 to 0.86 µg/L and PFHxS from 0.18 to 1.61 µg/L. PFOS remains the dominant congener; P50 values range from 1.67 µg/L to 8.06 µg/L. These levels in newborns, children & teenagers combined, and adults support the concentration levels reported in the EFSA opinion on the risks to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food (2020).</p> <p>The individual data collections prepared and made available within HBM4EU also contained aggregated data stratified by age, sex and educational level. From these stratifications it can be seen that the PFAS concentrations are in general higher in men compared to women for the teenager and adult studies. This could probably be explained by the elimination of PFASs through menstruation, and for mothers also through delivery and lactation. Also,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/European HBM dashboard that allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM) that includes metadata and aggregated data from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#discovery • D10.6: overview on aggregated data of existing HBM data collections obtained through HBM4EU. <p>Vorkamp K, Castaño A, Antignac JP, Boada</p>

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	<p>rather similar, with ratios between the highest and lowest median concentration always being less than 10. Based on existing HBM data, D10.4 presents the first annual list of European reference values (ERV).</p> <p>For the investigation of PFAS exposure, samples were collected between 2014-2021 across 9 sampling sites in Europe (Norway, Sweden, Greece, Slovenia, Spain, Slovakia, France, Belgium, Germany) in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in teenagers of 12-19 years old: 477 samples from the North, 445 from the South, 292 from the East and 743 from the West. Thus, a total of 1957 samples were available. In these samples 8 to 12 PFAS were measured including PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, and PFOS (sum of all isomers). Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p> <p>In addition, within WP8.5 (Targeted occupational studies with EU added values and coordination of activities) occupational PFAS exposure is investigated together with chromate exposure. Therefore, plasma samples of workers are analysed from five studies including a total of 155 samples. Results will be available in June 2022.</p> <p>In order to answer questions on exposure levels and sources and further support current and future HBM studies, WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe. These materials are:</p>	<p>there seems to be a trend that participants with higher educational level have higher exposure levels compared with low to medium educational level. This trend was however less obvious and could not be observed in all studies and for all compounds. In some studies, higher levels of PFASs were observed with increasing age, indicating possible cumulative exposure over time. This was however not observed for all studies and not for all compounds.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies have generated baseline levels of internal PFAS concentrations in serum/plasma samples of European teenagers 12-18 years of age from 9 sampling sites for the period 2014-2021. PFOS has the highest median values and P95 values observed, followed by PFOA, PFHxS and PFNA. In general, PFOS is the main determinant of the sum of 4 PFAS, the contribution of PFNA and PFHxS is lower. Risk for adverse health effects cannot be excluded: the indicator developed under HBM4EU shows that current combined exposure to PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS in teenagers exceeds the health-based guidance value based on the EFSA guideline value for a tolerable weekly intake of 4.4 ng/kg (2020) of 6.9 µg/L for $\Sigma(\text{PFOA} + \text{PFNA} + \text{PFHxS} + \text{PFOS})$</p>	<p>LD, Cequier E, Covaci A, Esteban López M, Haug LS, Kasper-Sonnenberg M, Koch HM, Pérez Luzardo O, Osīte A, Rambaud L, Pinorini MT, Sabbioni G, Thomsen C. Biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods targeting human exposure to chemicals selected for a European human biomonitoring initiative. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2021 Jan;146:106082. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106082 . Epub 2020 Nov 20. PMID: 33227583.</p> <p>Deliverable 7.2 Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands.</p> <p>Deliverable 7.6 - 2nd prioritisation Report on survey design: Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, tailored and transferred questionnaires for recruitment and sampling.</p> <p>Deliverable 8.8 Progress report on strategies adopted to align HBM studies across Europe and preliminary results.</p> <p>Deliverable 8.9 Report on progress targeted occupational studies.</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 9.9 Compilation of the analytical methods used by the HBM4EU laboratories for the substances on the 1st and 2nd prioritisation list.</p> <p>Deliverable 9.8 List of qualified laboratories: Scientific evaluation and the compilation of the lists of the laboratories that completed successfully the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the substances included in the two prioritisation rounds.</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium • manuals/guidelines for study planning and conduct • Standard Operating Procedures for qualified recruitment of participants, fieldwork, sampling and exchange of samples • different kinds of questionnaires for various age groups and substance (groups) • influence of thawing and freezing procedures on the integrity of biobanked samples in the literature and supplied a respective concept for a quality study • templates for the communication with participants • A R-script was developed to calculate the aggregated data in a standardised and comparable way. <p>In WP 8.4, Targeted fieldwork in combining HES and HBM surveys influencing and interfering factors for sampling and storage were identified, whereas for each substance group recommendations were made to avoid sample contamination or inappropriate storage conditions that may influence sample quality and hence the outcome of the analysis. For PFAS, specific recommendations are given, e.g. avoiding Teflon and other fluoropolymers as well as glass in the sampling material, and information on shipment and biobanking. In an additional deliverable (AD7.2), a literature search and a concept for a sample quality study on impact of thawing and freezing on integrity of human</p>	<p>in a fraction of the participants. Exceedances in the different studies and locations range from 1.3%-23.8% with an overall exceedance of 14.3% and an extent of exceedance (P95/6.9 µg/L) varying from 0.74 - 1.78. The studies conducted in Western and Northern Europe had the most teenagers exceeding the guidance value.</p> <p>P50 and P95 concentrations of sum of PFOS + PFHxS + PFOA + PFNA in serum are in the range of 2.55-5.15 µg/L and 5.09-12.31 µg/L across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the EFSA based value of 6.9 µg/L for teenagers ranges from 1.34-23.78%.</p> <p>All teenagers had detectable levels of PFOS in their blood samples. P50 and P95 of serum PFOS concentrations are in the range of 1.34-2.79 µg/L and 3.06-8.23 µg/L across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the HBM-I value of 5 µg/L for teenagers ranges from 1-18%.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of serum PFOA concentrations are in the range of 0.66-1.47 µg/L and 1.03-3.12 µg/L across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels</p>	<p>Deliverable 9.9 Second report on analytical results and new methods developed.</p> <p>Deliverable 10.4 1st annual list of exposure distributions and/or European reference values.</p> <p>Deliverable 10.5 Statistical Analysis Plan.</p> <p>Deliverable 10.6 Second annual list of exposure distributions and/or European Reference Values.</p> <p>Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of exposure distributions and/or European exposure values.</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 10.1 Final Data Management Plan (DMP) (preliminary version)</p> <p>Results:</p> <p>Deliverable 5.X: Approaches to mixture risk assessment of PFASs in the European population based on human hazard and biomonitoring data</p> <p>Bil et al: Approaches to mixture risk assessment of PFASs in the European population based on human hazard and biomonitoring data, in preparation</p>

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	<p>samples was conducted.</p> <p>For the Quality Assurance/Quality Control Scheme in the HBM4EU project (ICI/EQUAS) (WP9.4), the rounds 1-3 of proficiency testing for the determination of PFAS in serum including PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS (sum of all isomers) were concluded. The number of qualified laboratories for PFAS analysis after the 3rd round comprises 21.</p> <p>Impact indicators have been established and used to answer the policy questions.</p> <p>Considerations for the future: There is a need for extending analytical methods to include more substances (PFAS) in the existing methods, such as short-chain PFAS (PFBA, PFOeA, trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)) as well as intermediates from of fluorotelomer precursor PFAS (FTCAs, FTUnCAs) which may have a different toxicity compared to PFAAs. In addition, the implementation of analytical methods for the analysis of “total” PFAS is needed (this would be also future policy relevant for PFAS restriction and the EU PFAS strategy).</p>	<p>exceeding the HBM-I value of 2 µg/L for teenagers ranges from 0-20.28%.</p> <p>P50 serum PFPeA concentrations are in the range of 0.02-0.10 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 5 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.2 µg/L). P95 serum PFPeA concentrations are in the range of 0.17-0.19 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 5 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.2 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for PFPeA.</p> <p>P50 serum PFHxA concentrations are in the range of 0.07-0.14 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 6 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.25 µg/L). P95 serum PFHxA concentrations are in the range of 0.07-0.21 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 5 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.05-0.25 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for PFHxA.</p> <p>P50 serum PFHpA concentrations are in the range of 0.03-0.07 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 6 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.25 µg/L). P95 serum PFHpA concentrations are in the range of 0.09-0.16 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 5 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.25 µg/L). Health-based</p>	

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		<p>guidance values are not available for PFHpA.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of serum PFNA concentrations are in the range of 0.17-0.54 µg/L, with 1 study with P50 < detection limit of 0.5 µg/L, and 0.46-1.38 µg/L across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for PFNA.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of serum PFDA concentrations are in the range of 0.05-0.22 µg/L, with 3 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.2-0.25 µg/L) and 0.17-0.51 µg/L across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for PFDA.</p> <p>P50 serum PFUnDA concentrations are in the range of 0.04-0.11 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 5 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.004-0.25 µg/L). P95 serum PFUnDA concentrations are in the range of 0.08-0.35 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.25 µg/L. Health-based guidance values are not available for PFUnDA.</p> <p>P50 serum PFDoDA concentrations of all studies are < detection limit (range: 0.005-0.25 µg/L) across studies in teenagers. P95 serum PFDoDA concentrations are in the range of 0.025-0.030 µg/L across studies in</p>	

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		<p>teenagers, with 7 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.25 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for PFDoDA.</p> <p>P50 serum PFBS concentrations of all studies are < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.25 µg/L) across studies in teenagers. P95 serum PFBS concentrations are in the range of 0.20-0.37 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 7 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.25 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for PFBS.</p> <p>P50 and P95 of serum PFHxS concentrations are in the range of 0.23-0.68 µg/L, with 1 study with P50 < detection limit of 0.34 µg/L) and 0.43-2.32 µg/L across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for PFHxS.</p> <p>P50 serum PFHpS concentrations are in the range of 0.03-0.05 µg/L across studies in teenagers (with 4 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.05-0.25 µg/L). P95 serum PFHpS concentrations are in the range of 0.10-0.25 µg/L across studies in teenagers, with 2 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.05-0.2 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for PFHpS.</p> <p>Three different mixture risk assessment</p>	

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		<p>approaches indicate that PFAS exposure exceeds guidance values, and thus may cause adverse health effects in certain segments of the European population, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion. It should be mentioned that this work is meant as a scientific exploration of how to use HBM in risk assessment. This exercise explores various approaches to perform mixture risk assessment for PFASs that are based on pragmatism and available data and therefore have their underlying assumptions, limitations and uncertainties.</p>	
<p>2. Are there differences in exposure of the EU population to regulated and non-regulated PFASs?</p>	<p>As described in the answer to the policy question 1 various activities and efforts have been made to assess the exposure of the European population to various PFAS. HBM4EU existing and new HBM data collections and work on indicators (generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV) have been performed in order to assess the exposure of the European population to PFAS.</p>	<p>In general, there are limited data on PFAS beside PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS and PFNA, further the limits of detections are not sufficient in all studies to detect low concentrations. It can be assumed – also based on the results of the PBPK model that certain PFAS s accumulate slowly over time due to their long half-life.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies show that to date, PFOS and PFOA are still the substances occurring in the highest concentrations in blood in Europe. Other PFASs compounds are also detected in many human samples. Alternative PFASs compounds (substitutes of legacy PFASs) have lower exposure levels compared to</p>	<p>HBM4EU –Dashboard: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/ Additional Deliverable 5.5 Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV, https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-5-5-generating-indicators-incorporating-hbm-gv-first-visualisation-examples/ Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/</p>

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		<p>regulated PFAS compounds. However, due to a large proportion of non-detects for alternative PFASs and a big difference in absolute values of LOQs reached across studies there is a need for lowering the LOQs for these compounds.</p>	
<p>3. Has restriction of PFOS according to the POP Regulation led to a reduction in exposure, especially for children?</p>	<p>Concerning time trends observed in Human Biomonitoring studies the EFSA opinion on PFOS and PFOA in food states that generally, after the year 2000, the concentrations in serum/plasma of PFOS, PFOA and in some studies PFHxS have decreased, while the concentrations of PFNA, PFDA and PFUnDA have increased. No clear trends have been reported for other PFAS (EFSA, 2020).</p> <p>Within the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, PFASs have been studied in teenagers. Thus, no new data on exposure of children will become available. Time trends have also been explored within WP 10 using existing data, though limitations due to different study populations and geographical areas need to be considered.</p> <p>Within WP5 HBM indicators have been developed. Indicators are illustrators of data that bring information in an easy and accessible way to a broader audience be it scientists, policy makers or the general population. AD5.5 mainly used PFAS data from DEMOCOPHES and the first HBM4EU data collections to illustrate PFAS exposure and effects. PFAS data from adult women in Denmark and Belgium were available and have been used.</p>	<p>The existing data collected in HBM4EU demonstrate a decrease of PFAS within the observed period. Different datasets were considered investigating the burden to the four PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS) in adult human serum. Although only few datasets were available and there was uncertainty related to robustness, for PFOA and PFOS – which are the most regulated PFAS – a decrease was shown between 2008 and 2015. This is particularly clear in the case of time series measurements, such as those carried out within the framework of the German Environmental Specimen Bank. When comparing the plasma samples of young adults from the German Specimen Bank in the period from 2007 to 2019, a clear decrease can be seen. While the maximum P95 (P50) value for the sum of the 4 PFAS was 28.87 (13,82) µg/l in 2007, in 2019 it is only 8.28 (4,59) µg/l.</p> <p>Further, available HBM data in adult females aged 20-39 years from Belgium show a reduction of PFOS by</p>	<p>Additional Deliverable 5.5 Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV, https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/additional-deliverable-5-5-generating-indicators-incorporating-hbm-gv-first-visualisation-examples/</p>

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		<p>half from 2008 to 2014, while data from Denmark show only a minimal decrease from 2010 to 2012.</p> <p>Although in some individual EU countries (Austria, Germany, Belgium) decreasing time trends of PFOA and PFOS have been described, new data collected in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies still show that a fraction of the teenagers in Europe exceed guidance values for PFOA & PFOS and that substitute PFAS are detected. The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data will form baseline European exposure levels for PFASs in teenagers, allowing follow up studies to monitor increased or decreased usage.</p>	
<p>4. Is exposure driven by diet, consumer exposure, occupation or environmental contamination?</p>	<p>When identifying exposure levels and sources as well as groups at risk, WP7 questionnaires are of great value. They can be used to set up new studies and allow the harmonised collection of data on a participant's individual characteristics and their potential exposure pathways from different sources (sociodemographic characteristics, residential environment/home exposures, dietary habits, lifestyle, occupational exposure and health status) with PFAS. For PFAS, questionnaires for adults, adolescents and children are available.</p> <p>Within the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, PFASs exposure has been studied in teenagers. In addition, a targeted occupational study on hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) is conducted. In addition to chromium analysis, plasma samples of</p>	<p>Regarding exposure determinants in the HBM4EU data collections, besides cohort, sex and education, diet was an important determinant of PFASs. Higher serum levels of PFNA and PFOS were associated with higher consumption of fish and seafood (increase in serum levels by 20 and 21 %, respectively) and higher consumption of eggs (increase in serum levels by 14 and 11 %, respectively). Additionally, higher exposure to PFOS was linked to higher consumption of offal (increase in exposure by 14 %) and consumption of local food (increase in exposure by 40 %). For other food items (meat, fast</p>	<p>Deliverables: D12.1-12.5, AD 12.12 and AD12.13).</p> <p>Risk Assessment of Perfluorooctane Sulfonate (PFOS) using Dynamic Age Dependent Physiologically based Pharmacokinetic Model (PBPK) across Human Lifetime: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111287</p> <p>Deliverable 8.9: Report on progress targeted occupational studies Occupational Exposure: publication in preparation</p> <p>Deliverable 12.8 Report on the results of exposure reconstruction algorithms on available HBM data in the EU for all priority compounds</p> <p>Deliverable 12.6 Integrated exposure modelling</p>

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	<p>workers from five studies including a total of 155 samples are analysed for PFASs, as these substances are used in chromium plating. The study also includes the analyses of several effect biomarkers which are made mainly with the participants own funding. Results will be available in June 2022.</p> <p>Physiology-based toxicokinetic (PBTK) modelling has been used to link external exposure to internal dose in humans (e.g. concentration in urine) by describing the process of absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) that a substance undergoes in living organisms. Within HBM4EU a review of published models for PFAS was performed. Based on the PBPK models available, an improvement of the model was conducted for PFOS and PFOA and validated with human experimental data. Currently, the model is available for oral and inhalation exposure and will be extended for dermal exposure for the named two PFAS. An age-dependent PBTK model involving physiological and biological changes encompassing the full course of a human lifetime (children, adult and elderly) has been developed. This PBTK model considers age-dependent changes of system parameters like tissue volume, tissue blood flow, renal elimination and plasma protein binding for estimating age-related risk from chemical exposure. These models are being adopted for running different case scenarios including sensitive age groups, which can be applied as a tool for policymaking. Comprehensive work on external and internal exposure modelling has been performed, which is published in deliverables related to “from</p>	<p>food, drinking water, milk), no or weak associations with individual PFASs were found.</p> <p>Modelling external and internal PFASs exposure showed that food intake was the most important contributive route to the exposure of PFOS and PFOA, with percentages of 97% and 98% of the total intake, respectively. These estimations were made based on a study from Catalonia (D12.1). This is in line with the assessment of dietary exposure to PFOS and PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS by EFSA (EFSA 2018, 2020). Despite exposure in hot spot regions or specific occupational settings, diet is the main source of PFAS exposure.</p> <p>Preliminary data analysis of the study to investigate PFASs exposure in chromate plating facilities indicates a statistically significant difference in PFAS plasma concentrations of chrome platers (n=52) when compared to controls (n=57) for some PFAS compounds (namely PFOA, PFHxS, L-PFHpS and L-PFOS). Median concentrations of chrome platers were at maximum about two times higher (PFHxS and L-PFHpS) than respective median concentrations of controls. P95 levels of chrome platers were at maximum about 20 times higher (L-PFHpS and L-PFOS) when compared</p>	<p>platform</p> <p>Deliverable 12.5: Risk characterisation of the 1st set of prioritised substances using external exposure estimated from HBM data: a methodological approach</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data.</p>

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	<p>HBM to Exposure” within work package 12 (see respective Deliverables: D12.1-12.5, AD 12.9, AD 12.12 and AD12.13). Ongoing work of exposure assessment of the European population to PFAS will allow to develop an extended pan-European exposure modelling.</p> <p>Additionally, as stated in the answer to policy question 1, different work has been undertaken for the identification of the exposure of the EU population to PFAS. As described above exposure of European teenagers will be investigated, this will be accompanied by the assessment of determinants of exposure.</p>	<p>to controls.</p>	
<p>5. Which areas and environmental media in Europe are contaminated with PFASs?</p>	<p>A substance-group-specific statistical analysis plan has been developed for PFASs. Variables for assessing environmental contamination have been identified: place of birth, place of residence (near a fluorochemical industrial facility, near civilian airports, military bases, wastewater treatment facilities, or firefighting training facilities, near agricultural areas characterised by the use of soil conditioners), years of residence, consumption of tap water, use/consumption of groundwater or surface water, locally produced food, own grown vegetables, own raised livestock, fish and seafood from a local body of water.</p> <p>Primary focus of HBM4EU is exploring the background exposure of the general population and no specific studies in known hotspot areas were performed. HBM4EU study materials can however be used in national studies performed to investigate certain contamination cases, and several partners in HBM4EU are involved in studies investigating exposure in contaminated regions; the results of</p>	<p>PFASs accumulate in the environment and have been found to contaminate surface-, ground- and drinking water and accumulate in plants. PFASs production sites, fire training areas, airports and waste disposal facilities as well as sewage treatment plants can lead to contamination of the environment, which in turn leads to exposure of people living in these areas. Currently, there are several hotspots known in different countries (e.g., Germany, Sweden, Italy, Spain, The Netherlands, Belgium, Denmark and Austria). It can be assumed that hot spots exist in most European countries.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies indicate a geographical difference in PFASs exposure, with higher concentrations in Northern and Western Europe for the</p>	<p>European HBM dashboard: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 5.1 A (phased) plan for action: how structured multi-actor dialogues on human biomonitoring results can facilitate targeted policy action (generic canvas for HBM4EU)</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 5.5 Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV – first visualisation examples</p> <p>Additional Deliverable under WP5.5: Guidance on HBM in PFAS Hotspots</p>

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	<p>these studies will be used to answer the respective HBM4EU policy questions.</p> <p>A working group has been formed in HBM4EU which is currently developing a guidance document on how to deal with Human Biomonitoring, health risk assessment and risk communication in (PFASs) hot spots. The guidance will be published as Additional Deliverable under WP5.</p>	<p>legacy PFAS compounds (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS). Between 1 24 % of the subjects across the 9 data collections have exposure levels above the HBM guidance value deducted from the EFSA opinion 2020 for sum (PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS) of 6.9 µg/L, of which 17 24 % for Northern and Western Europe and 1 13 % in Southern and Eastern Europe.</p>	
<p>6. How can this feed into an assessment of the TDI for PFOS and PFOA set by EFSA?</p>	<p>Suitable PFAS studies for the examination of exposure-health relationships were identified within WP13.3, including studies in pregnant women, children and adolescents, adults and the elderly. Additionally, individual data from several birth cohorts were examined for associations of PFAS exposure and low birth weight, and birth weight as continuous outcome. Also, associations between PFAS and thyroid function in mothers and their newborn have been investigated.</p> <p>WP10/WP14 are currently studying associations between PFASs exposure, epigenetic and clinical biomarkers of effect, and asthma, allergy, metabolic disorders and sexual maturation in teenagers.</p> <p>Results of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies feed into the policy processes identified, including the broad restriction of PFAS under REACH but also the chemical strategy for sustainability (toxic free environment).</p> <p>HBM studies are very useful to inform policy makers and citizens, and can be a vehicle for (pro)active communication on environmental health risks. An additional deliverable has been prepared</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on the first HBM4EU research results on PFAS (April 2021) had the goal to discuss the results with selected scientists, risk assessors and risk managers to define main messages for policy making. It is clearly supported that there is an (additional) need for policy action, and the importance of dialogue between experts, risk managers and assessors was demonstrated. Concrete opportunities for the use of HBM4EU results include: Most recent and quality controlled HBM data are important to support the PFAS group restriction and to demonstrate that there is a need for action. • Results on e.g. health effects, MOA, mixture risk assessment can support the qualitative risk assessment. • HBM results can support the discussion started in the EU related to set maximum levels in food. 	<p>European HBM dashboard: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 5.1 A (phased) plan for action: how structured multi-actor dialogues on human biomonitoring results can facilitate targeted policy action (generic canvas for HBM4EU)</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 5.5 Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV – first visualisation examples Additional Deliverable under WP5.5: Guidance on HBM in PFAS Hotspots.</p> <p>D5.7. Workshop Report on the first HBM4EU research results on PFAS (from April 2021).</p> <p>Deliverable 5.8 Human Biomonitoring in risk assessment: 3rd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals.</p> <p>Deliverable 5.11: Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority</p>

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	<p>within WP5 (Translation of results into policy: ‘Timelines of Opportunity’,) in which a strategy has been proposed to systematically map both the ‘policy timeline(s)’ and ‘HBM4EU timeline(s)’, in order to identify potential windows of opportunity for policy uptake. The strategy takes into account different types of HBM4EU output as well as different types of policy processes that might benefit from HBM data. Furthermore, HBM4EU has contributed to the public consultation of the recent EFSA opinion on PFAS, 2020 by submitting feedback and comments. Experts of the CONTAM panel presented and discussed the essential parts of the opinion with the HBM4EU PFAS community per webex on April, 7.</p> <p>Two science to policy workshops have been organised with members of the EU-Commission, ECHA and EFSA. HBM studies have contributed to putting PFAS high on the political agenda and HBM4EU results can further support ongoing EU processes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At national level HBM4EU results can raise awareness among the public and among the policy makers, also since many important competences to reduce exposure are still situated at the national/local level. A follow up workshop has been organised in March 2022; the results will feed into regulatory processes, such as the broad restriction which is planned under REACH. <p>From the examinations of the birth cohorts several associations have been reported: (i) increased propensity for infections in the children up to age 4 and the frequency of antibiotics use until adolescent age, (ii) poorer cardiovascular risk profile based on higher cholesterol and lipid profile, higher fasting blood glucose, BMI and blood pressure (iii) higher body weight, BMI-score and waist circumference at age 9, among boys. Further, PFAS mixture was associated with an increase in triglyceride and insulin levels and decrease in HDL cholesterol. And a modest interaction with endogenous hormones has been found. Prenatal PFASs exposure was also associated with reproductive disorders.</p> <p>HBM4EU Aligned Studies results can become an important baseline to follow up effectiveness of policy measures.</p>	<p>chemicals</p> <p>Deliverable 5.9 3rd substance specific derivation of EU-wide health-based guidance values: Substance Dossier on PFHxS.</p> <p>D6.4: Report to provide a revision on the on the national needs (T6.1), the funding mechanisms (T6.2) and the long-term sustainability of HBM4EU (T6.3).</p> <p>Deliverable 6.6 HBM in Europe: legacy of HBM4EU and frameworks for medium- and long-term sustainability: informs also on activities/actions on PFAS on EU level.</p> <p>HBM4EU Contribution to the Public Consultation on the draft scientific opinion of the EFSA CONTAM Panel on the Risk to human health related to the presence of PFASs in food, April, 17 2020.</p>

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		<p>HBM based indicators are being developed within HBM4EU to track progress and can be included in state-of-the-environment reporting at EU- and national level. Continued investment in monitoring, ideally with a time interval of 2 to 3 years between data points, would be needed for this purpose.</p>	
<p>7. What is the impact of a pending 2016 ECHA decision to restrict the manufacturing, marketing and use of PFOA under REACH?</p>	<p>As described in the answer to the policy question 1 various activities and efforts have been made to assess the exposure of the European population to various PFAS. HBM4EU existing and new HBM data collections and work on indicators (Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV) have been performed in order to assess the exposure of the European population to PFAS.</p> <p>Human biomonitoring data are available in many countries but are heterogeneous with respect to age groups and substances measured. The reported median-values and 95th percentiles of the individual existing studies on PFAS were averaged (by taking the median) over the different studies of newborns, children & teenagers combined, and adults. These levels support the concentration levels reported in the EFSA opinion. Data on PFAS exposure were summarised in the Deliverable D10.4 and D10.6. Metadata and aggregated data from HBM studies having measured PFAS were integrated in IPCHEM. The European HBM dashboard visualises the aggregated HBM data; accessible via the HBM4EU website.</p>	<p>The data collections in HBM4EU indicate the decrease of PFOA within the observed period. This is particularly clear in the case of time series measurements, such as those carried out within the framework of the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB). Comparing the plasma samples of young adults from ESB in the period from 2007 to 2019 shows a decrease by half. However, although in some individual EU countries, decreasing time trends of PFOA have been described, the HBM4EU aligned studies still show that PFOS and PFOA are still the substances occurring in the highest concentrations in blood in Europe and a fraction of the teenagers in Europe exceed guidance values for PFOA. Other PFASs compounds have also been detected in many human samples. Alternative PFASs compounds have lower exposure levels compared to regulated PFAS compounds. However, due to a large</p>	<p>Deliverable 10.4 1st annual list of exposure distributions and/or European reference values</p> <p>Deliverable 10.6 Second annual list of exposure distributions and/or European Reference Values</p>

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		<p>proportion of non-detects for alternative PFASs and a big difference in absolute values of LOQs reached across studies there is a need for lowering the LOQ. It is of utmost importance to avoid regrettable substitutions.</p>	
<p>8. Is it important to eliminate legacy PFASs from material cycles (i.e. waste electronic equipment) when implementing a circular economy in order to protect human health?</p>	<p>This policy questions goes beyond the research focus of HBM4EU.</p> <p>However, due to the long half-life in humans, the exceedances of tolerable weekly intakes and internal benchmark dose levels of substances which are already restricted such as PFOS and PFOA it seems indicated to eliminate PFAS from material cycles when implementing a circular economy in order to protect human health.</p>		
<p>9. Can differences in PFASs profiles be observed in different population groups and time periods?</p>	<p>Efforts to assess PFASs exposure within HBM4EU are described above. Different research protocols have been developed to further analyse the PFASs data, including European exposure levels, exposure distributions, geographical comparisons, exposure determinants, exposure-effect associations. More results are expected to be published in the course of 2022.</p> <p>To study differences in PFASs profiles in different time periods, analysis of time trend studies is needed, which are currently not available at European level. The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data will form baseline European exposure levels for PFASs in teenagers, allowing follow up studies to</p>	<p>The individual existing data collections prepared and made available within HBM4EU contain aggregated data stratified by age, sex and educational level. From these stratifications it can be seen that the PFAS concentrations are in general higher in men compared to women for the teenager and adult studies. Also, there seems a trend that participants with higher educational level have higher exposure levels compared with low to medium educational level. This trend was however less obvious and could not be observed in all studies and for all</p>	<p>Source data: merged harmonised aggregated data obtained from Deliverable D10.6 (2nd annual list of exposure distributions and/or European reference values)</p> <p>D10.10 Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8</p> <p>Fábelová L. et al. in preparation: PFASs levels and exposure determinants in vulnerable population groups</p>

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	<p>monitor increased or decreased usage.</p> <p>Expanding the analytical range of PFAS compounds (including total extractable fluorine content to determine the amount of currently unidentified PFAS) was not possible under HBM4EU. This should be taken up in follow up initiatives such as the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC).</p>	<p>compounds. In some studies, higher levels of PFASs were observed with increasing age, indicating possible cumulative exposure over time. This was however not observed for all studies and for all compounds.</p> <p>Regarding exposure determinants in the HBM4EU data collections, besides cohort, sex and education, diet was an important determinant of PFASs. Higher serum levels of PFNA and PFOS were associated with higher consumption of fish and seafood (increase in serum levels by 20 and 21 %, respectively) and higher consumption of eggs (increase in serum levels by 14 and 11 %, respectively). Additionally, higher exposure to PFOS was linked to higher consumption of offal (increase in exposure by 14 %) and consumption of local food (increase in exposure by 40 %). For other food items (meat, fast food, drinking water, milk), no or weak associations with individual PFASs were found.</p> <p>Geographical differences in internal exposure can be observed in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies for PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and their sum. Highest median values are observed in studies conducted in Northern and Western Europe.</p>	

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		<p>So far, time trend data are available for the sum $\Sigma(\text{PFOA} + \text{PFNA} + \text{PFHxS} + \text{PFOS})$ only for Germany. When comparing the PFASs levels in plasma samples of young adults from the German Environmental Specimen Bank in the period from 2007 to 2019, a clear decrease can be seen. While the maximum P95 (P50) value for the sum of the 4 PFASs was 28.87 (13,82) $\mu\text{g/L}$ in 2007, in 2019 it is only 8.28 (4,59) $\mu\text{g/L}$. Data from two mother-child studies in Vienna/Austria also showed a decline in the P50 values for the sum of the 4 PFASs from 4.3 $\mu\text{g/l}$ in 2010 to 2.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ in 2019.</p>	
<p>10. What are the PFASs levels and health effects in vulnerable population groups?</p>	<p>The recent draft scientific opinion (EFSA 2020) points out that toddlers and other children had approximately two-fold higher mean intake than older age groups (adolescents, adults, elderly, very elderly). The CONTAM Panel concluded further, that parts of the European population exceed the tolerable weekly intake (TWI), which is of concern. Therefore, it can be assumed that toddlers and children are a vulnerable population group and are exposed to PFAS levels, which are cause of concern.</p> <p>As described above, PFAS exposure has been examined in European teenagers in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. Within WP 14.2, biomarkers of effect according to their utility in human studies were selected. Nuclear receptor activation, kisspeptin, thyroid and sex hormones and gonadotropins, glucose markers, serum lipids,</p>	<p>AD5.5. HBM-based indicators were developed and compared with HBM-GV_{GenPop} for several substances including PFAS, considering data of the sum of 4 PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS).</p> <p>As described in the answer to the above Policy Questions PFAS levels in European teenagers exceed health based guidance values, this has been visualised by the various indicators.</p> <p>Based on the review in D11.4 the following associations between health outcomes and PFAS exposure were identified: cardiovascular diseases (CVD overall, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, stroke), Metabolic</p>	<p>Additional Deliverable 5.5 Generating indicators incorporating HBM-GV – first visualisation examples</p> <p>Deliverable 11.4 Second update on the report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies and administrative registers and guidelines.</p> <p>Deliverable 13.4: Report on AOPs of priority substances.</p> <p>Deliverable 13.5: Identified gaps for the establishment of AOPs and required studies</p> <p>Deliverable 13.6: Final report on AOPs</p> <p>Deliverable 13.7: Final report on exposure-response associations based on pre-existing cohort data</p>

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	<p>adipokines, and oxidative stress are currently being measured in part of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and associations with PFASs exposure and asthma, allergy, BMI, waist circumference, body fat mass, glucose intolerance, diabetes, hypertension, pubertal development, and sexual maturation (as far as data are available) are studied.</p> <p>Within WP 13.1 reviews were conducted to investigate main adverse effects of PFAS. The association between exposure to PFAS and cholesterol/lipid metabolism and inflammatory responses with links to cardiovascular disease has been investigated and published in Critical Reviews in Toxicology (Fragki et al., 2020). In addition, associations between PFAS exposures and hypertension, overweight/obesity and insulin resistance have been investigated using the AOP helper (Kaiser et al. in preparation). Epidemiological studies published between 2007 and 2021 were reviewed for adverse birth outcomes associated with prenatal exposure to PFAS (Gundacker et al. in preparation). In addition, the key characteristics of PFAS-induced immunomodulation and immunotoxicity were summarised and discussed (Ehrlich et al. in preparation).</p> <p>In WP 13.1. Knowledge base on causal pathways from chemical exposure to health outcomes (Adverse outcome pathways) work on characterisation of the key events in the AOPs for disruption of cholesterol/lipid metabolism and inflammatory responses with links to cardiovascular disease; collection of information on potential mechanisms beyond PFAS-induced effects on birth weight and immune toxicity is ongoing. PFASs</p>	<p>syndrome (metabolic syndrome overall, obesity, glucose metabolism, diabetes, lipid metabolism), reproductive health (AGD, semen quality, reproductive hormones, fertility & fecundity), fetal development, kidney function, liver function, osteoporosis, hematological system (hemoglobin levels), asthma, COPD, skin irritation and inflammation, ADHD, kidney/liver/pancreatic cancer.</p> <p>In a collaboration between WP11 and WP14, an overview of the effects of endocrine disruptors, including PFAS on metabolic syndrome, was published. Some evidence of the association of PFAS, including substitutes of legacy PFAS with obesity, diabetes, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease has been observed.</p> <p>The association between pregnancy exposure to PFAS and later offspring immune function has been investigated in epidemiological data from cohort studies performed within the HBM4EU consortium. The results provided clear indications that higher maternal exposures to PFAS during pregnancy is associated with increased propensity for infections in the children up to age 4 and the frequency of antibiotics use until adolescent age. Inverse associations of maternal PFAS exposure with offspring growth trajectories and sleeping habits have</p>	<p>for the 1st and 2nd list of priority substances</p> <p>Deliverable 14.8 First report on the implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers for the 1st set of prioritised substances in the aligned studies</p> <p>Boesen SAH, Long M, Wielsøe M, Mustieles V, Fernandez MF, Bonefeld-Jørgensen EC. Exposure to Perfluoroalkyl acids and foetal and maternal thyroid status: a review. Environ Health. 2020;19(1):107. doi: 10.1186/s12940-020-00647-1.</p> <p>Styliani Fragki, Hubert Dirven, Tony Fletcher, Bettina Grasl-Kraupp, Kristine Bjerve Gützkow, Ron Hoogenboom, Sander Kersten, Birgitte Lindeman, Jochem Lousse, Ad Peijnenburg, Aldert H. Piersma, Hans M. G. Princen, Maria Uhl, Joost Westerhout, Marco J. Zeilmaker & Mirjam Luijten (2021) Systemic PFOS and PFOA exposure and disturbed lipid homeostasis in humans: what do we know and what not? Critical Reviews in Toxicology, 51:2, 141-164, DOI: 10.1080/10408444.2021.1888073</p> <p>Claudia Gundacker, Karine Audouze, Raimund Widhalm, Sebastian Granitzer, Martin Forsthuber Florence Jornod, Maria Wielsøe, Manhai Long, Þórhallur Ingi Halldórsson, Uhl Maria, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen: Low birth weight and exposure to per- and polyfluorinated substances (PFAS): A review of possible underlying mechanisms using the AOP-HelpFinder: in preparation</p>

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	<p>affect multiple aspects of the immune system, this is described in detail in the review from Ehrlich et al. In D 13.4 report on AOPs of priority substances first results addressing these endpoints were compiled. In D13.5. gaps for the establishment of AOPs were identified, and the need for required studies described.</p> <p>Suitable studies for the examination of exposure-health relationships of PFAS were identified within WP13.2. Health effects in humans based on birth and adult cohorts (D13.3) including studies in pregnant women, children and adolescents, adults and the elderly. Additionally, individual data from several birth cohorts were examined regarding associations of PFAS exposure and low birth weight, and birth weight as continuous outcome. A similar investigation has been conducted for the assessment of associations between PFAS and thyroid function in mothers and their newborn.</p> <p>The additional deliverable AD13.3, provides a concise summary on current progress, achievements as well as future plans in Task 13.2 cohorts within HBM4EU time frame, and also beyond.</p> <p>Within the Deliverable D11.4 (combination of health examination surveys with HBM: review on potential health effects) opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies have been summarised. Further, an extended review of the potential health effects of the HBM4EU priority substances have been performed.</p>	<p>been observed in mother –child cohorts. Also, associations of PFAS with poorer cardiovascular risk profile including higher total cholesterol and lipid profile, higher fasting blood glucose, BMI and blood pressure has been observed. In another cohort prenatal exposure to PFAS was associated with higher weight, BMIz-score and waist circumference at age 9, among boys. PFAS mixture was associated with an increase in triglyceride and insulin levels and decrease in HDL cholesterol. Further, three studies provide some evidence suggesting that exposure to PFAS as observed in background exposed may modestly interact with endogenous hormones. Prenatal PFASs exposure could be associated with reproductive disorders such as preeclampsia and pregnancy hypertension, delay of menarche and abnormal menstruation/length, reduction of birth weight, length, and change in gestational length, decreases in semen quality and sperm count. One study showed correlations with the anogenital distance in girls and a risk of cerebral palsy in boys. The preliminary findings on in utero exposures and offspring cognitive development highlight that more work is needed in sufficiently powered studies using robust</p>	<p>Andreas-Marius Kaiser, Maryam Zare Jeddi, Maria Uhl, Florence Jornod, Marieta Fernandez, Karine Audouze: Characterization of potential modes of action of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances related to metabolic outcomes using artificial intelligence: in preparation</p> <p>Veronika Ehrlich, Andreas-Marius Kaiser, Ingrid Hauenberger, Christina Hartmann, Rob Vandebriel, Wieneke Bil, Maryam Zare Jeddi, Mirjam Luijten, Birgitte Lindeman, Berit Granum, Philippe Grandjean, Maria Uhl A review is currently being prepared to investigate the adverse effects of PFAS on the immune system: “Mechanisms of modulation of immune health by per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances” in preparation.</p> <p>Haverinen E, Fernandez MF, Mustieles V, Tolonen H. Metabolic Syndrome and Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals: An Overview of Exposure and Health Effects. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. 2021; 18(24):13047.</p>

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		<p>outcomes assessment.</p> <p>Data on health impacts of different PFASs are available for a comparatively small number of PFASs, of which especially PFOS and PFOA are well researched. There is a need for human-relevant hazard and HBM data, and there are also gaps for the majority of the 4,000 PFAS currently used related to uses, exposure patterns and toxicity.</p>	
<p>11. How can mixture effects of environmental and human PFASs mixtures present to date be estimated?</p>	<p>As described above (Policy Question 10) suitable PFAS studies for the examination of exposure-health relationships were identified within WP13.2 (D13.3.) including studies in pregnant women, children and adolescents, adults and the elderly. Additionally, individual data from several birth cohorts have been merged for the examination of associations of PFAS exposure and low birth weight, and birth weight as continuous outcome. A similar investigation has been conducted for the assessment of associations between PFAS and thyroid function in mothers and their newborn. For more detailed information see also Policy Questions No. 1 and No. 10.</p> <p>Within WP 14 effect biomarkers for PFAS were successfully established.</p> <p>A methodology was developed to extract and fractionate the real mixture of PFAS from human serum samples. Placental extracts (alpha fractions), containing mixtures of persistent and lipophilic chemicals, showed significant anti-androgenic</p>	<p>Various approaches were available and further developed to estimate the risk resulting from exposure to mixtures of PFASs. In that respect, our aim was to refine the mixture risk assessment of PFASs taking three approaches for comparison, the Relative Potency Factor (RPF) approach, the Hazard Index (HI) approach, and the sum value approach of the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA). The latter approach uses the EFSA tolerable weekly intake (TWI) value for the sum of PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, and PFOS. The HI and RPF approach were adapted specifically with the purpose of being able to use human biomonitoring data as primary input to the risk assessment. All approaches indicate that PFAS exposure may cause adverse health effects in certain segments of the European population,</p>	<p>Deliverable 5.11: Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p> <p>Deliverable 13.7: Final report on exposure-response associations based on pre-existing cohort data for the 1st and 2nd list of priority substances</p> <p>Deliverable 14.5 Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 14.6 Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation</p> <p>Boesen SAH, Long M, Wielsøe M, Mustieles V, Fernandez MF, Bonefeld-Jørgensen EC. Exposure to Perfluoroalkyl acids and foetal and maternal thyroid status: a review. Environ</p>

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	<p>activity. The hormonal profile from placental tissue was quantified, as well as some epigenetic markers such as Histone H2AX phosphorylation (Gamma-H2AX), trimethylation of histone 3 at lysine (H3K4me) and DNA methylation of BDNF, in addition to untargeted metabolomic analysis. Finally, 8OHdG levels were assessed in urine samples coupled to the placentas from the same women. This work has shown that chemical mixtures isolated from human samples can be assessed, and its biological activity quantified using different biomarkers cell based tools. Placenta tissue could be used as a relevant biological matrix to assess both exposure and effect biomarkers. The placenta can also be used to explore the implementation of novel effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring programs, due to the volume and availability of this biological sample.</p> <p>In addition, there were activities related to the assessment of the biological effects of PFAS mixtures using in vitro biomarkers of combined activity, related to the generation of new knowledge on AOPs by in vitro research for the mechanism for PFAS on liver-cholesterol and lipid metabolism and intracellular levels of PFAS, and related to the identification of exposure-health associations from a cohort study (human milk biobanking).</p> <p>AD 14.6: The pilot study with INMA-Granada samples has demonstrated the technical feasibility to implement novel biomarkers of brain function such as BDNF, at different levels of biological organisation, in HBM4EU aligned studies. Moreover, the use of cell-based bioassays may help to better understand how specific chemical</p>	<p>thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion (2020) on PFASs in food, supporting the need for risk management measures and thereby the need for an EU-wide restriction on PFAS.</p> <p>The mixture risk assessments illustrate that HBM provides a highly valuable contribution to the assessment of the cumulative risk resulting from exposure to PFASs. It is inherent to HBM to reflect the aggregated exposure from different exposure routes and exposure sources and therefore reflects exposure from all potential sources.</p> <p>It should be mentioned that this current work is a scientific exploration of how to use HBM in risk assessment. This exercise presents several approaches to perform mixture risk assessment for PFASs that are based on pragmatism, and each approach has its strengths, assumptions, uncertainties and flaws. Further refining and extending quantitative mixture risk assessment for 'forever chemicals' is recommended and possible. To support the science-based grouping of PFASs, a better understanding of the modes of action of different PFASs is needed. Further studying relative potencies of PFAS for other effects, sex, life-stages, and species, and in particular for critical</p>	<p>Health. 2020;19(1):107. doi: 10.1186/s12940-020-00647-1.</p> <p>Maryam Zare Jeddi, Nancy B. Hopf, Susana Viegas, Anna Bal Price, Alicia Paini, Christoph van Thriel, Emilio Benfenati, Sophie Ndaw, Jos Bessems, Peter A. Behnisch, Gabriele Leng, Radu-Corneliu Duca, Hans Verhagen, Francesco Cubadda, Lorraine Brennan, Imran Ali, Arthur David, Vicente Mustieles, Mariana F. Fernandez, Henriqueta Louro, Robert Pasanen-Kase, Towards a systematic use of effect biomarkers in population and occupational biomonitoring, Environment International, 146, 2021, 106257, ISSN 0160-4120, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106257.</p> <p>F. Vela-Soria, J. García-Villanova, V. Mustieles, T. de Haro, J.P. Antignac, M.F. Fernandez, Assessment of perfluoroalkyl substances in placenta by coupling salt assisted liquid-liquid extraction with dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction prior to liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, Talanta, Volume 221, 2021, 121577, ISSN 0039-9140, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.121577.</p> <p>Vinggaard AM, Bonefeld-Jørgensen EC, Jensen TK, Fernandez MF, Rosenmai AK, Taxvig C, Rodriguez-Carrillo A, Wielsøe M, Long M, Olea N, Antignac JP, Hamers T, Lamoree M. Receptor-based in vitro activities to assess human exposure to chemical mixtures</p>

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	<p>mixtures contained in human samples may exert combined hormonal activities. Finally, the development of chemical's mixture isolation, such as PFAS, opens the possibility of assessing specific chemical families isolated from human samples, with potential implications for risk assessment and policy making.</p> <p>Within WP 5.3, three different mixture risk assessment strategies were compared that all used HBM data as primary input (D5.8). This preliminary mixture assessment, has been updated in D5.11 with the data from the aligned studies in teenagers. The first approach is the EFSA sum value approach, based on the recently derived EFSA TWI. The internal guidance value of 6.9 ng/mL will be compared to the sum of exposure to the 'EFSA-4' (PFOA, PFNA, PFOS, PFHxS). Additionally, two other approaches are introduced, that both are able to incorporate more than 4 PFAS in the risk assessment as cumulative exposure. These are the hazard index approach and the relative potency factor approach. All three approaches illustrate a cumulative risk in certain parts of the participating study cohorts and thereby confirm EFSA's earlier conclusions (EFSA 2020). Moreover, these exemplary mixture risk assessments show various possibilities by which HBM data may inform policy.</p>	<p>effects such as immune effects would be of added value. We also recommend considering mixture exposure at the individual level rather than using summary statistics for the summation of exposure to multiple compounds. Furthermore, it is preferable to include exposure and effect data in the risk assessment at the individual level.</p> <p>Positive associations with PFASs exposure and ASD/ADHD and behaviour in children were identified in several studies, however, data is inconsistent. Data on negative effects on developmental milestones are also inconsistent. In several case-studies associations with e.g. breast cancer, prostate cancer and colorectal cancer were found, but more prospective studies are needed. Related to endocrine disorders, lower testosterone and oestradiol levels as well as thyroid hormone disruptive potential were identified. There are also indications of immunosuppressive effects in several studies, as well as positive associations with asthma and allergy. Further, prenatal PFAS exposure is associated with higher fat percentage in children leading to an increased risk of overweight/obesity, and there are associations to glucose homeostasis, dyslipidemia, high cholesterol,</p>	<p>and related health impacts. <i>Environ Int.</i> 2021 Jan;146:106191. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106191. Epub 2020 Oct 14. PMID: 33068852.</p> <p>Moore, S.; Paalanen, L.; Melymuk, L.; Katsonouri, A.; Kolossa-Gehring, M.; Tolonen, H. The Association between ADHD and Environmental Chemicals—A Scoping Review. <i>Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health</i> 2022, 19, 2849. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052849</p> <p>Mattila T, Santonen T, Andersen HR, Katsonouri A, Szigeti T, Uhl M, Wąsowicz W, Lange R, Bocca B, Ruggieri F, Kolossa-Gehring M, Sarigiannis DA, Tolonen H. Scoping Review—The Association between Asthma and Environmental Chemicals. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.</i> 2021; 18(3):1323. https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031323 w—The Association between Asthma and Environmental Chemicals</p> <p>Ottenbros I, Govarts E, Lebret E, Vermeulen R, Schoeters G, Vlaanderen J. Network Analysis to Identify Communities Among Multiple Exposure Biomarkers Measured at Birth in Three Flemish General Population Samples. <i>Front Public Health.</i> 2021 Feb 10;9:590038. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.590038 . PMID: 33643986 ; PMID: PMC7902692.</p>

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		<p>metabolic syndrome and risk of diabetes. Related to reproductive disorders, positive associations with preeclampsia and pregnancy hypertension were identified. Further, prenatal PFAS exposure may result in a delay of menarche and may cause abnormal menstruation/length. Prenatal exposure can also reduce birth weight, length, APGAR score and change gestational length. Decreases in semen quality and sperm count were also found. Additionally, in one study correlations with anogenital distance in girls and a risk of cerebral palsy in boys have been shown.</p> <p>Based on the inventory of available effect biomarkers in WP 14 associations of PFAS exposure with certain health outcomes were identified. Positive associations with ASD/ADHD and behaviour in children were identified in several studies, however, data is inconsistent. Data on negative effects on developmental milestones are also inconsistent. In several case-studies associations with e.g. breast cancer, prostate cancer and colorectal cancer were found, but more prospective studies are needed. Related to endocrine disorders, lower testosterone and oestradiol levels as well as thyroid hormone disruptive potential were identified. There are also</p>	

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		<p>indications of immunosuppressive effects in several studies, as well as positive associations with asthma and allergy</p> <p>AD14.5: In 702 Danish females it was demonstrated that PFAS induced xenoestrogenic transactivity is significantly inverse related to birth weight, length and head circumference. Further, combined mixture of PFAS from placenta homogenate sample provided by the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort was isolated and xenoestrogenic transactivity was measured. Similar as for the serum samples, 52% of the placenta extracts significantly induced xenoestrogenic transactivity, and 68% further enhanced the transactivity of the natural E2 receptor ligand. In addition, a literature review on PFAS exposure and thyroid homeostatis in epidemiological studies was conducted.</p> <p>Maternal thyroid hormones are essential for fetal brain development and PFAA are suggested to interfere with these hormones in 2nd or 3rd trimesters. In addition, PFAS exposure may cause hypothyroid homeostasis.</p> <p>In the Scoping Review of Moore et al, 2022 the association between attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), a</p>	

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		<p>chronic neurodevelopment disorder and exposure to PFAS has been investigated.. The evidence for an association is small, but warrants further research.</p> <p>The association between HBM4EU priority substances and asthma has been investigated in a scoping review from Mattila et al., 2021. The evidence for PFAS was inconclusive.</p> <p>Ottenbros et al. described the use of network technics for graphical presentation of human biomonitoring data of mixtures (multiple exposure biomarkers) which facilitates the detection of exposure patterns and allows for the systematic comparison of observed exposure patterns between datasets and strata within datasets.</p> <p>52% of the F3-W2 placenta extracts (containing PFAS mixtures) tested showed a significantly induced xeno-estrogenic transactivity and 68% of the placenta extracts further enhanced the activity of the natural ligand E2. In future studies, the presence of individual PFAS in the placenta homogenates extract could be determined.</p>	
<p>12. How can PFAS substances of relevance for</p>	<p>For the majority of the 4,000 currently used PFAS considerable data gaps exist related to current uses, exposure patterns and toxicity. Besides regulatory action which is called for by member</p>	<p>PFAS are included in the 3rd list of prioritised substances as outcome of the 3rd prioritisation progress with the aim to produce a shortlist of priority</p>	<p>Deliverable 4.8 Third list of HBM4EU priority substances</p> <p>Deliverable 4.10 2nd Report on stakeholder</p>

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<p>human exposure and health be identified having in mind that more than 3000 substances are at the market?</p>	<p>states and the European Commission also research is needed. HBM4EU PFAS experts have submitted a statement to the public consultation on the draft scientific opinion on the risks to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food, which states among others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a need for Human Biomonitoring data for PFAS other than those addressed in the risk assessment (specifically those which are used/formed in high volumes as a result of substituting legacy PFAS). • There is a need to measure the total organofluorine content in humans in order to assess the magnitude of the so far unknown or not yet assessable contribution of PFAS in humans. Further, non-target analytical methods could be used to identify new relevant substances. • More longitudinal epidemiological PFAS studies are needed. Research on immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption and birth outcomes is required. Research on other toxicological endpoints is also needed including effects on the lungs/respiratory system from prenatal exposure, and cancers such as breast cancer in adults. • Research on adverse outcome pathways is needed. • To support the science-based grouping of PFAS, a better understanding of the modes of action of different PFASs is needed. • Further studying relative potencies of PFAS for mixture risk assessment would be of added value. 	<p>substances intended to feed in to PARC. It is recommended to study (mixtures of) legacy and substitution PFASs as well as groups of PFASs and total organofluorine content in humans in combination with information on exposure sources and routes and with (early) biomarkers of effect and with follow up of health outcomes in longitudinal studies. We stress the need for improving the analytical methods and standards for biomonitoring and for bringing down the LOD and LOQ. We also recommend performing studies that observe paired blood-urine samples to have a better insight into exposure to short-chain PFASs.</p>	<p>consultation and mapping of needs</p> <p>Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances</p> <p>These activities and publications have not been part of HBM4EU, but they were published by the CGL inspired by the HBM4EU framework:</p> <p>Kaiser, A.-M., Aro, R., Kärrman, A., Weiss, St., Hartmann, Ch., Uhl, M., Forsthuber, M., Gundacker, C., Yeung, L.W.Y., 2021. Comparison of extraction methods for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in human serum and placenta samples - insights into extractable organic fluorine (EOF). <i>Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry</i> 413, 865-876. https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-020-03041-5</p> <p>Kaiser, A.-M., Forsthuber, M., Aro, R., Kärrman, A., Gundacker, C., Zeisler, H., Foessleitner, P., Salzer, H., Hartmann, Ch., Uhl, M., Yeung, L.W.Y., 2021. Extractable organofluorine analysis in pooled human serum and placental tissue samples from an Austrian subpopulation – a mass balance analysis approach. <i>Environmental Science and Technology</i> 55(13), 9033-9042. https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c00883</p>
<p>13. How can identification and</p>	<p>This policy question goes beyond the scope of</p>		

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<p>assessment (including data on (potential) adverse effects on human health and the environment) of alternatives currently hampered by CBI (Confidential Business Information) be facilitated?</p>	<p>HBM4EU.</p>		
<p>14. How much are HBM values dependent on host characteristics and does this have implications for identifying vulnerable groups?</p>	<p>A new PBPK model for PFOA and PFOS was developed based on a previously reported model within WP 12. (D12.1). For validation purposes, data on PFOA and PFOS in human tissues from people living in the area of study (Tarragona County) were used.</p> <p>In AD12.3 exposure estimates were derived based on a consumption study and they were used as input for the PBPK model to estimate the concentration of 11 PFAS in human tissues. PKs were estimated by using data on PFAS concentrations in plasma and autopsy tissue samples.</p> <p>For model parameterisation, data on PFAS concentrations in blood and human tissues from three studies were used.</p> <p>In general, the assessment of the models showed</p>	<p>The individual data collections prepared and made available within HBM4EU contained aggregated data stratified by age, sex and educational level. From these stratifications it can be seen that the PFAS concentrations are in general higher in men compared to women for the teenager and adult studies.</p> <p>Also, there seems a trend that participants with higher educational level have higher exposure levels compared with low to medium educational level. This trend was however less obvious and could not be observed in all studies and for all compounds. In some studies, higher levels of PFASs were observed with</p>	<p>Source data: merged harmonised aggregated data obtained from Deliverable D10.6 (2nd annual list of exposure</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 12.3 Exposure model testing results</p> <p>Deliverable 12.4 Report on estimation of relevant tissue and biological fluid doses of 1st set of priority compounds in the EU population using refined PBTK modelling</p> <p>Deliverable 12.5: Risk characterisation of the 1st set of prioritised substances using external exposure estimated from HBM data: a methodological approach</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised</p>

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	<p>that there is a lack in data supporting integrated exposure, and another significant problem is the data quality. Further, there is a need for the detailed description of exposure mechanisms that are not straightforward such as inhalation or food ingestion.</p> <p>AD12.5: The PBPK model was used for exposure reconstruction. Data used was from the Tarragona cohort study, and only PFOS and PFOA were considered. Exposure estimates: Daily intakes were estimated with a constant oral exposure scenario.</p> <p>Ongoing work in WP12 concerns a dynamic age and gender specific PBPK model, and paediatrics case study.</p> <p>Excretion values are depending on several factors e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) genetic factors (for example SNPs in transporter protein genes), b) sex - females of reproductive age excrete more due to menstruation and reproduction - c) kidney health, gut health, gut microbiome - changes in excretion or reabsorption by either route leads to changes in serum levels, and so induces an association (+ve or -ve) between HBM and various health conditions correlated with renal or gut health. Reduced eGFR/kidney function is associated with reduced excretion higher serum PFAS <p>Knowledge of which factors lead to increased vulnerability is still incomplete. There is still a need for research in this area.</p>	<p>increasing age, indicating possible cumulative exposure over time. This was however not observed for all studies and for all compounds.</p> <p>AD12.3: A new PBPK model for PFOA and PFOS was developed based on a previously reported model within WP 12. (D12.1).</p> <p>Several discussion points have been identified, e.g. highlighting the importance to obtain partitioning data from humans and of PFAS levels in human tissues in order to refine the model.</p> <p>The exposure reconstruction via PBPK modelling offers unique opportunities related to HBM data interpretation. For these reconstructions a minimum information related to toxicokinetic behaviour of a substance (and its metabolites) is required, which allows a translation of measured biomarker levels at a given time-point with long-term daily intake patterns.</p> <p>Dynamic age and gender specific PBPK models and the paediatrics case will allow to contributing to the identification of vulnerable groups.</p>	<p>substances based on HBM data</p>

19 Pesticides

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<p>1. Which are the most suitable methods and biomarkers of exposure?</p>	<p>In WP9 a prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices, and analytical methods has been elaborated (D9.5). The list presents 9 suitable biomarkers for the category B pesticides (chlorpyrifos, glyphosate and pyrethroids) and 4 biomarkers for the category C pesticides (dimethoate and fipronil). Urine is the selected matrix for all the compounds except fipronil for which serum is the preferred matrix.</p> <p>Chlorpyrifos is metabolised to TCPy (3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol) and two unspecific diethyl phosphate biomarkers (DEP and DETP) which are all excreted in urine. TCPy is the most specific biomarker for chlorpyrifos exposure although two other pesticides, chlorpyrifos-methyl and triclopyr, are also metabolised to TCPy.</p> <p>Glyphosate is excreted both unchanged and as metabolites in urine. One urinary metabolite, aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), is also the main environmental degradation product. Since AMPA and glyphosate have a similar toxic profile, it is advised to measure both glyphosate and AMPA in urine as biomarker for the total glyphosate exposure.</p> <p>The biomarkers for pyrethroids include a group-specific biomarker, 3PBA (3-</p>	<p>Urinary biomarkers for glyphosate, chlorpyrifos and pyrethroids were identified and the most suitable analytical methods were evaluated and included in the updated list of laboratories, biomarkers, methods in HBM4EU online library. The biomarkers include glyphosate and AMPA for glyphosate, TCPy for chlorpyrifos, and a group-specific biomarker, 3PBA, representing the combined exposure to many pyrethroids, 5 semi-specific biomarkers representing exposure to two-five pyrethroids, and a specific biomarker for deltamethrin exposure. The methods have been established in two expert laboratories passing the QA/QC programme. These harmonised, validated methods have been used to analyse pesticide biomarkers in urine samples from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and are available for future studies.</p> <p>No suitable specific urinary biomarkers were available for dimethoate or fipronil, and no information was found for biomarkers for the glyphosate co-formulant Polyethoxylated tallow amine (POEA) or the pyrethroid co-formulant piperonyl butoxide (PBO) and therefore no methods could be selected.</p>	<p>Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances</p> <p>Updated list of laboratories, biomarkers, methods in HBM4EU online library https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/;</p> <p>Esteban López, M. et al. (2021) The European human biomonitoring platform – design and implementation of a laboratory quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) programme for selected priority chemicals. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113740</p>

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	<p>Phenoxybenzoic acid), representing the combined exposure to many pyrethroids, 5 semi-specific biomarkers representing exposure to two-five pyrethroids, and a specific biomarker for deltamethrin exposure. Two of the biomarkers have not been measured in large population studies, while the remaining pyrethroid biomarkers have been developed and included in different large biomonitoring programs.</p> <p>No information was found for biomarkers for the glyphosate co-formulant Polyethoxylated tallow amine (POEA) or the pyrethroid co-formulant piperonyl butoxide (PBO) and therefore no methods could be selected.</p> <p>Dimethoate is rapidly metabolised to unspecific dimethyl phosphates (DMP, DMTP, and DMDTP) which are excreted in urine. No suitable specific biomarker for dimethoate was available. The sum of the molar urinary concentrations of the three dimethyl phosphates will provide an estimate of dimethoate and other methylated organophosphate pesticides. By also including the three diethyl phosphates (DEP, DETP, and DEDTP) an estimate of the total exposure to organophosphates (including dimethoate and chlorpyrifos) will be achieved. All six metabolites (dialkyl phosphates, DAPs) are normally analysed in the same analytical run.</p> <p>Fipronil is mainly metabolised to fipronil</p>		

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	<p>sulphone which can be measured in serum/plasma. This biomarker has only been used in few studies and most of these are animal studies.</p> <p>LC-MS/MS was evaluated to be the most suitable analytical method for analysing all the biomarkers except for the pyrethroid biomarkers, CIF3CA (Cis-3-(2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid and trans-CDCA (trans-chrysanthemumdicarboxylic acid) for which GC-MS/MS and GC-HRMS, respectively, were assessed to be more suitable.</p> <p>A database of candidate laboratories for analysing the 2nd round of substances was elaborated (D9.6) and 36 laboratories were listed as candidates for analysing pesticides. Regarding the Interlaboratory Comparison Investigation (ICI)/EQUAS programme for the 2nd round of substances, it was decided that the approach used for the 1st set of substances would not be feasible due to time limitations. Thus, a shortened ICI/EQUAS scheme focused on the substances foreseen to be analysed in the aligned studies was established.</p> <p>Four expert laboratories were selected for analysing biomarkers for pyrethroids (cis-DBCA, cis-DCCA, trans-DCCA, 3-PBA, 4-F-3-PBA, CIF3CA), glyphosate (glyphosate, AMPA), and chlorpyrifos (TCPy) in three ICI</p>		

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	<p>rounds. Two of the laboratories qualified this QA/QC programme. Additionally, an extra QA/QC was implemented amongst laboratories that had already generated data outside the scope of HBM4EU and so, that data was under consideration for inclusion in the HBM4EU database. The purpose of these extra QA/QC exercises was to gain insight into the comparability of the data generated by these laboratories, using their methods as applied for the analyses already done, with the data generated by the approved expert laboratories. Two laboratories analysed urine samples for glyphosate and AMPA and three laboratories determined TCPy. The outcome demonstrated good comparability of analytical results for AMPA, 3-PBA and DBCA by the laboratories determining these biomarkers. For 4-F-3-PBA and cis-DCCA, also good comparability was observed for results reported by one laboratory. For glyphosate, TCPy, and trans-DCCA, a poorer comparability was observed. CIF3CA was not measured by any of the participants.</p>		
<p>2. What are the current exposure levels of the EU population to the prioritised pesticides: pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos and</p>	<p>In order to answer questions on exposure levels and sources and further support current and future HBM studies, WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe. These materials are:</p>	<p>The results from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, existing data-collections (included in the European HBM dashboard, and published studies all show a widespread exposure to pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos in the EU-population with detection rates of TCPY and 3-PBA above 90 % in most studies/data-collections. High detection rates were also seen for the more</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating

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<p>dimethoate, glyphosate (in combination with polyethoxylated tallow amine (POEA)), and fipronil and do the exposure levels differ between countries?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium • manuals/guidelines for study planning and conduct • Standard Operating Procedures for qualified recruitment of participants, fieldwork, sampling and exchange of samples • different kinds of questionnaires for various age groups and substances (groups) • influence of thawing and freezing procedures on the integrity of biobanked samples in the literature and supplied a respective concept for a quality study • templates for the communication with participants <p>When identifying exposure levels and sources as well as groups at risk, WP7 questionnaires are of great value. They can be used to set up new studies and allow the harmonised collection of data on a participant's individual characteristics and their potential exposure pathways from different sources (sociodemographic characteristics, residential environment/home exposures, dietary habits, lifestyle, occupational exposure and health status). For pesticides, questionnaires for adults and children addressing residential environment and home exposures, dietary habits, lifestyle and occupation are available</p>	<p>specific pyrethroid biomarkers in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, except for 4-F-3-PBA (specific biomarker for cyfluthrin). Lower detection rates of these biomarkers were seen in most published studies, likely due to higher LODs/LOQs.</p> <p>In the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, the median urinary TCPy concentrations among children varied between 6.5 ng/ml (Cyprus) to below LOQ of 0.05 ng/ml (France). Among adults the medians varied between 2.75 ng/ml (Israel) and below LOQ (France). For pyrethroids, medians for the group specific biomarker, 3-PBA, among children varied between 1.9 ng/ml (Cyprus) and 0.72 ng/ml (Slovenia), and between 0.82 ng/ml (France) and 0.21 ng/ml (Germany). Detection frequencies and medians for the more specific pyrethroid biomarkers differed between the countries and more detailed analyses of the exposure profiles are still ongoing in WP10.</p> <p>P50 of urinary TCPy concentrations are in the range of 0.52-5.71 µg/g crt, with 1 study with P50 < detection limit of 0.05 µg/L, in children and 0.53-2.51 µg/g crt with, 1 study with P50 < detection limit of 0.05 µg/L, in adults. P95 of urinary TCPy concentrations are in the range of 3.24-15.67 µg/g crt, with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.05 µg/L, in children and 1.98-6.70 µg/g crt, with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.05 µg/L, in adults. Health-based guidance values are not available for TCPy.</p> <p>P50 of urinary cis-DBCA concentrations are in the range of 0.21-1.31 µg/g crt across studies in</p>	<p>Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Deliverables D8.7 D8.8, D10.5 and D10.6 are available at https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • European HBM dashboard that allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/

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	<p>(D7.6). For the SPECIMEn study on pesticide mixtures a specific questionnaire has been elaborated.</p> <p>Initially, a gap analysis was performed in WP7 to get an overview of the number of studies on the 2nd round of priority substances within the participating countries based on a questionnaire distributed in 2018 (D7.5). A total of 26 studies (conducted or initiated/ongoing) reported to analyse pesticides. Most of these studies were carried out in the western European-defined region followed by the Northern and Southern regions and Israel. No studies on pesticides were reported from the Eastern region. Children were included in 12 of the studies while adults were included in 18, adolescents in 4, and elderly in 2 studies. Of these studies, 17 reported to have samples representative at national level (7 for children, 2 for adolescents, 8 for adults, and none for elderly).</p> <p>WP10 has developed a general and a substance-specific statistical analysis plan including variables, which are needed for the statistical analyses to address research questions for the pesticides on general exposure level including identification of high exposure subgroups, time trends including potential impact of regulation, geographic comparisons, and exposure determinants (D10.5).</p>	<p>children and 0.13-0.74 µg/g crt, with 1 study with P50 < detection limit of 0.1 µg/L, in adults. P95 of urinary cis-DBCA concentrations are in the range of 1.19-6.91 µg/g crt in children and 0.39-5.91 µg/g crt in adults. P50 of urinary cis-DCCA concentrations are in the range of 0.26-0.58 µg/g crt in children and 0.11-0.30 µg/g crt, with 1 study with P50 < quantification limit of 0.1 µg/L, in adults. P95 of urinary cis-DCCA concentrations are in the range of 1.58-2.46 µg/g crt in children and 0.38-1.10 µg/g crt in adults. P50 of urinary trans-DCCA concentrations are in the range of 0.27-1.13 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.20-0.31 µg/g crt across studies in adults. P95 of urinary trans-DCCA concentrations are in the range of 1.64-6.00 µg/g crt in children and 0.99-1.77 µg/g crt in adults. P50 of urinary 3-PBA concentrations are in the range of 0.65-1.84 µg/g crt in children and 0.32-0.79 µg/g crt in adults. P95 of urinary 3-PBA concentrations are in the range of 3.42-7.38 µg/g crt in children and 1.50-4.95 µg/g crt in adults. All P50 of urinary 4-F-3-PBA concentrations are < detection limit (range: 0.015-0.1 µg/L) in children and in adults. P95 of urinary 4-F-3-PBA concentrations are in the range of 0.09-0.28 µg/g crt, with 3 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.03-0.1 µg/L), across studies in children and 0.08 µg/g crt in one study in adults, with 3 studies with P95 < detection limit (range: 0.035-0.1 µg/L), in adults. P50 of urinary ClF3CA concentrations are in the range of 0.12-0.15 µg/g crt, with 2 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.02 - 0.1 µg/L) across studies in children and 0.19 µg/g crt in one</p>	

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	<p>A comprehensive review of the existing HBM-studies on the pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos, and glyphosate (including information on occupational exposures and other exposure determinants) performed within the HBM4EU associated countries is in progress in the scope of WP10. Overall, there are relatively few studies, several were performed before 2010, they are not EU-wide, and few studies address occupational exposures. A review article on this work is planned published primo 2022.</p> <p>For the existing data on pyrethroids and/or chlorpyrifos, 11 data collections from 7 countries have been included. Harmonisation and data-analyses are completed and publications are in preparation. These data were included and visualised by exposure distributions in D10.6 and the online European HBM dashboard.</p> <p>To obtain a better EU coverage for HBM exposure data, the HBM4EU Aligned Studies collected new data for Glyphosate and AMPA in children (6-11 years) and adults (20-39 years). The data in children were collected between 2014-2020 across 5 sampling sites in Europe (Slovenia, Cyprus, Belgium, France, and Germany) representing 971 individuals; data in adults were collected between 2014-2021 across 4 sampling sites in Europe (Iceland, Switzerland, France, and Germany)</p>	<p>study in adults, with 2 studies with P95 < detection limit of 0.1 µg/L. P95 of urinary C1F3CA concentrations are in the range of 0.24-0.93 µg/g crt in children and in the range of 0.43-0.90 µg/g crt across studies in adults.</p> <p>Glyphosate/AMPA measurements in children in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies showed that the exposure is wide across the EU with similar low concentrations for glyphosate and AMPA close to or beneath the LOQ. At the higher end of the exposure distribution (95 percentiles), the highest urinary concentrations were observed for both glyphosate and AMPA in Cyprus (1.03 and 0.66 ng/ml) and lowest in Slovenia (0.18 and 0.29 ng/ml). Transfer of all the data for adults were recently completed and data-analyses of these data is ongoing.</p> <p>P50 of urinary Glyphosate concentrations are in the range of 0.08-0.13 µg/g crt across studies in children with 3 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.01-0.03 µg/L). P50 of urinary glyphosate concentrations are all < detection limit (range: 0.02-0.1 µg/L) across studies in adults. P95 of urinary glyphosate concentrations are in the range of 0.20-0.84 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.21-0.38 µg/g crt across studies in adults.</p> <p>P50 of urinary AMPA concentrations are in the range of 0.15-0.19 µg/g crt across studies in children with 3 studies with P50 < detection limit (range: 0.1-0.2 µg/L). P50 of urinary AMPA concentrations is 0.10 µg/g crt in one study, in the</p>	

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	<p>representing 912 individuals.</p> <p>In addition, the HBM4EU Aligned Studies collected new data for 7 pesticide markers (TCPy, cis-DBCA, cis-DCCA, trans-DCCA, 3-PBA, 4-F-3-PBA, ClF3CA) in children (3-11 years) and adults (20-39 years). The data in children were collected between 2014-2021 across 6 sampling sites in Europe (Slovenia, Cyprus, Belgium, The Netherlands, France, and Israel) representing 863 individuals; data in adults were collected between 2014-2021 across 6 sampling sites in Europe (Iceland, Portugal, Switzerland, France, Germany, and Israel) representing 1184 individuals. Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p> <p>The biomarker data from Slovenia, France, and Germany were already available (analysed outside the scope of HMB4EU) and the comparability of these results was evaluated by an extra QA/QC exercise in WP9 as described under question 1.</p> <p>In the SPECIMEn study performed in WP15 (see AD15.7 for detailed description), urine samples were collected during the spraying and non-spraying season from children and their guardians living close (within 250 m) to agricultural fields treated with pesticides as well as from urban control populations, in five EU countries (Spain, the Netherlands,</p>	<p>other 3 studies P50 are all < detection limit (range: 0.1-0.2 µg/L). P95 of urinary AMPA concentrations are in the range of 0.26-0.59 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.24-0.38 µg/g crt, with 1 study with P95 < detection limit of 0.2 µg/L, across studies in adults.</p> <p>P50 of the sum of urinary Glyphosate+AMPA concentrations are in the range of 0.23-0.28 µg/g crt across studies in children and P50 is 0.13 µg/g crt in one study in adults. P95 of urinary glyphosate+AMPA concentrations are in the range of 0.65-1.45 µg/g crt across studies in children and P95 is 0.69 µg/g crt in one study in adults.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data provide a baseline of pesticide exposure for the European population for future assessment of the effectiveness of reducing pesticide use under the Farm to Fork Strategy. Overall, the results indicate marked difference in exposure between EU-countries but a better EU coverage of harmonised HBM data for these pesticides are needed to get a full picture of the exposure situation across Europe. No information on exposure to dimethoate, polyethoxylated tallow amine (POEA), and fipronil have been collected because no suitable biomarker methods were available.</p>	

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	<p>Switzerland, Czechia, Hungary and Latvia) to assess possible geographical hotspot areas close to agricultural fields.</p> <p>These urine samples were analysed by suspect screening approach developed under WP16, aiming to qualitatively detect an extended range (i.e. several hundreds to thousands) of pesticide related markers of exposure through a developed harmonised analytical workflow (from sample preparation, LC-HRMS data acquisition to data processing and reporting) applied by five laboratories/countries (FR, NL, SP, CZ, DE). The results provide insight in the feasibility of this analytical approach, and information on differences in detection frequencies of pesticides and exposure patterns between the included countries and subpopulations. From this provided picture of the reality of human internal exposure, these results will contribute to further rationale and prioritisation with regard to certain markers for which more quantitative and targeted methods will appear necessary and/or for which the inclusion in future HBM program will appear relevant.</p>		
<p>3. What are the main dietary sources of exposure across the member states?</p>	<p>Analyses of the main dietary and non-dietary sources of exposure are being analysed using existing HBM data from selected data collections available in the European HBM dashboard and from new HBM data obtained from analyses of urine samples from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies (see question 2).</p>	<p>Harmonised data-analyses of the main dietary and non-dietary sources of exposure for pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos, and glyphosate are still ongoing. These analyses are based on existing HBM data from selected data-collections and from the new HBM data obtained from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies.</p>	

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4. What are other potential sources and pathways of exposure?	A protocol for this work was prepared in WP10.		
5. What are exposure levels among occupationally exposed workers?	None of the HBM4EU data collections contain data from occupationally exposed individuals and very few published studies have addressed this issue. Thus, new HBM-data are needed to get information on exposure levels among populations occupationally exposed to pesticides.		
<p>6. Are the exposure levels of health-relevance/concern for vulnerable groups (infants, children and pregnant women) or high exposure population groups (e.g., occupational exposure)?</p> <p>8. Is it possible to establish EU wide accepted HBM guidance values for the pesticides that takes into account potential mixture effects and evidence from</p>	<p>In the scope of WP13, the text mining tool (AOP-helpFinder) developed at INSERM was applied to the prioritised pesticides to identify linkages with AOP events existing in the AOP wiki database. This tool automatically screens abstracts from the PubMed database. The results have been collected, structured and presented in a webserver named AOP4EUpest: Mapping of pesticides in Adverse Outcome Pathways using a text mining tool, published in <i>Bioinformatics</i> (Jornod et al., 2020)).</p> <p>Within WP13 and WP14, comprehensive literature reviews on health effects and toxic mechanisms have been performed. The primary aim of the reviews was to assess HBM exposure levels associated with adverse health outcomes taking into account vulnerable exposure windows (pregnant women and children), and to identify the most important mechanisms and potential</p>	<p>Evidence from epidemiological studies (including EU cohorts) combined with biological plausibility captured from toxicology studies and the capability of pyrethroids to interfere with neurodevelopmental key events (KEs) included in established Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) for adverse neurodevelopmental health outcomes suggest that pyrethroids are developmental neurotoxicants. The developing brain is particularly vulnerable to neurotoxicants, and exposure during major windows of vulnerability in foetal and early life, even at low doses without neurotoxic effects in other age-groups, may have long-term impact on neurodevelopment. Thus, current exposure levels of pyrethroid mixtures might be of concern for vulnerable population groups as pregnant women and children. However, lack of harmonised analytical methods for the urinary biomarkers combined with variety in outcome measurements in the published studies hamper the possibility to evaluate</p>	<p>Scoping document on pesticides</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/hbm4eu-substances/pesticides/</p> <p>Jornod, F., Rugard, M., Tamisier, L., Coumoul, X., Andersen, H. R., Barouki, R., & Audouze, K. (2020). AOP4EUpest: mapping of pesticides in adverse outcome pathways using a text mining tool. <i>Bioinformatics</i>, 36(15), 4379-4381. doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa545</p> <p>Link to AOP4EUpest server:</p> <p>http://www.biomedicale.parisdescartes.fr/aop4EUpest/home.php</p> <p>Fucic, A., Duca, R. C., Galea, K. S., Maric, T., Garcia, K., Bloom, M. S., . . . Vena, J. E. (2021). Reproductive Health Risks Associated with Occupational and Environmental Exposure to Pesticides. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i>, 18(12).</p>

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<p>epidemiological studies?</p>	<p>adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) and suitable effect biomarkers for the health outcomes of highest concern (D13.5 and D14.5).</p> <p>A joint systematic review: “Pyrethroids and developmental neurotoxicity – a systematic review of the epidemiological evidence and supporting mechanistic evidence” has been submitted for publication and is currently under review for publication. Because of considerable differences in methods used for assessing the outcomes (e.g., neurodevelopment) and for analysing the pesticide metabolites in urine, meta-analyses were not feasible. Since chlorpyrifos/chlorpyrifos-methyl did not get renewal of authorisation (expired 31 January 2020), it was decided to focus on pyrethroids in this review. The findings suggest pyrethroids to be probably human developmental neurotoxicants based on evidence from epidemiological studies and evidence for the capability of pyrethroids to interfere with neurodevelopmental key events (KEs) included in established Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) for adverse neurodevelopmental health outcomes.</p> <p>Another review publication entitled "Reproductive health risks associated with environmental and occupational exposure to pesticides" (Fucic et al. 2021) has been published. Pesticides were also included in</p>	<p>exposure-response relationships. Thus, more (longitudinal) studies on neurodevelopmental outcomes using harmonised/comparable methods for assessment of exposure biomarkers, (early) effect biomarkers and health outcomes would be highly relevant to establish safe exposure levels.</p> <p>Additional evidence from toxicology data and effect biomarkers analysed in the INMA Granada birth cohort suggest pyrethroids to be associated with reproductive and endocrine disturbances. However, studies on health effects associated with low chronic pyrethroid exposure are in general scarce and more studies are needed to confirm these findings and the potential mechanisms.</p> <p>Based on the HBM data obtained from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, risk assessments were performed for pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos. Generally, the HBM data on pyrethroids suggests a low concern for the general population. However, for some highly exposed children a risk cannot to be excluded. Some uncertainties must be considered, the main ones being the conservativeness of the screening level HBM-GVs used and the uncertainty related to the long-term exposure levels evaluated measurements in single spot urine samples. Besides, the ADIs settled for most pyrethroids are based on neurotoxicity observed in adult experimental animals, which may not sufficiently protect against developmental neurotoxicity. Thus, generation of data on the potential developmental</p>	<p>doi:10.3390/ijerph18126576</p> <p>Castiello F, Freire C. Exposure to non-persistent pesticides and puberty timing: a systematic review of the epidemiological evidence. <i>Eur J Endocrinol.</i> 2021;184(6):733-749. doi: 10.1530/EJE-20-1038.</p> <p>Suárez B, Vela-Soria F, Castiello F, Olivas-Martinez A, Acuña-Castroviejo D, Gómez-Vida J, Olea N, Fernández MF, Freire C. Organophosphate pesticide exposure, hormone levels, and interaction with PON1 polymorphisms in male adolescents. <i>Sci Total Environ.</i> 2021;769:144563. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144563.</p> <p>Freire, C., Suarez, B., Vela-Soria, F., Castiello, F., Reina-Perez, I., Andersen, H. R., . . . Fernandez, M. F. (2021). Urinary metabolites of non-persistent pesticides and serum hormones in Spanish adolescent males. <i>Environ Res</i>, 197, 111016. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2021.111016</p> <p>Mattila, T., Santonen, T., Andersen, H. R., Katsonouri, A., Szigeti, T., Uhl, M., . Tolonen, H. (2021). Scoping Review-The Association between Asthma and Environmental Chemicals. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i>, 18(3). doi:10.3390/ijerph18031323</p>

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	<p>several scoping reviews on environmental exposures related to Alzheimer’s disease (Elonheimo et al. 2021), asthma (Mattila et al 2021), and with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (Elonheimo et al. 2022, submitted).</p> <p>For chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, fipronil, pyrethroids and glyphosate, several classical and novel effect biomarkers for a range of health outcomes (cardiometabolic health, the immune system, pregnancy and reproductive outcomes, neurodevelopment and cancer) have been inventoried (D14.5).</p> <p>Besides, associations between HBM data and effect biomarkers and/or health outcomes have been analysed within some of the aligned study cohorts:</p> <p>In the INMA Granada birth cohort eight pesticide metabolites were measured in adolescents’ (aged 15-17 years) spot urine samples: 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy), 2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxypyrimidine (IMPy), malathion diacid (MDA), and diethyl thiophosphate (DETP); two generic metabolites of pyrethroids, 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA) and dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid (DCCA) the metabolite of insecticide carbaryl 1-naphthol (1-N); and the metabolite of ethylene-bis-dithiocarbamate fungicides ethylene thiourea (ETU). Additionally, the total sum of organophosphates (ΣOPs) and</p>	<p>neurotoxicity of pyrethroids is strongly encouraged as part of EU (re)evaluation of pyrethroids. Nevertheless, the approach developed provides a model for the setting of screening level HBM-GV for pyrethroid exposure and for its use in the assessment of the risks of pyrethroid mixtures. This same approach might be taken for other pesticides/pesticide groups to identify those for which a health risk cannot be excluded.</p> <p>Regarding the risk assessment for chlorpyrifos, the HBM data confirms concerns in all countries for several population groups, especially children, highlighting that the risk for children is clearly higher than for adults. For children the highest risk levels were observed for Israel and Cyprus; for adults, the highest risk levels were observed for Israel and Portugal. It should be noted that the urine samples from the aligned studies used for this risk assessment were collected before the withdrawal of authorisation for chlorpyrifos by February 2020. Thus, the exposure of EU citizens has likely been markedly reduced afterwards, which could be confirmed by collecting new data on TCPy from EU-populations. Further, the urinary marker TCPy covers only two closely related active substances, chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl, thus is not relevant, per se, for covering cumulative risk to pesticide mixtures. However, the combination of the specific urinary marker, TCPy, with a second biomarker, based on urinary levels of alkyl phosphate metabolites, common to several other organophosphate</p>	<p>Elonheimo, H. M., Andersen, H. R., Katsonouri, A., & Tolonen, H. (2021). Environmental Substances Associated with Alzheimer's Disease-A Scoping Review. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i>, 18(22). doi:10.3390/ijerph18221839</p> <p>Andersen, H. R., L. Dalsager, I. K. Jensen, C. A. G. Timmermann, T. S. Olesen, F. Trecca, F. Nielsen, G. Schoeters, H. B. Kyhl, P. Grandjean, N. Bilenberg, D. Bleses, and T. K. Jensen. "Prenatal Exposure to Pyrethroid and Organophosphate Insecticides and Language Development at Age 20-36 Months among Children in the Odense Child Cohort." <i>Int J Hyg Environ Health</i> 235 (May 4 2021): 113755. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113755</p> <p>Articles in progress</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-persistent pesticide exposure, BDNF, and behavioral function in adolescents: Exploring a novel effect biomarker approach (submitted to Environmental Research) • Exploratory study of kisspeptin and its relationship with non-persistent pesticide exposure and reproductive hormones in adolescent males from INMA-Granada cohort (manuscript ongoing). • Castiello, et al. Exposure to non-persistent pesticides and pubertal

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	<p>pyrethroids (ΣPYR), were calculated. Further, measurement of glyphosate and AMPA in children/adolescents (7-16 years) (>1500) from the INMA Project is planned.</p> <p>Preliminary results suggest associations between several of these pesticide biomarkers and effect biomarkers of adverse Neurodevelopment (decreased serum BDNF levels and higher BDNF gene DNA methylation). and more behavioral problems among adolescents.</p> <p>Further, associations with effect biomarkers of impaired Reproduction (higher serum kisspeptin protein and lower KISS1 gene DNA methylation).</p> <p>In the GENEIDA (Early life enviroNmental Exposures and Infant Development in Andalusia) cohort, exposure to organophosphate compounds (pesticides and Flame retardants) have been assessed on 694 mother/child pairs from the Early life enviroNmental Exposures and Infant Development in Andalusia (GENEIDA) birth cohort. Women were recruited in Ejido, Almería (Southeast Spain) in the first trimester of pregnancy (12–13 weeks of gestation) and then followed-up in the third trimester of pregnancy, and at delivery. The inclusion criteria were: 16 years old or older, intention of giving birth at the reference hospital mentioned above, singleton pregnancy, pregnancy without assisted</p>	<p>insecticides, would allow setting human biomonitoring programmes including a screening tier as for the pyrethroids, and a refined tier if the markers for the screening are exceeded. Such kind of programmes would facilitate the implementation and prioritisation of human biomonitoring.</p>	<p>development in boys and girls: the INMA Project.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Castiello, et al. Association of non-persistent pesticide exposure with sexual development in Spanish adolescent males: the INMA-Granada cohort. • Comprehensive review aimed at identifying the evidence on biomarkers of effect used in epidemiological and in vitro and vivo studies to assess health effects associated with the exposure to organophosphate (OP) compounds, including pesticides and flame retardants (FRs)' <p>Relevant deliverables mentioned in the text are available at https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/</p> <p>D5.11 Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 4th set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals</p>

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	<p>reproductive technology, lack of any chronic disease or being under medical treatment and absence of any language barrier. Behavior and neuropsychological development have been assessed in children at 14 months covering four domains: general cognitive, general motor, attention, and working memory. Investigations on possible associations between prenatal exposure to organophosphate compounds and biomarkers of brain damage levels in umbilical cord serum are ongoing.</p> <p>In the Odense Child Cohort (OCC), metabolites of pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos were measured in spot urine samples (N=1207) from gestational week 28. None of the metabolites was significantly associated with higher odds of delayed language development in the children at age 20-36 months (Andersen et al. 2021) although associations with higher ADHD-scores at the same age were previously found.</p> <p>Based on examples from the 1st set of substances it was concluded in WP5 that HBM would be particularly important for performing risk assessment (RA) for substances, for which several exposure routes may contribute to the body burden and the health effects. This is exactly the case for the pesticides, especially for pyrethroids used both as biocides and as agricultural pesticides.</p>		

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	<p>To enable translation of HBM data into external exposure levels for comparison with e.g., ADI values, information on toxicokinetic properties was needed. This issue was addressed in WP12 using toxicokinetic modelling to link an external exposure to an internal dosimetry in humans (e.g., concentration in blood, urine or in tissues) by describing the process of absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) that undergoes a substance in living organisms. A class of toxicokinetic models, the physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models, bases the description on the ADME processes on the physiology and the anatomy of individuals, and the biochemistry of the compounds. A comprehensive review of human PBTK models available for the HBM4EU 2nd set of compounds, including the prioritised pesticides, has been performed (AD12.8). Most models concern adults while toxicokinetic data on sensitive populations (pregnant women, foetuses or children) are still missing.</p> <p>Existing PBTK models for humans have been identified for four pyrethroids: deltamethrin (type II pyrethroids), permethrin (type I pyrethroids), cypermethrin (type II pyrethroids) and cyfluthrin (type II pyrethroids). Interestingly, one of the models for deltamethrin predicted a considerably higher brain concentration in humans than rats due to an almost six-fold higher cardiac</p>		

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	<p>output to the brain in humans. A generic model for pyrethroids has also been proposed as a tool to interpret the combined exposure to pyrethroids reflected by non-specific urinary biomarkers. Several PBTK models were also identified for chlorpyrifos and other organophosphate insecticides while no specific PBPK-models for neither humans or animal species were identified for glyphosate or the co-formulant Polyethoxylated tallow amine (POEA) or for fipronil.</p> <p>Some of the PBPK models have been parameterised and used for forward or reverse dosimetry to either translation of HBM data for the pesticides into external exposure doses for comparison with established guidance values for risk assessment (e.g., ADI) or to simulate the biologically effective dose of the compounds (AD12.10). However, most HBM studies on adverse health effects related to pyrethroid exposure are based on the group specific urinary metabolite 3PBA (3-phenoxybenzoic acid) reflecting the combined exposure to pyrethroids. The reason is that the detection frequency of more specific metabolites is typically very low because different pyrethroids are used alternately and they have short biological half-lives. Thus, besides comparing HBM concentrations of specific metabolites with the HBM-GV derived in WP5, an approach to use group-</p>		

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	<p>specific biomarkers, such as 3PBA, for translation into external exposure levels and integrated in assessment of cumulative risks of pesticide mixtures has been developed in WP5.3 (see below).</p> <p>HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs) for deltamethrin and cyfluthrin have been derived (task 5.2), and provisional HBM-GVs for the pyrethroids bifenthrin, cypermethrin, etofenprox, fenpropathrin, fenvalerate, λ-cyhalothrin, permethrin and tau-fluvalinate. Results will be available in Deliverable D5.12.</p> <p>These HBM-GV values were included in a combined risk assessment for pyrethroids based on HBM data (urinary metabolite concentrations) obtained from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. Since pyrethroids share common mechanism of action and critical effect, their effects can be considered additive. Therefore, an approach to assess the risk of exposure to a relevant mixture of pyrethroids was developed in WP5.3 for comparison of the group-specific biomarker, 3-PBA, reflecting a rough estimate of overall exposure to a mixtures of pyrethroids, with a screening HBM-GV. Thus, two risk assessments for pyrethroids and chlorpyrifos, respectively, based on HBM data obtained from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies have been performed under WP5.3. This work will be included in the deliverable</p>		

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	<p>report D5.11.</p> <p>For the pyrethroids, the risk assessments were based on the assumption that the available HBM data reflect chronic steady-state exposure meaning that the ADI values are the most appropriate toxicological reference values to compare with the exposure levels. In general, the key toxic endpoint in the setting of ADI values for the pyrethroids covered in this risk assessment is neurotoxicity seen in adult experimental animals.</p> <p>For chlorpyrifos/chlorpyrifos-methyl no ADIs have been proposed by EFSA after the withdrawal of authorisation by February 2020. Therefore, the Margin of Exposure (MoE) approach was used for the risk assessment of chlorpyrifos and several relevant Points of Departure - PoD (toxicological reference points) were included.</p>		
<p>7. How can cumulative risks of pesticide mixtures on sensitive health outcomes be assessed and integrated in regulation?</p>	<p>Besides the approach to assess the risk of exposure to a relevant mixture of pyrethroids via the group-specific biomarker 3-PBA, as described above, a major activity related to cumulative risk assessment is the investigation of exposure to mixtures of pesticides among residents living close to pesticide treated areas in the SPECIMEn study performed in WP15 (results are further described under the Substance group:</p>		

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	Chemical mixtures).		
<p>9. How can HBM data from HBM4EU feed into prioritisation of the pesticides for risk assessments and regulatory decision-making?</p>		<p>It is recommended to take potential analysis of exposure to a particular substance by means of HBM data into account as part of EU (re)evaluation of pesticides. This would mean that suitable metabolites for HBM studies should be proposed and HBM-GVs derived in all cases where this is possible. A respective section might be included in the overall evaluation (Volume 1) and would be subject to peer review by MS. The applicants should be requested to provide own proposals for analysis of their active ingredients and metabolites in HBM studies.</p> <p>Chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl are no longer authorised in the EU and all MRLs are set at the default value. As indicated above, the results based on real human exposure support this decision. Nevertheless, it should be noted that a similar assessment conducted with the “legally binding ADI” at the time of collecting the urine samples would have resulted in very different risk characterisation results. This fact confirms the need for rapid regulatory implementation of the scientific updates on pesticide toxicity. As mentioned above, the combination of TCP with a second biomarker, based on urinary levels of alkyl phosphate metabolites, should be considered for future activities.</p>	

20 Phthalates

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<p>1. Which are the most sensitive, reliable and cost-effective methods and biomarkers to measure phthalates and Hexamoll® and DINCH®?</p>	<p>In WP9 a prioritised list with most suitable biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods has been elaborated. In total 26 suitable biomarkers representing exposure to 14 parental compounds were selected. Two methods have been evaluated as being suitable to measure the metabolites: GC-MS-MS for measuring DPHP metabolites only and LC-MS-MS for all other biomarkers. Urine has been selected as matrix of choice for all compounds. No information has been found for DiPeP, DHNUP and DMEP. Hence, no methods or biomarkers could be selected (see D9.2). Furthermore, a final list of the parameters that has been included in the HBM4EU ICI/EQUAS has been elaborated in substance specific working groups based on the existence of solid and reliable analytical methods and the availability of reference material. The QA/QC programme included: MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP, OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH.</p> <p>In WP 9.3 “Development of new methods”, a feasibility study was conducted that identified new, valuable urinary exposure biomarkers for EU-labelled, reprotoxic phthalates currently not covered in HBM analytical methods (Cat C</p>	<p>HBM4EU has elaborated a prioritised list with most suitable biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods. In total 26 suitable biomarkers representing exposure to 14 parental compounds were selected. Two methods have been evaluated as being suitable to measure the metabolites: GC-MS-MS for measuring DPHP metabolites only and LC-MS-MS for all other biomarkers. Urine has been selected as matrix of choice for all compounds. In addition, a feasibility study was conducted that identified new, valuable urinary exposure biomarkers for EU-labelled, reprotoxic phthalates currently not covered in HBM analytical methods. This work provides a harmonised method covering biomarkers for all EU-regulated phthalates.</p> <p>The HBM4EU Quality Assurance/ Quality Control Programme was implemented for MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP, OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH.</p> <p>Throughout the ICI/EQUAS exercise, in combination with training and knowledge exchange, a substantial increase in capable laboratories being able to analyse DINCH/phthalates within HBM4EU was</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Updated list of laboratories, biomarkers, methods in HBM4EU online library https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/; • D9.2 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances • AD9.9 Compilation of the analytical methods used by the HBM4EU laboratories for the substances on the 1st and 2nd prioritisation list • Esteban López, M. et al. (2021) The European human biomonitoring platform – design and implementation of a laboratory quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) programme for selected priority chemicals. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113740

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	<p>phthalates): Di-isopentyl phthalate (DiPeP), Di-C7-11-(linear and branched)alkyl phthalate (DHNUP), Di-n-hexyl phthalate (DnHexP) and Di-(methoxyethyl) phthalate (DMOP). Biomarkers for these phthalates will be implemented in a new phthalate multi-method and tested with a small round robin test.</p> <p>A Quality Assurance/ Quality Control Programme was implemented in order to establish a European database of candidate laboratories that are equally qualified for exposure biomarker analysis within HBM4EU. For this an interlaboratory comparison investigation/external quality assurance scheme (ICI/EQUAS) scheme and evaluation criteria were developed (see Deliverable 9.4).</p>	<p>achieved: After the 4th round ICI/EQUAS a total of 20 laboratories from 14 countries could be identified, that successfully participated for the analysis of phthalates biomarkers. More than half of the laboratories qualified for the analysis of DEHP, DEP, DiBP, DnBP and BBzP biomarkers (□ 11/ 20). For the Cat B and C phthalates also an increasing number of approved laboratories was achieved, ranging from six to ten laboratories. For DINCH metabolites, 8 laboratories from 8 countries did successfully participate of which all qualified for the analysis of OH-MINCH and almost all for cx-MINCH (7/8). The most current list of candidate laboratories can be found on the HBM4EU online library (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vorkamp, K. et al. (2021) Biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods targeting human exposure to chemicals selected for a European human biomonitoring initiative. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106082

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<p>2. What is the extent of the current exposure of the EU population to the 16 phthalates (Cat A, B and C) and their substitute Hexamoll@ DINCH@?</p> <p>3. Do the exposure levels differ significantly between the countries?</p> <p>5. What are the high exposure groups? (Is there a statistically significant and toxicological relevant difference in mean concentration between adults and children? [...] between occupational exposed and non-exposed adults? [...] between male and female?)</p>	<p>In WP7.1 a gap analysis has been carried out to get an overview how many studies of phthalates and DINCH are available within the participating countries and has been summarised in a report (see D7.1). 42 studies in 12 different countries have been conducted or are initiated/ongoing, with measurements of phthalates and/or DINCH exposure over all age groups (Newborns, Children, Adolescents, Adults and Elderly). In general, most studies on this substance group have been carried out in the Northern or Eastern European-defined regions. 32 of the 42 studies reported to have biobanked samples and 6 of these studies are representative at national level. For the phthalate and DINCH substance group, most of the studies reported were with children and these studies were mostly conducted in Western Europe.</p> <p>In WP10, up to now, metadata of 55 different existing datasets, which measured phthalates are included into IPCHEM. Covering information from 17 different EU countries and Israel. Data owners/providers of 33 different studies have already provided their data on phthalates and DINCH in harmonised format to the European HBM dashboard created by HBM4EU which provides summary statistics for HBM data from different European countries.</p> <p>WP10 developed an R-script in order to be able to obtain aggregated data in a standardised and</p>	<p>HBM4EU Aligned Studies</p> <p>HBM4EU Aligned Studies (2014-2021) have generated new baseline levels of internal phthalate and DINCH concentrations in urine samples of the European general population for children (6-11 years) and teenagers (12-18 years). Almost every child and teenager investigated is internally exposed to some phthalate and DINCH metabolites (e.g. for DEHP, DiBP, DnBP, BBzP), whereas other phthalates such as DnOP, DCHP, DnPeP were only rarely detected. Highest levels were observed for DEP and DnBP in both age groups.</p> <p>P50 concentrations for the Sum (5-oxo + 5-OH-MEHP) are in the range of 11.14-39.07 µg/g crt across studies in children and 6.49-24.08 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary Sum (5-oxo + 5-OH-MEHP) concentrations are in the range of 42.18-100.38 µg/g crt across studies in children and 21.31-105.28 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers.</p> <p>P50 concentrations for the Sum (5-cx-MEPP + 5-OH-MEHP) are in the range of 14.45-47.98 µg/g crt across studies in children and 8.95-25.17 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary Sum (5-cx-MEPP + 5-OH-MEHP) concentrations are in the range of 49.36-152.49 µg/g crt across studies in children and 33.56-107.78 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers.</p>	<p>Field methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Fiddicke et al. (2020): A phased approach for preparation and organisation of human biomonitoring studies. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113684 <p>Exposure measurements:</p>

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	<p>comparable way of these different data sets. 32 data collections from 14 different countries shared harmonised aggregated data for phthalates and 12 data sets for DINCH could be harmonised based on this script. Exposure distributions of the obtained merged harmonised aggregated data output files was visualised by using box plots based on different percentiles (P5, 10, 25, 50, 75, 90, 95) in the European HBM dashboard.</p> <p>Gaps in EU-representative data on exposure to phthalates and DINCH (e.g. missing regions and/ or exposure biomarkers) are being filled in by targeted analyses of biobanked samples and/or the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. A sampling frame to obtain EU wide coverage with recent HBM exposure data was developed in WP8 (See D8.1). For phthalates and DINCH biobanked urinary samples have been analysed, already analysed data were shared and new data for 15 phthalate markers MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP) and 2 markers for phthalate substitute DINCH (OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH) have been collected in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies for children aged 6-11 years and for teenagers aged 12-18 years for all geographical regions.</p> <p>For children samples were collected between 2014-2021 across 12 sampling sites in Europe</p>	<p>All teenagers had detectable levels of MEP in their urine samples. P50 of urinary MEP concentrations are in the range of 8.89-63.51 µg/g crt across studies in children and 13.05-64.42 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MEP concentrations are in the range of 45.49-514.93 µg/g crt across studies in children and 99.02-484.41 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the BE-value of 23000 µg/g crt is 0% for children and teenagers.</p> <p>P50 of urinary MBzP concentrations are in the range of 1.36-11.88 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.86-6.91 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MBzP concentrations are in the range of 9.20-60.89 µg/g crt across studies in children and 5.11-51.61 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels the exceeding the BE-value of 23000 µg/g crt is 0% for children and teenagers.</p> <p>P50 of urinary MiBP concentrations are in the range of 15.76-48.33 µg/g crt across studies in children and 14.33-27.93 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MiBP concentrations are in the range of 51.44-261.03 µg/g crt across studies in children and 50.74-142.37 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for MiBP.</p>	<p>See WP9 summary under Q1</p> <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM4EU online library (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/) • Deliverable 10.10 Statistical analysis plan for the co-funded studies of WP8. Deliverable 10.12 Statistical analysis plan https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • HBM4EU Aligned Studies Data • European HBM dashboard that allows to visualise summary statistics from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/eu-hbm-dashboard/ • Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM) that includes metadata and aggregated data from existing HBM data collections obtained through the HBM4EU project: https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#discovery • D10.10 & D10.12: Statistical

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	<p>(Norway, Denmark, Greece, Slovenia, Italy, Slovakia, Poland, Czech Republic, France, Belgium, The Netherlands and Germany) representing 2880 individuals. The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data in teenagers were collected between 2014-2021 across 11 sampling sites in Europe (Norway, Sweden, Greece, Slovenia, Spain, Slovakia, Poland, Czech Republic, France, Belgium and Germany) representing 2799 individuals. Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p> <p>In order to answer questions on exposure levels and sources and further support current and future HBM studies, WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe. These materials are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium • manuals/guidelines for study planning and conduct • Standard Operating Procedures for qualified recruitment of participants, fieldwork, sampling and exchange of samples • different kinds of questionnaires for various age groups and substance (groups) • influence of thawing and freezing procedures 	<p>P50 of urinary MnBP concentrations are in the range of 13-40.38 µg/g crt across studies in children and 11.14-53.14 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MnBP concentrations are in the range of 45.96-250.40 µg/g crt across studies in children and 32.21-203.35 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels the exceeding the BE-value of 280 µg/g crt ranges from 0-3.73% for children and from 0-3.48% for teenagers.</p> <p>P50 of urinary MCHP concentrations are < detection limit (0.05-0.22 µg/L) in 6 studies or < quantification limit (0.1-0.2 µg/L) in 4 studies across studies in children and are < detection limit in (0.05-0.2 µg/L) in 6 studies or < quantification limit (0.2 µg/L) in 3 studies across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MCHP concentrations are in the range of 0.18-16 µg/g crt across studies in children (with 4 studies with a P95 value < detection limit (0.05-0.22 µg/L) and 2 studies with a P95 value < quantification limit of 0.2 µg/L) and 0.11-1.00 µg/g crt (with 5 studies with a P95 value < detection limit (0.05-0.2 µg/L) and 3 studies with a P95 value < quantification limit of 0.2 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for MCHP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary MnPeP concentrations are < detection limit (0.04-0.25 µg/L) in 6 studies or < quantification limit (0.1-0.2 µg/L) in 4 studies</p>	<p>analysis plan co-funded studies of WP8 including the plans for phthalates/DINCH for the aligned studies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research protocol describing the ongoing statistical analyses for the research questions on phthalates/DINCH using existing data collections (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-package-webpage/data-management-and-analysis/research-protocols-codebooks/).

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	<p>on the integrity of biobanked samples in the literature and supplied a respective concept for a quality study</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • templates for the communication with participants <p>When identifying exposure levels and sources as well as groups at risk, WP7 questionnaires are of great value. They can be used to set up new studies and allow the harmonised collection of data on a participant's individual characteristics and their potential exposure pathways from different sources (sociodemographic characteristics, residential environment/home exposures, dietary habits, lifestyle, occupational exposure and health status) with Phthalates and DINCH. For Phthalates and DINCH, questionnaires for adults, adolescents and children are available. Questionnaires for the 2nd occupational study on e-waste (incl. some plasticisers as biomarkers) have also been developed.</p> <p>WP9 designed and implemented a QA/QC program to ensure the comparability of the analytical results obtained in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. Furthermore, the Quality Assurance Unit (QAU) of WP9 revised the data of some aligned studies that analysed their samples before the HBM4EU QA/QC programme and so, data generated by laboratories that were not approved for the analysis of phthalates and/or DINCH metabolites. After a critical revision, the QAU</p>	<p>across studies in children and are < detection limit in (0.05-0.2 µg/L) in 4 studies or < quantification limit (0.2 µg/L) in 3 studies across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MnPeP concentrations are in the range of 0.21-15 µg/g crt across studies in children (with 4 studies with a P95 value < detection limit (0.07-0.25 µg/L) and 3 studies with a P95 value < quantification limit of 0.1-0.2 µg/L) and 0.50-1.41 µg/g crt (with 2 studies with a P95 value < detection limit (0.07 µg/L) and 3 studies with a P95 value < quantification limit of 0.2 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for MnPeP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary MEHP concentrations are in the range of 0.73-3.51 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.81-2.15 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MEHP concentrations are in the range of 3.40-14.44 µg/g crt across studies in children and 2.91-11.81 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for MEHP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary 5OH-MEHP concentrations are in the range of 6.57-20.30 µg/g crt across studies in children and 3.93-20.18 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary 5OH-MEHP concentrations are in the range of 24.48-62.38 µg/g crt across studies in children and 13.02-88.27 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are</p>	

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	<p>elaborated some recommendations on how to use the analytical data of these laboratories in HBM4EU.</p> <p>WP10 has developed a general and a substance-specific statistical analysis plan for phthalates and DINCH for existing and new HBM data collections. Variables which were needed for the statistical analyses to address substance-specific research questions on general exposure levels, time trends, geographic comparisons, and exposure determinants and reference values were defined. More information can be found in the Statistical Analysis Plans (D10.10 and D10.12).</p> <p>HBM based indicators for phthalates/DINCH with indicator graphs on time patterns, geographical differences and health impact are being developed under WP5 (statistical analysis in progress).</p>	<p>not available for 5OH-MEHP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary 5oxo-MEHP concentrations are in the range of 4.60-18.08 µg/g crt across studies in children and 2.49-7.53 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary 5oxo-MEHP concentrations are in the range of 16.99-53.87 µg/g crt across studies in children and 8.47-29.61 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for 5xo-MEHP.</p> <p>All children had detectable levels of 5cx-MEPP in their urine samples. P50 of urinary 5cx-MEPP concentrations are in the range of 8.22-28.16 µg/g crt across studies in children and 4.02-13.21 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary 5cx-MEPP concentrations are in the range of 26.61-90.43 µg/g crt across studies in children and 15.28-45.68 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for 5cx-MEPP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary MnOP concentrations are < detection limit (0.03-0.5 µg/L) in 6 studies or < quantification limit (0.1-0.2 µg/L) in 4 studies across studies in children and are < detection limit in (0.05-0.5 µg/L) in 6 studies or < quantification limit (0.2 µg/L) in 3 studies across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary MnOP concentrations are in the range of 0.56-0.60 µg/g crt across studies in children (with 5 studies with a P95 value < detection limit (0.033-0.5 µg/L) and 4 studies with a P95 value</p>	

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		<p>< quantification limit of 0.1-0.2 µg/L) and 0.27-0.42 µg/g crt (with 5 studies with a P95 value < detection limit (0.07-0.5 µg/L) and 3 studies with a P95 value < quantification limit of 0.2 µg/L). Health-based guidance values are not available for MnOP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary OH-MiNP concentrations are in the range of 1.95-7.63 µg/g crt across studies in children and 2.35-9.44 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary OH-MiNP concentrations are in the range of 7.16-50.05 µg/g crt across studies in children and 6.59-60.95 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels the exceeding the BE-value of 100 µg/g crt ranges from 0-0.33% for children and teenagers.</p> <p>P50 of urinary cx-MiNP concentrations are in the range of 0.34-11.59 µg/g crt across studies in children and 1.21-8.20 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary cx-MiNP concentrations are in the range of 0.68-73.51 µg/g crt across studies in children and 5.28-66.36 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. The share of individuals with exposure levels exceeding the BE-value of 100 µg/g crt ranges from 0-0.7% for children and from 0-0.66% for teenagers.</p> <p>P50 of urinary OH-MiDP concentrations are in the range of 0.67-3.20 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.34-1.54 µg/g crt (with 1 study with a P50 < detection limit of 0.20 µg/L) across</p>	

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		<p>studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary OH-MiDP concentrations are in the range of 2.65-11.28 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.59-10.16 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for OH-MiDP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary cx-MiDP concentrations are in the range of 0.50-1.33 µg/g crt (with 1 study with P50 < detection limit of 0.37 µg/L) across studies in children and 0.25-0.82 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary cx-MiDP concentrations are in the range of 1.60-7.09 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.93-4.28 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for cx-MiDP.</p> <p>P50 of urinary OH-MINCH concentrations are in the range of 1.20-4.04 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.55-2.1 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary OH-MINCH concentrations are in the range of 7.39-32.78 µg/g crt across studies in children and 3.93-25.86 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for OH-MINCH.</p> <p>P50 of urinary cx-MINCH concentrations are in the range of 0.51-2.81 µg/g crt across studies in children and 0.44-1.19 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. P95 of urinary cx-MINCH concentrations are in the range of 1.53-21.26 µg/g crt across studies in children and 2.12-</p>	

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		<p>8.37 µg/g crt across studies in teenagers. Health-based guidance values are not available for cx-MINCH.</p> <p>Age differences</p> <p>Higher levels of phthalates BBzP, DiBP, DEHP, and DINCH are found in children compared to teenagers who, in turn, have higher overall levels in DEP, DiDP and DiNP. In the analyses of existing HBM studies since 2005 including all regions, HBM4EU finds an indication for age differences (age groups between 3 to 60+) where, for example DnBP and DiDP levels children’s levels are higher than for adolescents and these, in turn, are higher than adult’s levels.</p> <p>Regional differences</p> <p>HBM4EU Aligned Studies revealed geographical differences in average internal exposure to phthalates and DINCH up to a factor of 9 between the different studies. Children from France, Italy and Slovenia, on average, have the highest levels (geometric means) in phthalates and DINCH compared to the European average, and Denmark, Hungary, and Belgium have the lowest concentrations. Teenagers, from France, Slovakia, and Norway are exposed the highest (geometric mean) and Belgium, Poland, and Sweden are the least exposed to phthalates and DINCH.</p> <p>HBM4EU also found differences between</p>	

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		<p>European regions in most phthalates and DINCH. For example, in children, there were no differences in DnBP and secondary metabolites of DEHP. But Eastern Europe had lower levels in DINP, BBzP, and DiDP compared to at least one other European region. For DINCH, Eastern and Western Europe had lower levels than Southern and Northern Europe. Regional differences for children indicate, however, a complex result pattern where pairwise comparisons between European regions depend on the phthalate or substitute studied.</p> <p>Occupational Data</p> <p>Occupational exposure to phthalates was studied among E-waste workers in HBM4EU E-waste study. Results will be available soon.</p>	
<p>4. What are the main sources of exposure and the reasons for differences in exposure (different regulations in different countries) to phthalates and Hexamoll® DINCH®?</p>	<p>Comparable HBM results have been obtained under the harmonised premises and QA/QC of WP7, WP8 and WP9 to support the robustness of the conclusions derived from them.</p> <p>WP7 has developed a concept for a study protocol for recruitment and sampling to ensure harmonised recruitment, sampling and questionnaire implementation. This harmonised procedure aims at obtaining comparable results across countries involved in the HBM4EU targeted studies. A substance-specific questionnaire for phthalates/DINCH was developed to collect all the necessary information concerning individual characteristics</p>	<p>Results from the analyses of the newly generated data from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies identified the daily use of body care and beauty products being important exposure determinants. However, depending on the physicochemical properties of the phthalates, other exposure pathways might get of importance, such as indoor dust through ingestion or inhalation of phthalates in gaseous and particles phase.</p> <p>In general, main common exposure determinants for children and teenagers are urbanisation and education, fast food, plastic food packaging, PVC floor, drinks in plastic</p>	<p>Field methods: See WP7 summary under Q2, 3, 5</p> <p>Exposure measurements: See WP9 summary under Q1</p> <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AD12.3 Exposure model testing results • WP10: Research protocol on exposure determinants phthalates for existing data collections can be found on the WP10 internal webpages of the HBM4EU website

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	<p>of the participants (sociodemographic, dietary, occupational, lifestyle, environmental and health factors) with the aim to characterise as well as identify possible sources and routes of exposures to these substances (see D7.3 and D7.6).</p> <p>In WP 10.4 a protocol has been developed to investigate exposure determinants on existing data sets on phthalate exposure for adults for different phthalates metabolites. Also for the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in children and teenagers exposure determinants were be investigated as described in the statistical analysis plan D10.12.</p> <p>In addition, the 2nd occupational study will investigate, by measuring urinary phthalates metabolites in workers of companies from 10 different countries, among others, what are the most relevant compounds in e-waste processing. Thereby, giving insights in important occupational exposure sources in the recycling sector.</p>	<p>bottle, cosmetics and hygiene products (fragrances, eyes make-up, body lotion).</p> <p>Important exposure determinants for children are physical activities (DEHP) and handheld electronical device usage > 4 hours per weekdays; also frequent plastic containers usage for food heating in microwaves (DINCH).</p> <p>Important exposure determinants for teenagers are the frequent use of local food (DINCH) and waste incineration nearby home; also a home construction year in the time between 2001 and 2006 (DEHP).</p> <p>The main source of exposure for phthalates and DINCH according to bottom-up calculations using the INTEGRA computational platform, where exposure data that account for multi-pathway and multi-route exposure have been used, as well as from regression analyses of the aligned studies, is diet through food contact materials.</p> <p>Existing data (adults) also show similar findings regarding daily use of beauty products and possible phthalates intake via diet because of food contact materials (packaging etc.). There is a limitation regarding existing data because of lack of information on all exposure determinants.</p> <p>Reasons for differences in exposures between countries with regards to national regulations and product content/quality control/monitoring</p>	<p>(https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-package-webpage/data-management-and-analysis/research-protocols-codebooks/).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D10.12: Statistical analysis plan co-funded studies of WP8 including the plans on exposure determinants for phthalates/DINCH in the aligned studies

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		(with focus on products from non-EU countries, e.g., e-market/shops) cannot be answered yet on the results obtained in HBM4EU. In general, regulatory measures to limit exposure to phthalates via food contact materials and cosmetics may be insufficient.	
<p>6. Are there different time trends for less regulated (DEP, DMP, DCHP, DPHP), regulated phthalates (DEHP, BBzP, DnBP, DiBP, DinP, DnOP) and the phthalates substitute Hexamoll® DINCH® ?</p> <p>&</p> <p>7. How effective have the different mitigation steps and regulations been for phthalates?</p>	<p>Recent and harmonised HBM data throughout Europe are indispensable to not only assess the populations risk from chemical exposure but to evaluate the suitability and success of current legislations and political measures in place.</p> <p>WP 8.2 and WP 10.4 studied existing data sets on phthalate exposure and evaluated time patterns for DINCH and phthalates in children and 4 European geographical areas by comparing three different time points (D8.4 & D10.12). For the first time point (2006-2010) already published exposure data were used, for the second time point (2011-2013) new analysis of DEMOCOPHES samples were conducted and for the third time point (2014-2020) data from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies are used.</p> <p>No published information on DINCH exposure in children was found for the first time point. Information for several phthalate metabolites is available in the literature. For the second time point, DEMOCOPHES samples were analysed</p>	<p>HBM4EU data analyses from Danish and German time trend studies in young adults show decreasing 24-hour excretion since the 2000s in the more regulated phthalates DEHP, BBzP, DnBP, and DiBP (in the range of 9-17 % yearly decrease, depending on the phthalate), and stability in DINP and DIDP/DPHP. Time trends since 2006 for less regulated phthalates (DEP, DMP) show decrease by about 17 % per year and phthalate, and substitutes DINCH and DEHTP show strong increases as determined in 24-hour excretion. These data seem to illustrate the effectiveness of policy action or lack/gaps thereof in case of phthalate substitutes.</p> <p>Data from existing HBM studies since 2005 from various European regions, available via the European HBM Dashboard, analysed in HBM4EU indicate decreases in the more regulated phthalates DEHP, DnBP, DiBP, DiDP, BBzP, but also the less regulated phthalates DEP and DMP.</p>	<p>Field methods: See WP7 summary under Q2, 3, 5</p> <p>Exposure measurements: See WP9 summary under Q1</p> <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research protocol on time trends phthalates for existing data collections can be found on the WP10 internal webpages of the HBM4EU website (https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-package-webpage/data-management-and-analysis/research-protocols-codebooks/). • D10.12: Statistical analysis plan co-funded studies of WP8 including the plans for time trend analysis for phthalates/DINCH • First papers on time trend analysis of existing data and aligned studies are expected

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	<p>from 4 geographical regions. (North: SE, DK East: PL, CZ, South: ES, CY, West: LX, DE, BE). For the second timepoint DINCH data of 8 out of 9 countries were made available to T8.2 and WP10 for time trend analysis. For the detailed description of planned measurements for the third time point, please see above and D8.4.</p> <p>In addition, a protocol in WP 10 has been developed to investigate time trends in studies with at least 3 repeated measurement points with individual data from Danish and German young adults (cross-sectional studies with repeated measurement design).</p>	<p>HBM4EU also evaluated time patterns for phthalates and DINCH in children and four European geographical areas by comparing HBM data from different studies from three different time points. When data for children from the DEMOCOPHES survey collected in the years 2010-2012 were compared to data from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies collected between 2014-2021, in general a lower exposure of DiBP in children was observed at the later time point, whereas DINCH exposure was, as expected, higher at the later time point. The HBM4EU Aligned Studies data will form baseline European exposure levels for phthalates and DINCH in teenagers, allowing follow up studies to monitor increased or decreased usage.</p> <p>As a result of the data presented, further monitoring of phthalates and its substitute DINCH (and DEHTP) is needed i) to assess the longer term success of recent regulatory measures and its impact to yield decreases in the exposure particularly towards DiBP and DnBP , and ii) follow up on increasing exposure levels of substitutes that are not (yet) a priority in single substance risk assessment to prevent regrettable substitution.</p>	<p>at the earliest in autumn 2022</p> <p>HBM4EU input to policy processes</p> <p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/the-project/science-to-policy/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM4EU input on four phthalates for European Chemicals Agency (2018). https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Input-on-four-phthalates.pdf • HBM4EU input on phthalates in medical device for Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks (2019). https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Input-on-phthalates-in-medical-devices.pdf • HBM4EU input on farm to fork strategy roadmap of the European Commission (2020). https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/HBM4EU-input-on-farm-to-fork-strategy-roadmap.pdf • HBM4EU input on chemicals strategy for sustainability roadmap of European Commission (2020).

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			<p>https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/HBM4EU-input-on-chemicals-strategy-for-sustainability-roadmap.pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HBM4EU input on EFSA's "Phthalates: draft opinion and exposure protocol open for public consultation". https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/phthalates-draft-opinion-and-exposure-protocol-open-public-consultation
<p>8. Is the exposure to phthalates and their substitutes of health relevance for the general population and vulnerable groups? What part of the population has exposure levels exceeding the HBM guidance values or TDI?</p> <p>9. Is the health-relevance dependent</p>	<p>HBM-GVs were derived for five phthalates (DEHP, DnBP, DiBP, BBzP and DPHP) and for the non-phthalate substitute DINCH. For the adult general population, the HBM-GVs for the specific metabolite(s) of the respective parent compounds in urine are the following: 0.5 mg/L for the sum of 5-oxo-MEHP and 5-OH-MEHP; 0.19 mg/L for MnBP, 0.23 mg/L for MiBP; 3 mg/L for MBzP; 0.5 mg/L for the sum of oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP and 4.5 mg/L for the sum of OH-MINCH and cx-MINCH. HBM-GVs for children (which are lower than for adults) and for workers were also specified.</p> <p>Within WP10 research protocols have been developed to investigate what proportion of the population from children and adolescents in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies as well as which population from existing data collection does</p>	<p>Single substance risk assessment</p> <p>Comparison of the newly generated HBM4EU Aligned Studies data with HBM-GVs showed that currently, exposure to DnBP and DiBP is a health concern in some countries, since the percentage of children and teenagers exceeding these values is highest for these highly regulated phthalates (up to 4%). The exposure to BBzP, DEP and DINCH is well below the corresponding health-based guidance values for both children and teenagers. One child exceeds the HBM-GV for BBzP. Some participants exceed the HBM-GV for DEHP. An impact on health cannot be excluded for these children and teenagers.</p> <p>For the phthalates studied (DEHP, DiNP, BBzP, DnBP and the replacement DINCH) daily intake</p>	<p>Field methods: See WP7 summary under Q2, 3, 5</p> <p>Exposure measurements: See WP9 summary under Q1</p> <p>Results</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D13.4 – HBM4EU web - https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-13.4-Report-on-AOPs-of-priority-substances.pdf Baken et al. paper - doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envs.2019.05.013 For more information on effect biomarkers please see:

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<p>on age or gender?</p>	<p>exceed HBM-GVs and also whether the mean concentration values differ with age or gender. More information can be found in the updated Statistical Analysis Plan (D10.10).</p> <p>In addition, WP 5.3 evaluated the strengths and limitations of using HBM data in risk assessment (D.5.5). For DEHP and the alternative plasticiser DINCH, RCRs were calculated based on metabolite concentrations in the DEMOCOPHES study using the HBM-GVs derived in task 5.2 and these were compared to RCR calculated in the restriction dossier from ECHA and the Danish EPA, 2016. As a result, RCR were in generally higher for children and lower for mothers when using the HBM-GVs.</p> <p>The work concerning the occupational population covered DiNP, DiDP and DPHP, because their use has not been extensively restricted in the occupational field and they are widely used in plastic product manufacturing. The calculated RCRs were well below one for DiNP and DiDP, based on a rough Biomonitoring Equivalents (BE) approach. The urinary concentration of the DPHP metabolite OH-MPHP is roughly 40x lower than the provisional EU HBM-GV of 0.9 mg/L, indicating a low occupational risk for this individual phthalate, based on conservative assumptions.</p> <p>Population exposure to phthalates and their substitutes is of outermost relevance for both</p>	<p>from exposure reconstruction based on data from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies was on average in the range of 0.1 to 1 µg/kg bw/d in most studies, far below the existing regulatory thresholds.</p> <p>Occupational exposure to DiNP, DiDP and DPHP was estimated to result in internal exposure levels that are not of health concern.</p> <p>Mixture risk assessment</p> <p>A mixture risk assessment of 5 selected phthalates (DEHP, DnBP, DiBP, BBzP and DiNP) is being carried out in HBM4EU aligned studies, since animal mixture toxicity studies revealed that some of the phthalates can act in an additive manner. Preliminary results show that, although only a small percentage of the European children and adolescents are exposed above HBM-GVs, approximately one sixth of the European children and teenagers is at risk from adverse effects of combined exposure of the 5 phthalates. Furthermore, the mixture risk assessment revealed that for most European children and adolescents combined risks are driven by multiple phthalates. Main drivers of the mixture risk are DnBP and DiBP. The mixture risk for the majority of children and teenagers would have gone unnoticed in single substance risk assessment. Furthermore, case studies are being carried out to evaluate a proof-of-concept for the identification of mixture health effects, one case study being a mixture</p>	<p>Deliverable Reports D14.2 “List of effect biomarkers for the first set of prioritised substances”, and D14.3 “Report on available biomarkers of effect of utility in human epidemiological studies for the 1st set of prioritised substances”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additionally a original manuscript entitled: “Phthalate exposure and reproductive hormones in peripubertal Spanish boys” will be available soon. Results suggest that exposure to some phthalate diesters, particularly high molecular weight ones, are associated with higher TT levels and/or TT/LH ratio among peripubertal boys. • D5.5 Human biomonitoring in risk assessment: 2nd set of examples on the use of HBM in risk assessments of HBM4EU priority chemicals. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • AD 5.4 Reporting for first and second set of substances. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/

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	<p>the general population and especially vulnerable groups including pregnant women, children and adolescents. This is due to three main reasons: 1) Exposure is ubiquitous and virtually all the population is exposed to phthalate metabolites in a daily basis; 2) Recent systematic reviews are showing that current levels of exposure to specific phthalate families are associated with reproductive, neurodevelopmental and other health endpoints); 3) The described exposure-health associations in the population are supported by toxicological knowledge.</p> <p>WP14 conducted an extensive literature review in order to have a detailed overview of existing biomarkers of effect for phthalates (D14.2). This included both, long established “traditional” effect biomarkers and less studied “novel” biomarkers of effect. Several effect biomarkers of different health outcomes, such as cancer, effects on reproduction, neurobehavioral changes, endocrine disruption, allergy or effects on immune system, allergy and cardiovascular or metabolic endpoints has been inventoried. A strategy for the selection of effect biomarkers substantiated with mechanistic information (e.g. AOPs), health outcomes and window of exposure (i.e. biomarkers of reproductive effects associated with phthalate exposure in children/adolescents) has been conducted jointly between WP 14 and WP 13 as a proof of concept and published. WP13 made a detailed</p>	<p>risk assessment for male reproductive health with a focus on semen quality, that includes certain phthalates. Final results will be available soon.</p> <p>Associations with health effects</p> <p>Combined toxicological data, effect biomarkers assessed in epidemiological studies and biological plausibility captured in several Adverse Outcome Pathways indicate associations between phthalate exposures and reproductive disorders in males.</p> <p>Additional evidence (also including limited number of human cohort studies) points to development of certain estrogen-dependent cancers, and possible metabolic-, neurodevelopmental- and immune-related health outcomes. In general, targeted human studies assessing exposures and health outcomes are limited and there is a clear gap and need for the future to confirm causality.</p> <p>Statistical analyses on HBM4EU Aligned Studies data are currently performed to look into the pathways linking exposure to phthalates/DINCH to health effects (neurodevelopment, asthma and allergy, sexual maturation, testicular function and metabolism and BMI) via established and novel effect biomarkers.</p>	<p>ables/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lange et al. (2021): The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU): Human biomonitoring guidance values for selected phthalates and a substitute plasticiser. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113722 • Deliverable 5.6 Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for selected phthalates. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • AD12.5: Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data <p>First papers on existing data and aligned studies are expected at the earliest in autumn 2022</p>

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	<p>overview of the available knowledge on AOPs for phthalates (D13.4) and subsequently summarised key knowledge gaps emerging from previous research. Specific activities, studies or other relevant steps to fill the missing information was proposed (D13.5). As a result, a number of health outcomes and associated effect biomarkers were proposed for further evaluation in HBM4EU. In a second step a thorough process in prioritising the best suited biomarkers of effect to be utilised in human epidemiological studies were conducted (D14.3). For phthalates several novel and traditional biomarkers of effect were proposed to be implemented in the HBM4EU Aligned Studies (WP8) for the following endpoints measured in children and teenagers: neurodevelopment, asthma and allergy, sexual maturation, testicular function and metabolism and BMI. Measurements of nuclear receptors, BDNF, Kisspeptin, oxidative stress, classical effect biomarkers, neurodevelopment, pubertal development/sexual maturation, and adverse metabolic effects in the HBM4EU aligned studies will serve as proof of principle to examine that the implementation of specific effect biomarkers will complement the interpretation of exposure biomarker measurements and thereby support the weight of evidence of exposure health-relationships. These exposure-effect associations are also described in the statistical analysis plan of the</p>		

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	<p>aligned studies (D10.12). A Directed Acyclic Graph was adopted for each exposure-effect association as visual aid to check for relevant confounders and for completeness of the statistical model. Statistical analyses are now being initiated by selected partners.</p> <p>WP12 has developed and improved a methodology for exposure reconstruction to deliver external exposure estimates from available (existing) HBM data. Aggregated HBM data from 13 different countries for different age groups including young children, young adults, seniors and (pregnant) mothers were used for the assessment. Daily intake estimates could be established for DEHP, DINP, BBzP, DnBP and DINCH. For DEHP, DINP and DnBP, in most of the studies included mean daily intakes were close or above 1 µg/kg bw/ d, whereas for DINCH estimates were lower and for BBzP markedly lower. These values are below EFSA's TDIs for the respective single compounds (DnBP = 10; BBzP = 500; DEHP = 50; DINP and DIDP = 150 µg/kg bw/d) (see AD12.5).</p>		

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<p>1. What is the current exposure of the EU population to PAHs?</p>	<p>Exposure to PAHs was addressed using the 1-OH-pyrene data collected from available HBM studies. 1-OH-pyrene is a major metabolite of pyrene and is representative for the PAHs mixtures, while it is the metabolite that is commonly measured in the majority of PAH-related HBM studies. The European HBM dashboard has 18 datasets with PAHs exposure data integrated and in IPCHEM metadata for 40 datasets with PAHs data are available.</p> <p>A PBTK model was parameterised and validated in Task 12.1 and it was coupled with the exposure reconstruction algorithms developed in Task 12.2. Based on the existing HBM data available prior to HBM4EU, the median value of pyrene exposure ranges between 0.025 µg/kg_bw/d for non-smokers in Belgium to 0.240 µg/kg_bw/d for smokers in Netherlands.</p> <p>New data for 13 PAH's markers (1-naphthol, 2-naphthol, 1,2 DHN, 2-FLUO, 3-FLUO, 9-FLUO, 1-PHEN, 2-PHEN, 3-PHEN, 4-PHEN, 9-PHEN, 1-PYR and 3-BaP) are available from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults (20-39 years). The Aligned Study data were collected between 2014-2021 across 10 sampling sites in Europe (Iceland, Denmark, Portugal, Croatia, Czech Republic, Poland, France, Switzerland, Luxembourg, and Germany) representing 2609</p>	<p>In order to answer questions on exposure levels and sources and further support current and future HBM studies, WP7 has produced a variety of materials to provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct in Europe.</p> <p>For PAH, questionnaires for adults, adolescents and children are available.</p> <p>Data prior to HBM4EU allowed to estimate that for most of the countries, median daily intake was around 0.050 µg/kg_bw/d, however, it has to be noted that, the bio samples were not collected in the same year, while analyses were performed by different laboratories, thus, hampering the overall intercomparison (AD12.5).</p> <p>Based on the data of the aligned studies, the median value of 1-naphthol in urine ranges between 0.13 µg/l in Switzerland to 1.81 µg/g crt in Poland. Higher values were observed for 2-naphthol in urine where the median value ranges between 1.28 µg/g crt in Germany to 8.03 µg/g crt in Poland. The median values of 2-fluo and 3-fluo in urine vary between 0.10 µg/g crt and 0.02 µg/g crt in Iceland to 0.31 µg/g crt and 0.11 µg/g crt in France respectively. The highest median value of 9-fluo in urine was observed in France (0.39 µg/l) and the lowest median</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable 4.9 Scoping documents for 2021 for the first and second round HBM4EU priority substances • Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: http://hbmjps.topick.pt/ • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ • Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 “Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires” https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ • Risk Assessment of PAHs based on literature data: DELIVERABLE 5.5 HUMAN BIOMONITORING IN RISK ASSESSMENT: 2ND SET OF EXAMPLES ON THE USE OF HBM IN RISK ASSESSMENTS OF HBM4EU PRIORITY CHEMICALS. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/ <p>Deliverable 10.9 Third annual list of</p>

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	<p>individuals. Not all biomarkers were analysed in all contributing studies, therefore number of sampling sites and data points can vary per biomarker.</p>	<p>value was observed in Luxembourg (0.17 µg/l). The median value of 1-phen in urine varies between 0.03 µg/g crt in Czech Republic to 0.17 µg/g crt in France. The median value of 2-phen ranges between 0.04 µg/g crt in Croatia to 0.09 µg/g crt in Czech Republic. The median value of 3-phen in urine, was highest France (0.12 µg/g crt) and the lowest median value was measured in Croatia (0.025 µg/g crt). The median value of 4-phen in urine varies between 0.02 µg/g crt in Iceland to 0.06 µg/g crt in Czech Republic. The median value of 9-phen ranges between 0.05 µg/g crt in France to 0.11 µg/g crt in Czech Republic. Regarding 1-HO-pyr, the highest median value was observed in Poland (0.24 µg/g crt) and the lowest median value was observed in Iceland (0.03 µg/g crt).</p>	<p>exposure distributions and/or European exposure values</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data</p> <p>Deliverable 12.8 Report on the results of exposure reconstruction algorithms on available HBM data in the EU for all priority compounds</p>
<p>3. What is the current exposure of different occupational groups?</p>	<p>Based on literature review and exposure reconstruction the following results were obtained. Exposure to the various occupational groups varies based on the specific activities of the related occupational sectors. The highest intake estimates were identified in soil remediation workers (in the range of 0.981 to 1.284 µg/kg_bw/d), followed by asphalt workers (0.093 to 0.325 µg/kg_bw/d) and workers in aluminum and rubber industry (0.035 to 0.100 µg/kg_bw/d).</p> <p>The lowest intake levels were identified to waste incinerator workers (0.004 to 0.104 µg/kg_bw/d), which is the only reported sector</p>	<p>Considering the review (T5.3), two main aspects are apparent: i) the exposure levels are still high in some occupational settings; ii) there is need for updated biomonitoring data from recent studies for PAHs exposure in occupational settings and iii) there is a need for developing new occupational studies, applying a set of exposure biomarkers, including a specific biomarker for BaP exposure, which would allow a better risk estimation for exposed workers.</p>	<p>Risk Assessment of PAHs based on literature data: DELIVERABLE 5.5 HUMAN BIOMONITORING IN RISK ASSESSMENT: 2ND SET OF EXAMPLES ON THE USE OF HBM IN RISK ASSESSMENTS OF HBM4EU PRIORITY CHEMICALS. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data</p>

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	<p>occupying both males and females. On the contrary, in all other sectors (soil remediation workers, asphalt workers, workers in aluminum and rubber industry) only males are being occupied and a differentiation on their intake results from their smoking habits, the time of their shift (pre shift, end of shift, post shift, next pre shift) and the age groups.</p> <p>The highest intake levels were related to soil remediation workers (1.284 µg/kg_bw/d) during the next pre shift, where pre shift and end of shift reported lower intakes (0.981 and 1.249 µg/kg_bw/d, respectively). For asphalt workers the highest intake was reported in the post shift and the specific age range of 35-52 (all workers were non-smokers). For workers in the aluminum and rubber industries, the lowest intake was reported for non-smokers (0.035 µg/kg_bw/d) comparing to smokers who exhibited a considerably higher intake (0.065 µg/kg_bw/d) (AD12.5).</p> <p>Based on reported data from PAH metabolites, the highest values were observed for 2-naphthol metabolite in urine across different European countries. The highest median concentrations of 2-naphthol metabolite were identified in skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers (7.76 µg/l), professionals (6.88 µg/l) and clerical support (6.10 µg/l) in France. The lowest median concentrations were identified in services and sales workers (4.61 µg/l), technicians and associate professionals (4.52 µg/l), craft and related trades workers</p>		

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	<p>(4.33 µg/l) and elementary occupations (3.81 µg/l). In Croatia, the highest median concentrations of 2-naphthol were observed in craft and related trades workers (7.82 µg/l), elementary occupations (6.9 µg/l), plant and machine operators and assemblers (6.74 µg/l), skilled agricultural (6.47 µg/l), services and sales workers (6.36 µg/l) and clerical support (6.29 µg/l). The lowest median concentrations were observed in professionals (4.64 µg/l), technicians and associate professionals (4.14 µg/l) and managers (1.92 µg/l). Regarding Luxembourg, the median concentrations were higher in elementary occupations (8.83 µg/l), services and sales workers (7.43 µg/l), plant and machine operators and assemblers (6.99 µg/l), clerical support (6.39 µg/l) and craft and related trades workers (5.43 µg/l) while the median concentrations were lower in technicians and associate professionals (3.95 µg/l), professionals (3.92 µg/l) and managers (3.15 µg/l). With regard to Czech Republic, the median concentrations of 2-naphthol vary between 3.96 µg/l in services and sales workers to 2.77 µg/l in clerical support. The median concentrations of 2-naphthol were observed in managers (6.74 µg/l) and services and sales workers and craft and related trades workers (5 µg/l), technicians and associate professionals (4.16 µg/l) and clerical support (3.13 µg/l) in Denmark. As regard Switzerland, the median values of 2-naphthol range between craft and related trades workers (4.48 µg/l), services and sales workers and clerical support</p>		

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	<p>(3.69 µg/l) to managers, professionals and technicians and associate professionals (2.53 µg/l). The highest median concentration of 2-naphthol was identified in plant and machine operators and assemblers (5.4 µg/l) in Iceland and the lowest concentrations were observed in services and sales workers and craft and related trades workers (2.46 µg/l). The highest median concentrations of 2-naphthol metabolite were identified in elementary occupations (11.36 µg/l) and clerical support (11.18 µg/l) in Portugal. The lowest median concentrations were identified in services and sales workers (6.75 µg/l), skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers (6.01 µg/l) and professionals (5.75 µg/l).</p>		
<p>3. Is there an association between air quality and human exposure to PAHs?</p>	<p>From exposure reconstruction studies it was shown that smokers have consistently higher exposure levels to pyrene, resulting in daily intakes of between 0.015 to 0.150 µg/kg_bw/d. Regarding hot spots, it is expected that they result in higher pyrene concentrations in the range of 0.005 to 0.01 µg/kg_bw/d. (AD12.5).</p> <p>Studies on associations with the density of traffic in France, Croatia and Switzerland, reported higher median values for 2-naphthol metabolite in urine of 6.03 µg/l, 5.7 µg/l and 2.84 µg/l respectively in intense traffic compared with light traffic (5.74 µg/l, 5.42 µg/l and 2.56 µg/l). Regarding the indoor use of biomass/coal burning, the median values were higher for 2-naphthol metabolite in Portugal, Czech Republic and Switzerland (6.93 µg/l,</p>	<p>Exposure reconstruction studies have shown that dietary exposure dominates exposure to PAHs (contributing to almost 90 %) of daily intake, while the contribution of inhalation is lower (about 10%), except for the cases where significant sources of inhalation exposure such as the proximity to industrial hot spots, heavily trafficked roads, biomass emissions, as well as smoking.</p> <p>Most studies on PAH exposure from air pollution, report external exposure. In HBM studies, mainly the urinary metabolite 1-OH-PYR is measured, probably because it still represents the best biomarker of occupational exposure to PAHs although it is mainly from dietary exposure except in cases with significant sources of inhalation</p>	<p>Deliverable 12.8 Report on the results of exposure reconstruction algorithms on available HBM data in the EU for all priority compounds</p> <p>Deliverable 12.5: Risk characterisation of the 1st set of prioritised substances using external exposure estimated from HBM data: a methodological approach</p>

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	<p>2.68 µg/l and 1.86 µg/l respectively). In connection to recent barbeque activities (last 24h), the highest median values were observed for 2-naphthol metabolite in urine in Croatia (8.2 µg/l) and Switzerland (4.46 µg/l) in comparison to those that didn't take part in barbeque activities (7.64 µg/l and 2.65 µg/l respectively). Regarding fireplace emissions, the highest median value of 2-naphthol was observed in Croatia (6.25 µg/l) compared to controls that didn't sit near to an open fireplace (5.2 µg/l) and the highest median value of 1-naphthol was observed in Switzerland (0.16 µg/l) in comparison to those didn't sit near to fireplace (0.13 µg/l). The highest median values were observed for 2-naphthol metabolite in urine in Czech Republic (3.27 µg/l), Iceland (15 µg/l) and Switzerland (4.19 µg/l) for the subjects with homes near a waste incineration plant.</p>	<p>exposure such as the proximity to industrial hot spots, heavily trafficked roads, biomass emissions, as well as smoking.</p>	
<p>4. Does exposure differ between countries? Why?</p>	<p>Based on the HBM data available prior to HBM4EU, the highest intake levels were calculated in Netherlands (0.073 to 0.245 µg/kg_bw/d) followed by Germany (0.019 to 0.125 µg/kg_bw/d) and Greece (0.060 to 0.065 µg/kg_bw/d), Denmark (0.041 to 0.095 µg/kg_bw/d), Czech (0.053 µg/kg_bw/d), France (0.022 to 0.078 µg/kg_bw/d) and Italy (0.041 to 0.059 µg/kg_bw/d), Spain (0.035 µg/kg_bw/d) and Belgium (0.029 µg/kg_bw/d). The lowest intake levels were reported in Sweden (0.013 to 0.036 µg/kg_bw/d). It has to be noted that in The Netherlands, Italy,</p>	<p>The differences in intake levels among the various countries are mostly explained by the differences in dietary intake, which is the result of increased soil contamination and dietary patterns (frequency of eating smoked food) and to a smaller extent to difference in air pollution levels.</p> <p>In specific studies several exposure modifiers such as age, smoking status and exposure to secondhand smoke, as well as residential location have been identified as key factors affecting the overall intake levels.</p>	<p>Deliverable 12.1 Review paper on PBTK/D models for the 1st set of priority compounds</p> <p>Additional Deliverable 12.5 Delivery of exposure estimates for the 1st set of prioritised substances based on HBM data</p> <p>Deliverable 12.8 Report on the results of exposure reconstruction algorithms on available HBM data in the EU for all priority compounds</p>

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	<p>France and Sweden the intake levels of smokers have been identified much higher compared to the ones of non-smokers (0.245 and 0.073 µg/kg_bw/d, 0.059 and 0.041 µg/kg_bw/d, 0.078 and 0.022 µg/kg_bw/d and 0.036 and 0.013 µg/kg_bw/d, respectively). In Germany the highest intake levels were reported for children of 5-8 years old, living near industrial hot spots (0.125 µg/kg_bw/d) while for children of the same ages living away from industrial hot spots the intake levels were much lower (0.064 µg/kg_bw/d). This is explained by the higher multimedia contamination in the area and the higher contribution to intake of both soil ingestion and ambient air inhalation.</p> <p>In Greece, living nearby areas with traffic congestion, the intake levels were higher than in urban areas free of traffic (0.065 and 0.060 µg/kg_bw/d, respectively). In Denmark the highest intake levels were reported for bus drivers of 27-60 years of age (0.095 µg/kg_bw/d) while the lowest ones were reported for people working in rural areas (0.041 µg/kg_bw/d) (AD12.5).</p> <p>The reason of these differences have been further explored using the HBM data from the aligned studies.</p> <p>Based on the reported median levels of 2-naphthol in urine: in Poland, Portugal, France, Luxembourg, Denmark, Croatia, Iceland, Switzerland, Czech Republic and Germany, the</p>		

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	<p>median levels of 2-naphthol in urine of smokers was higher compared to non-smokers (18.63 µg/l, 11.88 µg/l, 11.83 µg/l, 11.46 µg/l, 8.36 µg/l, 7.58 µg/l, 7.22 µg/l, 5.7 µg/l, 3.45 µg/l, 1.52 µg/l and 7.17 µg/l, 5.99 µg/l, 4.22 µg/l, 3.83 µg/l, 8.36 µg/l, 4.49 µg/l, 2.54 µg/l, 2.3 µg/l, 3.07 µg/l and 1.23 µg/l respectively). The median values of 1-naphthol in urine for smokers were higher in Poland (7.79 µg/l), France (7.02 µg/l), Croatia (5.33 µg/l), Iceland (5.32 µg/l), Denmark (3.91 µg/l), Portugal (3.57 µg/l) and Luxembourg (2.29 µg/l) compared to non-smokers (1.9 µg/l, 0.57 µg/l, 1.18 µg/l, 0.74 µg/l, 1.32 µg/l, 0.63 µg/l and 0.49 µg/l respectively). The rest of PAHs metabolites followed a similar pattern with lower median values.</p> <p>Regarding secondhand smoking, the highest concentrations were observed for 2-naphthol metabolite followed by 1-naphthol metabolite in urine for secondhand smokers compared to non-secondhand smokers in France, Croatia, Czech Republic, Poland, Switzerland and Germany. The median values of 2-naphthol metabolite in urine for secondhand smokers were higher in Poland (11.83 µg/l), France (8.66 µg/l), Switzerland (5.98 µg/l), Croatia (5.79 µg/l) and Czech Republic (3.96 µg/l) compared to non-secondhand smokers (7.56 µg/l, 4.65 µg/l, 2.52 µg/l, 4.79 µg/l and 2.92 µg/l, respectively). Regarding the 1-naphthol metabolite in urine, the highest median values for secondhand smokers were identified in Poland (4.85 µg/l),</p>		

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	Croatia (2.27 µg/l), Portugal (2.09 µg/l), France (1.49 µg/l) and Czech Republic (1.13 µg/l) compared to in non-secondhand smokers (1.95 µg/l, 1.19 µg/l, 0.91 µg/l, 0.59 µg/l and 0.98 µg/l, respectively).		
5. Can we see a decline in exposure to the eight PAHs restricted under REACH?	<p>Exposure to PAHs occurs through multiple pathways and routes. This also pertains for the 8 PAHs (benzo[a]pyrene, benzo[e]pyrene, benzo[a]anthracene, chrysene, benzo[b]fluoranthene, benzo[j]fluoranthene, benzo[k]fluoranthene and dibenzo[a,h]anthracene) restricted under REACH. Restrictions from REACH are expected to affect the contribution of exposure related mainly to consumer products. It is also likely that the restriction of use will result in a reduction in the overall tonnage that will be reflected in the soil levels, which in turn will be reflected in the food chain and the dietary intake. However, to identify a potential decline, a trend analysis is required.</p> <p>In HBM4EU estimated intake levels of data available in the HBM4EU dashboard and available in the literature prior to HBM4EU, were compared with HBM data collected in the HBM4EU aligned studies in adults (20-39 yrs) all over Europe. No real time trend analysis can be calculated as the sampling sites were different and the age groups but we could compare the aggregated data from the studies to draw some conclusions.</p>	It is concluded that the most recent values obtained in the HBM4EU aligned studies showed that the levels of internal exposure of the European adult population were similar to those from previous studies published in the literature. There were no indications that the newly obtained HBM data for 1-OHPyr were substantially lower than the ones previously measured and reported in the open literature. In addition, while comparing the risk estimations with the ones formerly estimated and presented in D5.5, the risk levels now estimated are at the same order of magnitude, with an exception of smokers (10-4), when considering solely oral (dietary) exposure. From the health policies questions perspective, further efforts should be envisaged for reducing intake and potential contamination with PAHs from various sources.	
6. Are the overall	The results of the aligned studies were used to	No analysis was done on stratified data	D5.11

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<p>exposure levels in the general population, children, and pregnant women above any health-relevant assessment levels (reference dose or HBM guidance values)?</p>	<p>update the PAHs risk assessment previously performed within D5.5 that was based on published data. The aligned study cohorts included adults from the general population from France (A_ANSP_ESTEBAN), Czech Republic (A_MU_(C)ELSPAC), Croatia (A_CIPH_HBM in Croatia), Germany (A_UBA_ESB), Iceland (A_UI_DIET_HBM), Luxembourg (A_LNS_Oriscav-Lux2), Poland (A_NIOM_POLAES) and Switzerland (A_SWISS TPH_HBM4EU).</p> <p>The excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) was estimated using two stages. In the first stage, the external exposure was reconstructed, i.e. the probable daily intake (PDI) of pyrene was estimated based on HBM data on 1-hydroxypyrene (1-OHPyr) available in the aligned studies. The PDI of pyrene intake levels were then translated into PAH4 (BaA, BbF, BaP, CHR) intake levels based on the assumption that pyrene intake was a surrogate of PAH4. In the second approach, for comparison, PAH4 dietary intake levels were derived from the country specific food residue and the food consumption data, available in the EFSA reports (2008, 2015c). Derived PAH4 intakes were then used as an input to estimate ELCR, using the ECHA-RAC (2018) formula.</p> <p>The mean intake of PAH4 derived from the EFSA data on the occurrence of PAHs in food was, in general, one order of magnitude higher than that estimated based on exposure reconstruction from the HBM4EU aligned study</p>	<p>since there are no reference values for that.</p> <p>Considering the indicative tolerable cancer risk level for the general population proposed by the EC (2001) at levels of 10⁻⁶, the Estimated Life Time Cancer Risk (ELCR) results obtained in the present work for 4 of the 7 countries included in the aligned studies (Luxembourg (A_LNS_Oriscav-Lux2), France (A_ANSP_ESTEBAN), Czech Republic (A_MU_(C)ELSPAC) and Poland(A_NIOM_POLAES)), all in the 10⁻⁵ range, are of concern.</p> <p>Uncertainties relate to considering only the oral intake route, using the biomarker 1-OHP in urine as a biomarker of other carcinogenic species co-occurring commonly with pyrene and as a reliable bioindicator of measured dietary polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon. In addition, exposure to PAHs mixture may modify metabolism or induce different effects, therefore a single metabolite may not adequately characterise exposure to PAHs.</p>	<p>HBM_risk_assessment_4th_set_examples</p>

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	<p>data (mean values of 1-OHPyr).</p> <p>In addition, input is provided (WP12), towards the association of the dose of toxic metabolites in the target tissue, with the observed HBM levels.</p>		

ⁱ The aligned studies made use of a variety of materials produced in WP7 that provide the groundwork for a harmonised approach to study planning and conduct of HBM studies in Europe. These materials are:

- data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium
 - manuals/guidelines for study planning and conduct
 - Standard Operating Procedures for qualified recruitment of participants, fieldwork, sampling and exchange of samples
 - different kinds of questionnaires for various age groups and substance (groups)
 - influence of thawing and freezing procedures on the integrity of biobanked samples in the literature and supplied a respective concept for a quality study
 - templates for the communication with participants
- Data platform with information on existing, ongoing and planned general and occupational HBM studies in the HBM4EU consortium: <http://hbmjps.topick.pt/>
 • Online library which includes harmonised questionnaires, guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures, templates for communication with participants etc. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/>
 Description of all mentioned materials developed under WP7: D7.9 "Overall report on WP7 documents for survey design, Study protocols, SOPs and Guidelines, and questionnaires"
<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>